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iNnovative EV-charging EnviRonment for Future Low-cost mAss deploymentT

NEVERFLAT

Project number:	101192973
Project name:	iNnovative EV-charging EnviRonment for Future Low-cost mAss deploymentT
Topic:	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D5-01-01
Type of action:	HORIZON-IA
Starting date of action:	1 January 2025
Project duration:	42 months
Project end date:	30.06.2028
Deliverable number:	D1.1
Deliverable title:	SotA and barriers/gaps analysis of current market development
Document version:	Ver1
WP number:	WP1
Lead beneficiary:	08-HUB
Main author(s):	Mertkan Kalyoncu, 08-HUB
Internal reviewers:	Corneliu Barbu, 01-AARU and Abhishek Gupta, 06-TUB
Nature of deliverable:	R
Dissemination level:	PU
Delivery date from Annex 1:	06/2025
Actual delivery date:	01/2026

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Executive Summary

Keywords: Bidirectional Charging, Market Integration, Interoperability, Cost-effectiveness

NEVERFLAT aims to develop and demonstrate, in real-life settings, an innovative, efficient, and user-friendly pervasive low-cost smart bi-directional charging infrastructure for electric vehicles (EVs), directly contributing to a specific strategic objective of the 2Zero Partnership – developing affordable, inclusive, user-friendly charging infrastructure concepts and technologies that include vehicle and grid interaction. A complete, integrated, and deployed charging solution will be validated in extensive operational urban and peri-urban environments across pilot sites in Germany, Romania, and Spain, showcasing the potential for widespread adoption, user acceptance, and seamless coverage interoperable across European country borders, thereby helping remove barriers to EV user acceptability.

NEVERFLAT Deliverable D1.1 provides a detailed review of the state-of-the-art (SoTA) of existing technologies, standards, and services, along with a regulatory and market overview and analyses of socio-economic and business models related to bidirectional charging and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) applications, to identify gaps and barriers that must be overcome to enable cost-effective mass deployment.

The analysis in this deliverable shows that bidirectional EV charging is technically feasible with currently available technologies. Modern power electronics can enable efficient bidirectional operation across a range of battery voltages, and their integration in DC microgrids to integrate renewable generation is also mature. Communication standards have evolved to support bidirectional charging and authentication, and the backend communication supports bidirectional charging and distributed energy resource control. Modern concepts, such as tokenization of bidirectional services and integration with virtual power plants (VPPs), are also analyzed in this deliverable. However, from a technical standpoint, market readiness remains limited due to increased hardware complexity, higher costs compared to unidirectional chargers, incomplete standard adoption, and restricted availability of V2G-enabled vehicles.

The deliverable also assesses regulatory frameworks, market roles, and business models across the European Union and project Member States (Spain, Romania, and Germany). Regulatory uncertainty, metering and calibration requirements, and unclear business propositions for flexibility services are identified as critical non-technical barriers to wide-scale adoption of this technology. Socio-economic analysis indicates that viable V2G business models depend on low hardware costs, clear value propositions for end users, and access to energy and flexibility markets.

In conclusion, the NEVERFLAT Deliverable D1.1 establishes that the primary obstacles to the mass deployment of bidirectional EV charging are no longer technical feasibility but cost, interoperability, regulatory alignment, and market integration. Based on these findings, the deliverable recommends focusing on low-power, cost-effective DC bidirectional chargers, standardized communication stacks, DC-microgrid-ready architectures, and the development of roaming services.

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Acronyms

AC	Alternating Current. (p. 95)
AFIR	Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation. (p. 37, 85)
BM	Balancing Markets. (p. 92)
BPT	Bidirectional Power Transfer. (p. 33, 44, 54)
CDR	Charge Detail Record. (p. 60)
CDRs	Charge Detail Records. (p. 34)
CPMS	Charge Point Management Systems. (p. 54)
CPO	Charge Point Operators. (p. 38)
CSP	Charging Station Provider. (p. 93)
DC	Direct Current. (p. 95)
DER	Distributed Energy Resources. (p. 17)
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology. (p. 60)
DR	Demand Response. (p. 92)
DSO	Distribution System Operator. (p. 45, 92)
EEU	Energy End Users. (p. 95)
eMP	eMobility Providers. (p. 38)
EMSP	E-Mobility Service Provider. (p. 95)
EP	Energy Producer. (p. 96)
ESS	Energy Storage Systems. (p. 96)
EV	Electric Vehicle. (p. 1, 15, 16, 72)
EVA	Electric Vehicle Aggregators. (p. 92)
EVCL	Electric Vehicle Charging Load. (p. 97)
EVSE	Electric Vehicle and Charging Station. (p. 16)
FCS	Fast Charging Stations. (p. 97)
HMI	Human-Machine Interface. (p. 15)
IoT	Internet of Things. (p. 72)
MEU	Mobility End User. (p. 95)

MINLP	Mixed-Integer Nonlinear Programming. (p. 80)
MKI	Managed Key Infrastructure. (p. 65)
MUTN	Microscopic Urban Transportation Network. (p. 96)
OCP	Open Charge Point Protocol. (p. 17)
OPCP	Open Plug & Charge Protocol. (p. 34)
OSCP	Open Smart Charging Protocol. (p. 45)
PDN	Power Distribution Network. (p. 96)
PLC	Power Line Communication. (p. 16)
POI	Point of Interest. (p. 34)
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement. (p. 96)
PSFB	phase-shifted full-bridge. (p. 14)
PV	Photovoltaic. (p. 94)
RPO	Remuneration and Payment Operator. (p. 95)
SaaS	Software-as-a-Service. (p. 93)
SCS	Smart Charging Stations. (p. 97)
SCSP	Smart Charging Service Provider. (p. 95)
SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture Model. (p. 96)
SICS	Slow Charging Station. (p. 97)
SoC	State of Charge. (p. 35)
SoH	State of Health. (p. 35)
SUMO	Simulation of Urban MObility. (p. 96)
TSO	Transmission System Operator. (p. 93)
UDR	User Discharge Rate. (p. 97)
V2B	Vehicle-to-Building. (p. 99)
V2B2	Vehicle-to-Building-to-Grid. (p. 99)
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid. (p. 14, 71, 72)
V2H	Vehicle-to-Home. (p. 94)
V2L	Vehicle-to-Load. (p. 72, 99)
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle. (p. 72, 99)
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything. (p. 72)
VPP	Virtual Power Plants. (p. 71, 72)
VPPO	Virtual Power Plant Operators. (p. 95)

1

Introduction

Electric Vehicle (EV) adoption has increased rapidly over the past few years as it is seen as a key component of decarbonizing the energy system. At the same time, countries accelerating EV adoption also recognize the broader impact of the system constraints imposed by insufficient charging infrastructure, aging and limited capacity of the national grids, inconsistent standards, and societal acceptance of this technology.

The availability of charging infrastructure is a key enabler of broader adoption of green transportation. As such, it suffers from limited capacity, charger quality, geographic and demographic inequalities, compatibility issues, and data concerns. It is also widely accepted that a robust and reliable EV charging system could connect to and support power grids in the transition to a more flexible, resilient, and connected energy system.

At the same time, the wide adoption of renewable energy poses significant challenges to the grid due to the misalignment between production and consumption. To reduce this imbalance and to maintain power quality requirements, large amounts of energy storage would be needed. Instead of deploying new and expensive energy storage solutions, the EV batteries may be used for this purpose.

Bidirectional charging is the process in which the energy in an electric vehicle's battery can flow in both directions, from the grid to the battery and back, to power other loads or return it to the grid when needed or desired. That way, EV batteries can provide grid support or participate in energy markets, charging when electricity prices are low and discharging when they are high. However, to enable the penetration of more renewable energy on the grid, the bidirectional charging should be regarded in the context of renewable microgrid applications, where the technologies are seamlessly coupled through a system architecture that enables smart and optimal operation of the integrated system, to reduce grid congestion and reduce peak demand to ensure power system resilience and grid capacity.

The NEVERFLAT project is addressing the European Commission's calls for the deployment of charging infrastructure that is ubiquitous, parallel, and anticipatory towards the growth of the EV sales, as requested in its HORIZON-CL5-2024-D5-01-01 calls for proposals, 'Smart, low-cost per-

vasive stationary slow charging and bi-directional solutions synergic with the grid for EV mass deployment'. As such, the project aims to develop charging solutions that are fully interoperable across European countries, enabling massive, smart, low-cost on-street charging of EVs to support the grid and to ensure optimal planning for mass deployment based on user needs [1].

The NEVERFLAT project [2] is composed of 13 European partners from Spain, Germany, Romania, Estonia and Denmark, that aims to develop and demonstrate in real-life an innovative, efficient, and user-friendly pervasive low-cost smart bi-directional charging infrastructure for electric vehicles (EVs) and validate its EV user acceptability in densely populated areas settings, directly contributing to specific strategic objective of the 2Zero Partnership [3] - developing affordable, inclusive, user-friendly charging infrastructure concepts and technologies that include vehicle and grid interaction. The complete, integrated, and deployed charging solution will be tested in extensive operational urban and peri-urban environments at pilot sites in Germany, Romania, and Spain, showcasing the potential for widespread adoption, user acceptance, and seamless coverage that is interoperable across European country borders [4].

The NEVERFLAT project is positioned at the intersection of power electronics, communication standards, and market/regulatory/social frameworks. The project explicitly targets the development of a bidirectional multimodal charging station and its use in microgrid architecture for V2G control. In this context, the four pilot cases are critical to the success of the project: Europe's largest startup hub in the middle of ringberlin campus [5]; a college campus area in the Alba Iulia municipality in Romania; the Alava Technology Park in Vitoria - Gasteiz, Spain; a residential and office building with EV charging with energy storage in Bucharest, Romania. Using these pilot cases and based on key indicators crucial for assessing the readiness for mass deployment and replicability of the bi-directional charging stations, the NEVERFLAT project will demonstrate the effectiveness, scalability, and quantifiable improvement in user acceptability of the developed smart charging infrastructure in an operational environment, bringing this technology to TRL 7 [6].

2

Objective and Scope

Deliverable D1.1 of the NEVERFLAT project establishes the technical and market baseline for an integrated, bidirectional EV charging station ecosystem in a DC microgrid architecture. The document provides a structured state-of-the-art (SotA) survey, benchmarks key technologies and protocols, and identifies challenges and opportunities to mass deployment. It is intended to support the rest of the project by providing benchmarks for Key Performance Parameters (KPPs) for component design and system integration.

This review aims towards five concrete objectives:

1. it consolidates a SotA overview of power electronics for charging stations, communication protocols, and DC microgrids;
2. it defines KPPs and it benchmarks architectures for bidirectional EVSE (Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment);
3. it specifies bidirectional power transfer (BPT) roaming/service requirements and it identifies protocol gaps;
4. it reviews regulatory and market constraints and success factors across EU and its project partners (Germany, Romania and Spain)
5. it recommends actionable initiatives to guide project work and the design validation in project pilot cases.

This review is divided into several major areas:

- **Technical State of the Art and Benchmarking.** The scope of this report is to survey EVSE hardware (AC/DC, uni- and bidirectional), converter topologies, communication protocols, and safety and compliance requirements for EV charging in Europe. It benchmarks commercial charging solutions and derives KPPs for a bidirectional DC charging station (e.g., ISO 15118-20 at the EV interface; OCPP 2.1 upstream; bidirectional power stage; wide output voltage; 7 kW charge/discharge; and compliance with relevant standards, such as IEC 61851/62196/60364/60529). This report also includes a DC microgrid review covering components, control and operation modes, and standards, including protection zones, as well as a summary of DC microgrid projects worldwide.

- Service-Layer Interoperability for bidirectional power transfer (BPT). This work identifies the minimal viable feature-set for a BPT-capable roaming service layer: enriched point-of-interest (POI) data for EVSE BPT capability, EV data (State-of-Charge / State-of-Health SoC/SoH) required by the user, authenticated sessions, authorization, and multi-contract handling for charge and discharge, user preference capture (departure time, target SoC, discharge consent), charging-profile orchestration, dynamic tariff exchange, signed metering for billing, and integration hooks to energy-market actors (DSO/TSO/aggregators/VPPs). It lists pilot projects based on BPT relevance [6], e-Roaming protocols, vehicle-to-grid (V2G) management, and energy tokenization. It continues with a review of Virtual Power Plants (VPP) for bidirectional applications and a charging infrastructure deployment planner.
- Regulatory and Market Baseline. This survey consolidates the regulatory constraints (low voltage directive and EMC, installation codes, Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation AFIR transparency, metering, and calibration) and role allocations across the smart-charging ecosystem (charge point operators CPO, e-mobility (service) providers EMSP/eMP, aggregators, VPP, TSO/DSO) for the EU-level and the partner countries of the NEVERFLAT project. It then assesses barriers for relevant standardization activities.
- Socio-Economic and Business Models. The analysis categorizes V2G business models, identifies adoption drivers and challenges, and reviews lessons from European pilots (e.g., Nissan-TenneT, Utrecht city, OVO PowerLoop, Parker). It summarizes strategic opportunities and critical success factors relevant to project pilots.
- Insights and Recommendations. The report ends with overarching insights and a set of recommendations for NEVERFLAT design choices:
 1. prioritize a low-cost, low-power DC bidirectional charger for on-street parking;
 2. adopt ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1 to ensure V2G readiness and project viability after its end;
 3. include a design for DC microgrid for the pilot sites for renewable energy integration;
 4. ensure interoperability, cybersecurity and data governance; and (v) align with regulatory and other constraints for conformance and clarity.

3

Methodology

The methodology combines structured literature/standards review, technology, regulatory, and market benchmarking, and synthesis into design requirements based on Key Performance Parameters (KPPs).

1. Document Structure. This review begins with introductory chapters (Introduction; Objective and Scope; Methodology; and the NEVERFLAT Project overview) and proceeds to an expanded SotA that is organized by technical pillars: bidirectional charging stations; DC microgrids; bidirectional charging services; V2G energy management and forecasting; Plug&Charge and Charge Point Management System; energy tokenization; integrated infrastructure system; VPPs; and infrastructure deployment planning. Each pillar describes technology benchmarking and includes explicit KPPs, gaps, and recommendations. The technology pillars are complemented by regulatory/market and socio-economic chapters.
2. Bidirectional Charging SotA and KPPs. The analysis reviews basic concepts of current charging technologies and modes, and it enumerates EVSE functional and communication layers (user HMI; EV–EVSE via ISO 15118-20/PLC; EVSE–backend via OCPP 2.1), relevant safety and installation standards (IEC 61851/62196/60364; IP ratings per IEC 60529; CE via LVD/EMC/RoHS), and power-stage options (PSFB, resonant, DAB, CLLC) with their implications for efficiency, voltage window, and bidirectionality. A benchmark of commercial devices (AC, AC/DC, DC/DC; uni/bidirectional) supports a KPP overview and the project’s choice of a 7 kW bidirectional DC charger as the first-stage product.
3. DC Microgrid Analysis. The study compares AC and DC microgrids and their control strategies, details components (DERs, ESS, loads/DSM, PCC, communication, control), and explains a three-layer control hierarchy (primary droop; secondary voltage restoration; tertiary EMS). It references Current/OS concepts (voltage bands, zones, pre-charging, earthing) and protection zones and compiles a multi-site benchmark of existing DC microgrids (universities, military, industrial, islanded systems). Key gaps and barriers—protection selectivity, standardization, cost—are summarized into design constraints and KPPs for the project’s reference DC bus.
4. Enablers for BPT. First, eRoaming features for BPT services are defined and analyzed based on pilot projects across the EU and filtered by relevance to smart charging and V2X, then benchmarked against a feature set covering EV/EVSE data, authentication/authorization, user pref-

erences, CDRs, profile handling, tariffs, and market-actor integration. Open eRoaming protocols (OCHP, OICP, eMIP, OCPI) are analyzed against the same metrics and key insights, recommendations, and KPPs are also provided. Second, V2G management and forecast are addressed through a thorough literature review and system overview, concluding with KPPs, gaps, and recommendations. The technical analysis continues with a baseline analysis of the charge point management system, based on existing functionalities, to meet stakeholder requirements and extend it to support bidirectional charging. This section also contains an overview of the barriers and recommendations for improvement based on a set of KPPs. Next, a review of energy tokenization based on a qualitative scoring system and a set of basic requirements is presented, followed by a comparative analysis of the existing charging station architecture and the definition of functional and technical requirements to support bidirectional charging and data centralization. A literature review of virtual power plants (VPPs) and an analysis of the charging infrastructure deployment planner conclude the technical review of this report.

5. Regulatory/ Market and Socio-Economic/ Business Analysis. Roles and responsibilities are mapped for a market-integrated bidirectional charging ecosystem (CPO, EMSP/ eMP, aggregator/ VPP, DSO/ TSO, OEMs). EU-level and national landscapes (Germany, Romania, Spain) are reviewed against criteria including market structures, flexibility access, metering/calibration, and AFIR transparency obligations. Socio-economic factors, business barriers, and value-capture models are synthesized into strategic recommendations.
6. Synthesis into Design Guidance. Each pillar concludes with gaps/barriers and KPPs. In aggregate, these drive the NEVERFLAT design stance: adopt mature open standards (15118-20, OCPP 2.1), target an affordable bidirectional DC charger, enable DC microgrid coupling where beneficial, and define a roaming-grade BPT feature set to unlock large-scale deployment.

4

The NEVERFLAT Project

The NEVERFLAT project, a 42-months project started in January 2025 funded by the European Union by Grant number 101192973 awarded under the call HORIZON-CL5-2024-D5-01-01, aims to contribute to the establishment of large-scale smart on-street low-cost charging of EVs, fully interoperable across European country borders and available at any time to improve the overall efficiency of power supply to the grid, based on seamless processes and space-and-time-oriented prediction and control of the global charging power demand. The project will combine technological innovations in charging infrastructure, data-driven optimization, and socio-economic considerations to create a comprehensive solution to advance electric mobility with ubiquitous, interoperable, efficient, low-power, and bidirectional on-street charging, while ensuring inclusivity, efficiency, and environmental sustainability. Key technological innovations like the new low-cost compact multimodal charging station for bidirectional use, improved optimization of deployment and positioning of the new charging solutions, or strategic management and microgrid control system for V2G applications - will be developed in the project using cutting-edge technologies (advanced ML predictive models, WBG semiconductors, Digital Twins). Socio-cultural and business model innovations triggered by the large-scale deployment of bidirectional charging technology will also be addressed in the project. Broad and multidisciplinary (technical, business/commercial, and socio-cultural) innovations will be necessary to reach the project goals.

Specifically, the NEVERFLAT project will:

- Define and formalize user needs, requirements, and technical specifications for the development of the innovative, pervasive smart EV charging infrastructure system. The requirement will serve as a backbone to develop solutions available on non-discriminatory terms to a wide range of users, to enable the choice of e-mobility service providers and vehicle manufacturers
- Develop methodology and architecture for optimal deployment and optimization of the bidirectional power supply management based on statistical models for parking, traffic, and grid configuration to enable exhaustive coverage of service based on grid infrastructure and capacity constraints, charging needs, and parking patterns.
- Develop innovative, interoperable, efficient, compact low power bi-directional multimodal charging stations integrated with local grids, renewable energy generation, and storage to op-

timize the use of energy resources and infrastructures and reduce costs

- Design and setup of new value-added services and business models based on the innovative charging infrastructure, promoting equity and sustainable processes through social innovation, based on established socio-cultural databases to enable long-term and opportunistic charging types
- Implement and seamlessly integrate the complete pervasive smart EV charging system, accessible to the end-users via the developed people-friendly end-user applications and tools to enable real-time access to battery information while respecting GDPR and data disclosure terms
- Demonstrate its effectiveness, scalability, and quantifiably improved user acceptability of the developed smart charging infrastructure on four distinct representative urban and peri-urban pilot sites based on socio-cultural databases, which include charging habits, practices, and other community characteristics
- Engage with the stakeholders for mass community uptake (including clustering activities), and provide a sound business exploitation strategy to address user needs in different communities and reduce investment costs

Table 4.1: NEVERFLAT project participants.

Nr.	Legal name	Country
1	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	Denmark
2	FUNDACION TEKNIKER	Spain
3	FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA DEL'ENERGIA DE CATALUNYA	Spain
4	EDENTIFY FOUNDATION MTU	Estonia
5	INGARTEK CONSULTING SL	Spain
6	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN	Germany
7	Grid & Co. GmbH	Germany
8	HUBJECT GMBH	Germany
9	ASOCIATIA BEIA - GRID INSTITUT	Romania
10	Fundación Vitoria-Gasteiz Araba Mobility LabFundazioa	Spain
11	CENTRUL ROMAN AL ENERGIEI - CRE	Romania
12	MUNICIPALITY OF ALBA IULIA	Romania
13	STANSOL ENERGY SL	Spain

5

State of the Art Analysis

5.1 Bidirectional Charging Station

5.1.1 Methodology

This section provides an overview of current charging technologies and standards related to bidirectional charging stations. It first explains the basic concepts of on-board and off-board chargers and the differences between AC and DC charging methods. The following sections describes the different charging modes defined in IEC 61851, the main EV charging standards and their connectors (such as CCS, CHAdeMO, Tesla/NACS, GB/T) and the essential safety requirements for EV charging in Europe. It then discusses DC converter architectures for unidirectional and bidirectional power flow and highlights the impact of these designs on both charging efficiency and V2G readiness. Finally, the analysis presents examples of commercial charging solutions based on AC, AC/DC and DC/DC technologies and summarizes key performance parameters (KPPs).

5.1.2 SotA Analysis - Charging Stations

Electric vehicle (EV) charging stations are infrastructure systems designed to provide electrical energy to recharge the batteries of electric vehicles. These stations can vary widely in terms of power levels, charging speeds, and the technology employed. Broadly, charging systems are categorized into onboard and offboard chargers, depending on whether the battery charger is integrated within the vehicle or installed externally as part of the charging station.

In general, all electric vehicles have onboard chargers that can charge the vehicle's battery by connecting them to the AC grid. In contrast, offboard chargers are chargers that are located outside the vehicle, where, ignoring the protections, the charger output is connected directly to the battery terminals, so in this case the voltage input to the vehicle is in the form of DC. Offboard chargers are known as DC chargers, while wallboxes and other systems that provide connection to the AC main grid for the onboard chargers are known as AC chargers [7].

By definition, a battery charger is an electronic device designed to supply electrical power to a rechargeable battery, restoring its energy storage capacity. Ideally, to extend the life of the battery,

this charger should supply the current and voltage required at any given moment, which is usually indicated by the Battery Management System (BMS), which is in communication with the charger. Therefore, AC chargers are not really chargers, however, because they are widely known in this way, for ease of reading in this document this type of system will be referred to as AC chargers.

Regarding the differences between onboard and offboard chargers, onboard chargers are generally lower power due to the inherent limitations of being built into the car (limitations of weight, size, heat dissipation and vehicle cost). Currently, the usual maximum charge among commercial vehicles is 22 kW for three-phase inputs and 7.4 kW for single-phase inputs (i.e., 32 A per phase in both cases). However, it is common for the maximum rating to be limited to ratings considerably lower than 22 kW, a common rating being 11 kW [7].

Charging Modes

In Europe (Refer Table 5.1), the IEC 61851 standard is followed, which it defines different charging modes. Specifically, the IEC 61851-1 standard defines four charging modes (it should be noted that mode 1 is prohibited in most European countries, because there are no protections between the car charger and the socket) [8]:

Table 5.1: Charging modes defined by IEC 61851-1 standard.

Charging Mode	Type	Voltage	Current	Output Power	Typical Use
Mode 1	AC	Up to 250V (single-phase)	Up to 16 A	Up to 3.7 kW (single-phase)	Not recommended due to safety risks; rarely used.
		Up to 480V (three-phase)	Up to 16 A	Up to 11 kW (three-phase)	
Mode 2	AC	Up to 250V (single-phase)	Up to 32 A	Up to 7.4 kW (single-phase)	Occasional or emergency charging using standard outlets.
Mode 3	AC	Up to 480V (three-phase)	Up to 32 A	Up to 22 kW (three-phase)	Regular charging at home, work, or public stations; requires dedicated EVSE (Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment).
		Up to 250V (single-phase)	Up to 32 A		
		Up to 480V (three-phase)	Up to 63 A	Up to 43.5 kW (three-phase)	
Mode 4	DC	Up to 1000V or more	Up to 400 A or more	Up to 400 kW	Fast charging at public stations; rapid charging for long-distance travel.

EV Charging Standards: Connectors and Protocols

Electric vehicle (EV) charging standards ensure compatibility between vehicles and charging infrastructure by defining connectors, communication protocols, and power delivery systems. While efforts exist to harmonize these standards globally, regional preferences and legacy systems have

led to a fragmented landscape. Below is an overview of the major standards, their applications, and V2G considerations.

Combined Charging System : The Combined Charging System (CCS) is a standard supporting both AC and DC charging [9]. It exists in two regional variants since three phase AC connection in buildings is less common in North America:

- CCS1 (Combo 1): North America.
- CCS2 (Combo 2): Europe, Australia, and parts of Asia

CCS integrates a traditional AC connector (Type 1 for CCS1, Type 2 for CCS2) with two additional DC pins, enabling seamless switching between AC and DC charging.

- Power Levels: Up to 350 kW (CCS2).
- V2G Integration: ISO 15118-20 introduces bidirectional charging.
- Adoption: Backed by the CharIN alliance, CCS dominates Europe and is expanding in North America.

CHAdeMO : CHAdeMO is a DC fast-charging standard easily recognized by its circular connector developed in Japan [9]. It was widely adopted by early EVs, including the Nissan Leaf and Mitsubishi i-MiEV.

- Power Levels: up to 400 kW (generally 50–150 kW).
- V2G Integration: CHAdeMO was a pioneer standard for bidirectional charging.
- Adoption: Prevalent in Japan, but the use is reducing in Europe and North America.

Currently, CHAdeMO is being replaced, especially by CCS. However, its successor, ChaoJi, promises up to 900 kW and improved compatibility with CCS.

Tesla Connectors : Tesla initially developed proprietary connectors that offered both AC and DC charging through a single compact port [9]. However, in Europe, Tesla vehicles use CCS2 due to regulations. Some of its features are:

- Power Levels: Typically, up to 250 kW (V3) and higher in newer V4 stations.
- V2G Integration: Currently, no Tesla model on the road advertises or has been certified for vehicle-to-grid (V2G) operation. The only bidirectional feature released so far is Powershare on the Cybertruck, which is limited to vehicle-to-load (V2L) and vehicle-to-home (V2H); Tesla managers stated during Investor Day (1 March 2023) that full bidirectional capability is targeted for 2025 but is “not available yet” [10].
- Adoption: In North America Tesla vehicles use Tesla’s own connector, now recognized as NACS. However, in Europe newer Tesla models use CCS2.

North American Charging Standard : The North American Charging Standard (NACS), developed from Tesla’s original design, has been standardized by SAE as J3400 (2024) [11]. It combines AC and DC fast charging in a slim, single-port layout. It should be considered that since three phase AC grid are not common in US buildings. Therefore, just single-phase AC is considered for the

connectors, requiring less pins. For legacy Level 1 & 2 charging, vehicles can still use the widely deployed SAE J1772 Type 1 plug via a simple passive adapter [9].

- Power Levels: Up to 250 kW (Tesla V3 Superchargers) and potentially higher at newer stations.
- V2G Integration: Tesla has shown interest in bidirectional charging, however, full-scale commercial V2G under NACS is not available.
- Adoption: Announcements by Ford, GM, Rivian, and other automakers to adopt NACS in North America. Due to Tesla's extensive Supercharger network, NACS is becoming a strong competitor to CCS1.

GB/T : GB/T standard is mandated by national regulations in China [9].

- Power Levels: Supports DC charging up to 237.5 kW.
- V2G Integration: Ongoing updates to GB/T protocols aim to incorporate V2G technology.
- Adoption: It is mainly used in China.

Electrical Safety Standards for EV Charging Systems in Europe

In Europe, the Combined Charging System (CCS) has emerged as the most widely adopted EV charging standard. Due to that, CCS will be the primary focus of the following sections. European electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure is governed by rigorous safety standards to protect users and equipment. Below is a detailed breakdown of the relevant standards.

IEC 61851 Series: EV Charging System Requirements : The IEC 61851 series is the core international standard for conductive EV charging systems. It defines how EV supply equipment (EVSE) should safely deliver power to vehicles [12]. IEC 61851-1 covers general requirements for chargers up to 1000 V AC or 1500 V DC input, and outputs up to 1000 V AC or 1500 V DC. It addresses operating conditions, the interface between charger and vehicle, and detailed electrical safety requirements for the EVSE. Subsequent parts cover specific implementations, AC vs. DC charging and communications:

- IEC 61851-21-1/21-2: EMC and safety requirements for on-board and off-board charging equipment (e.g. vehicle EMC and off-board charger EMC) [13].
- IEC 61851-23: Requirements for DC fast charging stations (off-board DC chargers) [12].
- IEC 61851-24: Digital communication between a DC charger and EV (control protocols for Mode 4 DC charging) [14].
- IEC 61851-25: Specific requirements for DC supply equipment. Galvanic isolation is required [15].

As mentioned before, the IEC 61851 series distinguish between AC charging (Modes 1-3, where the vehicle's onboard charger typically provides galvanic isolation) and DC charging (Mode 4, off-board charger provides DC power). The standards do not mandate an isolation transformer for AC chargers; instead, safety is achieved via protective earth and residual current devices (RCDs). In practice, EV onboard chargers include internal isolation between the mains and the battery, but the AC EVSE itself usually feeds line voltage directly to the vehicle under controlled conditions. By contrast, DC charging requires galvanic isolation of the output: it indicates that the DC supply circuit of a charging station must be an ungrounded (IT) system with continuous insulation monitoring

[16]. That is to say, the high-voltage DC connected to the EV must be isolated from the AC mains and earth. Any loss of isolation must trigger an automatic shutdown.

IEC 62196 Series: Charging Connectors and Couplers : IEC 62196 is a series of standards defining the design and safety of plugs, socket-outlets, vehicle connectors, and inlets used for EV charging [17]. These are the familiar connector types (Type 2, CCS, etc.) that physically connects the EV to the charging station. Therefore, IEC 62196 ensures interoperability and safety by standardizing dimensions, contact arrangements, and performance requirements. Major parts include:

- IEC 62196-1: General requirements and tests for EV connectors (applicable to all types) [17].
- IEC 62196-2: Specific requirements for AC charging connectors (e.g. Type 1, Type 2, and Type 3 configurations) [16].
- IEC 62196-3: Specific requirements for DC high-power charging connectors (e.g. CCS2) [18].

The IEC 62196 standards ensures that connector designs prevent user access to live contacts and can handle the electrical stresses of charging. For example, connectors must be finger-proof when disconnected – live pins cannot be touched with a finger or standardized test probe – and are weather-resistant. A minimum protection of around IP44 is required (protected against solid objects >1 mm and water splashes from any direction). When a vehicle plug is connected into a socket, the assembly achieves at least IP44 water protection, suitable for outdoor charging considering different weather conditions. IEC 62196 also specifies temperature rise limits, mechanical strength and interlock provisions. An example requirement is that the connector must not be live until it's properly engaged and the EVSE and EV have exchanged control signals – this is implemented via the control pilot pin and proximity detection in Type 2/CCS connectors.

IEC 60364-7-722: Installation Requirements for EV Charging : IEC 60364-7-722 is the specific part of the low-voltage electrical installation code (IEC 60364 series) that covers EV charging installations [13]. It applies to fixed electrical installations that supply EV charging equipment, defining wiring methods, circuit protection, and earthing specifically for EV charge points. A requirement of IEC 60364-7-722 is that each EV charging outlet or cable connection are protected from residual currents. Each AC charging point must be protected by an RCD (Residual Current Device) with a rated residual current ≤ 30 mA. For this reason, many modern charging stations include a 6 mA DC residual current monitoring device internally.

Additionally, IEC 60364-7-722 requires [13]:

- Dedicated circuits for EV charging points sized for continuous charging.
- Overcurrent protection (circuit breakers or fuses), to protect against overloads and short-circuits.
- Proper grounding arrangements: The EVSE and vehicle exposed metal must be connected following the indications of this standard.

IEC 60529: Ingress Protection (IP) Ratings : Charging stations must often operate in harsh outdoor conditions (rain, dust, cold, heat), so considerations must be taken to protect the electrical components from the environment. IEC 60529 defines the standard Ingress Protection (IP) code system for enclosures, which is commonly used to define the level of the seal against dust and water [19]. The code consists of two digits: the first for solid object protection (0–6) and the second

for water ingress protection (0–9). European EVSE products typically carry IP ratings such as IP54 or higher for outdoor units, meaning they are dust-protected (5: limited ingress, no harmful deposit) and splash-proof from all directions (4: water splashing against the enclosure). For example, a wall-mounted home charger installed outdoors is commonly IP54. The IEC 61851 and IEC 62196 standards reference IEC 60529 to test that enclosures and connectors meet these IP ratings. For example, IEC 61851-1 requires that enclosure leakage of water must not impair safety or functionality. Connectors per IEC 62196-1 are tested for water ingress with spray conditions to ensure they meet at least IP44.

EU Directives and Mandatory Certifications (CE Marking) : In Europe, EV charging stations must follow European Union directives that ensure safety and electromagnetic compatibility in addition to technical standards mentioned above. These are mandatory for EVSE sold or used in the EU. Main directives and certifications are:

- Low Voltage Directive – 2014/35/EU: This directive considers the electrical safety of equipment that work between 50 V and 1000 V AC (or 75–1500 V DC), where most EV charging stations work [20].
- Electromagnetic Compatibility Directive (EMC) – 2014/30/EU. The EMC Directive indicates the limits on conducted and radiated emissions and requires immunity [21].
- Environmental and Material Directives: Although it is not directly related to electrical safety, EVSE must comply with Restriction of Hazardous Substances (RoHS) directive (2011/65/EU) [22].

DC Converter architecture

The isolated DC-DC stage of an external electric vehicle charger must adapt the high-voltage rectified DC bus (typically hundreds of volts) to the voltage level of the battery. It must also provide galvanic isolation for safety reasons [15]. This isolation ensures that there is no direct electrical connection between the grid side and the vehicle battery, protecting users and equipment from high voltage and eliminating ground loop currents. In practice, this isolation is usually achieved by means of transformers.

Commonly, high-power charger designs use unidirectional isolated converter topologies. The most common topologies are the phase-shifted full-bridge (PSFB) converter and various resonant converters (such as LLC resonant types) [9]. In a PSFB, the primary side consists of four semiconductor switches in an H-bridge arrangement that turns the DC bus into a high-frequency AC waveform. The secondary side then uses a diode bridge rectifier to convert the transformer's AC output to DC of the battery. In practice, the transformer's alternating output is passively rectified into a unipolar DC waveform by the diodes, which is then filtered and delivered to charge the battery. This approach is relatively simple and robust since only the primary side switches require active control. In addition, diodes inherently limit the power flow to one direction, making the parallelization of different modules easier.

However, to enable Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology, the DC-DC converter must be bidirectional. This is generally obtained by replacing the diodes on the secondary side with actively controlled semiconductor switches (IGBTs or MOSFETs). The resulting architecture is often referred to as

a dual active bridge (DAB) converter [23]. Resonant CLLC converters are also common for this purpose [24].

Another challenge is that the nominal voltage of vehicle batteries has been increasing significantly, from earlier plug-in hybrid batteries operating around 200 V to current electric vehicles with battery voltages that can reach up to 900 V. This increasing voltage range forces the charger's DC-DC converter to accommodate a wide output voltage range, complicating the design of efficient converters. Most power converter topologies are optimized to operate efficiently at specific voltage points or within relatively narrow voltage ranges; thus, ensuring high efficiency across such a broad battery voltage window requires more complex control strategies, selectable transformer turns ratios, multi-winding transformers, etc. Designing these converters to maintain high efficiency, reliability, and safety across the entire voltage spectrum is a significant engineering challenge in modern EV charger development.

Communication layers

Electric vehicle charging systems rely on multiple communication interfaces to ensure a safe, efficient and user-friendly charging process. These interfaces operate at different levels: between the charging station and the user, between the Electric Vehicle (EV) and the charging station, and between the charging station and the backend management system.

Communication between the charging station and the user : The user communication interface encompasses the interaction between the electric vehicle driver (user) and the charging station. This is typically done through a Human-Machine Interface (HMI) on the charger (such as a display screen, indicator lights and control buttons or touch screens) and through authentication/payment devices (such as RFID card readers, contactless payment terminals and/ or ISO 15118 based Plug&Charge). In addition, the chargers also support smartphone-based interactions such as, a mobile app to initiate a session remotely or via direct Bluetooth/Wi-Fi connection with the station, but in most cases the app communicates through the backend. The messages exchanged on this interface are usually authentication (user account or payment method identification) and login/logout commands. User communications are used for:

- Authentication and authorization: verifying the user's identity or payment method before charging. This can be done by ISO 15118 based Plug&Charge, reading an RFID card or token, processing a credit card payment, or receiving a command from a mobile app. Successful authentication causes the station to allow power to flow.
- User instructions and feedback: The charging station communicates information to the user via displays or LEDs, e.g., showing the price, charging progress (energy supplied, charging duration) and any error or warning messages. European standards require a transparent display of prices (per kWh, per session, per minute, etc.) before and during charging, so that users are informed of the costs and further aspects, such as transparent (signed) metering data.
- Session control: allows the user to start or stop charging sessions and select options. For example, a user can press a start button after plugging in or choose a charging profile if offered. The interface sends these options to the charger control system.
- Safety and assistance: Some interface elements, such as the emergency stop buttons, are provided for safety and, although not a data protocol, their activation is communicated to imme-

diately interrupt the charging process.

Communication between the charging station and the Electric Vehicle (ISO 15118-20) : The EV communication interface manages the data exchange between the Electric Vehicle and Charging Station (EVSE). It is primarily a machine-to-machine communication link that operates through the charging connector. In conductive charging, the interface uses the control pilot and proximity lines defined in IEC 61851-1 for basic signaling (such as EV detection and charging availability switching), and leverages Power Line Communication (PLC) for high-level digital communication.

The communication stack is governed by the ISO 15118 family of standards, in particular the latest ISO 15118-20 (2022) introduces the V2G technology [25]. In addition, latest ISO 15118-20, advanced the automated authentication mechanism of “Plug&Charge” to a mutual authentication (mTLS) and supports coordinated bidirectional power transfer (exchange of energy prices or schedules) to optimize how and when the electric vehicle is (dis-)charged [25].

The message exchange between the EV and EVSE defined in ISO 15118 covers all aspects of session management [25]:

- **Authentication:** When the EV is plugged in, the EVSE and the EV exchange messages to establish a secure link and identify each other. This eliminates the need for the user to swipe a card: the vehicle itself automatically authorizes by exchanging cryptographic credentials with the station.
- **Negotiation of charging parameters:** The electric vehicle and the charger negotiate the electrical charging parameters. For a DC session, for example, the EV communicates its battery requirements (maximum voltage, current, target state of charge, etc.), and the EVSE communicates its available output capacities; they then agree on an appropriate charging current/voltage profile. This negotiation is either continuous or iterative, allowing for dynamic power flow adjustment. For AC, the protocol can similarly coordinate acceptable current levels beyond the basic IEC 61851 PWM (Pulse Width Modulation) signal.
- **Real-time control and monitoring:** During charging, the EV sends status information (such as the state of charge of its battery or any fault conditions) and can request changes (e.g., to reduce current or stop when charging targets are met). The EVSE sends control commands (such as start/stop signals or current limits) and can also send informational messages (such as current energy price or tariff data, in support of smart charging). ISO 15118 supports V2G use cases, which means that the EVSE or backend can provide a tariff or charging control schedule to the EV, which the EV can use to optimize charging times and rates.
- **Bidirectional power coordination:** If the EV and charger are V2G compliant according to ISO 15118-20, communication will also include negotiation of discharge parameters. The EV can indicate its ability to feed back energy, and control messages accordingly.
- **Session termination and data transfer:** At the end of a charge (or if interrupted), the EV and EVSE perform a controlled shutdown of the power flow. The EV can receive a final summary (e.g., total energy delivered) and the EVSE can get the data it needs (such as the final meter reading or charging session details). If Plug&Charge is being used, the transaction log for the session is linked to the certificate and contract identifier that were used, allowing the backend systems to process billing for that session.

Communication between the charging station and the Backend (OCPP 2.1) : The backend communication interface connects the charging station (EVSE) to remote management systems, typically the charging point operator's backend, usually a cloud-based charging station management system (CSMS). This is usually a connection to the Internet or an enterprise network that allows the operator or service provider to monitor and control the station. The de facto standard protocol for this interface is the Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP), developed by the Open Charge Alliance. OCPP (currently version 2.1) defines the structured exchange of messages between a charger and the backend, ranging from session authorization to billing data. OCPP is not an official standard (e.g., ISO, CEN or IEC), but it has been widely adopted in Europe and around the world as an interoperability solution, as it allows charging stations and network software from different vendors to work together [9]. In fact, in Europe, OCPP is often required in public charging infrastructure deployments to ensure openness. Efforts are underway to formalize it as an international standard, but as of OCPP 2.1 it remains an industry-driven specification.

The OCPP protocol defines a wide range of message types (in a request-response pattern) that the EVSE and backend exchange. They span functional categories such as Authorize, BootNotification, StartTransaction/StopTransaction, MeterValues, StatusNotification, FirmwareUpdate and many more, each with a defined data model. OCPP 2.1 (released in 2025) is the latest version that includes support for ISO 15118-20 with bidirectional power transfer and new functional blocks on Bidirectional energy flows and Distributed Energy Resources (DER) control.

The purpose of backend communication is to enable centralized management and integration of the charging station into broader services. A few functionalities offered by OCPP are listed below. Authentication and authorization: When a user triggers an authentication by e.g., presenting a token or via Plug&Charge, the station can use OCPP to ask the backend to authorize that user. For example, the station sends an authorize message with the RFID tag identifier or EV certificate data; the backend checks whether this credential is valid (e.g., whether it corresponds to a registered customer or a valid payment method) and responds with an acceptance or a rejection.

This ensures that the station is only energized for authorized users and links the session to a customer account or payment record. Control and monitoring of charging sessions: The backend can remotely monitor sessions and receive real-time status updates. OCPP allows an operator or automated system to start or stop charging. Meanwhile, the station sends messages whenever its status changes (e.g., from Available to Busy, Charging, Terminating, or if an error occurs). This allows the network operator to have an up-to-date view of the status of each charger and to display availability to users. Periodic heartbeat messages also assure the backend that the charger is online.

- Load management (smart charging): OCPP supports charging management by allowing the backend to send charging profiles or power limits to the station. For example, a central system can impose a maximum charging speed by instructing each charger not to exceed certain current values. Through OCPP, the backend can impose a schedule or constraints that the EVSE then applies in its control of EV charging (in concert with the EV communication interface).
- Billing and metering: One function of the backend link is to transfer (signed) meter data for billing. The EVSE typically measures the energy supplied to the EV. The backend uses these chargeDetailRecords to calculate the cost of charging or to record the consumption in the user's account.

- Firmware updates and diagnostics: To maintain reliability and security, charging stations receive remote firmware updates through the backend.

5.1.3 Benchmark of commercial charging station characteristics

Commercially available charging stations range from simple AC wallboxes to large-scale DC fast chargers. The main differences lie in power level, charging speed and whether the design supports unidirectional or bidirectional operation. As electric vehicle adoption grows, manufacturers are expanding their offerings to meet residential, commercial and public charging needs, with increasing emphasis on features such as smart connectivity, payment options and V2G compatibility.

AC charging stations

AC chargers rely on the vehicle's on-board charger to convert alternating current into the direct current needed by the battery. They are usually less expensive and easier to install than high-power DC chargers. These chargers are further divided into unidirectional (charging only) and bidirectional (charging and discharging).

Unidirectional AC charging stations : There are a large number of unidirectional mode 3 AC chargers. The following table lists some of the commercial AC chargers.

Table 5.2: *Unidirectional commercial AC chargers [26]–[28].*

Model	Input voltage	Power	Manufacturer	Communications	Standard/Protocols
Lite Kubo	Three phase or single-phase AC	22 kW	Veltium	Ethernet Bluetooth	IEC 61851-1 IP54
Commander 2	Three phase or single-phase AC	22 kW	Wallbox	Touch screen Wi-Fi Ethernet Bluetooth 3G/4G	IP54 IEC 61851-1 IEC 61851-22 IEC 62196-2
Viars	Single phase AC	7.4 kW	Orbis	Ethernet Wifi 4G	OCPP 1.6 IP44 IEC 61851-1 EN IEC 61851-21-2 EN IEC 63000

Bidirectional AC charging stations : Bidirectional AC chargers allow both charging from the grid and returning power to the grid (V2G). They are less common than unidirectional units due to additional hardware requirements and evolving standards. In the following table some commercial and announced AC bidirectional chargers can be seen.

Table 5.3: Bidirectional commercial AC chargers [29], [30].

Model	Input voltage	Power	Manufacturer	Communications	Standard/Protocols
Go 2	Three phase or single-phase AC	7 kW with single phase and 22 kW for three phases	Zaptec	Bluetooth Wifi 4G	IEC 61851-1, IEC 61439-7 IEC 62955, IP54 IEC 62955, OCPP 1.6 ISO 15118
Mobilize Power-Box	Three phase AC	22 kW	Mobilize	Wifi Ethernet	OCPP 1.6, EN 61851 EN 62196, EN 50620 IEC 61439-7, IEC 62196-2 EN 17186, IEC 62893 IEC 62305-4, IP55 ISO 15118-20

DC charging stations

DC charging stations can be classified based on whether they are unidirectional or bidirectional, and on whether their input power is AC or DC.

AC/DC unidirectional charging stations : Unidirectional AC/DC chargers include the necessary power electronics to convert three-phase AC directly to DC at higher power levels. These devices are typically installed in public or commercial environments where faster charging speeds are required. In the following table some commercial DC unidirectional are listed.

Table 5.4: AC/DC Unidirectional Chargers. [31]–[34]

Model	Input voltage	Power	Manufacturer	Communications	Standard/Protocols
UltraCharge30	Three phase AC	30 kW	Rolec	4G Bluetooth Touch screen Ethernet	OCPP 1.6 IP55 EN 61851 IEC 62196 DIN 70121 ISO 15118 P&C
EVEMOVE II	Three phase AC	240–360 kW	EVEMOVE	4G Ethernet Wifi	IP54 ISO 11518 (P&C) OCPP 1.6

Model	Input voltage	Power	Manufacturer	Communications	Standard/Protocols
Denka	Three phase AC	20 kW / 40 kW	V2C	Wifi Ethernet Bluetooth 4G	OCPP 1.6
					IEC 61851-1 IEC 61851-23 IEC 62477-1 IEC 61851-21-2 EN 61851-1-21-2 ISO 15118
Supernova	Three phase AC	60 kW	Wallbox	Ethernet 2G/3G/4G/LTE Touch display	ISO 15118
					IEC 61851-1 IEC 61851-23 IEC 61851-21-2 OCPP 1.6

AC/DC bidirectional charging stations : Currently, most bidirectional chargers are AC/DC-s. In most cases they are used for private (dis-) charging purposes, e.g., home charging, and have just entered the market. However, it is expected that the number of available DC bidirectional chargers will increase throughout 2025, therefore, reaching a higher market penetration. In the following table some already commercially available and announced DC bidirectional chargers are listed alongside their primary characteristics.

Table 5.5: AC/DC Bidirectional Chargers. [35]–[38]

Model	Input voltage	Power	Manufacturer	Communications	Standard/Protocols
Quasar 2	Three phase AC	11.5 kW	Wallbox	Bluetooth 4G Wifi	No public information available yet.
					ISO 15118-20 OCPP 2.0.1
Ambibox DC Wallbox	Three phase AC	11 kW	Ambi charge	Ethernet WLAN RS485/RS232	IP54 EN 61000-6-2 EN 61000-6-3 IEC 61851-1 IEC 61851-23
					IP43 IEC 61851-1 IEC 61851-23
HIGHBURY DC Bi-Directional	Three phase AC	11 kW	Rectifier Technologies	Wifi Bluetooth Cellular Ethernet RS485 MODBUS	UL 1741 UL 9741 ISO 15118-2 CHAdEMO V2X OCPP 2.0
					CHAdEMO V2X UL 1741 UL 9741
Fermata Energy FE-20	Three phase AC	20 kW	Fermata	-	CHAdEMO V2X UL 1741 UL 9741

DC/DC charging stations : DC/DC chargers are designed primarily for use in charging hubs, with multiple high-power chargers. In these configurations, DC input is provided to allow the creation

of a local DC microgrid, which avoids the need for individual AC to DC rectification at each charger. This approach can increase overall system efficiency. Commercial availability is still very limited, as only the Rapid ST 200/400 from Ingeteam have reached the market. This is mainly because connecting directly to the AC mains is simpler than building a dedicated DC bus. Consequently, DC/DC chargers are currently reserved for more complex charging areas (with different DC load, chargers, Photovoltaic panels, etc.), where the extra complexity is offset by meaningful efficiency gains. In the following table the main characteristics of the RAPID St 200/400 charger can be seen.

Table 5.6: DC/DC Chargers. [39]

Model	Input voltage	Power	Manufacturer	Communications	Standard/Protocols
RAPID 200/400	DC	200–400 kW	Ingeteam	Touch screen 3G/4G Ethernet	IEC 61851-1 IEC 61851-23 IEC 61851-24 CHAdeMO 1.0.0 DIN 70121 ISO 15118 IEC 61000 OCPP

5.1.4 Key Gaps and Barriers

Although bidirectional EV charging stations are now technically feasible, several obstacles still delay their large-scale deployment. Chief among them is the overlap between CCS (particularly CCS2) in Europe and the legacy CHAdeMO ecosystem. Supporting both protocols forces manufacturers to certify the same hardware against two largely incompatible communication stacks, thereby increasing cost and time to market. Inside the charger, bidirectional operation is technically more demanding than simple one-way charging. Power stages must be fitted with an additional active bridge and more complicated modulation strategies. These requirements translate directly to the complexity of the system, all of which raise the price of the charging station. The task is complicated further by the broad battery-voltage window found in today's vehicles. Early plug-in hybrids charged at roughly 200 V, whereas the newest performance EVs approach 900 V. Achieving high efficiency across such a wide span forces engineers towards more complicated designs, improving performance but adding cost and complexity. Finally, the software layer that enables vehicle-to-grid services is only partially in place. The current OCPP specification and ISO 15118-20 do include all the messages needed for bidirectional power exchange, yet only a minority of public chargers have upgraded to OCPP 2.1 and ISO 15118-20 V2G, and relatively few commercially available EVs ship with ISO 15118-20 V2G fully enabled. Compounding the problem, IEC 61851-23:2023—the safety and hardware reference for DC chargers—still anchors all state diagrams to the legacy ISO 15118-2/DIN 70121 message set and even though it includes the basics for bidirectional charging, ISO 15118-20 is not considered.

5.1.5 Bidirectional charging station Key Performance Parameters

Building on the discussion above, the benchmark key performance parameters (KPPs) for the DC electric-vehicle charging station are as follows:

Table 5.7: Benchmark KPPs for the bidirectional charging station.

Bidirectional charging station feature	Supported
V2G communication (vehicle ↔ charging station) and Plug&Charge support	ISO 15118-20
Back-end communication with V2G support	OCPP 2.1
Bidirectional power flow	Bidirectional power stage
Wide Output Voltage	Wide output voltage from 200 V to 900 V by using adequate power converter architecture and control strategies
Power output	Discharge/charge at 7 kW while preserving high power density through an optimized converter architecture and advanced control strategies.
Safety	Following the recommendations by: IEC 60529, IEC 60364-7-722, IEC 62196 Series, IEC 61851

5.1.6 Conclusions and recommendations for NEVERFLAT

Bidirectional charging has progressed from conceptual research to deployable reality, and the technology required to design and manufacture bidirectional DC charging stations is available today. Nevertheless, integrating reversible power flow, secure data exchange and full regulatory compliance imposes a higher level of design complexity than that of conventional unidirectional chargers, which in turn elevates manufacturing cost.

For communications, ISO 15118-20 governs vehicle-to-grid messaging and Plug&Charge authentication, while OCPP 2.0.1 extends bidirectional capability to the back-end network. These protocols, combined with the standards defined in IEC 60529, IEC 60364-7-722, IEC 62196, and IEC 61851, define a pathway for bidirectional charging stations.

On the power stage side, the most suitable converter architectures are the CLLC resonant converter and the dual-active-bridge (DAB), both of which achieve high power density and intrinsic bidirectional energy transfer. However, the required wide output voltage demanded by differences in the voltage of the battery pack, complicates its design.

Therefore, from the perspective of the charging station itself, and leaving aside critical factors such as business models and the broader integration of V2G technology into the grid (addressed in subsequent sections), it is technically feasible to manufacture bidirectional chargers today.

Thus, currently, the principal barrier to widespread deployment is the additional cost of these chargers, which currently offers users no clear immediate benefit. Moreover, limited vehicle-side market readiness makes it difficult for consumers to justify investing in this technology.

Accordingly, it is recommended to develop a low-power 7 kW DC bidirectional charger for NEVERFLAT. The reduced power level lowers hardware and installation costs, making the product more accessible for residential and small-commercial sites. Establishing a network of such chargers will facilitate smoother adoption of V2G technology and pave the way for broader market acceptance.

5.2 DC Microgrid

Microgrids are a suitable, reliable and clean solution to integrate distributed generation into the mains grid. In that field, DC microgrids are revolutionizing energy systems by directly integrating renewable energy sources without AC/DC conversions. This section provides a DC microgrids state of the art.

5.2.1 Methodology

This document adopts a structured methodological approach. Firstly, a state of the art analysis is provided, which compares DC and AC microgrids, and explains the main DC microgrid components, control hierarchy, strategies, operation modes and standards. Secondly, a benchmark of existing DC microgrids is shown and gaps remaining are identified. Finally, NEVERFLAT key performance parameters are identified and the conclusions are explained.

5.2.2 SotA Analysis - DC Microgrids

Microgrids are localized power networks that integrate distributed energy resources, storage systems, and loads within a bounded electrical domain [7], [8]. They are engineered to operate either connected to the main utility grid or independently in islanded mode, providing enhanced resilience and flexibility. In the past, AC became the standard due to its benefits over DC at generation, transmission and distribution level [7]. AC microgrids are more extended than DC microgrids due to their advantages:

- Capability of integrating with conventional utility grid or in islanded mode, which makes them versatile.
- Simpler protection and fault management. The use of periodic zero voltage crossings facilitates the extinction suppression of fault currents.
- Compatibility with the alternating rotating machines and AC based loads.

However, nowadays the advantages of DC microgrids over AC microgrids are becoming more relevant over AC microgrids. Their main advantages are listed below:

- DC microgrids are simpler systems as they do not require frequency synchronization and reactive power management [8].
- Renewable energy sources (e.g. photovoltaic or fuel cells), energy storage (e.g. batteries) and DC loads, provide/require DC power.
- DC microgrids facilitate their coupling [40]. DC microgrids avoid AC-DC conversions, which leads to lower energy losses and increased system efficiency, reducing overall system costs [41].

Figure 5.1 shows a diagram of an AC and a DC microgrid. Both cases are bus-based, which means that the energy resources (PV and wind), storage (battery), loads and the grid are connected to the respective bus. The difference remains in the topology of that bus (AC vs. DC) which determines which converters are needed to allow the connection of all the elements.

Figure 5.1: AC (left) vs. DC (right) microgrid layouts.

Main Components of DC Microgrids

A DC microgrid is formed by different components that work together to guarantee reliable and efficient energy generation and distribution [42]. Table 5.8 explains each element function (DERs, ESSs, loads, PCC, communication and control) whereas Figure 5.2 shows a DC microgrid layout, including all those elements explained: DERs (PV and wind generation and fuel cell), ESSs (battery supercapacitor) and loads, all of them connected to the DC bus with their respective converters (communication by the control system) and to the mains grid through the PCC.

Table 5.8: Main components of DC microgrids.

Component	Description and classification	Functions
Distributed Energy Resources (DERs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Renewable energy sources (PVs, wind turbines, fuel cells). - Traditional sources (e.g. diesel generators) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide greater flexibility and reduce dependence on centralized grids. - Improve reliability, sustainability and efficiency of DC microgrids.
Energy Storage Systems (ESSs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Batteries (lithium-ion, lead-acid, flow batteries), supercapacitors, and flywheels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide energy storage and backup power, balance loads, and manage energy effectively.
Loads and demand side management (DSM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Critical loads: demand an uninterrupted power supply (loads in hospitals, data centers, and other essential services). - Non-critical loads: can adapt to flexible consumption patterns. - Demand side management (DSM) helps in optimizing energy consumption patterns in DC microgrids. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DSM focuses on shifting energy demand from peak to off-peak hours, balancing supply and demand, reducing energy storage requirements and improving system performance.
Point of common coupling (PCC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interface between the microgrid and the main utility grid to enable power exchange and integration with the broader electrical network. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinate multiple renewable energy sources connected to the microgrid, managing their simultaneous power injection into the main grid while ensuring compliance with relevant standards.

Component	Description and classification	Functions
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protocols such as Modbus (simplicity for controller-to-device communication) and IEC 61850 (interoperability across different equipment). - Distributed Network Protocol 3 (DNP3) can be used in supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA). - Message Telemetry Transport (MQTT) or TCP/UDP-based protocols often appear in Internet of Things (IoT) driven solutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinate control actions and share operational data efficiently. - The protocols help central or distributed controllers to exchange status updates, control signals and safety parameters in near real time.
Control system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary, secondary, tertiary. - Centralized, decentralized, distributed. 	- Control the coordination of DERs, ESSs, and loads to maintain stable and efficient operation.

Figure 5.2: DC microgrid layout.

Control Hierarchy and Strategies

The control system of a DC microgrid follows a hierarchical structure formed by three levels:

- i **Primary control:** It operates at the local level and is responsible for immediate, fast-response tasks (power balancing, voltage regulation, load sharing) [42]. It is usually implemented through droop control methods, which adjust the output of distributed energy resources based on voltage variations at the DC bus, without the need for communication between them [43].
- ii **Secondary control:** It ensures that the power supplied by all the converters is equal to the power scheduled by the tertiary control and facilitates the coordination of distributed generators [44]. It uses communication links to collect data and provide system adjustments.
- iii **Tertiary control:** Also known as Energy Management System (EMS), it ensures proper load sharing among microgrids within a cluster [44]. It is focused on optimizing power flows, ensuring energy efficiency and preserving economic operation across the microgrid network [40].

According to the control strategies of DC microgrids, they can be mainly divided into three categories:

- **Centralized control:** A single central controller will try to maintain the DC bus voltage processing all the relevant data [44]. It can optimize power flow, deal with different loads, and handle real-time adjustments. It has limitations like vulnerability to single-point failures, reduced scalability and dependency on communication links [42].
- **Decentralized control:** Control strategies are achieved exclusively by local controllers, which manage operations independently without communication links. One example of decentralized control is the droop control method. In that approach, a “droop curve” is established, which relates the output voltage of a power source to the current it supplies [43]. As the current increases, the output voltage decreases according to a predefined slope, as shown in Figure 5.3, where:
 - U_{nom} : Nominal voltage
 - U_{db} : Voltage deadband range (no power transfer)
 - U_2 : Voltage at which the converters will transfer full power from the energy source towards the DC bus.
 - U_3 : Voltage at which the converters will transfer full power from the DC bus towards the energy sink.

It offers reliability and simplicity, as it eliminates the dependency on communication links. However, its limitation includes lower accuracy due to the lack of information among different power electronic sources.

- **Distributed control:** It combines the strengths of both centralized and decentralized strategies. There is a distributed controller in each power electronic source to ensure good voltage regulation and proper load sharing, but they are also linked to each other by a communication link. It enables collaborative decision without relying on a single central controller, improving resilience and scalability [45].

Operation Modes of DC Microgrids

DC microgrids can be operated either in the islanded or the grid-connected mode.

- **Islanded mode:** In this mode, the microgrid operates isolated from the mains grid, providing power to the local loads independently. Therefore, it relies completely on its own DERs and ESSs to meet the local demand [46]. It is very useful in areas with unreliable or non-existent grid infrastructure.
- **Grid-connected mode:** The microgrid is connected to the main power grid, allowing the exchange of power between the microgrid and the mains grid. It can draw power from the grid during periods of high demand or supply the excess of electricity back to the grid when generation exceeds local demand. The main advantages are to provide a reliable and stable power supply by leveraging the utility grid’s infrastructure and reducing the need for additional ESSs.

DC Microgrid Standards

According to regulatory framework, the regulatory environment for microgrids is complex since it combines multiple existing regulations that have not been specifically devised for microgrids [47].

Figure 5.3: Example of droop control curve. [43]

First Standards : Table 5.9 summarizes some general descriptions and scopes of existing standards

Table 5.9: General descriptions of standards related to DC Microgrids.

Nr.	Standard	Description	Scope
1	IEEE 1547	Criteria and requirements for interconnection of DERs with the mains grid.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designed for AC systems and some of its contents can be used as a reference when designing DC systems. - Islanded and grid connected modes. - Normal and abnormal operation. - Requirements for distributed sources.
2	ETSI EN 300 132-3-1	Power supply interface at the input to data/telecom equipment. Part 3, subpart 1: direct current source up to 400 V.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designed for data/telecom equipment. - For voltage levels of up to 400 V. - Voltage level in normal operation and requirements for abnormal operation. - Limit of fault current. - Grounding and EMC.
3	IEC SG4	LVDC distribution system up to 1500 V.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinate the standardization of different areas (e.g. data centers, commercial buildings, etc.). - Energy efficiency, EMC. - Life cycle, protection and grounding.

Nr.	Standard	Description	Scope
4	EPRI and Emergence	Standard for 400 Vdc in buildings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DC bus voltage limits consideration. - Guidelines for testing in abnormal operation. - Outdoor electrical uses, including electric vehicle charging and outdoor LED lighting.

Nowadays, Current/OS is trying to standardize DC microgrids internationally.

Current/ OS : Founded in 2021, Current/OS is a nonprofit organization defining standards for DC microgrids and installations. It is formed by over 80 partners across America, Europe and Asia, with industry leaders such as ABB, Mersen, Schneider Electric, Tridonic or Siemens on board and a liaison a member of the IEC Systems Committee for Low Voltage Direct Current.

There are four key considerations behind Current/OS's technical decisions: (1) addressing DC safety concerns; (2) creating a multi-vendor system; (3) making DC installations simple for any professional: easy to design, install, control and maintain; (4) taking building energy resilience and flexibility to unseen levels. Current/OS technical. Current/OS rules are collected in a public document that can be easily downloaded from Current/OS's website [48].

Table 5.10: *Current/OS: rules and benefits.*

Rules	Benefits
Voltage bands	Global convergence within IEC.
Power Management	Reduce power demand for resilience.
Electrical Protection	Arc-free, minimal design, 66% cable-saving installations.
Pre-Charging	Well-established to energize the DC microgrids.
Earthing	TNS-isolated C&I applications are safer, easier and more efficient.

- **Voltage Bands:** Current/OS defines different voltage bands which are shown in Figure 4. With DC systems' microgrids, nominal voltage value is just a label. The key values are the voltage band limits inside which the system operates. Those specific voltage bands defined by Current OS, have been formalized by IEC technical report 63282: system bus voltage unipolar or bipolar with 1400 / 700 / 350 labels.
- **Power Management:** Current/OS defines a control-loop hierarchy based on primary, secondary and tertiary control. The primary control is based on droop control for power balancing; secondary control for voltage restoration (islanding and grid-reconnection) and tertiary control for energy management. With respect to primary control, the power converters regulate the current flow according to the voltage level sensed and a programmable droop curve with the goal of balancing the power input and output in the grid.
- **Electrical protection:** Current/OS uses the concept of zones to reduce complexity while ensuring effective protection for DC microgrids. The concept of zones consists of mapping out and electrical schematic to classify areas based on their level of risk and protection from the most dangerous (DC Zone 0) to the safest (DC Zone 4).

Figure 5.4: Current O/S voltage bands. [48]

The general fault protective solution is safety wire inter-trip. Alongside the power cable, a small 48 V wire runs in parallel within the same cable, serving as a high impedance signal. If it is short-circuited, the signal drops to zero, turning down the connected source and disconnecting the power feed to the grid.

Table 5.11: Current/OS protection zones.

DC Zone	Main characteristics of the circuits
DC Zone 0	- High short-circuit current source. - No overcurrent protection.
DC Zone 1	- Overcurrent protection devices (OCPD) on the DC bus have breaking time < 50 μ s (e.g. EMCBs and fuses). - Multiple sources, all connected to a common distribution board.
DC Zone 2.1	- Sources cannot deliver a current much higher than the nominal. - OCPD with breaking time < 50 μ s on the DC bus. - Energy stored in capacitors does not exceed 600 J. - Multiple sources, all connected to a single distribution board.
DC Zone 2.2	- Sources (or inductor) that limit the fault current rise and peak. - OCPD with breaking time < 1 μ s (e.g. SCHCBs) on the DC bus. - Multiple distributed sources.
DC Zone 3	- OCPD with breaking time < 10 μ s (e.g. SCHCBs) on the DC bus. - Multiple distributed sources.
DC Zone 4	- Same as DC Zone 3 with single source.

- **Precharging:** Current/OS specifies a black start and precharge procedure:
 1. Step 1: black start with almost no current to allow the bus to reach U2.
 2. Step 2: precharge the capacitors with limited current to avoid over current protections tripping.
 3. Step 3: activation of the loads.
- **Earthing:** Faults and disturbances in the DC grid shall not propagate or cause malfunctions in the AC grid and similarly, faults and disturbances in the AC side shall not propagate or cause malfunction in the DC part of the grid. Therefore, in Current/OS installations only galvanically isolated converters shall be used for interfacing between the AC and the DC grid. Additionally, Current/OS recommends a TNS configuration, or single-point grounding for the DC side, earthing the midpoint of the DC voltage band.

5.2.3 Benchmark of Existing DC Microgrids

This section summarizes the main characteristics of fourteen case studies of DC microgrid existing in the world (info extracted from [42]). As it can be seen, all of them have solar PV as primary source and are coupled with battery storage, commonly lithium-ion.

Table 5.12: Summary of DC microgrid projects in the world. [42]

Case study	Power rating	Energy Sources	Storage	Operation mode	Control strategy	Voltage level	Primary application
Xiamen University, China [49]	150 kW	Solar PV	Lead Acid 87 kWh	Grid connected	Centralized	380 V _{DC}	Commercial building
Burlington DC Microgrid, Canada [50]	20 kW	Solar PV, natural gas	200 kW / 100 kWh VRFB	Grid connected	Decentralized	±380 V _{DC}	Industrial demo
Bosch DC Microgrid, California [51]	288 kW	Solar PV	180 kWh lithium-ion battery	Grid connected	Centralized	380 V _{DC}	Commercial facility
Okiubica, Sanitation Quebec, Japan [52]	50 kW	Solar PV (20 kW) + 30 kW grid	25 kWh lithium-ion batteries	Islanded	Centralized	380 V _{DC}	Office
Nobusaka Island DC Microgrid, Japan [53]	9 kW	Solar PV (8 kW) + wind (1 kW)	48 kWh lithium-ion battery	Islanded	Decentralized	360 V _{DC}	Island power supply
Kirtland Air Force Base, USA [54]	250 kW	Solar PV, natural gas generator	200 kWh lithium-ion battery	Grid connected	Centralized	±375 V _{DC}	Military testbed
Pitt Ohio Trucking Terminal, USA [55]	55.4 kW	Solar PV (50.4 kW) + wind (5 kW)	75 kWh battery	Grid connected	Distributed	380 V _{DC}	Commercial
Federal University of Pará, Brazil [56]	1.47 kW	Solar PV	9.5 kWh battery	Islanded	Centralized	24 V _{DC}	Research laboratory
Coconut Island, Hawaii, USA [57]	6.16 kW	Solar PV	8 kW/ 8 kWh battery	Islanded	Centralized	48 V _{DC}	Island, remote facility
TACC, USA [58]	500 kW	Solar PV (200 kW) + 300 kW grid	200 kWh battery	Grid connected	Distributed	380 V _{DC}	Data center
Fort Bragg, USA [59]	153 kW	Solar PV	100 kWh battery	Grid connected	Centralized	380 V _{DC}	Military

Case study	Power rating	Energy Sources	Storage	Operation mode	Control strategy	Voltage level	Primary application
Eindhoven, Netherlands [60]	2 kW	Solar PV, supplemented by grid	No reported	Grid connected	Distributed	380 V _{DC}	Commercial Building
Fraunhofer Institute, Germany [61]	30 kW	Solar PV, μ CHP unit	100 kWh battery	Grid connected	Decentralized	380 V _{DC}	commercial Demo
CESI RICERCA DER Microgrid, Italy [62]	25 kW	Solar PV (10 kW) + diesel engine (7 kW) + wind (8 kW)	100 kWh battery	Grid connected	Centralized	380 V _{DC}	Military

5.2.4 Key Gaps and Barriers

Despite the advantages of DC microgrids, there are some challenges that need to be fulfilled for their widespread utilization. The main key gaps are:

- Voltage stability and control: the fluctuating energy flows require advanced control algorithms. They require optimization to balance performance and cost.
- Protection and fault management: higher complexity due to the lack of natural zero crossing-points.
- Standardization: a lack of solid common protocols and the absence of standardized components that guarantee compatibility among devices from different manufacturers complicates the integration and the scalability.
- High initial costs: the bidirectionality affects also the cost, as there are needed bidirectional converters, and advanced storage systems.

In overall, the main barriers of the DC microgrids are the technical difficulties in maintaining voltage stability and protection, and the lack of a solid standardization, along with the high initial cost.

5.2.5 DC Microgrid key performance parameters

Following the elaborations above, the following benchmark key performance parameters (KPPs) for the DC microgrid are derived:

Table 5.13: Benchmark KPPs for the DC microgrid.

DC Microgrid features	Feature type	Supported
Components	Distributed Energy Sources (DERs)	PVs
	Energy Storage Systems (ESSs)	Lithium-ion battery, electric vehicle battery.

DC Microgrid features	Feature type	Supported
	Loads and Demand Management (DSM)	Non-critical loads. At least one DC charger for electric vehicle.
Control strategy		Decentralized or distributed (depending on commercial inverters options).
Operation modes		Islanded and grid-connected.

5.2.6 Conclusions and recommendations for NEVERFLAT

All DC microgrids have a huge potential for transforming energy systems based on renewable energies, improving their energy efficiency and supporting decentralized power generation. Although DC microgrids face several challenges such as the voltage stability and protection, global efforts to create standardized protocols will help them to play an important role in future energy systems.

5.3 Bidirectional Charging Service

The evolution of electric vehicle ecosystems has seen enormous challenges especially with the fragmentation of the market and various players in the ecosystem. The interoperability between them has been a major concern in enabling a smooth charging experience for the end consumer. This very challenge paved the path for the rise of eRoaming platforms that enabled the interoperability between the actors involved by acting as a central point of contact.

With the steady advancement of electric vehicles and the increasing initiatives in smart charging and vehicle to grid technologies, we see ourselves in a similar situation where the market is fragmented with many players involved from both sectors, the eMobility and energy sectors, with various value propositions. Hence, we see the need again for a new role in the market that acts as a central point of contact for all the relevant stakeholders involved in the new value chain enabling interoperability in terms of information orchestration relevant for the execution of Bidirectional Power Transfer (BPT). We now call this actor the Bidirectional Power Transfer Service Provider.

In this section we will define the expectations of the market for this role and analyze on a high-level which feature set an eRoaming service provider should offer to enable BPT to its stakeholders. Accordingly, we define the needed features or services, respectively, that from a technical and business perspective are required for BPT. Based on these metrics we then perform a state-of-the-art analysis for existing eRoaming protocols in the market.

5.3.1 eRoaming as Enabler for BPT Services

With the continued evolution of the electromobility ecosystem, eRoaming platforms are increasingly expected to advance available functionalities and features to support BPT (roaming) services. While we do not think that existing and new roles will merge into a single role, an interplay between these platforms is necessary to unfold the full potential of Bidirectional Power Transfer services.

Traditionally, eRoaming platforms have provided a reliable foundation for enabling interoperability across different charging networks, allowing users to access, authenticate, and pay for charging

services seamlessly [63]. We expect that these core functionalities of eRoaming will remain in the respective ecosystems but will be advanced to enable BPT services. These yet to be advanced eRoaming features encompass for instance the ability to specify BPT capabilities of charging stations within Point of Interest (POI) or EVSE (Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment) data, respectively, authorization processes to initiate discharging, the amount of energy that has been discharged in a session in ChargeDetailRecords for billing purposes. Features that are necessary for the sole orchestration of bidirectional power transfer, such as third-party integration from the energy market, EV data, charging profiles, will be hosted in separate, hub-like platforms, enabled through standards and protocols like ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1. These protocols facilitate secure communication, automated authentication, and unfold the potential for bidirectional power exchange, aligning the functionalities of eRoaming platforms.

An instructive analogy can be found in the development of the Plug&Charge (ISO 15118) ecosystem. While Plug&Charge enables a secure communication layer (TLS), certificate handling, and authentication processes e.g., via the Open Plug & Charge Protocol (OPCP), eRoaming-related features were further developed to support Plug&Charge processes. These include static EVSE information, authorization procedures, and Charge Detail Records (CDRs) for billing purposes, all of which remained within the eRoaming ecosystem.

eRoaming platforms already have a widespread market throughout the world handling millions of charging sessions every day, connecting all relevant stakeholders, including EV OEMs, EVSE OEMs, CPOs and EMPs, in the eMobility ecosystem. This established network of eRoaming platforms can be leveraged to enable BPT services relevant for V2G purposes within a dedicated hub solution. Hence, by advancing available eRoaming services and building on that a dedicated BPT hub solution as well as enabling the interplay among these ecosystems, we expect a ramp-up and seamless adoption of BPT services in the market. This evolution marks a natural and necessary step for the eMobility sector, bridging the demand side of the energy market with the response side of the mobility sector through interoperable, modular platforms.

Please note that in the following sections, we deliberately refrain from making a strict separation between functionalities assigned to the eRoaming platform and those envisioned for a dedicated BPT hub. The analysis is conducted from a broader system-level perspective, focusing on the overarching role of roaming providers in enabling BPT services across interconnected ecosystems.

5.3.2 Envisioning BPT Roaming Provider (base layer)

The adoption of V2G technology is still at a relatively early stage. Most services and offerings within the ecosystem are proprietary solutions hindering interoperability and scalability and thus, mass-deployment of the respective infrastructure, e.g., BPT capable charging stations. Hence, within this section we are going to define basic features that are necessary to support BPT services within the ecosystem. It is important to note that this set of features are curated based on wide expertise of Hsubject as a leading eRoaming provider in the market and its close collaboration with the eMobility market along with the knowledge gained from participation in varied projects, supported by internal expert interviews. The projects include both EU level and especially National level (Germany) such as DeRive & Mobility2Grid, with focus on enabling smart and Bidirectional charging with Charging profiles orchestration and Data flow enablement via interfaces based on open protocols.

This feature set is not definitive, and further services may be needed, which are likely to be realized during the later stages of the project. Nevertheless, it gives a first illustration of the needed input data and processes that we define as necessary for BPT purposes.

Table 5.14: Feature set for BPT Roaming Provider

Metric	Definition
EV Data	EV related data/ information that are crucial for BPT services. Among others, this encompasses data such as State of Charge (SoC), State of Health (SoH), battery capacity, voltage range for (dis-) charging, V2G services the vehicle offers to participate in.
EVSE POI Data	EVSE related data exceeding state-of-the-art information for sole charging purposes. These data can encompass, among others, information on whether the EVSE supports BPT and with which power, compliance with ISO 15118-20, V2G service the EVSE supports.
Authentication (ISO 15118)	Refers to the support of secure authentication methods, specifically Plug&Charge. Note that ISO 15118-20 is necessary for the exchange of standardized charging profiles between the EVSE and EV, whereas Plug&Charge is technically not mandatory for V2G purposes. However, as Plug&Charge is part of ISO 15118 (-2 and -20) and as charging infrastructure as well as the energy market is critical, cybersecurity for the information exchange between EVSE and EV is essential.
Authorization & Contract Handling	Indicates whether authorization data points or (business) processes are specified encompassing BPT. E.g., one authorization for one session that has subsequent charging and discharging within this session or separate authorization processes are required as each charging and discharging addresses different contracts of the EV user with the corresponding entity such as EMP and/ or energy supplier.
User Preferences Handling	Defines the capability if end user preferences and constraints can be captured. These data can encompass, among others, BPT/ V2G services opt-in, desired SoC after the session, departure time and maximum energy that the user allows to be discharged.
Charge Detail Records & Billing (signed meter data)	Assesses if Charge Detail Records (CDRs) support both charging and discharging as well as if this is the case, signing meter data are supported. The reflection of this is crucial for transparent billing toward the end user while complying with local regulations (e.g., calibration law in Germany).
ChargingProfile Handling	Specifies if charging profiles can be orchestrated and sent to the according recipient executing the calculated charging profiles. It is important to note that charging profiles are the results of all processed input data that encompass, among other, user preferences, grid constraints, EV and EVSE capabilities etc.
Dynamic Pricing/ Energy tariff support	Indicates whether the communication of time-based or real-time price information for implicit demand response purposes is possible and/ or if pricing information from the energy provider can be retrieved.
Demand Side integration (3 rd parties, e.g., energy market)	Indicates if third parties, especially energy market participants, such as VPPs, DSOs, TSOs, aggregators etc., are integrated into the overall system and whether information exchanges with these actors are covered. E.g., some V2G use cases require a trigger signal from energy market participants, such as TSO for frequency reserve services in explicit demand response programs.

5.3.3 Methodology- Roaming for BPT Services

This study follows a two-step approach to capture as much information as possible in terms of where the market currently stands:

- i SotA analysis and benchmarking of pilot projects on EU level
- ii SotA analysis and benchmarking of roaming protocols with the highest market penetration in Europe

Figure 5.5: Methodology followed in this document.

Pilot Projects: The first phase of the analysis involves the identification and evaluation of pilot projects relevant for Smart Charging and BPT services on EU level. Thereafter, each project is evaluated by their relevance and a subsequent benchmarking is conducted to understand the coverage of the BPT roaming metrics specified in the clause before within these projects. The methodology is designed to ensure the selection of high-impact projects that contribute meaningfully to the understanding of the current technological and commercial landscape of BPT roaming services. Projects are initially identified and filtered based on their technological scope—with priority given to projects focusing specifically on smart charging, V2X (vehicle-to-everything) charging, and grid integration. Within this curated pool, each project is assessed through examination of the publicly available documentation, including reports and deliverables, to assess the relevance and depth of content related to smart charging and BPT services. Only those projects demonstrating significant alignment with the defined focus areas are selected for detailed review. These selected projects form the basis for the SotA analysis, offering insights into the current technological landscape and the evaluation of emerging trends and requirements in BPT roaming services.

For the further elaboration of the projects selected in this study for the SotA analysis, and in accordance with the methodology defined above, each project has been examined through the lens of its relevance to enabling roaming capabilities for future BPT service providers. To ensure consistency and comparability, the following structured template has been used to briefly present the details of

Figure 5.6: Methodology for SotA Analysis of Pilot Projects.

each selected project.

eRoaming Protocols: Further, an analysis of eRoaming protocols with high market penetration is conducted and evaluated based on the previously described metrics that are essential to offer BPT roaming services. Traditional SotA analysis and benchmarking are usually performed by identifying and analyzing commercially available services and products. However, the V2G industry as mentioned before is still in its very early stages, there barely exist any commercial offerings in this market landscape. Accordingly, to follow a scientific approach, the authors deliberately analyzed (open) eRoaming protocols. The main hypothesis is that a market-wide V2G rollout is only possible through interoperability, which in turn fosters scalability. Without (open) protocols supporting BPT roaming services, commercially available offerings or proprietary solutions are not sustainable. Eventually, the results of the analysis (pilot projects and eRoaming protocols) are merged to understand the SotA of the eMobility market on BPT services as well as to derive key insights and barriers hindering a market-wide rollout of BPT/ V2G services.

What is eRoaming? eRoaming, as acknowledged within the framework of European Union regulations, facilitates seamless access for electric vehicle users to cross-provider charging infrastructure through unified authentication and authorization methods and enables integrated billing solutions. Although eRoaming is not explicitly mandated as a universal requirement, the EU's Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR) strongly promotes its implementation. This encouragement aims to enhance user convenience and support the development of a harmonized, cross-border charging ecosystem, ultimately contributing to greater interoperability and adoption of EVs across Member States as well as facilitating the market throughput of eMobility as such. The EU prioritizes voluntary roaming agreements over mandates, emphasizing market-driven solutions while ensuring transparency and user convenience. This approach aims to reduce fragmentation in charging networks and alleviate range anxiety for EV drivers [64], [65].

eRoaming platforms, such as the Hsubject Brokering System (HBS), lower market entry barriers for participants in the eMobility ecosystem by fostering interoperability through standardized technical and business integration of partner systems. Cross-provider charging infrastructure enables non-discriminatory access to charging stations, meeting the charging needs of end users while supporting greater market penetration of eMobility.

Figure 5.7: Pictographic representation of Roaming network solution.

Business Integration: Through a standardized contract and single-point-of-contact approach, market participants, such as eMobility Providers (eMP) and Charge Point Operators (CPO), can focus on their solution offerings to their customers and target customer groups, reducing the overall contractual and business complexity by participating in a B2B marketplace for charging purposes. E.g., CPOs can offer their charging infrastructure to multiple EMPs through an Offer-to-All approach, instead of having bilateral agreements with each market participant.

Technical Integration: eRoaming platforms enable efficient and interoperable technical integration of actors along the eMobility value chain, such as Charge Point Operators (CPOs), eMobility Providers (EMPs), EV OEMs, through standardized, open protocols. These protocols enable seamless communication and compatibility across charging networks by defining common interfaces, data flows and business processes. Using protocols such as OICP, OCPI, eMIP or OCHP, partner systems can exchange essential information for processes like authentication (e.g., ISO 15118-based Plug&Charge), authorization, session tracking, and billing. This standardization simplifies integration efforts, ensures consistent data exchange, and supports scalable growth in the eMobility sector.

Public Accessibility: Through cross-provider charging infrastructure offered within the eRoaming marketplace, end users have access to cross-border charging services to fulfill their charging needs. Hence, eRoaming enables inclusivity and non-discriminatory access to the charging infrastructure as emphasized by the European Commission

5.3.4 SotA Analysis - Pilot Projects

The initial phase of the SotA analysis involves identifying pertinent research and innovation projects within the European Union. This process draws primarily on publicly funded initiatives supported by major EU frameworks. Based on the initial identification from the 2Zero network of projects, we found 44 ongoing and 206 completed projects. After filtering them according to the defined technology criteria, we identified 36 projects related to grid integration, smart charging, and V2X technologies, as outlined in the methodology [66]. The projects are rated based on the relevance to BPT services as Low, Medium and High.

- **Low:** No relevance to BPT roaming.
- **Medium:** Covers smart charging or grid integration.
- **High:** Demonstrates BPT and/or eRoaming roles

Table 5.15: Table Pilot Project selection based on BPT relevance.

Project	BPT service Relevance	Consideration for SotA Analysis	Remarks
eCharge4Drivers	Low	No	No relevant deliverables for BPT transfer
User-CHI	High	Yes	User interaction, BPT
INCIT-EV	Low	No	Focussed more on bidirectional charging infrastructure than roaming
SELFIE	Low	No	Smart battery thermal management system focus
CEVOLVER	Low	No	Connected energy & Thermal management
FITGEN	Low	No	Concentration on next-gen EV Powertrains
ASSURED	Low	No	Focus on High-power fast charging, minimal roaming/BPT overlap
ELECTRIFIC	Medium	No*	No sufficient evidence available online
FABRIC	Low	No	Focus on Dynamic wireless charging
COTEVOS	Medium	Yes	EV interoperability and conformance testing
EMERALD	Low	No	Concentrated on Power electronics
FastInCharge	Low	No	Focus on Ultra-fast charging infrastructure
MOBINCITY	Low	No	Mobility intelligence oriented
eCo-FEV	Low	No	Communication architecture focus
UNPLUGGED	Low	No	Focus on Inductive charging technology
Green eMotion	Medium	Yes	eRoaming & grid integration
ICT4VEU	Low	No	Information & Communication Technology oriented
Mobi.Europe	Low	No	Focus on harmonization
MOLECULES	Medium	No*	No sufficient evidence available online
smartCEM	Low	No	Urban mobility services
e-DASH	Medium	No*	No sufficient evidence available online
SMARTV2G	High	Yes	Focus on V2G and grid integration
IoE	Low	No	Conceptual on Internet of Energy
OpEneR	Low	No	Efficient Routing and no BPT
PowerUp	Low	No	Battery management system

Note: *not considered for SotA due to lack of evidence online

Project	BPT service Relevance	Consideration for SotA Analysis	Remarks
P-MOB	Low	No	Light weight eVs & modularity
ELVIRE	Medium	No*	No sufficient evidence available online
MERGE	Low	No	Very high-level interpretation of smart charging
SCALE	High	Yes	Direct support for V2G/BPT, integration with flexibility markets
EV4EU	Medium	Yes	Demonstrates real-world BPT and smart charging use cases
FLOW	Medium	Yes	Covers charging ecosystem flexibility and interoperability
XL-Connect	Medium	Yes	Focused on interoperability and smart services
DriVe2X	Medium	Yes	Emphasizes V2X technology and interoperability
ePowerMove	Medium	No*	No relevant data yet available as project started in Jan 2025
FLEXMCS	Medium	No*	No relevant data yet available as project started in Jan 2025
MACBETH	Less	No	MCS charging deployment, predictive maintenance

Note: *not considered for SotA due to lack of evidence online

Based on the thorough review of the publicly available documents, we have evaluated the shortlisted projects in terms of the relevance of the contents of the projects with the BPT services feature set as previously defined in this document. Accordingly, a brief description of these High and Medium rated projects along with their relevant datasets, is provided below.

COTEVOS establishes laboratory infrastructure to test the interoperability of EV and grid systems. Though it lacks physical demonstrations, it emphasizes technical readiness for POI data exchange and user participation. It documents EV connectivity parameters and user preferences, making it moderately relevant for modelling BPT communication flows in testing environments [67], [68].

DRIVE2X promotes the adoption of bidirectional charging through smart charging algorithms, predictive modeling, and affordable charger units. It operates across sites in Amsterdam, the UK, Hungary, Portugal, Sweden, and Italy. Use cases include V2B, V2G, and V2H in various public and private environments. The project refers to key BPT roaming aspects such as Time-of-Use tariffs, metering and POI data, offering moderate relevance for future integration scenarios [69]–[72].

EV4EU aims to develop user-centric strategies to facilitate the mass adoption of electric vehicles across the EU. It implements tools, applications, and open data platforms to support V2X integration. Demonstration sites include Portugal, Denmark, Greece, and Slovenia, each focusing on different aspects such as grid impact, energy management, and V2X strategies. The project mentions

various POI data exchanges relevant to BPT, including bid information and EV connection status. It is moderately relevant for BPT roaming due to its emphasis on use-case-based data integration [73]–[75].

FLOW focuses on enhancing user-centric V2X smart charging solutions and their integration into energy grids. With demonstrations in Denmark, Italy, Spain, Ireland, and the Czech Republic, FLOW explores smart charging across public and private contexts. It discusses BPT-related aspects like billing, pricing, pre-payment, and energy flow reservation. These align moderately with BPT roaming needs, especially in the context of interoperable protocol comparisons [76], [77].

Green eMotion aggregates various regional and national electromobility efforts into a harmonized European initiative. It involves 12 demo regions and tests a range of eMobility use cases including smart charging, grid integration, and cross-border roaming. BPT relevance is moderate, reflected in parameters such as EVSE POI (e.g., timestamps, V2G data) and DSO interfaces (e.g., energy offers). It also incorporates user preferences like availability windows [78].

SCALE aims to enable mass deployment of interoperable smart charging and V2X services. It features diverse use cases such as Vehicle-to-Home, -Business, -Depot, and -Public in countries like Germany, Norway, and the Netherlands. SCALE addresses BPT roaming parameters comprehensively, including user preferences, dynamic SoC, aggregator signals, and EMSP influence on session pricing. Its high relevance makes it a critical reference point for BPT service design [79], [80].

SMARTV2G enables real-time energy exchange between EVs and the grid, with deployments in Barcelona and Slovenia. It emphasizes grid-responsive charging based on user and DSO signals. The project supports frequent metering intervals and dynamic tariffs, while also incorporating user-defined SoC levels and participation preferences. Its high relevance stems from the depth of BPT parameters modeled and demonstrated [81].

USER CHI stands out with a high relevance to BPT roaming. It focuses on developing user-centric charging infrastructure along TEN-T corridors, demonstrating services in cities like Barcelona, Berlin, Rome, Turku, and Budapest. The project features interoperability across CPOs and EMSPs, automated invoicing, and energy balancing systems. BPT parameters include transaction-level payment handling, CPO and EV POI data, and user preferences such as departure time and battery capacity [82]–[84].

XL-CONNECT is designed to optimize EV charging across the entire value chain, integrating both socio-economic and technical factors. While its demonstration sites span Belgium, Germany, Italy, and Portugal, detailed use cases are pending. The project addresses POI data at the scenario level, such as street or home charging, capturing parameters like battery capacity, SoC, and tariff behavior. Its relevance to BPT roaming lies in the digital twin approach and scenario-based POI modeling [85]

Based on these insights the following table is benchmarking each identified project against the previously specified BPT roaming metrics.

Table 5.16: Benchmarking of shortlisted Pilot projects with the selected BPT Roaming metrics.

Metric	COTEVOS	DriVe2X	EV4EU	FLOW	Green eMotion	SCALE	SMARTV2G	USER CHI	XL-CONNECT
EV Data	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X
EVSE POI Data	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Authentication (ISO 15118)				Only -2		-20		Only -2	
Authorization & Contract Handling	X		X capacity contracts	X	X	X	X	X	X
User Preferences	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Charge Detail Records & Billing	X	X	X				X	X	
Charging Profile Handling		X	X	X		X	X	X	
Dynamic Energy tariff support	X (TOU)	X			X				
Demand Side integration (3 rd parties, e.g., energy market actors)		DSO	VPP DSO Aggregator			DSO Aggregator	DSO Aggregator	DSO Aggregator	DSO
Metering Data	X	X		X			X		

5.3.5 SotA Analysis – eRoaming Protocols

eRoaming protocols are the digital backbone that enable different eMobility actors such as EV OEMs, EMPs and CPOs to interoperate across networks. Thus, these protocols must evolve to handle not only unidirectional charging, but also the added complexity of BPT logic to meet the requirements of a scalable, interoperable V2G ecosystem. This section analyzes whether today's widely adopted (open) eRoaming protocols support BPT to ensure interoperability and thus, to derive if potential scalable solutions are possible within the existing eMobility landscape. The hypothesis is simple: Without BPT compatible (open) eRoaming protocols, interoperability is only possible with high limitations directly affecting scalable commercial offerings. Without interoperability, BPT for V2G purposes will be mainly confined to proprietary solutions, hindering scalability and thereby broader market adoption. This analysis, and benchmarking study, focuses on four major protocols commonly used for eRoaming in the European EV market:

Table 5.17: *eRoaming Protocols selected for analysis*

Protocol	Most recent version	Remark
Open Clearing House Protocol (OCHP)	V1.4	GitHub – OCHP [86] (Last changes: 14.12.2023)
Open Interchange Protocol (OICP)	v2.3	GitHub – OICP [87]
eMobility Protocol Inter-Operation (eMIP)	V1.0.17	eMIP Protocol PDF [88]
Open Charge Point Interface (OCPI)	v3.0-2	OCPI GitHub [89] / evRoaming.org [90] OCPI v3.0 is currently under review for (public) commenting.

These protocols were selected based on their market relevance/penetration and future relevance in roaming scenarios across Europe. The protocols are analyzed and benchmarked against each other based on the previously defined metrics that we have identified as crucial to support BPT roaming services. Each metric for each protocol is evaluated based on the following approach:

- **No:** Not supported or unspecified
- **Yes:** The feature is supported or specified.
- **UPT:** Supported for unidirectional power transfer only.
- **BPT:** BPT-relevant structures exist (even if partial or high-level).

Based on this approach, the following table shall illustrate the results from the conducted analysis for each respective protocol.

Table 5.18: *Benchmarking of selected eRoaming protocols.*

Feature:	OCHP [86]	OICP	eMIP	OCPI
OpenProtocol	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Supports Roaming	Yes, Hub	Yes, Hub	Yes, Hub	Yes, Hub or Peer2Peer
EV Data	No	No	No	No
EVSE POI Data	UPT (cl. ChargePointInfo class)	UPT	UPT	UPT (cl. 5.4.8., v3.0)
Authentication (ISO 15118)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes (cl. 5.4.9., v3.0)
Authorization & Contract Handling	UPT ¹	UPT (cl. 5.1.2 & 5.2.2)	UPT ² (cl. 11.4.2 & 11.4.3)	UPT ² (cl. 11.4.2. & cl. 11.4.3.)
User Preferences Handling	No	No	BPT (cl. 7.8.0 & 7.8.2 ff.)	BPT (cl. 9.3.2, v2.3 & cl. 7.4.1., v3.0)

¹ No information on potential business process for the authorization of discharging or BPT, respectively.

² No information on potential business process for the authorization of discharging or BPT, respectively. The data structure only points towards charging by also specifying the maximum energy to be charged in the data field "max_energy".

³ Contains only information for the charging process. No information or dedicated data fields assigned for discharging.

Feature:	OCHP [86]	OICP	eMIP	OCPI
Charge Detail Records & Billing (signed meter data)	UPT ³ (cl. CDRInfo class)	UPT	UPT	(BPT) (cl. 8.5.2 & cl. 8.5.5, v3.0)
ChargingProfile Handling	No	No	No	UPT (cl. 13.6.4. and cl. 13.6.5., v3.0)
Dynamic Pricing/Energy tariff support	UPT (Dynamic/Flexible Pricing)	No	No (no information provided)	UPT (cl. 9.5.6. ff. & cl. 11.4.4., v3.0)
Demand Side integration (3 rd parties, e.g., energy market)	No	No	No	UPT (high-level) (cl. 13.2., ff., v3.0)

¹ No information on potential business process for the authorization of discharging or BPT, respectively.

² No information on potential business process for the authorization of discharging or BPT, respectively. The data structure only points towards charging by also specifying the maximum energy to be charged in the data field "max_energy".

³ Contains only information for the charging process. No information or dedicated data fields assigned for discharging.

5.3.6 Key Insights and Barriers

Pilot Projects: Pilot projects play a crucial role in advancing technology. They push the boundaries of current systems, offering insights into both emerging capabilities and practical challenges. In the context of BPT, such projects highlight what is feasible today while identifying the gaps that remain. Although the volume of pilot activity across Europe is promising, relatively few projects explicitly address BPT in the context of eRoaming. From an initial pool of over 250 initiatives, 36 were filtered based on thematic relevance, with 9 selected for in-depth analysis aligned with the objectives of the NEVERFLAT project. Projects like **USER CHI**, **SMARTV2G**, and **SCALE** demonstrated high relevance through features such as dynamic SoC handling, real-time energy exchange, and cross-operator interoperability. Others, including **EV4EU**, **FLOW**, **XL-CONNECT**, **DRIVE2X**, **COTEVOS**, and **Green eMotion**, explored aspects such as POI data, smart charging strategies, and metering, contributing valuable building blocks for future BPT roaming services. Collectively, the projects span a wide range of BPT use cases such as V2G, V2H, and V2B implemented across public and private charging settings. Many integrate user preferences, grid interaction, and stakeholder coordination across actors such as CPOs, EMSPs, and DSOs. While most initiatives describe roaming-related functionalities at a conceptual level, detailed specifications for interfaces, data models, and business processes are often lacking. The role of a BPT Roaming Service Provider is typically implicit, framed through the lens of aggregators or platform providers. Overall, the benchmarking of the defined BPT metrics against the focus areas addressed by the selected pilot projects confirms that the key functional pillars for BPT Roaming are developing in the right direction. The individual strengths and insights of each project will be actively incorporated, if possible, into the subsequent phases of the NEVERFLAT project, particularly in system architecture design and requirements engineering.

eRoaming Protocols The research and analysis conducted as part of this study indicate that the currently analyzed eRoaming protocols - namely OCHP, eMIP, OICP, and OCPI - are presently focused on enabling information exchanges related to unidirectional power transfer or charging purposes, respectively. While these protocols provide a solid foundation for standard eMobility charging services, they do not yet fully support the range of data flows and service orchestration required to enable Bidirectional Power Transfer (BPT) or Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) interactions across key stakeholders. These stakeholders include, among others, eMobility Service Providers (EMPs), Charge Point Operators (CPOs), and energy market participants such as energy suppliers, energy aggregators and flexibility providers. That said, some protocols are beginning to evolve in a direction that could support more advanced charging functionalities. OCPI version 3.0, for example, introduces capabilities for transmitting charging profiles and defines (new) roles such as the Smart Charging Service Provider that facilitate the generation and coordination of these profiles. However, in its current form, OCPI v3.0 does not yet allow for the communication of V2G-related signals, which are essential for realizing full bidirectional energy flows. Among the protocols studied, OCPI v3.0 provides the most concrete indications of potential future BPT support. Though still in the review phase at the time of writing, it includes two noteworthy elements relevant to bidirectional energy exchange. First, it defines a ChargingPreferences data type (Section 7.4.1) - [90], which enables the transmission of user preferences such as departure time and desired state of charge (SoC). This object also includes a Boolean attribute, `discharge_allowed`, which specifies whether the end user consents to vehicle discharge. However, this appears to be the only data element in the protocol currently related to BPT, and no additional process-oriented or semantic structures are defined for discharge coordination. Furthermore, OCPI v3.0 enables the itemization of charging and discharging sequences within a ChargeDetailRecord, which is linked to a specific session. However, the data structure of the ChargeDetailRecord indicates that each session reflects a net positive energy inflow, as the attribute `total_energy` specifies only the total amount of energy charged. Second, the OCPI v3.0 draft includes an internal note stating: “TODO how about V2G / bidirectional charging? Profiles only have a ‘maximum limit’ as of now” (Section 13, page 218) - [90]. This suggests that support for bidirectional charging is under consideration, and it is reasonable to expect that future iterations of the protocol may include more extensive BPT supporting features. Whether such elements will be incorporated during the current review cycle remains uncertain. In summary, while current (open) eRoaming protocols are well-suited for charging scenarios (not necessarily unidirectional Smart Charging, but the coverage of simple charging needs), they do not yet offer the comprehensive service definitions and data structures needed to support the orchestration of BPT or V2G across the broader eMobility ecosystem. Other protocols and standards - such as ISO 15118-20, the Open Smart Charging Protocol (OSCP), and OCPP 2.1 - already provide mechanisms to facilitate both smart and bidirectional charging, including the exchange of charging profiles for BPT purposes. However, these standards are generally tailored to specific stakeholder relationships that fall outside the typical scope of eRoaming - for instance, OSCP is primarily designed for communication between Distribution System Operator (DSO) and Charge Point Operators (CPOs). The current delineation between eRoaming frameworks and smart charging standards underscores the need for future alignment and harmonization. Bridging this gap will be essential to unlocking the full potential of BPT as an integrated, interoperable service within the eMobility and energy sectors.

5.3.7 Recommendations for Action

The integration of Bidirectional Power Transfer (BPT) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) capabilities into (open) eRoaming protocols is, in our view, a critical enabler for the development of interoperable and scalable bidirectional charging solutions. The introduction of eRoaming has successfully delivered seamless, cross-border, and cross-provider charging experiences for end users by ensuring both contractual and technical interoperability between key stakeholders including EV and EVSE OEMs, eMobility Providers (EMPs), and Charge Point Operators (CPOs). Today, the landscape for V2G and BPT faces similar structural challenges to those that existed before the advent of eRoaming: a fragmented market with limited interoperability and scalability. To address these challenges and foster a unified, future-ready ecosystem, we recommend the following actions to relevant stakeholders across the public and private sectors, including standardization bodies, industry associations, and actors in the eMobility and energy domains:

- **Extend eRoaming protocols to support BPT and V2G services** As a first step, eRoaming protocols should be expanded to enable information exchange on key data sets related to discharging, such as V2G-relevant POI data (vehicle and charging station capabilities), contractual handling and authorization flows, and user preferences. A second phase, or already in parallel, could then focus on establishing a modular BPT service that utilizes the BPT enabled services/information from eRoaming for the generation and orchestration of charging profiles.
- **Ensure harmonization with existing standards** Align developments in eRoaming protocols with existing open standards such as ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1, which already offer support for smart and bidirectional charging. Harmonization will avoid duplication, reduce integration effort, and support end-to-end interoperability.
- **Prioritize interoperability and scalability over proprietary solutions** Stakeholders should focus on the development of open, interoperable services to enable seamless integration across the V2G value chain. Proprietary or isolated approaches may solve short-term needs but risk increasing market fragmentation in the long run.

By proactively addressing these areas, the industry can build upon the lessons learned from the evolution of eRoaming and ensure that BPT and V2G services can scale effectively.

5.3.8 Qualitative Key Performance Parameters

Based on the conducted research, analysis and evaluations on the current market conditions in pilot projects and eRoaming protocols, Hubject will explore, facilitate, prototype and test the following features within NEVERFLAT in alignment with the envisioned developments of our project partners:

- EVSE POI Data
- EV Data
- Secure Communication and Authentication based on ISO 15118-20
- Authorization and contract handling processes
- ChargeDetailRecord & billing processes
- ChargingProfile Orchestration (optional)
- Dynamic Pricing/ Energy tariff support (optional)
- Demand Side Integration (optional)

It is important to note that the features to be developed are subject to changes based on insights and further evaluations within the NEVERFLAT project. Furthermore, Hsubject will ensure to align its implementations in accordance with existing open protocols and will foster harmonization among other, not directly to eRoaming linked protocols, e.g., OCPP. Some features are marked as optional due to the consortium set-up within NEVERFLAT. This means that one or more features could be deployed by other partners or that this service may be captured at a later stage to consider stakeholder needs, especially from the energy markets, that are not represented within NEVERFLAT.

5.4 V2G Energy Demand / Supply Forecast and Management

5.4.1 Methodology

The data used here were sourced from scientific databases such as ScienceDirect, IEEE Xplore, and Google Scholar, using keywords that considered both the general topic and the specifics of this section. Keywords and abbreviations included are listed as follows:

- For the V2G management section: electric vehicles (EV), smart charging, vehicle-to-grid (V2G), energy management system (EMS), optimization, management, and artificial intelligence (AI).
- For the demand and supply forecasting: forecasting, demand forecast, generation forecast, supply forecast, PV generation forecasting, machine learning (ML), and statistical forecasting.

A set of articles was selected considering the fit on the topic, relevance of the journal, year of publication, and citation score. The selected articles were summarized to build the state of the art on both topics (V2G management and energy demand and generation forecasting). The results of the literature review and state of the art are presented in the following subsections.

5.4.2 V2G Management

In the scientific literature, the V2G management system is mainly formulated as an optimization problem, characterized by different objective functions and constraints. The following table provides an overview of the V2G management problem formulations found in the literature.

Table 5.19: Literature review of V2G management systems.

Reference	Summary
[91]	<p>Optimal management of a microgrid with a V2G system. The problem formulation includes a PV plant, controllable, shiftable and critical loads, a V2G system with a constraint on range anxiety.</p> <p>The objective function is an overall cost minimization for the entire microgrid.</p> <p>Input profiles are assumed deterministic.</p> <p>The problem is formulated as a mixed integer linear programming problem and solved with CPLEX.</p> <p>Power grid is modelled as a single node for energy input/output.</p>
[92]	<p>Optimal management of a microgrid with a V2G system, but considering uncertainty sources. In this case, the problem is solved through robust optimization.</p> <p>The initial state of charge and the wind turbine power are modelled through rectangular uncertainty sets.</p>

Reference	Summary
	The objective functions are two: cost minimization and greenhouse gas emission minimization. They are combined through weights in a single final objective function. The results are compared with stochastic optimization.
[93]	This formulation is another optimal management of a microgrid with V2G systems, with specific load curves and considerations related to a ski resort. The formulation does not take into account uncertainty sources.
[94]	This model includes only V2G with a vehicle connected to a grid's node through the charging station. It considers different objective functions including cost and battery degradation minimization, load variance minimization or minimization of load peak-valley difference.
[95]	This work focuses mainly on grid studies. The outcome of V2G is provided as input for power flow analyses. Once the analysis is completed, the distribution system operator can check if the V2G scheduling satisfied grid constraints. If no issues are identified, the charging/discharging schedules are confirmed.
[96]	This review analyses the main features of V2G optimization problems in the literature, including the different objective functions, constraints and V2G services analysed until 2016.
[97]	A cost-benefit analysis is carried out in a V2G pilot project, in Shanghai, identifying how EV owners, grid operators and power plant owners are affected by V2G, in terms of profitability. Apparently, in the Chinese context, grid operators' economic losses can be high when remunerating EVs for V2G services, and more balance should be sought between these three participants, to incentivize the V2G technology.
[98]	This paper reviews the main charging strategies, providing a comprehensive list of classical optimization and machine learning-based techniques for EV charging. They include linear programming, mixed-integer models solved with dynamic programming, heuristic algorithms and learning techniques including supervised, unsupervised, reinforcement and deep learning.
[99]	This work proposes a stochastic approach for coordinating charging and discharging on EVs, based on Monte Carlo simulations for accounting PV generation and EV departure times.
[100]	After a broad review of EV battery technologies and charging infrastructure, the paper focuses on the capabilities of providing ancillary services through V2G in the UK electricity market framework. The authors assess EV participation through V2G to frequency, reserve and flexibility markets and include societal impacts in terms of environmental benefits, social equity, and blackout recovery.
[101]	This paper focuses on the optimal scheduling of electric bus fleets. It considers a non-linear battery degradation curve, that is linearized to reduce the computational burden of the model, leading to a mixed integer linear programming problem.
[102]	This paper proposes a multi-level scheduling approach that accounts for both the EV charging and discharging, and the power grid. The proposed model is validated on the IEEE 33 bus system, assuming the presence of 100 EVs.
[103]	This paper develops a mixed integer linear programming (MILP) model to optimize V2G scheduling, while considering both calendar and cycle aging of the battery. The model is used to compare four cases: immediate charging, smart charging without V2G, V2G without degradation model and V2G with degradation. Results show that the V2G model leads to reduced scheduling costs, with a slight increase of cycle aging due to the bidirectional energy exchange.

Reference	Summary
[104]	This paper presents a V2G management strategy based on two layers: a centralized V2G state coordinator, that is used to respond to peak shaving requirements and improve grid conditions, and a real-time V2G controller, based on fuzzy logic, that receives the reference power from the centralized coordinator.

Inputs

- PV power forecast: A forecast of the energy production from PV systems should be available for the time horizon defined for the V2G manager. Therefore, the V2G manager should allocate more charging events during high PV production.
- Energy purchase and sales prices: The forecast of grid interaction prices is necessary to minimize the cost of charging and/or increase the EV owner's profitability.
- Charging station parameters: Maximum and minimum power, and efficiency are needed to constrain the scheduled power from each station.
- Battery degradation model: A degradation model for the EV battery is necessary to estimate the impact of the V2G decisions on the EV owner's costs. This need could be mitigated if a clearly defined warranty policy assures EV owners that battery degradation is within the manufacturer's safe range.
- EV battery's state of charge at the start of the charging session: EV battery's state of charge status at the time of connection should be known, so that the energy requirements can be computed.
- Expected departure time: The connection time could determine the participation of the EV in the V2G services. Therefore, the expected departure time should be estimated or well-defined for each EV.
- Expected minimum state of charge at the end of the charging session: The energy requirement of each EV should be known to determine the participation of the EV in the V2G services. Therefore, the aimed or final state of charge status should be well defined.
- Charger power limits: The charging profile is ultimately defined by the EV battery's BMS, not by the V2G manager. Therefore, it is necessary to predict the charging limits imposed by a typical BMS. This will avoid delays and uncertainties in the energy charged.
- User preferences: EV owners could decide to have different levels of participation in the V2G decisions, banning or limiting EV participation in the V2G schedule.

Outputs

- Power level to charge/discharge at each time step
- Charging and discharging plans (V2G plans) for the charging points within the system. Since charging points are following the optimal V2G plans, this results in power levels of charging points at each time step. This data could be used in a grid model to validate the safety of the grid operation under the charging/discharging events scheduled.

5.4.3 Summary

The reviewed literature identified two main application domains for V2G management: microgrid energy management and grid power flow management and service provision. A cross-cutting theme

in both applications is the impact of V2G on EV battery degradation and how this aspect is considered in the V2G management algorithms. When V2G management is done for microgrid energy management, the optimization objectives mainly focus on minimizing operational costs and environmental impact (carbon emissions). Additionally, electrical metrics like voltage deviations and line congestion could be alleviated when the optimization objective is to minimize load variance or peak-valley load difference. On the other hand, when V2G management is integrated with the main grid operation management, the V2G problem complexity is usually reduced. In this scenario, V2G actions could be first validated by the distribution system operator to ensure grid metrics remain within safe limits before V2G management actions are executed. Furthermore, ancillary services such as voltage and frequency regulation could be provided through coordinated V2G management. However, the regulatory framework for V2G participation in this type of market is not yet clearly defined. Compensation models and economic feasibility remain aspects that need further development.

To solve the V2G problem, a mathematical framework that defines the optimization objectives and constraints of the V2G is a common approach. A software-based solution provides a set of actions based on the inputs described in the previous section and other parameters such as the number of charging stations, nominal power, efficiency, etc. The typical constraints related to microgrid applications are the microgrid power balance, the battery's C-rate and SoC (State of Charge) limits, renewable energy generation limits, and local load requirements. Additionally, the impact of the V2G on EV battery degradation must be assessed and integrated into the economic assessment of the solution provided. This analysis typically considers two main battery degradation mechanisms: cycling and calendar degradation. Both mechanisms are of relevance in the V2G management. However, cycling aging is expected to have a higher impact on the outcome of the optimization. Moreover, these aging mechanisms are sensitive to battery chemistry, which should be considered in the definition of the V2G manager. On the other hand, while the V2G manager is not expected to directly regulate the main grid operations, a grid model is necessary to validate that the V2G outputs do not degrade the grid operation beyond the permitted limits.

5.4.4 Demand and Generation Forecasting

The independent variables employed for forecasting can be broadly classified as:

- **Autoregressive variables:** historical data of the variable of interest available up to the current time t_n (E_i).
- **Explanatory variables:** external factors that influence future energy demand or production, such as temperature, wind speed, humidity or solar radiation (X_i).

Additionally, each forecasting model involves selecting and optimizing a set of hyperparameters β , that are crucial for obtaining accurate forecasting outputs.

Hence, the forecasting process can be written in functional form as:

$$\hat{E}_{n+h|n} = f(E_1, \dots, E_n, X_1, \dots, X_p, \beta) \quad (5.1)$$

Where the function f depends on the specific choice of the model.

The NEVERFLAT project will mainly focus on point forecasts, which consist of generating a single predicted value for each time step in the forecasting horizon. Furthermore, the forecasting horizon will be limited to less than a week, which is referred to as short-term forecasting.

5.4.5 Forecasting Methods

Energy generation and demand forecasting methods can be classified in two main categories: statistical and machine learning-based. Statistical forecasting methods have been traditionally employed for forecasting before the recent developments of machine learning techniques. Their main advantage, compared to machine learning, is their interpretability: the relationship between the forecast output and the inputs can be explained more easily. However, these methods offer lower forecasting accuracy in complex scenarios, especially in the presence of strongly non-linear relationships, weak seasonality or strong dependence on multiple external variables. Examples of statistical methods include autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models, exponential smoothing or generalized additive models. Machine learning methods, on the other hand, return more accurate forecasts even in more complex cases. They are ideal for dealing with large and high dimensional datasets, with many features, and can outperform traditional methods, provided that sufficient data are available. However, this comes at the expense of interpretability and higher computational burden. The following table provides a list of recent contributions to energy demand and generation forecasting.

Table 5.20: *Literature review of generation and load forecasting.*

Reference	Summary
[105]	The authors propose the application of temporal fusion transformers (TFT) for the forecasting of day-ahead PV power production. It is compared to ARIMA, long short-term memory (LSTM), extreme gradient boosting XGBoost) and multilayer perceptron (MLP). The main advantage of TFT is the enhanced interpretability of the results, and a better understanding of feature importance in the resulting output. The model is shown to work with a high accuracy during
[106]	This work focuses specifically on PV rooftop systems. The ARIMA method is employed for long-term (monthly) energy yield of the systems. Results show that the most accurate model is ARIMA (3,0,4), that allows to find a confidence interval that has a 95% probability of containing the actual energy yield.
[107]	In this work, PV power production forecasting is employed to maximize PV self-consumption and is part of an energy management system developed to minimize EV charging costs at the workplace. The forecasting is carried out through an ARIMA model, and is provided as input to the EMS, modelled as a MLP optimization problem. Results show that implementing the forecast and EMS in the EV charging strategy reduces costs by approximately four times.
[108]	The LSTM model is proposed for power generation forecasting and compared with alternative models such as the Holt-Winter model, the MLP, ARIMA and SARIMA and their extension with exogenous parameters. The authors claim LSTM model returns the forecasting results with highest accuracy, compared to the other methods, in terms of all the performance metrics (Mean Absolute Error – MAE, Root Mean Squared Error – RMSE, Mean Absolute Percentage Error – MAPE).

Reference	Summary
[109]	This paper introduces a novel short-term load forecasting model based on the Fourier decomposition of time-series, before applying the ARIMA model, defined as FARIMA. The proposed method is divided in different steps. After applying a Fast Fourier Transform to translate the time series to the frequency domain, the most significant frequencies are identified and filtered. After working on the periodic component, the trend is identified through a polynomial regression model and removed. Finally, ARIMA modelling allows forecasting each component of the decomposed time series separately. The final forecasting is obtained by summing the forecasted components. The proposed FARIMA approach appears to be robust with datasets exhibiting multi-frequency seasonality, unlike state-of-art statistical methods for load forecasting.
[110]	The authors combine LSTM neural networks with convolutional neural networks (CNN) in a hybrid deep learning framework. The aim is to solve the load forecasting problem for a single household. The CNN is used in the feature processing phase, for feature extraction and data enhancement, to improve the final accuracy of the forecasting. The authors compare their proposed hybrid model approach with the ARIMA model, the support vector regression or LSTM alone, and claim that their approach outperforms the others in terms of all the performance metrics: RMSE, MAE and MAPE.
[111]	A hybrid model combining both linear and non-linear input series is proposed for forecasting. Input data are first divided into their linear and non-linear components by employing empirical mode decomposition and wavelet transform. Two models are split. ARIMA model is applied to predict the linear part, and a wavelet neural network is used to predict the non-linear component. Results reveal that the hybrid model shows a significant drop in forecasting error when compared to classical models, for both residential and short-period interval forecasting.
[112]	The work compares ARIMA (statistical method) and artificial neural networks (machine learning), in terms of commonly employed error indices, such as MSE or MAPE for short-term load forecasting. Artificial neural networks show higher accuracy in load prediction, especially in the presence of non-linear relationships between the predictors and the predicted time series.

5.4.6 Summary

The reviewed literature identified two primary approaches: statistical methods and machine learning-based. Although both methods offer distinct features, in the context of NEVERFLAT project, the selection of one approach above the other will be highly influenced by the amount and quality of data available, as well as the trade-off between computational burden and accuracy of the forecasts. On one hand, statistical methods such as ARIMA could be used in a scenario of limited but high-quality data. The models are relatively simple to implement and results for renewable generation and load could be acceptable under stable and expected conditions. However, its performance could be affected by specific conditions such as rainy days and special social events that could introduce variability in generation and loads that statistical models might not be able to reproduce accurately. Such limitations can impact the accuracy of forecasts and, consequently, the performance of V2G management. On the other hand, if data availability is sufficient, machine learning-based methods could be used, producing stronger predictions with higher adaptability in scenarios with high uncertainty and variability. However, data quantity and quality needed for training and validation could be a bottleneck for these methods. Moreover, a robust preprocessing strategy and high computational power must be ensured. Therefore, the decision to employ a specific forecasting technique will come with a detailed assessment of the data available, computational capacity, and the desired

accuracy of the results. Depending on the outcome of the data assessment, a hybrid methodology could also be considered.

Key Insights and Recognized Barriers In general, data availability is a determinant of the methodology selection and efficiency of the tools developed under NEVERFLAT project. Both, V2G manager and the forecasting tools require high data quality. However, when machine learning, deep learning, or other artificial intelligence methods are considered, the amount of data is also a challenge to be considered. Having enough and high-quality training data is crucial for forecast accuracy and for decision-making quality. Availability of EV owners' behavior data could be limited for some pilots. Also, this data could be different depending on use cases (commercial EV fleet vs individual EV owners). Therefore, estimating user behavior such as connection time, arrival and departure times, and energy requirements could be challenging. More conservative methodologies could require less data, but maybe more specific ones, to develop exact optimization approaches such as linear/non-linear programming, dynamic programming, etc. Furthermore, these methods could handle constraints explicitly, improving reliability compared to some artificial intelligence methods. However, exact methods could have limited scalability. Hybrid solutions that use artificial intelligence and exact methods could provide practical solutions. Furthermore, grid models should be developed to evaluate the impact of the V2G plan on the grid, avoiding potential disruption of grid operation. On the other hand, most battery warranties do not consider V2G services, and many users are nervous about using this. Therefore, battery degradation models that accurately quantify the impact of V2G services on battery life and EV owner costs is of high importance to engage EV owners in this market with transparency and guaranteed rewards. Identifying cases when EV owners should not participate on V2G is as important as exploiting V2G to the fullest when it is feasible and benefits stakeholders (DSO, CPO, EV charging aggregators, and EV owners). Finally, data and human behavior uncertainty will always be present in real implementations. Therefore, risk assessment and worst-case scenario studies could help determine practical developments without falling into too conservative solutions.

Key Performance Parameters Considering the operation expected by the V2G manager and forecasting system, the next KPP are defined.

- **V2G**
 - V2G system is capable of connecting with sensors, forecasting database, and actuators (charging stations, local storage system, renewable energy generators, controllable load).
 - The system should be capable of changing charging/discharging power set points of the charging stations
 - Cost of charging EVs should be lower for the EV owner if it participates in V2G
 - Amount of V2G sessions successfully executed
 - Success rate of V2G sessions executed
 - When V2G supports active power, substation power should be flattened due to V2G actions
 - When V2G supports reactive power, voltage deviations from the grid should be lower
- **Forecasting**
 - Data collection system successfully connects with data providers
 - Data preparation system successfully evaluates and cleans data

- Forecasting system successfully provides a prediction of load and generation for the next 24 hours
- The prediction provided by the forecasting system accuracy is within accepted ranges for normal conditions
- The prediction provided by the forecasting system accuracy is within accepted ranges for abnormal high variability conditions

5.5 Plug&Charge (ISO 5118-20) and e-Roaming Ready Charge Point Management System

5.5.1 Methodology

As the concept of bidirectional charging is still in its very early stages and OCPP 2.1 has been just recently published in February 2025, commercially available Charge Point Management Systems (CPMS) do not yet support Bidirectional Power Transfer (BPT) functionalities. Consequently, a conventional state-of-the-art (SotA) analysis proves insufficient, as current market solutions cannot serve as a direct benchmark for the CPMS targeted in this project.

Instead, this analysis takes a two-step, forward-looking approach:

1. In a first step, a baseline analysis of classical CPMS is conducted, giving an overview of currently available CPMS functionalities, focusing on core capabilities such as technical operation, billing mechanisms, smart charging features, and system integration. This establishes the foundational state of the art.
2. In a second step and building on this baseline, the analysis then shifts focus to the additional key functionalities required to support bidirectional charging. This includes the evaluation of key enabling standards such as OCPP 2.1 and ISO 15118-20, the technical implications of bidirectional energy flows, and the integration of external systems like V2G managers and DSOs.

This comparative analysis forms the foundation for the benchmarking framework in [Chapter 3](#), which defines the expected performance characteristics of a CPMS capable of supporting bidirectional energy flows. Based on these insights, the document then outlines key technical and systemic barriers and formulates recommendations for the system development. From these, a set of Key Performance Parameters (KPPs) is derived to serve as qualitative benchmarks for evaluating the backend implementation in the project context.

5.5.2 State of the Art Analysis

Unidirectional Charge Point Management Systems

Charge Point Management Systems are central software platforms used by Charge Point Operators (CPOs) to efficiently operate and maintain their charging infrastructure. A CPMS typically connects all charge points via a secure VPN or encrypted APIs, enabling real-time monitoring, diagnostics, and control as well as quick intervention in case of a malfunction.

Core CPMS functionalities include:

- Technical operation and real-time monitoring of charge points
- Remote fault detection and recovery
- Facilitation and billing of different use cases:
 - ad-hoc charging (direct payment, e.g., via credit card or PayPal)
 - contract-based charging (direct charging contract with the CPO, consolidated monthly billing)
 - eRoaming (allowing users to charge across networks via roaming hubs)
- Support for multiple authentication methods (RFID, app, Plug&Charge)
- Integration with roaming platforms and energy management systems (EMS)
- Static and dynamic load management
- Basic smart charging (V1G, e.g., unidirectional smart charging)
- Reporting, analytics, and integration with customer portals or fleet systems

In advanced systems, these functionalities are extended to support energy optimization, customer portals, and interoperability with third-party components [113].

Key Sub-technologies für Bidirectional Charge Point Management Systems

To enable bidirectional power transfer, however, several key sub-technologies must be supported by a CPMS. The following sections outline their state of development and relevance to the project.

A - Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) The Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) is a modular application protocol for the communication between charging stations and a CPMS. The protocol is managed by the non-profit Open Charge Alliance based in the Netherlands and is open and royalty-free. Although it is not an official standard, its widespread use in the industry has made it the de facto standard [114]–[116].

Versions and current state Currently, there are three versions of OCPP available in the market: Versions 1.6, 2.0.1, and 2.1 with OCPP 2.1 being the latest version, released in February 2025. OCPP 1.6 was published in 2015 and is currently by far the most widespread version in the market. The successor of OCPP 1.5 introduced several new features, most notably and relevant for NEVERFLAT the smart charging features such as charging profiles or load management. However, OCPP 1.6 does not natively support ISO 15118-2, which is essential to enable Plug&Charge. Due to the slow uptake of the subsequent version OCPP 2.0.1 though, a backport was integrated into the protocol to allow for ISO 15118-2 based functions. As Vehicle-to-Grid or bidirectional power transfer was introduced at a later stage and is directly tied to ISO 15118-20, which was published in 2022, BPT related features are not supported in the combination of OCPP 1.6 and ISO 15118-2 [117]. The successor of version 1.6, OCPP 2.0.1, was introduced in 2020. Its most relevant new features are the integration of ISO 15118-2 which enabled Plug&Charge as well as extended smart charging functionalities, e.g., direct support of the input from (home) energy management systems ([H]EMS) and the support of integrated smart charging from the CPMS via the charging station to the electric vehicle. Due to a number of reasons, such as backward compatibility, OCPP 2.0.1 is not really established in the market yet. Currently, the Open Charge Alliance website lists less than 50 certified charging stations supporting OCPP 2.0.1 compared to over 1,000 for OCPP 1.6 [118]. The reasons for the slow uptake are mainly high costs and the fact, that OCPP 2.x is not downward compatible to earlier versions

which makes it difficult to operate mixed charging infrastructures running on both OCPP 1.6 and 2.x. Additionally, the switch to the latest version is not really necessary, considering the fact that the backport in OCPP 1.6 makes ISO 15118 functions like Plug&Charge possible without upgrading to the latest OCPP version [119]. OCPP 2.1 as the latest version of the Open Charge Point Protocol was released at the beginning of 2025 and features several new functionalities that are highly relevant for the NEVERFLAT project. Most importantly, it now has a new functional block for bidirectional charging that enables bidirectional energy flows such as V2G services. This comes in conjunction with native support of ISO 15118-20 – the evolution of ISO 15118-2 – which is crucial for bidirectional power transfer. In addition, OCPP 2.1 features enhanced EMS support as well as a new functional block on distributed energy resources (DER) control that enables the integration of DER. Since OCPP 2.1 has only just been released, it has not really been adopted in the market yet. As of now the list of certified charging stations and charge point management systems on the official website of the Open Charger Alliance does not even list OCPP 2.1 as an option when filtering for specific versions [114], [118], [120], [121].

Figure 5.8: OCPP versions comparison, own illustration, based on [120].

B - ISO 15118-20 ISO 15118 is an international standard series for the communication between an electric vehicle (EV) and a charging station (electric vehicle supply equipment – EVSE). Published by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), it defines the technical requirements for communication between EV and EVSE with the goal to ensure interoperability between different vehicles and charging systems [115], [122].

Versions and current state ISO 15118 consists of several parts, of which ISO 15118-2:2014 and ISO 15118-20 are of particular relevance for the project with ISO 15118-20 being the upgraded version of ISO 15118-2. Both versions define the network and application protocol requirements and are important for smart charging. While ISO 15118-2 was already published in 2014 and mainly introduced Plug&Charge and charging profiles for early unidirectional smart charging functionalities such as energy management as well as safety features like encrypted communication, it was upgraded in 2022 to version ISO 15118-20 with the goal to support more sophisticated smart charging possibilities such as inductive charging, the storage of multiple charging certificates, and, most notably, bidirectional power transfer. ISO 15118-20 is therefore considered a prerequisite for grid-friendly charging

of EVs and natively supported in OCPP 2.1 [25], [115], [123], [124]. To date, the adaptation of ISO 15118-20 is still in the early stages. However, it is expected that more and more vehicle OEMs and charging station manufacturers will support the standard in their products over the coming years [122], [125].

Figure 5.9: 15118-2/-20 versions comparison, own illustration, based on [25], [115], [120], [122]–[124].

C - Billing of BPT Services As of now, billing of charging sessions is only available for unidirectional charging. It covers a diverse range of possible use cases with the most common ones being ad-hoc charging, charging via charging contract, and eRoaming. Ad-hoc charging describes a charging process in which an EV user spontaneously charges at a charging station without being associated with the CPO or EMP via a specific charging contract. Billing and payment are mostly done via credit card or online payment services like PayPal. After the charging process is completed, the user receives an invoice with the charging details, as does the operator of the charging station. The CPO gets an overview of all completed charging processes including the charge detail records (CDRs) with all important information about each charging process (e.g., start and end time of the session, location of the charger, tariff, etc.) in his charge point management system. Another option is charging via a charging contract between an EV user and a CPO who acts as an EMP. This contract allows the user to charge at all the CPO's charging stations at a certain tariff. To do so, the user first needs to go through an authentication and authorization process. This is usually done by a RFID card or an app. After the charging process is complete, the driver does not necessarily need to pay right away, but instead the end user can receive a monthly bill that lists all charging activities and the respective prices. Billing and payment are carried out by the CPMS.[126] eRoaming further expands the possibilities of contractual charging by allowing EV users to charge their vehicles beyond the network of charging stations directly supported by their contract partner serving as both the CPO and EMP. Through eRoaming, drivers gain access to a wide range of charging stations operated by other CPOs that have established roaming agreements with their EMP.

These roaming agreements are typically established and managed via a roaming hub – a central platform that connects multiple EMPs and CPOs and facilitates communication between them. This hub enables a standardized, scalable way to ensure interoperability across different systems and providers. By leveraging such roaming hubs, EV drivers are no longer limited to a specific provider's charging stations but benefit from a broad, interconnected charging network. This model brings

clear advantages for all stakeholders:

- EV users enjoy greater flexibility and coverage, with access to more charging stations across regions and countries.
- EMPs can enhance their offering by giving customers access to more infrastructure without the need to build or operate stations themselves.
- CPOs benefit from increased station utilization and revenue by opening their infrastructure to users from various EMPs.

The billing process in eRoaming is similar to that of standard contractual charging. However, the involvement of a roaming platform or hub is key: it coordinates roaming agreements and handles the secure exchange of charging session data and billing information between EMPs and CPOs. This ensures that users can charge seamlessly at any station within their EMP's roaming network—without needing separate contracts or authentication systems [127], [128].

D - Interfaces to Partner Systems The CPMS provided does not run isolated from the other components and technologies to be developed by the partners within NEVERFLAT. Instead, the goal is to create a complete integrated charging infrastructure system. And since the CPMS connects most of the actors and components involved, it plays a pivotal role in creating such an integrated system. Hence, it is essential to deploy appropriate interfaces to ensure a maximum flexibility and compatibility to partner systems. This is especially true because the final design of the charging solution is yet to be determined in the further course of the project. The most important standards that need to be implemented are OCPP 2.1 for communication between the CPMS and the EVSE and ISO 15118-20 for communication between EVSE and EV. In addition, a complete bidirectional charging system also requires interfaces to external systems that provide grid-related information, such as the current state of the distribution grid or dynamic price signals that indicate charging or discharging needs for electric vehicles. These data are typically provided by distribution system operators (DSOs) and are essential for intelligently aligning charging behavior with the needs of the power system. The integration of such information can be realized, for example, through Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) managers or energy management systems (EMS) that coordinate charging processes based on real-time grid and market signals. Furthermore, to enable public and interoperable bidirectional charging across multiple networks, the CPMS must also support interfaces to roaming and bidirectional power transfer hubs, respectively, to ensure seamless roaming experiences for EV users. These interfaces as well should as well be based on the latest open standards to ensure long-term interoperability and scalability. The exact standards will be elaborated in the further course of the project.

5.5.3 Benchmarking from Analysis

The benchmark developed from the above state-of-the-art review sets the expectations for a CPMS capable of managing bidirectional charging. The following table summarizes the key dimensions:

Table 5.21: CPMS-Benchmarking

Category	Current CPMS	Bidirectional-ready CPMS
Communication Protocols	OCPP 1.6 or 2.0.1, partial ISO 15118-2	OCPP 2.1, full ISO 15118-20

Category	Current CPMS	Bidirectional-ready CPMS
Billing	Session-based, unidirectional only	BPT metering, new tariff models for energy export, flexible billing
Authentication	RFID, app, Plug&Charge	Secure certificate storage (ISO 15118-20)
Smart Charging/Load control	Plug&Charge, V1G, Static/dynamic load control	V2G services, EMS integration, DER coordination
External Interfaces	Roaming, basic DSO signal support	Additional interfaces to V2G services, BPT roaming

This benchmark guides both the technical development and later evaluation of the project CPMS.

5.5.4 Key Insights and Barriers

While the path to a Plug&Charge and eRoaming-ready CPMS appears conceptually clear, several critical gaps and implementation challenges remain that need to be overcome in order to reach the full potential of bidirectional charging.

Technical Barriers Although all previously discussed billing models—ad-hoc, contract-based, and eRoaming—could, in principle, be extended to support bidirectional power transfer (BPT), doing so in practice requires several backend enhancements:

- Accurate measurement of reverse energy flows from the vehicle to the grid is essential and must be reliably processed by the CPMS.
- Billing systems must evolve to reflect new tariff components for energy discharge, time-based incentives, or grid-support services.
- The CPMS needs to be flexible enough to accommodate emerging and currently undefined BPT use cases. As bidirectional applications mature, additional scenarios may arise that need to be implemented in the backend and supported contractually.

Integration and Protocol Implementation Challenges Implementing support for protocols like OCPP 2.1 and ISO 15118-20 poses significant challenges at the CPMS level:

- These standards introduce complex communication processes, dynamic energy flows, and new use case logic that are based on more sophisticated data models and functionalities that require extensive backend adaptations.
- The same is true for the additional standards used for the interfaces to other components such as the V2G manager, which are still evolving and require bespoke integration.

At the system level, one of the main barriers lies in the slow market uptake of OCPP 2.1 and ISO 15118-20. Many charging stations and EVs still rely on earlier protocol versions or support only partial implementations of the newer ones. This leads to limited compatibility, additional complexity in integration, and potential communication failures that the CPMS must detect and compensate for. This hinders the interoperability between different system components and thus the adoption of bidirectional charging.

5.5.5 Recommendations and Key Performance Parameters

To ensure a successful implementation of bidirectional charging functionality, the CPMS must be developed in close coordination with other system components, such as the charging station or the V2G manager. Since standards like ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1 must be supported by several involved components, their implementation should be planned and carried out jointly within the project. This includes regular compatibility tests between the CPMS and partner components to ensure that communication works reliably and as intended. This strategic and technical alignment is essential to ensure reliable and interoperable system behavior. Following the elaborations above, the following qualitative benchmark KPPs for the CPMS are derived:

- Technical handling of negative energy flows
- Support of all relevant use cases defined in the course of the project
- Billing of all relevant use cases defined in the course of the project
- Integrable with partner systems: Support of relevant, state-of-the-art standards such as ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1
- Scalability for mass deployment

These KPPs define the performance goals against which the CPMS will be evaluated during and at the end of the project.

5.6 Energy Tokenization

This section analyses different technological solutions to assess their suitability and capabilities for fulfilling the tokenisation needs of energy services in the NEVERFLAT project. The tokenisation service will be data-agnostic but tailored to the energy domain, retrieving Charge Detail Record (CDR) data and transferring pre-minted Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) tokens to users' wallets. Each solution is evaluated against key metrics that define its ability to meet service requirements.

5.6.1 Define Analysis Methodology on Energy Tokenization

This section begins by outlining the methodology used to evaluate SOTA technologies related to asset tokenization. A qualitative scoring system is introduced to support the evaluation process, and the methodological steps are described.

Table 5.22: *Energy Tokenisation scoring system*

Score	Description
1	Does not meet requirements (significant deficiencies, unsuitable solution).
2	Partially meets requirements (not fully adequate, significant improvements needed).
3	Adequately meets requirements (acceptable performance, minor improvements necessary).
4	Fully meets requirements (effective performance, only minor optimizations suggested).
5	Exceeds requirements (ideal solution, optimal performance, no improvements necessary).

Evaluation Steps: Following steps need to be followed:

- **Step 1:** Define Analysis Methodology

- **Step 2:** Define metrics for analysis and benchmarking purposes
- **Step 3:** Evaluate general network types based on metrics defined and presented scoring system.
- **Step 4:** Review of integration options (existing energy tokenisation solutions).
- **Step 5:** Based on evaluation scores from Step 3 and 4, recommend a “best fit” technology for further analysis.
- **Step 6:** Extrapolate and evaluate specific technologies that fall under the “best fit” network type. Use the established scoring system to objectively score each solution
- **Step 7:** Formulate actionable recommendations based on the scoring and comparative analysis outcomes, identifying suitable solutions for adoption and outlining potential pathways for implementation or adaptation.

5.6.2 Metrics

Analysing the SotA for tokenization related technologies requires a basic understanding of the system’s intended requirements and relevant metrics. To that end, we present an initial relevant metric elicitation below and score it using our predefined scoring system. This is not meant to define fixed or final needs but to establish a foundational understanding that supports the evaluation of relevant technologies.

Table 5.23: *Energy Tokenisation basic requirements.*

Metric	Description
Transaction fees	<p>What: Cost per transaction for processing and validation on the network.</p> <p>Why: Impacts economic sustainability and user adoption, especially for frequent micro-transactions in energy services.</p>
Decentralisation	<p>What: Degree to which network control and validation are distributed among independent parties.</p> <p>Why: Ensures trust minimization and resilience, supporting the NEVERFLAT goal of fair, open infrastructure.</p>
Non-Custodial Wallet	<p>What: A secure blockchain wallet where users directly manage their keys.</p> <p>Why: Empowers users with full ownership and control, aligning with NEVERFLAT’s user-centric, trust-driven design.</p>
Smart Contracts	<p>What: Code that automates token issuance, transfer, and redemption.</p> <p>Why: Ensures fast, transparent, rule-based transactions, essential for efficient energy market operations.</p>
Real Time Data	<p>What: Live data feeds integrated into the system.</p> <p>Why: Enables tokens to reflect actual usage and grid conditions, supporting dynamic energy balancing.</p>
API Connectivity	<p>What: RESTful APIs for system integration.</p> <p>Why: Ensures interoperability with NEVERFLAT modules and third parties, facilitating seamless services.</p>
Transaction Speed	<p>What: Fast transaction processing time.</p> <p>Why: Critical for smooth user interactions at charging stations, preventing delays in token settlements.</p>
Interoperability	<p>What: Ability to work with different systems and standards.</p>

Metric	Description
	Why: Supports cross-border, multi-actor compatibility, key to NEVERFLAT's reach and user acceptance.
Security & Compliance	What: Full encryption and GDPR-compliant protection. Why: Safeguards personal and transactional data, ensuring trust and legal compliance.
Scalability	What: System capacity to expand as needed. Why: Prepares for growth, integrating future energy markets and e-mobility services.
User Experience	What: Intuitive, real-time wallet interface. Why: Ensures easy onboarding and token use, fostering broad adoption and accessibility.

5.6.3 Evaluate Network Type

Tokenisation services can be implemented on different infrastructures, each with distinct characteristics. Public blockchains are open, decentralised networks offering transparency and trustlessness but with higher costs and slower performance. Private (permissioned) blockchains, whilst running on the same technology, are controlled by a set group of 'validators' rather than a full decentralised network, providing better control and retaining some decentralisation features. Traditional databases are fully centralised, fast, and efficient but lack the transparency, auditability, and trust mechanisms inherent to blockchain systems.

Table 5.24: Energy Tokenisation network type evaluation [129].

Metric	Public Blockchain	Permissioned Blockchain	Traditional Database Token
Transaction fees	3	4	5
Decentralisation	5	2	0
Smart Contracts	5	5	1
Real-time Data	5	5	5
API Connectivity	5	5	5
Transaction Speed	4	4	5
Interoperability (Charging Infra, IoT)	5	5	5
Security & Compliance (GDPR, Encryption)	4	5	3

Two network types score highly when evaluated against our chosen metrics based on this evaluation, it is recommended that NEVERFLAT build its own solution on top of a public or private blockchain network. Both public and private implementations can be built on top of open source DLT's i.e. NEVERFLAT could build a private Ethereum network of its own or connect to the public main net, each solution presents distinct advantages and trade-offs:

- **Public Blockchain – Best for Decentralisation & Transparency**
 - **Benefits:**

- * High decentralisation ensures trustlessness and censorship resistance.
- * Mature ecosystems support extensive integration and developer activity.
- * Transparent and auditable transactions enhance accountability.
- * Strong community driven innovation and tooling.
- **Trade-offs:**
 - * Variable transaction fees and potential network congestion.
 - * Limited control over governance and upgrade paths.
 - * On-chain data must be strictly controlled or encrypted.
- **Permissioned Blockchain – Best for Compliance & Control**
 - **Benefits:**
 - * Enhanced data privacy and regulatory compliance (e.g., GDPR).
 - * Controlled governance and access management.
 - **Trade-offs:**
 - * Reduced decentralisation and trustlessness.
 - * Higher setup and maintenance complexity.

5.6.4 Evaluation of specific technologies within the Best fit network type

Based on the evaluations conducted, the next step is an analysis of DLT that can deliver both public and/or private blockchain solutions. Below such technologies are evaluated and scored based on the basic metrics outlined earlier.

Table 5.25: Blockchain technology evaluation.

Requirements	Ethereum (Mainnet)	Polygon	Solana	IOTA (Rebased)	SUI
Transaction fees	1	4	5	5	5
Decentralisation	5	4	3	2	2
Non-Custodial Wallet	5	5	5	3	5
Smart Contracts	5	5	5	3	5
Real-time Data	3	5	5	3	5
API Connectivity	5	5	5	5	5
Transaction Speed (<5 sec)	3	5	5	5	5
Interoperability (Charging Infra, IoT)	5	5	3	5	3
Security & Compliance (GDPR, Encryption)	5	5	4	3	5
Scalability	3	5	5	5	5
User Experience (wallet, onboarding)	4	5	4	5	5

5.6.5 Prebuilt customizable solutions

The project also has the option to build a custom integration with an already existing service provider over creating its own solution from scratch. The solutions evaluated below make use of public blockchains so come with the inherent trust, auditability and transparency along with giving users

non-custodial control over their own assets i.e. tokenised energy. With that in mind let's look at some preexisting solutions and analyse whether they would be a sensible fit for our project needs.

Powerledger Powerledger is a hybrid blockchain platform (public Ethereum + private proof of stake (PoS) sidechain) designed for peer-to-peer energy trading, renewable energy certificate (REC) tokenisation, and grid flexibility services. It has been deployed in multiple real-world projects across Australia, the US, and Asia. Powerledger has piloted token-based incentives for EV charging behaviour and supports wallet integrations, making it suitable for user facing applications like NEVERFLAT [130].

Energy Web Energy Web is a non-profit organisation operating the Energy Web Chain, a permissioned blockchain built for the energy sector. Its flagship toolkit, EW Origin, supports REC tokenisation, flexible demand programs, and real time asset tracking. Energy Web has direct use cases involving EV integration and supports non-custodial wallets and smart contract-based incentives. It's backed by major utilities and has a strong European presence, aligning well with EU regulatory expectations [131].

Equigy Equigy is a TSO led initiative supported by European grid operators like TenneT, Swissgrid, and Terna. It uses Hyperledger Fabric to enable crowd balancing, enabling assets like EVs and home batteries to participate in balancing markets. While not built as a public facing token platform, it supports V2G integration and time-based flexibility contributions. It may be more suited for backend grid integration rather than a user facing app but has proven utility scale deployment [132].

Table 5.26: Integration options evaluation

Solution	Supports Time Based Tokenisation	Supports Bidirectional Charging / V2G	Non-Custodial Wallet Integration	Real Time Interaction/User Feedback	Customisability for Incentive Logic
Powerledger	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High
Energy Web (EWF)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High
Equigy	Partial	Yes	Unclear	No	Medium

If the project aims to integrate with an existing energy tokenisation solution, Energy Web (EWF) emerges as the most suitable option. It aligns strongly with the NEVERFLAT use case by offering dedicated tools for energy attribute tracking, compatibility with EV grid integration and bidirectional charging, support for non-custodial wallets, and a regulatory framework aligned with EU standards. EWF provides robust SDKs and active ecosystem support, making it highly integratable for delivering real time user incentives and dynamic token logic. While minor front-end customisation may be required, its backend maturity and sector specific focus make it the most strategic choice. Powerledger remains a viable alternative, particularly for real time trading dynamics, though additional localisation and compliance work would likely be needed for EU deployment.

5.6.6 Recommendations

Following the evaluation of tokenization technologies and blockchain candidates and based on the metrics outlined above, we recommend that NEVERFLAT develop a custom solution built on public blockchain architecture. This approach offers the best alignment with the project's need for transparency, trust, decentralised control, and core technical requirements.

Among the assessed DLT's, Polygon emerges as the optimal blockchain candidate for the NEVERFLAT project. It supports flexible deployment models, public or permissioned, making it adaptable to evolving project needs. Polygon demonstrates strong and consistent performance across key metrics including scalability, transaction speed, interoperability, and security compliance. It balances decentralisation with governance control, and its mature ecosystem, robust API connectivity, and developer support make it a future proof choice.

A public blockchain architecture, particularly with Polygon, brings the following benefits:

- **Reduced complexity** – Developing on the public Polygon network, as opposed to deploying a private instance, reduces operational complexity, particularly with respect to the requirement for consortium members to host and maintain their own network nodes.
- **Immutability** – Ensures tamper-proof records once published.
- **Verifiability** – Enables stakeholders to confirm data integrity independently.
- **Auditability** – Provides a complete transactional history.
- **Transparency** – Builds trust in the incentive mechanisms.
- **Security** – Utilises proven cryptographic standards.
- **Decentralisation** – Minimises reliance on central authorities and improves system resilience.

To reduce user friction and support broad adoption, we propose deploying Managed Key Infrastructure (MKI). This will abstract away the complexities of wallet management and transaction signing. Users will be able to engage with the system securely without needing to manage private keys or hold native tokens (e.g., MATIC) for transaction fees. This design enhances onboarding, usability, and user experience while preserving decentralisation and security.

Alternative third-party platforms, such as Energy Web, Powerledger, and Equigy, were also considered. However, we recommend against adopting pre-built solutions at this stage due to several limitations:

- **Reduced Customisability** – Fixed token logic and workflows may not suit NEVERFLAT's dynamic incentive models or real-time data needs.
- **Compliance Uncertainty** – GDPR and EU data protection alignment may be harder to guarantee in third-party systems.
- **Integration Constraints** – Custom solutions offer better integration with our IoT and EV charging infrastructure.
- **Vendor Lock-In** – Third-party platforms may restrict future governance and scalability options.
- **User Friction** – Many still require native token management, creating unnecessary complexity.

5.7 Integrated Pervasive Smart Low-Power Bi-Directional EV Charging Infrastructure System

5.7.1 Methodology

The integrated bidirectional charging infrastructure system to be created within NEVERFLAT does not currently exist on the market and has yet to be developed. At present, there are only some manufacturer-specific, proprietary solutions that are used for showcases as well as two newly introduced commercial solutions: One by Renault, Mobilize, and The Mobility House for bidirectional charging in France [133] and one by Octopus Energy and BYD in the UK [134]. However, both solutions also rely on proprietary technology, working only with specific EVs (Renault 5 and Alpine A290 in France and the BYD Dolphin in the UK, respectively) and requiring a specific wallbox as well as a specific charging contract (Mobilize Power in France and Octopus in the UK). Consequently, a conventional State of the Art (SotA) analysis focused solely on existing products is not suitable for deriving meaningful system specifications or Key Performance Parameters (KPPs).

Instead, this analysis follows a top-down architectural approach that proceeds in three stages:

1. Comparative analysis of existing charging system architectures, starting with classical unidirectional setups and moving toward emerging bidirectional solutions. This includes a discussion of key system actors, communication standards, and integration complexity.
2. Definition of functional and technical requirements for the envisioned system, based on gaps identified in existing approaches and the goals and constraints outlined in the NEVERFLAT Grant Agreement.
3. Development of a draft system architecture, reflecting the identified requirements and incorporating newly defined components to support bidirectional energy flows, data centralization, and multi-actor coordination.

As the specific architectural details and in particular the interfaces best suited to fulfil the requirements will be elaborated in the further course of the project, this analysis concentrates on the high-level structure of the system, addressing key questions such as what the system should be capable of and how it should be fundamentally designed. In this way, redundancy is avoided and meaningful KPPs can still be derived that can be used to evaluate the final charging infrastructure system.

5.7.2 State-of-the-Art Analysis

Comparison of Unidirectional and Bidirectional Charging Systems

From a technological perspective, classical unidirectional charging systems are well established and widely deployed. Their architecture is typically centered around a few core components: the electric vehicle (EV), the charging station (EVSE), a backend charge point management system (CPMS), and, where applicable, an eRoaming platform. These systems rely primarily on standardized communication protocols such as OCPP 1.6 or 2.0 and offer limited integration complexity. Energy flows are strictly unidirectional, moving from the grid to the vehicle. Data exchange between components is often fragmented, with system logic concentrated in the backend. [127], [135], [136]

In contrast, bidirectional charging systems—also referred to as V2G or V2X solutions—are still emerging and currently exist mostly as pilot deployments or within research projects. Notable initiatives include EU-funded projects such as SCALE [80], Drive2X [70], EV4EU [73], and XL-Connect [85]. These systems introduce a broader set of technical and organizational requirements, including the need to incorporate local renewable energy sources (RES), dynamic grid interaction, and additional actors such as aggregators and V2G managers. Communication flows become multidirectional, requiring more advanced and interoperable protocols like ISO 15118-20, OCPP 2.1, openADR, or EE-BUS. The system architecture becomes more modular and layered, typically separating hardware and software tiers while centralizing data flows through harmonized ingestion and storage mechanisms.

NEVERFLAT extends these developments by proposing a pervasive, smart, open and integrated infrastructure system capable of managing bidirectional flows, local RES integration, and cross-platform coordination that is suitable for mass deployment.

NEVERFLAT System Components

Building on the architectural insights above as well as the project’s Grant Agreement, the NEVERFLAT system consists of the following key components, listed in Table 5.27, divided into hardware and software tiers:

Table 5.27: NEVERFLAT System Components

System components
Hardware Tier
Charging Station
Coupled renewable energy sources (RES)
Local grid
Software tier
Charging infrastructure deployment planner and optimizer module
Generation and demand forecasting and V2G management module
NEVERFLAT applications and tools suite
Charge point management system
eRoaming platform
Source data
Data storage and ingestion service

Except for the RES and the local grid, all components listed above will be newly developed within the NEVERFLAT project by various partners. As their detailed technical specifications are outlined in the Grant Agreement and individual SotA deliverables, they are not further elaborated here.

Functional Requirements

From a system perspective, one of the key functional requirements for a public charging infrastructure system is interoperability and compatibility with a wide range of components and technologies. This can be achieved through the use of the latest and open standards, ensuring seamless integration across different sites and use cases. Creating an open system instead of a proprietary solution

enables not only seamless integration across different sites and use cases but also forms the basis for future large-scale deployment and long-term commercial success. This requirement is also reflected in the project's Grant Agreement [137].

Another fundamental goal is to build a system that is:

- Integrated and operational
- Deployment-ready
- Efficient
- User-friendly
- Low-cost

These qualities are reflected in the Grant Agreement [137], and serve as guiding principles for the system architecture. Some attributes – such as being operational or integrated – are directly achieved through technical development and system completeness. Others, such as user-friendliness or cost-efficiency, require targeted and intensive efforts from the project partners and feedback loops throughout the project duration.

5.7.3 Benchmarking: Classical vs. Bidirectional Charging Systems

To better understand the architectural advances proposed in NEVERFLAT, this section benchmarks classical unidirectional charging systems against emerging bidirectional solutions, with a specific focus on system setup and the actors involved.

Table 5.28: *Charging Infrastructure Systems Benchmarking*

Category	Classical Charging System	Bidirectional Charging System
Core Actors	EV, EVSE, CPMS, eRoaming platform	+ V2G Manager, Grid Interface, RES, Aggregator
System Architecture	Backend-centric, limited interaction depth	Dual-layer architecture: Hardware & Software tightly integrated
Communication Protocols	OCPP 1.6/2.0.1, ISO 15118-2	OCPP 2.1, ISO 15118-20, + additional protocols (e.g., openADR, EEBUS, etc.)
Energy Flows	Unidirectional (Grid → EV)	Bidirectional (Grid ↔ EV), incl. RES integration
Data Handling	Fragmented or local	Centralized data handling, harmonized via database
Standardization Level	Mature and widely implemented	Emerging, requires further harmonization

This benchmarking, as shown in Table 5.28, illustrates that bidirectional systems not only require more components but also significantly more complex interactions. The NEVERFLAT architecture addresses these by integrating all components through a central data layer and a modular interface concept built on open standards.

5.7.4 Proposed System Structure: The NEVERFLAT Architecture

Based on the functional requirements defined earlier and internal project expertise, a preliminary system architecture has been designed developed that seems best-fitted to address the identified functional demands. This draft remains subject to revision as the project progresses, but already offers a clear picture of component roles and key interfaces.

Figure 5.10: Integrated charging infrastructure system - proposed structure

As shown in Figure 5.10, the system consists of two interconnected sub-systems: The hardware tier on the left-hand side of the figure and the software tier on the right-hand side.

Hardware Tier The hardware layer includes the general power grid and integrated local RES on the one hand as well as the EV and the EVSE on the other. These components are linked through both data interfaces and physical energy flows. Since the charging system is supposed to be bidirectional, power flows can occur in both directions: From the grid via the EVSE into the EV and vice versa with the exception of the RES that can only unidirectionally supply energy – either to the grid or the EV.

Software Tier The software tier consists of the two components that in conjunction with the EVSE and the EV form the process chain of “traditional” unidirectional charging: The OCPP backend, which includes energy management, the user app as well as billing functionalities, and the eRoaming platform. These elements are complemented by the components that will be developed within NEVERFLAT with the data storage sitting right at the center of the system, connecting all the other newly developed components. This setup enables the integration of the abovementioned elements required for the actual bidirectional charging process as well as the deployment planner, which is

not involved in the charging process itself, but is crucial for the identification of appropriate sites for charging stations once mass deployment takes place. The four “traditional” elements of the EV charging chain (i.e. EV, EVSE, backend and eRoaming platform) form the basis for the whole system as they are essential for any kind of EV charging. The backend then is connected to the components that enable smart, bidirectional charging. The V2G manager acts as a higher-level grid control system and is the connection to the energy system and local RES, where all information regarding the current state of the grid, including generation and demand forecast, is gathered and processed, resulting in optimized energy flows into and out of the EV. The data storage, in turn, is the central point where all the relevant data from the individual components is collected, harmonized and stored so that it can be processed and analyzed as well as accessed by the other components.

Interfaces In addition to the components themselves, also a number of interfaces for the connection between the different sub-systems need to be defined to ensure effective and efficient data transfers. While the exact standards for setting up the system will only be determined later in the project, the Grant Agreement, as mentioned above, specifies that the architecture should be based on open standards to create an open system. To achieve this, state-of-the-art open standards will be employed to ensure that the system can be easily adapted to specific needs at various sites. This approach not only guarantees support for all relevant use cases but also ensures that the system can be deployed across different locations, environments, and configurations — for example, by integrating external energy management systems (EMS). This will facilitate the future large-scale deployment of the charging solution. As of now, only two standards have been defined that are to be used in the system: OCPP 2.1 for communication between the backend and EVSE and ISO 15118-20 for communication between EVSE and EV. Those are described in more detail in the CPMS section. Other standards that could be used for the respective interfaces are, for example, open Automated Demand Response (openADR) or EEBUS for the connection to the power grid and for the integration of local generation plants, or OICP for the connection between the backend and the roaming platform. By setting up the system this way, we not only ensure effective integration, but also adhere to the requirements specified in the Grant Agreement while at the same time maximizing efficiency.

5.7.5 Key Insights and Barriers

One of the key takeaways is the architectural shift required to support bidirectional energy flows and system-wide interoperability. While classical unidirectional systems rely on a relatively simple backend-centric structure, bidirectional systems necessitate greater modularity, data centralization, and multi-actor integration. This includes components such as the V2G manager, forecasting modules, and harmonized data ingestion platforms – none of which are found in traditional setups. Key gaps and barriers in the development of an open and interoperable charging infrastructure system can be identified on both a general and project-specific level. On a broader scale, one major challenge lies in the limited adoption of already defined standards for BPT such as ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1, which, despite being available and due to several reasons, are not yet widely implemented across the industry (Refer Section 5.5). In addition, for several system interfaces such as the connection between a V2G manager and the CPMS, suitable open standards have not yet been defined. From a project-specific perspective, beyond the task of selecting appropriate standards, the main challenge is to ensure full compatibility between all developed components throughout the system architecture, which requires close collaboration between all parties involved and regular compatibility testing

during the development process.

5.7.6 Recommendations and Key Performance Parameters

To ensure the successful development and deployment of the NEVERFLAT charging infrastructure system, a number of key recommendations can be derived from the analysis. First and foremost, the system should be built entirely on open and widely supported standards. In addition to OCPP 2.1 for communication between backend and EVSE, and ISO 15118-20 for the interface between EV and EVSE, other standards such as openADR, EEBUS, or OICP should be considered for integrating grid services and eRoaming functionalities.

Furthermore, the overall system architecture should follow a modular and scalable design principle in order to enable flexible adaptations in future system upgrades or deployments in different technical environments. A centralized and harmonized data handling approach should be adopted to ensure seamless communication between components while minimizing latency and avoiding redundancies. This is particularly important considering the increased number of actors and systems involved in bidirectional charging. To reduce complexity and increase efficiency, the number of system interfaces should be kept to a necessary minimum, following the principle of “as many as needed, as few as possible.”

In addition, it is strongly recommended to establish a robust process for cross-partner interface coordination and integration testing throughout the development phase. Given the distributed development across different project partners, regular validation of interoperability is crucial to ensure the system functions reliably as a whole. Based on the above considerations and requirements, a number of qualitative and quantitative Key Performance Parameters have been identified.

- **Open, interoperable system:** The system should support and be set up based on state-of-the-art and open standards.
- **Efficiency:** As an indicator for efficiency, for instance, latency limits can be defined to ensure system responsiveness.
- **Low-cost:** Overall system costs should not exceed those of standard DC charging stations with comparable performance and backend functionality.
- **User-friendliness:** Usability could be measured through user feedback, for example by aiming for at least 90% user satisfaction in surveys.
- **Operational/Availability:** Define thresholds for the availability of the charging system that must not be undercut, e.g.,
 - At least 95% availability during pilot phase and
 - At least 99% availability for the final system

Together, these recommendations and performance targets define a clear development path and measurable quality standards for the realization of the NEVERFLAT integrated bidirectional charging infrastructure.

5.8 Virtual Power Plants

This study employs a systematic literature review to evaluate the integration of vehicle-to-grid Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)) systems within Virtual Power Plants (VPP), focusing on (i) technological portfolio,

(ii) ancillary services and their control techniques, (iii) data infrastructure, (iv) forecasting methods and (v) Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) interaction models. Doing so enables identification of patterns, best practices and critical gaps in current implementations of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X)-systems in Virtual Power Plants (VPP)s, thereby enabling insights for future deployments.

In the process 23 references were selected for the systematic literature review, comprising 5 real-world research projects and 18 academic studies, which were analyzed based on the previously outlined research questions. This comparative overview aims to highlight commonalities, distinctions, and critical limitations across current implementations, providing a structured foundation for identifying best practices and research opportunities relevant to the NEVERFLAT project. The results of the review are shown in chapter 5.8.1 (See Tab.5.29 for further information).

5.8.1 Literature Review

Technology Portfolios

Portfolios range from Electric Vehicle (EV)-only implementations [138]–[140] to multi-DER systems incorporating PV, wind, stationary storage, and demand response [141]–[145]. Pilots such as *V2X Suisse* [146] and *Project Sciurus* [147] demonstrate large-scale V2G with production EV models.

Ancillary Services and Control Methods

Frequency regulation is the most common ancillary service, appearing in both research [145], [148]–[150] and pilots [146], [147], [151]. Voltage control through reactive power support feature prominently in grid-integrated studies [148], [149], [152], [153]. Advanced control strategies include grid-forming control [154], multi-objective robust optimisation [142], bi-level MIQCP formulations [153], and stochastic optimisation with reinforcement learning [143]. Pilots often employ rule-based or tariff-driven control [145], while some studies omit control specifics altogether [138], [141].

Data Infrastructure

While many studies present advanced Internet of Things (IoT)–edge–cloud architectures with standardised protocols such as OCPP, IEC 61850, or IEC 63110 [144], [149], [152], [154], several simulation-based works abstract away infrastructure details [139], [140], [142], [155]. Pilots such as *V2X Suisse* [146] and *Project Sciurus* [147] use cloud platforms for aggregation and optimisation, with varying degrees of integration with other DERs. Privacy-preserving fleet management using anonymised state data has also been proposed [140].

Forecasting Methods

Forecasting sophistication varies widely. Advanced approaches employ machine learning (LSTM, GRU, CNN) for RES and load [144], temporal convolutional networks for load [153], and probabilistic Monte Carlo methods for Electric Vehicle (EV) behaviour [140], [156]. Others rely on deterministic forecasts from historical data or external sources [139], [141], [145], or omit forecasting entirely [146], [151], [157].

V2X Interaction Types

Most implementations centre on Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) [138], [139], [142]–[147], [150]–[157]. V1G-only scenarios occur when discharging is excluded for privacy or technical reasons [140], [158]. V2H and V2B are emerging, often in pilot contexts [144]–[146], [149], [157], while Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle-to-Load (V2L) remain limited to conceptual mentions or small-scale trials [146],

[149].

Distinctions

Unique contributions include cross-brand interoperability validation [154], regional market feasibility with agent-based dispatch [139], privacy-preserving fleet control [140], large-scale domestic trials profiling customer archetypes [147], and data-centric architectures integrating blockchain and AI for secure energy markets [144]. Grid-aware formulations explicitly quantify trade-offs between grid stability and EV profitability [153].

Limitations

Common limitations include unrealistic assumptions on EV availability and perfect information [138], [140]–[143], [145], [153], lack of economically viable business models [146], [147], and simplified battery degradation models [138], [153]. Scalability and computational complexity remain significant barriers for optimization-based approaches [153], [155], and interoperability challenges persist despite some progress [144], [145], [149], [152], [154].

The selected body of work spans both academic research and large-scale pilot projects, covering a range of technology portfolios, ancillary services and control methods, data infrastructures, forecasting methods and V2X interaction models. The common thread is the centrality of EVs as flexible assets in **VPPs**, frequently paired with other distributed energy resources (DERs) such as photovoltaic (PV) systems, wind turbines, and stationary batteries [141]–[145], [155], [156]. Several studies focus exclusively on EV fleets, either in market feasibility contexts [139] or in privacy-preserving fleet coordination [140], while others embed EVs into detailed network models to study losses and voltage profiles [153].

Overall, the literature and pilot experience demonstrate that integrating V2G into VPP is technically feasible and can deliver grid-supportive services, but large-scale deployment is hindered by economic, interoperability, and behavioral uncertainties. Addressing these gaps requires real-world data integration, refined control strategies accounting for stochastic user behavior, and viable market mechanisms to ensure long-term participation.

5.8.2 Conclusion

The current state-of-the-art in integrating electric vehicles with virtual power plants demonstrates a clear trend toward leveraging bidirectional EV charging for ancillary services such as voltage regulation, frequency support, and peak load management. Various approaches include centralized VPP aggregators that coordinate household loads, rooftop PV, stationary batteries, and EVs, employing advanced optimization techniques, employing advanced optimization techniques (e.g., genetic algorithms, MILP) and more recently machine learning methods (e.g. deep-learning, LSTM) to balance economic objectives with grid stability. Pilot projects and simulations demonstrate that V2G-equipped fleets can respond within seconds to grid events, confirming technical feasibility on small to medium scales. A general framework that includes utilities, aggregators, EV owners, grid operators, and third-party service providers is largely missing. Similarly, few studies base their models on extensive, real-world datasets. Most works are based on idealized assumptions (e.g communication infrastructure, real-world market conditions, simplistic EV user behaviour). It would be valuable for future research to explore end-to-end architectures validated with large-scale operational data,

incorporating probabilistic user behavior as well as dynamic market and weather conditions.

Table 5.29: Literature review of virtual power plant integrated bidirectional charging applications

KPI		References																							
		[138]	[154] ¹	[147] ¹	[158]	[141]	[151] ¹	[148]	[146] ¹	[157] ¹	[159]	[160]	[149]	[150]	[139]	[142]	[143]	[152]	[156]	[140]	[155]	[153]	[144]	[145]	
Technology Portfolio	Bidirectional Charging Stations	x	x	x				x	x	x			x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	
	EVs	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
	Battery Storage					x					x	x	x	x		x						x	x	x	
	Photovoltaic Panels					x					x		x	x		x	x							x	x
	Wind Power Plants										x					x		x	x	x	x				x
	Fuel Cells													x											
	Gas Turbines																	x							
	Micro-CHP																								
	Distributed Generators										x														
	Loads															x	x			x	x	x	x	x	x
	Distributed Resources																x		x					x	x
	Stationary Transformers																				x			x	x
	Substations																							x	x
	Smart Meters																				x			x	
Ancillary Service & Control Methods	Frequency Regulation	x		x	x		x		x	x		x	x	x			x	x	x		x	x	x	x	
	Voltage Regulation	x						x					x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
	Load Shifting															x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	
	Peak Shaving													x	x	x		x		x	x	x	x	x	
	Demand Response										x				x	x	x						x	x	
	Islanded Operation		x							x															
	Active Power Control		x			x							x												
	Reactive Power Control		x			x		x					x	x			x	x		x			x		
	Grid-Forming Control		x														x	x					x	x	x
	Energy Trading														x										x
Data Infrastructure	OCCP		x						x																
	SCCP		x																						
	IEC 63110		x																						
	IEC 15118		x											x											
	IEC 61851		x											x											
	IEEE 1547													x											
	IEEE 929													x											
	IEC 6180-90-8		x																						
	Modbus									x															
	CHAdEMO		x																						
	RS485																	x							
	ICT												x						x				x		
	IOT													x						x	x		x	x	x
	Cloud based			x						x	x					x			x	x	x		x	x	x
Blockchain														x										x	
Wi-Fi																		x							
Bluetooth																								x	
Forecasting Methods	Generation			x		x		x					x			x	x		x		x	x	x	x	
	Load					x										x				x	x	x	x	x	
	Weather													x						x			x	x	x
	Dis/-charging			x													x	x	x						
	Windenergy																							x	x
	Solarenergy																x	x	x					x	x
	SOC		x																	x	x	x			x
	price					x	x													x			x	x	x
V2X Type	V2G	x	x	x		x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
	V2B					x																		x	
	V2H							x	x			x												x	
	V2L								x																
	V2V								x				x												

¹ Pilot projects; unmarked columns are academic studies.

5.9 Charging Infrastructure Deployment Planner

5.9.1 Introduction

The growth of electric mobility and the integration of V2G technology present new challenges for the efficient planning and distribution of charging infrastructure in urban areas. V2G technology allows EVs not only to charge their batteries but also to return electricity to the grid, contributing to grid stability and a more sustainable mobility ecosystem. The objective of this document is to analyse the state of the art in planning V2G charging infrastructure and to establish the methodological foundations for developing an adaptable planning tool for different urban and regional contexts. The proposed deployment is structured into three key phases: (1) predicting the future need for charging stations, (2) estimating the need for charging infrastructure at the urban scale considering variables such as socio-demographic factors, urban morphology and traffic intensity, and (3) optimizing the distribution of V2G charging stations across urban areas. The resulting tool will be adaptable to different urban policies by allowing the modification of the weights assigned to each factor through an interactive interface, enabling stakeholders to tailor the infrastructure planning according to their specific needs.

Figure 5.11: Development phase diagram.

5.9.2 Methodology

To guide the development of the V2G planning tool, this document adopts a structured methodological approach. The analysis is organized around the three core functional phases of the planning workflow.

For each phase, the methodology involves a review of relevant literature to examine how different approaches have addressed the associated planning challenges. In Phase 1, the focus is on methods used to estimate future infrastructure needs, including those based on historical usage, EV adoption projections, mobility patterns, analogical inference, and uncertainty-aware planning. In Phase 2, beyond mapping existing methods for identifying priority areas, special attention is given to understanding the underlying factors that drive spatial variation in charging demand. This dual focus

enables the derivation of a demand distribution model that is not only data-driven but also sensitive to the socio-urban dynamics influencing infrastructure needs. In Phase 3, the goal is to identify and compare optimization algorithms that can effectively distribute a predefined number of V2G chargers across a city or territory at the same time, taking into account spatial priorities.

Given the limited real-world deployment of V2G technology, the methodology relies heavily on literature and case studies focused on conventional unidirectional public charging infrastructure, particularly slow chargers. This indirect evidence base is used to infer behavioral, technical, and planning principles that can be reasonably transferred to the V2G context.

Subsequently, a benchmark of existing planning tools is conducted to identify how current solutions address the phases outlined above, and where gaps remain. The combination of literature-based evidence and market analysis provides a comprehensive foundation for defining the functional requirements and performance parameters of the proposed planning tool.

5.9.3 State of the Art Analysis

Phase 1: Forecasting Future Demand for Charging Infrastructure Estimating the future number of public V2G charging points is essential to anticipate infrastructure needs and plan effective deployments. Several forecasting approaches have been proposed in the literature, each leveraging different data sources, assumptions, and modelling techniques.

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Forecasting based on historical usage data One of the most straightforward approaches to estimating future charging demand is to analyse historical data from existing networks. Time series models such as ARIMA and SARIMA are commonly used to forecast electricity consumption based on past usage patterns. Louie (2017) demonstrated this method using data from over 2,400 charging stations in the U.S. [161]. More recently, Sanami et al. (2025) applied LSTM models with attention mechanisms, improving short-term forecasting accuracy and enhancing model interpretability [162]. These methods are particularly effective in contexts where rich historical datasets are available, and they have shown that incorporating external variables such as weather conditions can significantly improve prediction performance.

Forecasting based on EV adoption trends This approach estimates future charging infrastructure needs by linking charger deployment to projected EV uptake. Logistic growth and diffusion models are commonly used to simulate adoption trajectories over time. For example, Yuan et al. (2023) developed a parameterized Bass network diffusion model to predict EV adoption in Washington State, capturing both temporal dynamics and socio-demographic factors such as income and peer influence [163]. In a more infrastructure-oriented application, Castro et al. (2022) used logistic growth projections of EV penetration to estimate future energy and power demand for a fast-charging station integrated with local PV and battery storage in Campinas, Brazil [164]. This study highlights how

adoption forecasts can inform site-level energy planning, optimizing charging capacity and minimizing grid impacts through renewable integration. Together, these methods support anticipatory planning by aligning infrastructure deployment with expected EV market evolution.

Forecasting based on mobility patterns This approach estimates charging demand by analysing spatial and temporal mobility data, such as traffic flows, trip purposes, and parking behaviours. By integrating GIS with traffic analysis, researchers can predict where and when charging demand will occur. For instance, Mahmoudi et al. (2024) combined GIS-based traffic analysis with charging profiles to forecast spatial load distributions, enabling infrastructure planning aligned with mobility behaviours [165]. Additionally, Schläpfer et al. (2021) introduced a framework that infers population-wide mobility patterns from anonymized mobile phone location data and superimposes a vehicle charging and discharging scheme [166]. This method allows for the estimation of aggregate V2G energy supply and demand at fine-grained spatial and temporal scales, supporting the planning of city-wide V2G infrastructures. Such models are particularly useful in urban contexts where travel patterns significantly influence charging needs.

Forecasting based on analogical inference In areas with scarce operational data, charging demand estimation can be approached through analogical inference, transferring insights from cities with similar characteristics. This strategy relies on matching urban, demographic, and mobility profiles to extrapolate likely infrastructure needs. The SPAP framework exemplifies this approach by combining spatial-temporal domain adaptation with iterative optimization to simultaneously predict demand and plan charger deployment in new cities. Applied to Chinese cities, it significantly outperformed existing deployments in revenue and planning efficiency [167]. Despite its promise, this method remains sensitive to context-specific variables such as policy frameworks, EV adoption incentives, and local travel behaviour.

Forecasting based on uncertainty-aware To address the inherent uncertainties in EV adoption rates, user behaviour, and renewable energy availability, several studies emphasize the importance of uncertainty-aware planning. Techniques such as scenario analysis and stochastic optimization help assess infrastructure robustness under varying future conditions. For instance, Niu et al. (2023) develop bi-objective models that account for uncertainties in charging demand, PV generation, and household loads to optimize V2G charger deployment and operations, demonstrating reduced load variability and improved system flexibility [168]. In practice, hybrid models that combine multiple approaches are increasingly common, as they balance the strengths and limitations of each method. For the planning of V2G infrastructure, the added complexity of bidirectional energy flow and grid integration demands predictive models that go beyond vehicle counts and include temporal charging patterns and user willingness to participate in V2G services.

Phase 2: Spatial prioritization for EV charger deployment based on urban factors Once the total charging demand in a region has been estimated, a key challenge lies in identifying the most suitable locations for deploying EV charging stations. This task depends heavily on the spatial characteristics of the urban environment. The literature presents various approaches to evaluate and prioritize locations based on different urban data dimensions, ranging from user needs to infrastructure readiness. Five main approaches identified in recent studies are set out below.

Urban morphology and socio-demographic indicators This approach identifies suitable locations for EV charging infrastructure by analysing urban structure and population characteristics using spatial multi-criteria methods. One study developed a GIS-based model to determine optimal on-street residential charging locations in Birmingham, UK, integrating factors such as population density, off-street parking availability, road type, and proximity to dwellings [169]. The findings highlight how urban morphology, and residential context can be operationalised through geospatial analysis to support targeted, efficient, and context-sensitive infrastructure deployment.

Grid constraints and energy system readiness This approach defines spatial constraints for EV charger deployment by incorporating the physical and operational limitations of the electrical grid into infrastructure planning. One study proposes a dual-layer control strategy to forecast optimal allocation and scheduling of charging stations under high penetration scenarios, addressing distribution network constraints and variable charging demand [170]. Another model uses Voronoi diagrams to structure the planning area and applies a profit maximization function that includes grid-related limitations such as transformer capacity and voltage drops, ensuring the technical feasibility of each candidate site [171]. These methodologies support the identification of grid-compatible areas and help align charging infrastructure deployment with system capacity, enhancing reliability and resilience.

Accessibility and equity-based prioritization This approach emphasizes ensuring equitable access to EV charging infrastructure by integrating socio-demographic indicators and spatial accessibility analyses. Studies have highlighted disparities in charging station distribution, often favouring affluent areas and leaving marginalized communities underserved. For instance, Ermagun and Tian (2024) conducted a national study revealing that areas with higher shares of racial minorities and lower-income populations have significantly less access to public EV charging stations [172]. Similarly, a framework proposed by researchers in Hong Kong assessed both horizontal and vertical equity in charger distribution, demonstrating severe spatial inequities in certain regions [173]. To address these disparities, planning methodologies have been developed that utilize GIS to identify optimal locations for community charging stations, ensuring that residents are within a reasonable walking distance—typically five to ten minutes—from a charging point [174]. These strategies aim to rectify inequities by strategically placing chargers in underserved areas, promoting inclusive and sustainable EV adoption.

Mobility behaviour and usage pattern mapping This approach leverages empirical data on travel behaviour and charging habits to inform the spatial planning of EV charging infrastructure. By analysing large-scale datasets, researchers can identify patterns in charging demand and optimize station placement accordingly. For instance, a study by Junker et al. (2025) applied causal discovery techniques to extensive charging data from Palo Alto and Boulder, revealing that charging demand is primarily influenced by proximity to amenities, EV registration density, and adjacency to high-traffic routes [175]. Similarly, Lei et al. (2021) examined trajectory data from a fully electrified taxi fleet in Shenzhen, China, uncovering temporal and spatial regularities in charging activities linked to drivers' shift schedules [176]. These insights enable planners to align charging infrastructure deployment with actual usage patterns, enhancing efficiency and user convenience. Together, these four perspectives provide a multi-dimensional foundation for identifying priority areas for charger

deployment. In the proposed planning tool, these criteria will be combined into a single need map through a weighted multicriteria approach, with parameters adjustable to local policy and territorial priorities.

Phase 3: Optimization of Charger Placement Once the demand for charging infrastructure has been spatially distributed, the final step involves optimizing the allocation of V2G chargers across analysis units. This phase explores various algorithmic strategies to identify the most suitable locations and capacities, considering multiple constraints and planning goals.

Facility Location Models Classical facility location models, such as the maximal covering location model and the p-median model, are widely used to determine optimal siting by minimizing travel distances or maximizing demand coverage within fixed budget constraints. Luo and Qiu (2020) proposed an enhanced model that incorporates reservation systems, idle time penalties, and waiting times during peak hours, aiming to improve resource utilization and reduce operational costs [177].

Metaheuristics and Estimation of Distribution Algorithms Shahmoradi et al. (2022) developed a hybrid Estimation of Distribution Algorithm (EDA) for EV charging schedule optimization, combining Markov and Mallows-based models [178]. Their approach minimized total tardiness while accounting for constraints such as charging line assignments and time windows.

Hybrid and Solver-Based Approaches Hybrid methods combining heuristics with exact solvers, such as Mixed-Integer Nonlinear Programming (MINLP), offer scalability and precision. Truc et al. (2025) applied this approach to optimize charger placement in Ho Chi Minh City, using the Gurobi solver and Branch-and-Cut techniques to generate a cost-effective and stakeholder-informed deployment plan [179].

Network Flow Models Network flow models enable the integration of travel patterns and demand flows into charger location planning. Kong et al. (2017) proposed a hierarchical model that combines flow-capturing location problems, queuing theory, and battery charging dynamics to optimize fast-charging station siting while maximizing electrified vehicle-miles travelled [180]. Together, these methodologies support the systematic allocation of V2G charging points, ensuring infrastructure deployment is technically feasible, cost-effective, and responsive to real-world mobility patterns. The selected optimization approach will be embedded in the planning tool, enabling scenario-based testing and policy-adaptive decision-making for varied urban and regional contexts.

5.9.4 Benchmarking of Existing Planning Tools

To complement the literature review, this section presents a comparative benchmark of existing tools designed to support the spatial planning of EV charging infrastructure. The selected platforms are analysed based on their planning approach, scalability, spatial criteria, grid integration, and demonstrated use cases, with the aim of identifying strengths and limitations relevant to large-scale deployment strategies.

Table 5.30: Benchmark of existing planning tools.

Criteria	Localiser [181]	SandTech Planner [182]	Mosaic Factor [183]	CARTO for EV Charging [184]	ERM ILIT [185]
Type of planning	Tool for infrastructure network managers.	Urban and municipal planning. Searches for zones to maximize benefit and minimize cost.	Estimates future needs and optimizes location based on data.	Site selection through spatial analysis.	Regional identification of charger locations.
Charger type	All (fast -- slow)	All (fast -- slow)	All (fast -- slow)	–	Fast charging
Urban/rural applicability	Urban and rural	Urban	Urban and rural	Urban	Urban and rural
Deployment scale	Individual	Urban planning (massive deployment)	Massive	Individual	Medium, regional focus, scale not specified
Spatial criteria used	Demand, mobility, sociodemographics, traffic, POIs, parking availability.	Zoning, demand clustering, population, land use, EV ownership.	Mobility patterns, socio-demographic data, charging behavior.	First step: population density, distance to charger. Second: geospatial database with 72 social variables (Carto Geosegmentation).	Existing infrastructure, traffic, commercial activity, demographics, environmental factors.
Grid integration	Yes	Yes	No	No	Partial
Underlying technology	–	Artificial intelligence, geospatial analysis. Planner for current and near-future infrastructure.	Mobility data analysis, long-term forecasting models.	Spatial data science, geospatial analysis.	GIS-based analysis
Demonstrated applications	Germany. 15 years of experience, over 1.2 million charging points analysed.	–	Projects in Europe (Barcelona–Spain, Luxembourg, Trentino–Italy).	USA	USA

It is noted that some commercial tools offer comparable functionalities; however, customisation to the

specific criteria, user behaviours associated with V2G and slow charging, and the business models to be developed for the use cases is essential for the NEVERFLAT project.

5.9.5 Gaps and Functional Requirements

Based on the findings from the literature review and tool benchmarking, this section outlines the main gaps identified and the functional requirements that will guide the development of the planning tool within the project.

Identified Gaps

- **Lack of integration between planning phases:** Most tools address demand forecasting, spatial prioritization, or optimization of individual chargers, but do not offer a unified workflow that combines forecasting with spatial optimization and also that is for multiple chargers at the same time.
- **Limited consideration of grid constraints:** While energy network limitations are critical for V2G deployment, most tools do not incorporate detailed grid capacity or infrastructure data into location analysis.
- **Insufficient support for large-scale deployments:** Many tools are designed for individual site placement or small-scale scenarios, lacking scalability for mass installation strategies.
- **Low adaptability to regional or local contexts:** Existing platforms often rely on static criteria, offering limited flexibility to adjust planning parameters to specific urban, rural, or policy environments.
- **Weak alignment with user behaviour, socio-demographic factors, and equity principles:** Few tools incorporate empirical mobility patterns, socio-economic indicators, or spatial equity considerations such as accessibility for underserved populations.
- **Lack of focus on public slow-charging infrastructure:** Current solutions tend to prioritise fast or private charging, with little attention to the challenges and business models of public-access slow chargers.

Functional Requirements

- **Modular planning workflow:** The tool should integrate demand forecasting, spatial prioritization, and charger allocation in a single, streamlined process.
- **Scenario customisation:** Users must be able to adjust planning parameters (e.g. weight of criteria, charger density targets, equity thresholds) to reflect local policies and strategic goals.
- **Grid-aware location filtering:** The tool should incorporate grid capacity and technical limitations to identify sites compatible with V2G and low-voltage infrastructure.
- **Support for large-scale deployments:** The system must be capable of handling mass charger allocation across large territories or full municipalities.
- **Inclusion of socio-territorial data:** The tool should allow integration of local demographic, land use and mobility data to tailor planning to specific contexts.
- **Adaptability to diverse user needs:** While not explicitly designed to target specific social groups, the tool should enable planning approaches that can help reach a broader user base when combined with suitable business models.

- **Output interpretability:** Results must be visualised in clear, map-based outputs with key indicators (coverage, accessibility, energy demand, equity), exportable for stakeholder engagement.

These functional requirements will guide the development of the planning tool proposed within the project. By addressing the limitations found in existing approaches, the tool aims to offer a flexible and comprehensive solution for the deployment of public slow-charging V2G infrastructure, with the ability to adapt to different territorial contexts and support broader accessibility objectives aligned with the project's business model.

5.10 Identified Key Challenges

The State-of-the-Art (SotA) analysis conducted within the NEVERFLAT project reveals a multifaceted landscape of technical, operational, and systemic challenges hindering the large-scale deployment of bidirectional charging infrastructure and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) services across Europe.

One of the most critical challenges is the **fragmentation of standards and protocol readiness**. Despite the formalization of ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1, these protocols are not yet widely adopted or implemented across existing charging infrastructure and electric vehicles. Many chargers remain locked into legacy protocols such as ISO 15118-2, which lack native bidirectional support. Furthermore, the existence of a wide range of (open) protocols for demand response - such as OSCP, EEBus, SEP 2.0, and OpenADR - introduces additional complexity and uncertainty for implementers. The lack of a harmonized or dominant standard complicates system integration and may hinder interoperability across devices and platforms. Similarly, gaps persist in the implementation of robust cybersecurity measures, particularly around certificate management, OSCP validation, and support for mTLS authentication chains.

A second major barrier concerns the **technical complexity and cost of bidirectional chargers**. Enabling bidirectional power transfer through hardware such as dual-active-bridge (DAB) or CLLC converters necessitates additional components and design sophistication. These systems must handle wide voltage ranges (200V–900V), and accommodate emerging standards, driving up both production and maintenance costs. As a result, there is limited market availability of affordable, certified, and interoperable DC bidirectional chargers.

From a grid integration perspective, the absence of **scalable energy and load forecasting mechanisms** remains a challenge. Forecasting tools lack the resolution, standardization, and interoperability needed to align with grid requirements, while backend systems often operate in isolation without holistic integration into energy markets or the respective actors such as DSOs and TSOs.

Further, **eRoaming services to support BPT** is still in its infancy, with current platforms currently not covering needed information exchanges to fully accommodate bidirectional power transfer services, contractual roles, and settlements required for V2G use cases. Protocol extensions and adaptations (e.g., OCPI extensions) have been proposed but are not yet harmonized across the market.

Lastly, **the lack of compelling business models and incentives** remains a critical challenge. The current Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) for V2G-compatible infrastructure is high, while end-users

see minimal tangible benefits. Regulatory uncertainties, unclear revenue mechanisms, and administrative burdens further discourage investment.

5.11 Conclusion and Recommendations

The NEVERFLAT SotA and barrier analysis confirms that while the technological foundation for bidirectional charging and V2G services is largely in place, its ecosystem remains underdeveloped, fragmented, and economically unattractive for wide-scale adoption. Nevertheless, strategic and coordinated action can address these shortcomings. To accelerate deployment, the following recommendations are derived:

1. **Promote harmonization and enforcement of standards:** Ensure widespread adoption of ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1, including updates to national and EU-level guidelines that incentivize or mandate their implementation. This should include provisions for cybersecurity and interoperability testing.
2. **Facilitate the development and deployment of cost-effective bidirectional charging hardware:** The European Commission, together with industry actors, should promote the development and large-scale deployment of technically mature and cost-efficient DC bidirectional charging solutions, particularly targeting residential and small-commercial applications (e.g. 10 kW). Emphasis should be placed on modular and scalable designs that reduce hardware complexity while meeting interoperability and safety requirements.
3. **Enhance grid integration and interoperability across energy systems:** Stakeholders across the mobility and energy domains should prioritise the advancement of interoperable forecasting and control solutions that connect Charge Point Management Systems (CPMSs), Home and Building Energy Management Systems (HEMS/BEMS), and grid operators. This includes the development and adoption of standardised APIs, common data models, and shared information platforms to enable coordinated operation and system-level optimisation.
4. **Extend eRoaming protocols to enable Bidirectional Power Transfer (BPT) and V2G services:** Existing eRoaming protocols (e.g., OCPI, OICP) should be extended to support information exchanges and features necessary for bidirectional power transfer services. These encompass, among others, relevant POI data of BPT enabled charging stations, authorization process and contractual handlings as well as billing and settlement processes.
5. **Address user-side barriers:** Educate end users on the benefits and potential savings of smart and bidirectional charging. Offer streamlined onboarding processes and transparent billing mechanisms to increase trust and engagement.

6

Regulatory and Market Analysis

This chapter introduces a comprehensive regulatory and market analysis essential for enabling smart and bidirectional EV charging ecosystems. It begins by identifying and evaluating the roles and responsibilities of key stakeholders, such as grid operators, service providers, and end-users. This section provides a state-of-the-art overview of how these roles are currently defined across different markets and regulatory frameworks. Emphasis is placed on the alignment of responsibilities with emerging technologies and business models. The analysis serves as a foundation for identifying gaps, benchmarking best practices, and proposing harmonized role distributions to support large-scale deployment.

6.1 Roles and Responsibilities

6.1.1 Methodology

The methodology followed for this section of the state-of-the-art analysis has been an approach similar to PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses) [186], where multiple data banks have been searched for the relevant publications, websites, and project reports delivering information on the following topics:

- Key stakeholders in market-integrated bi-directional smart charging;
- Existing market frameworks and business models;
- Regulatory and technical challenges;
- Simulation framework and market integration models and market integration; models;
- Optimization of role distributions.

6.1.2 Key Roles in Smart Charging Ecosystem

According to [187] and AFIR [188] there are following key stakeholders with their respective roles in market-integrated bi-directional smart charging or in general smart charging based on [189].

Table 6.1: Roles, definitions and responsibilities in V2G context.

Role	Definition and classification	Functions
End User	According to AFIR Art 2 point (24), an End user is 'a natural or legal person purchasing an alternative fuel for direct use in a vehicle'.	Providers of flexibility in terms of charging and discharging; acceptance and usage behaviour are crucial.
DSO (Distribution System Operator)	According to Directive (EU) 2019/944, Article 2, point (29), a DSO is 'a natural or legal person responsible for operating, maintaining, and developing the distribution system, including interconnections with other systems'.	Consumers of local flexibility to manage congestion and voltage. DSOs manage the low-voltage network that delivers electricity to end users, including EV charging points operated by CPOs.
TSO (Transmission System Operator)	Defined in Directive (EU) 2019/944 Article 2, point (35) as 'a person responsible for operating, maintaining, and developing the transmission system and ensuring its ability to meet demand'.	Consumers of system-wide flexibility like balancing reserves. TSOs operate high-voltage networks, coordinate with DSOs, and help balance grid stability in EV charging scenarios.
Aggregators	Intermediaries pooling and managing flexibility from various consumer and producer resources.	Sell flexibility services in different energy markets; optimize aggregated demand or generation assets.
OEMs (EV Manufacturers)	Responsible for EV design and back-end communications. Ensure compliance with safety, environmental, and performance standards.	Develop V2G-capable vehicles, issue declarations of conformity, and select vehicle type approvals to meet regulatory requirements.
Policy Makers and Regulators	Entities defining legal frameworks, market access, and incentives.	Enable smart grid services, ensure fair competition, security, and market openness for V2G stakeholders.
Charging Point Operator (CPO)	Defined by AFIR Art 2 (39) as the entity managing a recharging point on behalf of users or MSPs.	Provide EVSE infrastructure, manage technical/communication features, handle roaming and interoperability settings.
ICT Providers	Provide communication protocols and systems for smart charging infrastructure.	Enable real-time control and data exchange between EVs, grid, and management platforms.
Charger Manufacturer	Design and build compliant charging/discharging equipment for EVs.	Ensure V2G readiness through standard-compliant hardware.
Mobility Service Provider (MSP)	Defined in AFIR Art 2 (36) as a provider of charging services to end users, often via contracts.	Enable contract-based access to CPO networks for EV users, typically through roaming agreements.
E-Roaming Platform	Per AFIR Article 2 (26): a platform linking MSPs and CPOs to enable roaming and interoperability.	Facilitates service exchange, payment, and data flow; supports scalability, cybersecurity, and interoperability in EV charging.

Role	Definition and classification	Functions
SCSP – Smart Charging Service Provider	A role focused on providing smart charging services with added value.	Implements optimization, scheduling, and dynamic grid-responsive charging strategies.
VPPO – Virtual Power Plant Operator	Coordinates distributed energy resources like batteries, solar, flexible loads as a virtual power plant.	Optimizes assets collectively to deliver grid services and energy supply without owning the physical assets.

Role distribution is primarily based on key stakeholders involved in market-integrated bidirectional smart charging and is also influenced by existing market frameworks, business models, and the regulatory and technical challenges they face. Additionally, the simulation framework and various market integration models play a significant role in shaping and optimizing how these responsibilities are allocated. Therefore, the following sub-sections provide a structured overview of stakeholder roles, responsibilities, and interactions, reflecting both current practice and future-oriented developments in the smart charging and V2G ecosystem.

6.1.3 Analysis for Roles Distribution and Key Stakeholders in Market-Integrated Bi-Directional Smart Charging

Based on research on key stakeholders in market-integrated bi-directional smart charging, the following information has been extracted as relevant for the NEVERFLAT project and the deliverable D1.1.

Source: *Active integration of electric vehicles into distribution grids: Barriers and frameworks for flexibility services*

[187] highlights that EVs, which are largely idle throughout the day, offer significant potential for providing flexibility services to distribution grids through smart charging and V2G technologies. These services include:

- Congestion management
- Voltage regulation
- Peak shaving
- System balancing

While technical feasibility has been well established through simulations and European demonstrator projects, large-scale implementation is hindered by various regulatory, economic, and institutional barriers. Key limitations include:

- Unclear value of local flexibility
- Lack of regulatory support at the distribution level
- Underdeveloped market structures

The authors identify four main frameworks for enabling EV-based flexibility:

- **Grid codes** – focused on technical compliance
- **Connection agreements** – based on negotiated control
- **Tariffs** – using price signals
- **Market-based mechanisms** – including local flexibility markets and bilateral contracts

Each of these approaches offers promise, but also presents challenges, especially around user engagement and scalability. User behaviour and acceptance are central to successful implementation. Flexibility solutions must:

- Respect user mobility needs and battery health
- Offer sufficient user control
- Include appropriate incentives

Additional complications include the limited availability of bidirectional chargers and user concerns about battery degradation. Moreover, improved coordination between distribution system operators (DSOs) and transmission system operators (TSOs) is essential to prevent conflicts when activating EV flexibility across grid levels. There is a clear distinction between technical and non-technical barriers. While challenges such as charger compatibility and battery wear are being addressed, regulatory, economic, and institutional factors remain the most significant obstacles. The paper distinguishes between different control strategies:

- **Centralized control** enables globally optimized charging but requires significant communication infrastructure.
- **Decentralized control** reduces ICT requirements but may lead to suboptimal outcomes under high EV penetration.

A further differentiation is made regarding spatial configurations for flexibility use:

- **Behind-the-meter applications** – targeting end-user benefits such as bill savings and self-consumption
- **Distribution grid-level services** – supporting congestion and voltage management
- **System-wide services** – including balancing and energy market arbitrage

These distinctions underscore the need for tailored solutions that reflect varying levels of technology readiness, market maturity, user behaviour, and the prevailing regulatory context.

Source: *Tempering the Promise of Electric Mobility? A Sociotechnical Review and Research Agenda for Vehicle-Grid-Integration (VGI) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)*

[190] focuses on vehicle-grid integration (VGI), particularly through bidirectional vehicle-to-grid (V2G) systems, which offer a range of technical, financial, environmental, and behavioral benefits. These benefits include enhanced grid reliability, improved integration of renewable energy sources, emissions reductions, and the creation of new revenue opportunities for vehicle owners. While much of the existing research emphasizes technical feasibility—such as battery performance, grid communication protocols, and infrastructure—this paper highlights the importance of sociotechnical factors. These include user behavior, regulatory and policy frameworks, and the role of institutional support, all of which are crucial for achieving large-scale adoption of VGI solutions. Consumer motivation is shaped by both financial and environmental considerations. On the one hand, lower energy

bills and revenue-sharing models serve as financial incentives. On the other hand, environmental values, such as reducing carbon footprints, also play a motivating role. However, several barriers remain, including range anxiety, concerns over privacy, and distrust of institutions, which can hinder participation in V2G programs. The paper advocates the following key outcomes:

- Unidirectional charging is simpler and less costly to implement, while V2G offers greater grid value but requires more complex infrastructure and investment.
- Vehicle-grid integration is more easily deployed in fleet settings, where unified actors manage multiple vehicles, compared to private consumer settings, which involve fragmented interests.
- Aggregated V2G participation, where multiple vehicles are coordinated together, increases the overall value potential but also raises operational and management complexity.
- Different engagement strategies, such as time-of-use pricing, revenue sharing, and environmentally oriented messaging, can help attract consumer participation.
- High upfront costs associated with V2G technologies, combined with the tendency of consumers to undervalue long-term savings, pose significant barriers to widespread adoption.

Source: **Integrating electric vehicles as virtual power plants: A comprehensive review on vehicle-to-grid (V2G) concepts, interface topologies, marketing and future prospects**

[149] explores the potential of vehicle-to-grid (V2G) systems and their integration into virtual power plants (VPPs), positioning electric vehicles (EVs) as distributed energy resources capable of supporting grid stability. When aggregated in VPP structures, EVs can enhance system flexibility and reliability. Four main V2G integration modes are identified—stand-alone, grid-connected, transition, and grid-supported—each offering distinct operational benefits and associated technical requirements. In particular, grid-supported V2G systems are shown to provide critical power quality and ancillary services. These include active and reactive power support, voltage regulation, harmonic filtering, and frequency regulation, positioning EVs as valuable grid assets. The paper also provides an overview of interface and control strategies, reviewing various converter topologies such as single-stage, two-stage, and hybrid/multi-stage designs. The choice of topology is influenced by factors such as integration depth, system scalability, and cost. Effective operation of these systems requires robust control algorithms and advanced communication infrastructure to ensure coordinated interaction between EVs, aggregators, and grid operators. Real-world implementations of V2G and VPP projects, including initiatives like PARKER, E-FLEX, and ACES, are reviewed to highlight increasing technical viability and growing market interest. While these projects demonstrate promising results, full commercialization remains in early stages. Despite growing momentum, several limitations are identified:

- **Technical:** Battery degradation, harmonic distortion, bidirectional interface complexity, and AC/DC grid compatibility.
- **Economic:** High upfront costs, insufficient financial incentives, and complex stakeholder cost-benefit assessments.
- **Regulatory:** Absence of standardized regulatory frameworks and limited harmonization of technical standards at the international level.
- **Behavioural:** User concerns regarding battery health, range anxiety, and low trust in utility providers hinder adoption.

- **Communication Infrastructure:** Coordinating large numbers of EVs, aggregators, and grid operators poses ongoing technical and organizational challenges.

Source: Utilization of Electric Vehicles for Vehicle-to-Grid Services: Progress and Perspectives

[191] identifies key performance indicators within a bidirectional vehicle to grid charging framework. Centralized architecture can be scalable although complex, where aggregators manage charging/ discharging across fleets. Decentralized architecture enables optimization of local systems individually and tends to be more flexible and user-trust friendly. Charging systems range from Level 1 (basic) to Level 3 (fast charging), with varying cost, compatibility and speed. It outlines recurring challenges consistent with previous analyses, emphasizing the interdependence of technical design, user acceptance, and system-level coordination. It highlights that the choice of operational mode, direction of energy flow, and power converter configuration—whether single-stage, dual-stage, or multi-stage hybrid architectures—must align with the intended scale of integration and the system’s flexibility requirements. A comprehensive set of barriers is discussed:

- **Engineering Constraints:** Issues such as accelerated battery aging, electrical noise (harmonics), complexities in enabling bidirectional power transfer, and mismatches between alternating and direct current systems pose significant hurdles.
- **Financial Factors:** Elevated capital expenditures, scarce economic incentives for participants, and the difficulty of projecting long-term returns hinder broader investment in V2G and VPP infrastructure.
- **Policy and Standards:** The absence of unified technical and regulatory guidelines across regions results in fragmented deployment and inhibits cross-border scalability.
- **User-Centric Challenges:** Widespread concerns among users—particularly about long-term battery performance, limitations on driving range, and skepticism toward utility operators—limit engagement with emerging V2G platforms.
- **Digital and Control Systems:** The technological ecosystem required to orchestrate real-time interactions among EV fleets, aggregators, and grid operators remains complex and underdeveloped, requiring further innovation in communication protocols and control algorithms.

Source: Driving the Grid: The Role of V2G in Modern Energy Ecosystem

[192] shares several thematic overlaps with previous research, it distinguishes itself through the integration of scenario planning as a tool to evaluate the financial implications of V2G participation for end-users. By modeling four distinct scenarios, the analysis demonstrates how profitability varies significantly based on dynamic electricity pricing structures and varying levels of user engagement. This forward-looking approach highlights the economic uncertainty and sensitivity of V2G returns under different market conditions. A notable innovation in this work is the inclusion of real estate developers as key stakeholders in the V2G ecosystem. Their involvement facilitates the deployment of V2G infrastructure within residential and commercial developments, particularly in shared energy systems such as community energy hubs or building-level microgrids. This perspective broadens the implementation context beyond individual EV owners or fleet operators, offering a more integrated urban energy model. The thesis also directly tackles concerns often underemphasized in prior literature—specifically, the substantial privacy and cybersecurity risks associated with V2G systems. Real-time data collection related to energy consumption and vehicle location raises

legitimate concerns about data protection, surveillance, and user trust. Addressing these challenges is present

6.1.4 Roles Distribution and Existing Market Frameworks and Business Models

Based on further research with respect to the role distribution and existing market frameworks and business models, the following information is relevant for NEVERFLAT project:

Source: Scalable Bidirectional Smart charging SGAM architecture: use case analysis for a viable business to integrate Electric Vehicles as distributed energy resources based on IEC standards

[193] aligns stakeholder roles according to the Harmonized Electricity Market Role Model developed by ENTSO-E [194], which facilitates standardized interactions and enhances interoperability across European energy markets. By mapping actors consistently within this framework, the study supports seamless integration of EV-based flexibility solutions into broader market structures. A range of existing market frameworks and business models are examined, each representing different approaches to monetizing EV flexibility:

- **Dynamic Energy Pricing Framework:** Enables EV owners to respond to real-time electricity prices by optimizing their charging and discharging behavior, effectively transforming them into active market participants.
- **Battery Leasing Model:** Involves leasing rather than outright ownership of EV batteries. This model allows for co-ownership among Balancing Responsible Parties (BRPs), Transmission System Operators (TSOs), and other actors, facilitating shared use for grid services and encouraging second-life battery applications after vehicle use.
- **Energy Arbitrage Model:** Capitalizes on electricity price fluctuations by charging during off-peak, low-cost periods and discharging to the grid during high-price periods, allowing users to profit from temporal price differentials.
- **Demand Response Flexibility Contracts:** EV users lease their charging flexibility to BRPs through structured contracts, receiving compensation in exchange for allowing third-party control over charging schedules in support of grid stability.
- **Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) Participation:** EVs are integrated into ancillary service markets where they provide frequency regulation services under the coordination of TSOs to manage short-term supply-demand imbalances.

The analysis applies the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) to conceptualize system design, functionality, and role allocation. SGAM, widely used in European smart grid projects under IEC standards, provides a structured, multi-layered framework to represent business, function, communication, and technology layers in grid systems. The thesis emphasizes the business layer—also known as the Computational Independent Model (CIM)—focusing on market logic and stakeholder interaction rather than technical implementation, which is addressed in later layers such as Platform Independent Models (PIMs). A significant barrier identified is the absence of a standardized multilateral contracting system across the European market. Without a unified contractual framework binding all stakeholders—including EV owners, aggregators, DSOs, TSOs, and market operators—the deployment of cross-border or harmonized V2G services remains constrained.

Source: **A Review of Bidirectional Charging Grid Support Applications and Battery Degradation Considerations**

[195] places significant emphasis on the role of Virtual Power Plants (VPPs) as a framework for aggregating distributed energy resources (DERs)—including electric vehicles (EVs), stationary batteries, and flexible household devices such as smart thermostats. These aggregated assets are monetized through participation in capacity markets, provision of ancillary services (e.g., frequency regulation, voltage support), and engagement in demand response programs. By coordinating DERs at scale, VPPs act as flexible, dispatchable units that enhance grid reliability and market efficiency. A detailed examination is provided of the revenue streams available to both VPP operators and EV owners. These include:

- **Energy Arbitrage:** Storing electricity when wholesale prices are low and discharging during peak-price periods to capture price differentials.
- **Capacity Payments:** Compensation for maintaining available capacity to support grid stability during peak demand or contingency events.
- **Ancillary Services:** Payments for providing services such as frequency control and voltage regulation to transmission and distribution system operators.

The work explores the full cost structure associated with VPP deployment and DER integration, outlining key components such as system implementation, operational management, customer acquisition, and long-term maintenance of the DER management platform. A notable contribution of this thesis is its focus on battery longevity, specifically through aging-aware optimization. The study proposes artificial intelligence (AI)-based optimization models that incorporate battery degradation profiles into scheduling decisions, ensuring that economic returns do not come at the cost of excessive battery wear. The analysis provides comprehensive coverage of bidirectional use cases, where EVs not only consume but also inject power into the grid under various operational modes. This is complemented by a review of real-world pilot projects, particularly from North America, including use cases such as V2G-enabled rideshare fleets. These case studies demonstrate growing technical feasibility and stakeholder interest, further validating the relevance of the proposed approaches in practical settings.

Source: **Smart Charging Business Model Framework for Electric Vehicle Aggregators**

[196] presents a comprehensive analysis of market frameworks and business models tailored specifically for Electric Vehicle Aggregators (EVA). It explores the mechanisms of explicit Demand Response (DR) participation, whereby EVAs engage in Balancing Markets (BM) by offering upward or downward flexibility, i.e., by increasing or reducing load. Within these BMs, EVAs trade this flexibility to support real-time system balancing and receive both capacity and energy payments. Additionally, the paper examines the role of EVAs in congestion management and voltage support via cooperation with Distribution System Operator (DSO), contributing to the deferral of costly grid upgrades. The potential for energy arbitrage is also highlighted in bidirectional systems, where EVAs charge vehicles during periods of low electricity prices and discharge during high-price periods. The paper further outlines key value propositions provided by EVAs, including reduced charging costs, mitigation of energy imbalances, provision of ancillary services to the grid, dynamic pricing offerings for end-users, battery life preservation, integration of renewable energy sources, and greenhouse

gas emissions reduction. Revenue generation approaches are classified into three primary models: Software-as-a-Service (SaaS), commission-based structures dependent on realized energy savings or flexibility revenues, and profit-sharing schemes involving the EVA, charging station providers, and electric vehicle users.

A case study is presented, analyzing an EVA's participation in the European Union's manual Frequency Restoration Reserve (mFRR) balancing market. The findings demonstrate tangible cost reductions for EV users and profit-sharing opportunities for all stakeholders, with real profitability supported by actual market data. To support this, the paper introduces a dedicated business model framework uniquely adapted to EVAs, distinguishing itself from broader DR aggregator models by integrating all aspects of value creation, delivery, and capture. The model is validated through real-world implementation, simulating market-based pricing, customer behaviors, and DR events. The approach is explicitly stakeholder-centric, offering detailed mappings of roles, interactions, legal arrangements, and communication protocols among key actors, such as between the EVA and Transmission System Operator (TSO), and between the EVA and Charging Station Provider (CSP). Finally, the framework embeds environmental considerations, emphasizing the EVA's role in enhancing renewable energy utilization, reducing emissions, and fostering wider electric vehicle adoption.

Source: Vehicle-to-Grid Business Model – Entering the Swiss Energy Market

[197] investigates market frameworks and business models centered around Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) integration and electric vehicle flexibility services, with a specific focus on the Swiss market. The analysis begins with ancillary services, identified as the primary revenue source, including frequency regulation, balancing services, and peak shaving. Congestion management is also explored, particularly within emerging local flexibility markets, as illustrated by pilot projects such as USEF in the Netherlands. The potential of self-consumption optimization is considered, where electric vehicles are paired with photovoltaic (PV) systems to enhance local energy use and reduce dependence on the grid. Meanwhile, energy arbitrage is assessed as unprofitable in the Swiss context, offering minimal return on investment. The study reviews various business models. Car-sharing programs, such as We Drive Solar, incorporate smart charging technology to allow electric vehicles to serve dual purposes—transportation and energy flexibility. These shared EVs can participate in grid services and congestion markets, with the model benefiting from complementary usage patterns: shared vehicles operate during the day, while employees' private EVs contribute to grid services at night.

For residential V2G applications, cases like those involving Nissan and Enel demonstrate integration of V2G-enabled electric vehicles with rooftop PV installations. This setup can deliver savings on network charges and income from ancillary services, although the high initial cost of necessary hardware limits economic viability. Fleet-based V2G models, such as the collaboration between Nuvve and Frederiksberg, leverage centralized fleets with predictable usage to provide reliable grid services. By establishing direct connections with transmission system operators (TSOs), these fleets can secure a larger portion of revenue. However, this approach's profitability depends heavily on scalability. The proposed business model is specifically designed to align with Switzerland's regulatory, technical, and economic context. A comparative multi-case analysis of three pilot projects from the Netherlands, Italy, and Denmark is conducted to establish a broad base of insights. Based on this analysis, a prototype business model is introduced that combines workplace and fleet charging

with on-site PV generation. It outlines a phased development strategy: starting with unidirectional charging, advancing to bidirectional capability, and culminating in full integration into energy service markets. To guide successful implementation and assessment, a success factor framework is presented. It identifies standardization, stakeholder collaboration, cost structure efficiency, incentive mechanisms, and market scalability as essential for sustainable V2G deployment. The paper also addresses key limitations, notably the high capital expenditure required for V2G hardware and the challenge of fragmented standards, particularly the coexistence of CHAdeMO and ISO 15118.

Source: Prospects of electric vehicle V2G multi-use: Profitability and GHG emissions for use case combinations of smart and bidirectional charging today and 2030

[198] presents an evaluation of market frameworks and business models for Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) and Vehicle-to-Home (V2H) applications, with a focus on private users and combined optimization strategies. It examines the participation of V2G systems in Germany's three spot electricity markets—Day-Ahead (DA), Intraday Auction (IA), and Continuous Intraday (CI)—where energy arbitrage is performed by charging electric vehicles (EVs) during low-price periods and discharging them when prices are high. Since participation requires a minimum aggregated capacity of 1 megawatt, effective aggregation of multiple EVs is essential. The analysis also covers V2H use cases aimed at enhancing the self-consumption of Photovoltaic (PV) electricity. In this configuration, EVs are charged using solar energy generated on-site, reducing reliance on the grid. When operated in bidirectional mode, the EV can supply electricity to the household but does not export energy back to the grid. A hybrid use case is explored, combining both V2G and V2H approaches to capitalize on electricity market arbitrage and PV self-consumption. This integrated model necessitates sophisticated metering systems and precise scheduling, often supported by optimization tools such as eFlame to manage operations effectively.

The business models are analyzed through a user-centric lens, emphasizing annual cost savings per EV. By 2030, projected savings could reach up to €2,780 per vehicle annually. The revenue streams primarily include market arbitrage—charging at low prices and discharging at high ones—and the avoidance of retail electricity tariffs through optimized PV usage. However, economic feasibility remains influenced by several cost-related barriers, such as the high upfront expenditure for bidirectional charging infrastructure and the need for additional metering and hardware systems. In 2021, financial viability was only observed when V2G and V2H functionalities were applied in combination. Projections for 2030 indicate that all examined use cases are expected to become profitable due to decreasing technology costs and wider electricity price spreads. The paper emphasizes a private-user-oriented approach and models the simultaneous optimization of V2G and V2H functions. It also incorporates a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) perspective by evaluating both operational greenhouse gas emissions and the environmental impact of hardware production. Future emission factors for 2030 are considered in line with the European Green Deal and Germany's climate policy objectives. To ensure realism, the model accounts for practical constraints such as limited charging availability, battery degradation expressed in Equivalent Full Cycles (EFC), and detailed simulations of user behavior. It draws on 200 individual user profiles to reflect diverse and realistic patterns in driving and charging, thereby enhancing the robustness and relevance of the findings.

Source: Realizing Smart Charging of Electric Vehicles at Public Charging Infrastructures Using Standards-Based Communication Architecture

[189] examines existing market frameworks and business models for Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) and smart charging solutions, shaped by evolving regulatory and economic conditions. It highlights the influence of key European Union regulations, notably the EU Data Act (Regulation 2023/2854) and the Renewable Energy Directive (RED III), which mandate that original equipment manufacturers share state of charge (SoC) data. These regulatory measures are intended to foster fair competition and ensure interoperability among diverse systems and service providers. A central element in the emerging business landscape is the Smart Charging Service Provider (SCSP), which assumes a key role in demand aggregation and the coordination of smart charging operations. The SCSP may operate independently or be incorporated within existing functions, such as those of Charge Point Operators (CPOs) or Virtual Power Plant Operators (VPPO), thus enhancing both operational efficiency and data access.

The financial structure within this ecosystem involves multiple actors. The Mobility End User (MEU) makes payments to the E-Mobility Service Provider (EMSP) for mobility services. In turn, the CPO remunerates the VPPO for energy provision, while the EMSP, SCSP, and CPO each contribute to the Remuneration and Payment Operator (RPO) to support transaction clearing and settlement processes. To secure broad stakeholder involvement and long-term sustainability, the equitable distribution of smart charging benefits—such as dynamic pricing and enhanced integration of renewable energy—is emphasized. This equitable sharing is particularly crucial for encouraging MEU participation, which is vital to the success of the system. The paper introduces a standards-based architecture for smart charging, distinguishing it from many proprietary solutions currently in use. The approach is built exclusively on open and widely adopted standards, including ISO 15118 for communication between electric vehicles and charging stations, OICP 2.x for interoperability across charging networks, and IEC 61850 for energy system communication. A key contribution is the development of a role-centric model that clearly delineates the responsibilities and interactions of different actors, in line with regulatory expectations. This model enables structured, scalable deployment of smart charging services across a diverse market landscape.

The feasibility of the proposed system is demonstrated through real-world trials conducted at the EUREF Campus, utilizing both Alternating Current (AC) and Direct Current (DC) charging infrastructure. These tests confirm that the standards-based approach is operationally viable. Finally, the paper underscores the growing importance of data portability. With forthcoming regulatory changes poised to improve access to electric vehicle data, the removal of data silos is expected to enhance competition and stimulate innovation across the smart charging sector.

Source: Actors and roles in integration of electric vehicles in energy markets and power systems

[199] presents three distinct role distribution scenarios for Energy End Users (EEU) within the context of smart charging and energy market participation, each reflecting varying degrees of involvement and system complexity. In the first scenario, the EEU engages in a passive model by entering into a conventional contract with an energy supplier. This arrangement limits the EEU's role in the energy system, offering little control over energy sourcing or participation in market dynamics. The second scenario illustrates a direct market participation model, where the EEU adopts a proactive

stance. Acting as a balancing party, the EEU becomes responsible for forecasting energy demand and placing bids directly in the electricity market. While this approach provides increased independence, it also demands considerable expertise in forecasting and market operations. The third scenario represents a more integrated approach, wherein the EEU contracts with a Virtual Power Plant Operator (VPPO). The VPPO handles energy procurement, trading, and balancing services on behalf of the EEU. In this configuration, the EEU supplies the VPPO with flexibility data—such as battery status or available charging periods—while the Energy Producer (EP) delivers electricity under a Power Purchase Agreement (PPA). This model combines the benefits of active participation with professional management, using the VPPO's capabilities to optimize value extraction.

The market framework underlying these scenarios is based on liberalized energy systems, particularly Germany's, and is designed in accordance with the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) and European Union regulatory directives. A central innovation in this framework is the VPPO-centric model, which facilitates coordination between EPs and EEUs through PPAs and market trading, aligning energy flexibility with renewable generation. Fleet operators are positioned as multi-functional actors, capable of optimizing charging patterns and participating in electricity markets. Revenue streams are distributed across stakeholders, with EPs benefiting from direct marketing and PPAs, VPPOs receiving procurement margins and service fees, and EEUs realizing savings in both cost and emissions through their provision of flexibility. The paper introduces a comprehensive glossary comprising 58 roles, each with either legal definition or functional relevance emerging from the electric vehicle domain. A scenario-based evaluation approach is employed, utilizing object-oriented modeling and simulation to analyze annual emissions, revenues, and costs across different actor configurations. The paper also conducts a quantitative multilateral benefit analysis, which reveals that systems incorporating VPPOs achieve superior economic and environmental performance compared to other models. Finally, the paper delivers policy-relevant insights, including recommendations for improving market structure through enhanced actor transparency and expanded access to energy-related data.

6.1.5 Roles Distribution and Simulation Framework

Furthermore, based on the research for the state-of-the-art analysis with respect to the role distribution and simulation framework, integration models for V2G and optimization of role distributions the following information has been found to be relevant.

Source: V2Sim: An Open-Source Microscopic V2G Simulation Platform in Urban Power and Transportation Network

[200] introduces the V2Sim simulation framework, which models the interaction between electric vehicles (EVs) and the power grid through an integrated and modular architecture. The framework incorporates the Microscopic Urban Transportation Network (MUTN), developed using the Simulation of Urban MObility (SUMO), to capture detailed vehicle behavior. This includes car-following, lane-changing, routing, and charging processes at the level of individual vehicles, allowing for precise tracking of energy consumption and mobility patterns. The Power Distribution Network (PDN), based on the DistFlow model, simulates voltage and current constraints, Energy Storage Systems (ESS), and renewable energy inputs. It dynamically optimizes power generation according to real-time grid conditions and cost considerations. At the core of the system is the V2G Dispatcher, which

manages bidirectional energy flows and assigns discharging tasks to EVs connected at Smart Charging Stations (SCS), facilitating efficient use of vehicle flexibility. The entire framework is designed to be extensible and plugin-based in Python, enabling users to modify V2G strategies, charging algorithms, and grid behavior dynamically. The simulation workflow includes setting up transportation and power networks, generating EVs and trip schedules, placing charging infrastructure, configuring plugins, executing simulations (either serially or in parallel), and visualizing outcomes.

V2Sim supports multiple V2G integration models, allowing for realistic and adaptable simulations. The Time-of-Use V2G Participation model restricts discharging to specific periods—such as 8:00–10:00 and 13:00–16:00—aligning EV-grid interaction with market signals or system needs. User-Constrained Discharging permits energy discharge only when the EV's state of charge (SoC) exceeds a user-defined limit and the compensation, represented by the User Discharge Rate (UDR), meets acceptable thresholds. SCS aggregate EVs and operate as dispatchable units, allocating discharging tasks according to vehicle availability and capacity. Additionally, V2Sim allows for user-defined V2G strategies that can prioritize goals such as revenue maximization, battery preservation, or behavioral customization. Although not explicitly framed in business or economic terms, V2Sim inherently supports optimization of energy usage and infrastructure allocation through several system-level mechanisms. EV routing and charging decisions are tailored based on individual SoC levels, trip distances, user-defined parameters, and fluctuating electricity prices, enabling a decentralized yet efficient system-wide response.

Load balancing between Fast Charging Stations (FCS) and Slow Charging Station (SICS) is achieved by adjusting pricing schemes or charger availability, guiding user behavior to distribute demand more evenly and avoid congestion. The V2G dispatch strategy is centrally managed, responding to grid load conditions by allocating discharging power equitably among EVs at SICSs without placing excessive demand on individual vehicles. Capacity Sensitivity Analysis is employed to examine how changes in charger numbers at FCSs and SICSs influence the distribution of Electric Vehicle Charging Load (EVCL) and the development of bottlenecks. These insights support the strategic planning of infrastructure deployment. The integration of Energy Storage Systems (ESS) into the PDN illustrates that utility-scale batteries can serve as a substitute for V2G services during peak periods, reducing the need for continuous user engagement and enhancing grid stability. The relevance and applicability of the V2Sim framework are underscored by its recent development and publication, positioning it as a timely and practical tool for modeling complex EV-grid interactions.

Source: Modeling and Architectural Framework of Off-Board V2G Integrator for Smart Grid

[201] presents a simulation framework for a Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) system developed using MATLAB/SIMULINK, concentrating on a scenario involving the discharging of two electric vehicles (EVs). The integration model is based on an off-board V2G integrator employing a centralized charger configuration, which is particularly well-suited for settings with multiple EVs, such as institutional fleets or parking facilities. The model adheres to IEEE 1547 standards, ensuring compatibility and proper interconnection with the utility grid. The technical design incorporates several critical components aimed at achieving stable and efficient operation. A buck converter is used to regulate direct current (DC) voltage levels, while a DC-AC inverter facilitates grid interfacing. System control is executed through a Proportional-Integral (PI) algorithm, ensuring the delivery of a

sinusoidal output current. Additionally, the system includes both PQ (active and reactive power) and PV (voltage and frequency) control strategies, enabling effective grid parameter management. Performance evaluation of the model reveals a high power conversion efficiency of 91.85%. Testing was conducted under a 100 kW load condition, with the grid operating at a frequency of 50 Hz and a voltage level of 415 V. The simulation primarily serves to validate the technical performance of V2G operations, focusing on aspects such as power quality, inverter efficiency, and seamless grid connectivity.

While the paper does not explicitly explore role distribution among stakeholders in a V2G system, it implicitly promotes an aggregator-centric coordination approach. By centralizing control functions, this model simplifies interactions between individual EV users and the power grid, thereby reducing system complexity and enhancing scalability. The paper also emphasizes the benefits of centralized off-board charging. This configuration is particularly cost-effective in institutional or fleet environments, as it reduces the need for complex onboard hardware in each vehicle. The centralized infrastructure approach leads to lower per-vehicle hardware costs and reduced maintenance requirements, making it a viable option for large-scale deployment. However, the scope of the paper is limited to technical validation and does not address economic or market-based optimization strategies. It does not examine potential cost-sharing mechanisms, incentive structures, or revenue distribution models for aggregators—factors that are critical for the practical implementation and financial viability of V2G systems. These dimensions remain beyond the technical focus of the study.

Notably, this paper diverges from the prevailing emphasis on onboard systems in V2G research by focusing on off-board charger architectures. It employs MATLAB-based physical simulations to quantitatively validate energy flows and inverter control mechanisms. Unlike many academic models, the framework includes IEEE 1547 compliance, aligning it with practical grid integration requirements. The research is specifically tailored to institutional parking scenarios, underlining its relevance for fleet or campus environments involving multiple connected EVs.

Source: The V2G Process With the Predictive Model

[202] introduces a simulation framework for Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) integration, developed using MATLAB/Simulink in conjunction with the dSPACE Automotive Simulation Model (ASM). The framework is grounded in real-world data collected from a BMW i3 electric vehicle (EV) driven along an 8 km urban route. Central to the model is a predictive control structure inspired by Model Predictive Control (MPC), which combines simulation-based forecasting with real-time measurement. This hybrid learning approach incorporates variables such as route, vehicle load, speed, and ambient temperature to estimate energy consumption prior to initiating a V2G session. Machine learning is embedded in the system through a hybrid supervised learning model that functions in both offline and online modes. It continuously refines its forecasts using historical driving data while minimizing prediction errors in real time, achieving an accuracy margin within 0.5 percent. The model adapts dynamically to fluctuations in driving behavior, traffic flow, and grid conditions, increasing the reliability of energy forecasting for V2G operations.

The integration model establishes a data-driven and contractual relationship between the EV user and the V2G operator. Users supply essential inputs such as expected departure time and required driving range. Based on this data, the predictive engine calculates the amount of energy available

for grid discharge, while ensuring that the vehicle's mobility requirements are fully satisfied. The model is intended for deployment within a low-voltage grid context, contributing to localized energy balancing. Optimization of role distribution is achieved through strategic timing of decisions and the targeted placement of computational tasks. By assigning predictive and processing responsibilities to the aggregator or service provider, the model reduces the burden on end users, eliminating the need for intensive user-side computation or data monitoring. This results in a system that enhances overall grid stability while maintaining user convenience. The approach reflects a decentralized and user-centric method of optimization, differing from conventional centralized grid control strategies.

The framework combines real-world testing with simulation through its integration of BMW i3 data and supports flexible communication protocols such as ISO 15118. It emphasizes the protection of user energy reserves following V2G sessions and applies adaptive machine learning for precise and responsive energy forecasting. Evaluated under realistic urban driving conditions, the system demonstrates both functional accuracy and operational flexibility.

Source: Integrating electric vehicles as virtual power plants: A comprehensive review on vehicle-to-grid (V2G) concepts, interface topologies, marketing and future prospects

[149] presents a simulation of a photovoltaic (PV)-assisted Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) system developed using MATLAB/Simulink. The model integrates a 100 kW battery electric vehicle, a 70 kW PV array, dynamic building load profiles, and points of interaction with the grid. It simulates bidirectional energy exchange across a 24-hour cycle, enabling real-time transitions between charging, discharging, and idle states. The system also quantifies energy savings and evaluates the electric vehicle's contributions to the power grid.

Four operational modes of V2G integration are identified within the framework. In stand-alone mode, the electric vehicle operates independently of the grid, supporting use cases such as Vehicle-to-Home (V2H), Vehicle-to-Building (V2B), Vehicle-to-Load (V2L), Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V), and Vehicle-to-Building-to-Grid (V2B2). Grid-connected mode positions the EV as a distributed energy resource, enabling configurations such as direct grid injection and PV-assisted V2G. Transition mode allows for automated switching between stand-alone and grid-connected operations, incorporating smart load control and fault detection capabilities. In grid-supported mode, the EV acts as a grid stabilizer, delivering services such as voltage and frequency regulation, power factor correction, and harmonic mitigation, often facilitated through V2G systems or auxiliary converter configurations. Although the paper does not present a specific optimization algorithm, it introduces several system-level strategies for role distribution within V2G frameworks. It stresses the importance of scheduling EV charging and discharging activities around periods of peak demand to enhance overall system efficiency. The discussion also acknowledges the challenge of balancing variable renewable energy generation, battery limitations, and grid flexibility requirements.

Energy management algorithms are employed to coordinate power flows between EVs, renewable energy sources, and the power grid. Aggregators are highlighted as central figures in managing economic dispatch, generating forecasts, and delivering real-time grid support services. The overarching objective of the optimization strategy is to improve system efficiency, reduce battery degradation, and limit disturbances to the power grid while increasing revenue potential. The paper offers a detailed taxonomy that categorizes V2G integration types, energy units, converter topologies, and

power flow strategies. This hardware-oriented classification includes in-depth analysis of converter interface designs, such as single-stage, two-stage, and hybrid multi-stage configurations. Additionally, the paper incorporates a market overview featuring notable V2G pilot projects like VIGIL, ACES, and Parker, alongside global market growth projections. Future directions explored include Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X), cloud-integrated mobility solutions, and predictive management algorithms. The paper concludes with a comprehensive review of key technical standards governing V2G systems, including IEEE 1547, UL 1741, and IEC 61851.

Source: A conceptual framework for the vehicle-to-grid (V2G) implementation

[203] presents a simulation framework designed to quantify the grid support capabilities and energy services enabled by large-scale aggregations of battery electric vehicles (EVs). The model simulates the effects of EV charging on grid load profiles, assesses the potential for frequency regulation, and evaluates the energy available from vehicle batteries. Key scenarios explored include nighttime load leveling, daytime frequency regulation through rapid battery response, peak shaving, and delaying the activation of peaking power units. Simulations involving up to 100,000 EVs demonstrate the capacity to deliver as much as 200 MW of power. While no specific software tools are identified, the framework is built upon actual utility data from system operators such as ISO New England (NE-ISO), PJM Interconnection, and the California Independent System Operator (CAISO). System performance is assessed using metrics such as sustained power delivery (in megawatts), available energy reserves (in megawatt-hours), and pricing for services like frequency regulation.

The integration model proposed follows a dual-role aggregation strategy. First, EV fleets are managed as controllable loads that can be strategically scheduled to flatten off-peak demand and minimize the need for regulation services. Second, these fleets operate as dispatchable generation or storage units, supplying capacity and frequency regulation during peak demand or contingency events. A hierarchical, bidirectional communication infrastructure utilizing ZigBee technology connects aggregators with Independent System Operators (ISOs), Energy Service Providers (ESPs), residential locations, and parking facilities. This network enables secure and scalable data exchange, supporting functions such as state-of-charge monitoring, plug-in compliance verification, and administration of contractual and billing operations.

The framework centers role distribution optimization on the aggregator as the principal coordinating entity. Aggregators oversee data exchange, user interaction, and economic management, dynamically assigning EVs as loads or grid resources based on real-time state-of-charge data and user-defined preferences. Load scheduling is optimized through centralized management of charging activities. The system leverages state-of-charge information and time-of-use pricing to align energy dispatch with grid-level objectives. Incentive mechanisms are also employed to encourage user participation. Aggregators offer bundled incentives—including battery maintenance, discounted electricity rates, and priority parking—to foster sustained engagement. Participation contracts are structured with tiered benefits and penalties. Penalty provisions ensure compliance with plug-in requirements, while long-term and reliable participation is rewarded, aligning user behavior with broader system goals.

This framework is the first to holistically integrate the economic, physical, and regulatory aspects of V2G implementation. It advances beyond technical feasibility to address institutional condi-

tions essential for real-world deployment. The dual-layer structure separates the physical system—comprising batteries and energy flows—from an informational layer responsible for control operations, billing, user preference management, and state-of-charge tracking. A significant contribution of the paper is its practical incentive model, outlining commercially viable approaches for partnerships between aggregators and EV owners. Aggregator economics are also emphasized, with noted advantages in centralized procurement, economies of scale, and streamlined contracting processes. By incorporating real-world utility data from NE-ISO, PJM, and CAISO, the framework enhances its policy relevance and applicability to actual market conditions.

Source: Planning integrated energy systems coupling V2G as a flexible storage

[204] introduces a simulation framework that applies a multi-objective optimization model to minimize both total system cost and annual carbon emissions. The optimization process utilizes an enhanced version of the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II), incorporating diversity-maximization techniques to improve the quality and robustness of the resulting solutions. A stochastic simulation layer is integrated into the model to capture the inherent variability in electric vehicle (EV) behavior, including factors such as arrival times, state of charge (SoC), and duration of stay. The framework is applied to six case studies spanning three cities and two distinct area types—residential and commercial. Implemented in MATLAB 2020b, the model incorporates realistic inputs such as time-of-use electricity tariffs, local demand patterns, and actual energy pricing data. These features ensure both technical precision and practical relevance in the simulation outcomes. Within the integration model, Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) is represented as a flexible, bidirectional energy storage component embedded in a broader Integrated Energy System (IES). The system configuration includes various energy assets, such as Combined Heat and Power (CHP) units, boilers, photovoltaic systems, heat pumps, absorption chillers, electric chillers, and EV charging/discharging stations. Three operational scenarios are evaluated: an IES with no EV participation, an IES with unidirectional grid-to-vehicle charging, and an IES with fully bidirectional V2G operation. Core control variables encompass EV charging and discharging schedules, the operational status and capacity of energy devices, and time-dependent factors such as energy prices and load demand variations.

While not explicitly framed as a role optimization study, the framework effectively achieves functional role coordination through its control strategies. Charging behavior is guided by SoC thresholds, electricity price signals, and local energy balancing requirements. The system responds to seasonal changes—emphasizing price responsiveness during summer months and integration with CHP systems in winter. The framework supports decentralized energy flexibility, with V2G dispatch optimized to reduce overall system costs and environmental impact. Sensitivity analyses are conducted to assess the effects of varying EV fleet sizes, pricing structures, and system configurations. Findings indicate that system performance improves with increased EV participation, but the marginal benefits plateau once the fleet exceeds approximately 300 vehicles. A key feature of this study is its integrated approach, which simultaneously co-optimizes the design of the Integrated Energy System and the operation of the EV fleet under uncertainty. Stochastic EV modeling is informed by real-world data from the National Household Travel Survey, capturing realistic SoC variability and charging behavior.

The case studies span multiple cities—Beijing, Shanghai, and Xiamen—and encompass different

climate zones and usage contexts, including both residential and commercial sectors. The trade-offs between cost and emissions are visualized using a Pareto frontier, and the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to an Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) is applied to identify balanced decision points. The improved NSGA-II algorithm, augmented with diversity-maximization heuristics, enhances convergence speed and solution diversity throughout the optimization process.

Source: **A Simulation Tool for V2G Enabled Demand Response Based on Model Predictive Control**

[205] presents a simulation study utilizing EV2Gym, an open-source platform specifically developed for real-time Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) experimentation. The platform supports simulations involving up to 60 electric vehicle supply equipment (EVSE) units and 120 electric vehicles (EVs). Charging behavior within the simulations is modeled based on realistic profiles from the ElaadNL dataset. Grid-side variables include transformer capacity limitations, solar generation, and inflexible load profiles, which are drawn from sources such as Pecan Street and Renewables.ninja. The system also models demand response scenarios with curtailment events affecting up to 20 percent of load, issued with a 15-minute lead time. Performance is evaluated through several key metrics: total energy exchanged (in kilowatt-hours), frequency of transformer overloads, calendar and cyclic battery degradation, as well as overall operational costs and profits.

For integration modeling, the paper introduces two Model Predictive Control (MPC)-based approaches. The first, Economic Model Predictive Control (eMPC), is designed to minimize the operational costs of charge point operators by optimizing the trade-off between electricity purchases and revenue from discharging activities. This method accommodates both unidirectional (G2V) and bidirectional (V2G) modes, relying on day-ahead electricity price forecasts to schedule energy exchange. The second approach, Optimal Control with Maximum Flexibility (OCMF), aims to enhance the flexibility each charger can offer while minimizing total system costs. This model actively monitors both upward and downward flexibility margins and allows real-time adjustments to power delivery to support participation in demand response events. Both control strategies employ MPC techniques to revise charging and discharging schedules every 15 minutes, maintain compliance with user-defined constraints such as battery state-of-charge, and solve the underlying optimization problems using Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP).

While the study does not explicitly frame its analysis as a role optimization effort, it effectively achieves functional role distribution through its control architecture. Centralized control by charge point operators (CPOs) balances user requirements—such as charging deadlines and SoC thresholds—with grid-level considerations like cost efficiency and demand response obligations. The application of MPC enables each EVSE to act as a responsive flexibility resource. The CPO continuously updates decisions based on real-time information, including vehicle availability, current SoC, and grid connectivity limits. The system architecture supports clear role separation by organizing simulation layers for market inputs, user preferences, and technical constraints. This modular structure provides scalability and establishes a foundation for future implementations with more complex, role-oriented models.

The paper stands out due to several technical innovations. It introduces EV2Gym as one of the few open-source simulation platforms to integrate full MPC capability. The framework allows for

real-time demand response participation and includes comprehensive battery degradation modeling, capturing both calendar aging and cyclic wear to assess long-term V2G viability. In addition, the paper offers a comparative analysis of four distinct control strategies: economic MPC in G2V and V2G configurations, and Optimal Control with Maximum Flexibility under both modes. Each strategy is evaluated through 50 simulation runs per scenario, with variations in EV fleet size, transformer availability, electricity pricing, and demand response event frequency. The use of real-world datasets ensures that simulation results are grounded in realistic energy consumption patterns and EV usage behavior.

Source: Modeling and Simulation of Vehicle to Grid (V2G) Integration

[206] presents a simulation framework developed in MATLAB/Simulink that models the 24-hour operation of a microgrid incorporating Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) capabilities. The system includes 100 electric vehicles (EVs), each with a rated power of 40 kilowatts, collectively delivering a V2G capacity of 4 megawatts. The framework is tested under various dynamic conditions, including wind farm disconnection, partial shading of photovoltaic (PV) panels, and the startup of an asynchronous machine. The analysis focuses on key performance metrics such as the evolution of the state of charge (SoC) across different initial levels, grid frequency stability under varying V2G response times, power quality through total harmonic distortion (THD), voltage stability, and the contribution of each energy source to the microgrid. The integration model is based on a microgrid-coupled V2G configuration that combines renewable energy sources—namely wind and solar—with a diesel generator and bidirectional EV charging. Within this setup, V2G operations facilitate peak shaving, load leveling, frequency regulation, and voltage support.

The technical framework includes detailed modeling of vehicle dynamics, SoC behavior with distinct charging and discharging efficiencies, inverter functionality covering both active and reactive power flow, and time-dependent generation models for PV and wind energy. Grid-tied inverter models enable synchronization and regulated bidirectional energy exchange between the EVs and the microgrid. Although the paper does not explicitly label its approach as role optimization, it effectively achieves functional coordination at the system level. EVs with lower initial SoC levels are prioritized for energy contribution during peak demand, allowing for load balancing based on SoC thresholds. The implementation of fast-response V2G notably enhances frequency stability, reducing frequency deviation from ± 0.25 Hz to approximately ± 0.05 Hz. Power quality is also improved through V2G participation, with total harmonic distortion reduced from 2 percent to 1 percent. Coordination of load and energy delivery is refined by aligning V2G activity with EV availability and SoC status, resulting in a more efficient and balanced system operation. The paper presents a community-scale microgrid simulation that integrates electric vehicles alongside solar, wind, and diesel energy resources. The model features realistic, multi-vehicle profiles that capture variation in SoC and user behavior. It quantifies the impact of V2G participation through grid-level indicators such as frequency deviation, voltage regulation, and harmonic distortion. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of V2G in enhancing system performance, particularly under conditions of renewable energy variability and fluctuating demand.

Source: Modeling and evaluating bidirectionally chargeable electric vehicles in the future European energy system

[207] presents a simulation framework based on the Integrated Simulation Model for Unit Dispatch and Expansion with Regionalization (ISAaR), a linear optimization tool for planning dispatch and capacity expansion in multi-energy systems. The model operates over a time horizon from 2025 to 2050, using five-year increments. Bidirectional electric vehicles are integrated into the system through detailed state-of-charge equations that incorporate both charging and discharging efficiencies, as well as energy consumption associated with mobility. Time-dependent vehicle availability is informed by empirical data from German mobility studies. Three distinct integration scenarios are analyzed. The first scenario utilizes discrete electric vehicle profiles derived from 1,000 synthetic datasets, providing high resolution but incurring significant computational demand—approximately 410 million time steps. The second scenario applies a clustering technique using k-means to group vehicle behaviors into between five and fifty representative clusters, reducing computational complexity while retaining key behavioral diversity. The third scenario aggregates all EV behavior into a single national profile, offering the highest computational efficiency and enabling its use in continent-scale energy planning models, albeit with reduced granularity.

In each scenario, electric vehicles are treated as energy storage units within the ISAaR framework, subject to constraints including power limits, state-of-charge boundaries, and energy conversion efficiencies. This paper is the first EU-wide energy system model to optimize the deployment rates of V2G-enabled electric vehicles for cost-effectiveness. By introducing both clustered and aggregated EV modeling techniques, it allows scalable integration of electric mobility into long-term energy system planning. Geographic variation in the value of V2G integration is also explored, with results indicating that Southern European countries stand to benefit most due to higher levels of solar energy availability. The study clearly differentiates the effects of smart charging, unmanaged charging, and full V2G implementation on the overall performance of the energy system. The paper also identifies several limitations. The aggregated EV behavior is based solely on German mobility data, which may not accurately capture regional behavioral differences across Europe. Furthermore, local grid constraints—such as distribution network overloads—are not explicitly modeled. The analysis also omits user-side economic factors, including pricing structures or incentives, and assumes static user behavior, without incorporating responsiveness to market dynamics or changes over time.

Source: Distributed Coordination of Electric Vehicles Providing V2G Services

[208] differentiates between centralized and distributed optimization approaches for Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) role distribution, with a primary emphasis on developing a distributed coordination mechanism. In the centralized model, the objective is to minimize load variance throughout the distribution network by utilizing comprehensive data, including electric vehicle (EV) plug-in times, forecasts of distributed energy resources, and state-of-charge information. This optimization is performed using Sequential Quadratic Programming; however, the method encounters scalability limitations due to significant computational and data requirements. The distributed model is structured as a multi-agent decision-making framework. It employs a hierarchical, price-based control architecture in which the Regional Aggregation Unit functions as the leader, generating virtual price signals that reflect local demand and renewable energy availability. Vehicle Controller agents then adjust their charging and discharging behavior to minimize individual energy costs while contributing to system-wide load balancing. This coordination is executed through iterative communication until convergence is reached, which is mathematically proven within the study. Notably, the virtual price

ing mechanism is used solely for coordination purposes and does not represent actual electricity market prices.

System performance is evaluated using metrics such as voltage deviation, network losses, renewable energy penetration limits, load variance reduction, and the effectiveness of coordination across a diverse EV fleet. The study introduces several innovations in the coordination of V2G systems. It presents a multi-layered, hierarchical agent-based architecture tailored for medium-voltage distribution networks. The distributed optimization is grounded in a Nash Certainty Equivalence framework, and its convergence is rigorously validated. The results demonstrate that the distributed control strategy achieves outcomes comparable to those of centralized methods, despite significantly lower data and computational burdens. The model incorporates a heterogeneous EV fleet, accounting for variations in battery capacity, plug-in availability, and willingness to participate through partial capacity contributions. Simulations are conducted on a real-world rural medium-voltage grid from Ikaria Island, using actual substation configurations and renewable generation data.

Designed for both scalability and flexibility, the system can accommodate a range of deployment scales—from individual residential EVs to large fleet aggregations. Control units such as Regional Aggregation Units, Mid Grid Aggregation Units, and Cluster Vehicle Controllers are modular and can be replicated across different sections of the distribution network as needed.

Source: The role of energy communities in electricity grid balancing: A flexible tool for smart grid power distribution optimization

[209] presents two primary optimization strategies for managing role distribution within energy communities. The first is a bi-objective optimization framework focused on peer-to-peer energy exchange and bidirectional interactions between electric vehicles and the community, including vehicle-to-community and community-to-vehicle energy flows. The objective is to maximize both self-consumption and self-sufficiency by optimizing energy dispatch across consumers, stationary batteries, and electric vehicles over a 24-hour cycle. This approach achieves complete self-consumption and 55% self-sufficiency; however, it leads to increased battery cycling and higher stress on EV batteries due to minimized reliance on the external grid. The second strategy targets grid balancing, employing an index called the Grid Balancing Factor. This optimization aims to flatten the community load profile and support frequency regulation by coordinating the dispatch of storage systems and electric vehicles based on predicted load patterns. While this method increases grid dependence slightly, it results in an optimal grid balancing score. Under this strategy, 14.3 megawatt-hours of surplus energy are stored, with 1.46 megawatt-hours and 7.71 megawatt-hours allocated for upward and downward frequency regulation, respectively.

The framework integrates dual optimization mechanisms: peer-to-peer energy sharing combined with electric vehicle dispatch through vehicle-to-community and community-to-vehicle operations, and grid balancing through predictive load reshaping. A novel metric—the Grid Balancing Factor—is introduced to quantify a community's ability to stabilize grid frequency using internal assets. A hierarchical, priority-based dispatch system is also implemented, which dynamically allocates surplus energy among electric vehicles, battery systems, and local consumers. This mechanism ensures adaptive energy distribution based on system priorities and resource availability. The paper is grounded in a multi-agent simulation environment that models realistic residential and office

energy consumption patterns, photovoltaic generation, and electric vehicle mobility behavior. It concludes with a comparative analysis highlighting the trade-offs between maximizing economic self-sufficiency and contributing to broader grid-level stability objectives.

Source: Multi-objective optimization strategy for distribution network considering V2G-enabled electric vehicles in building integrated energy system

[210] presents a co-optimization framework that simultaneously manages electric vehicle (EV) charging behavior and capacitor compensation to improve distribution grid performance. The primary objectives are to minimize active power losses and reduce voltage deviations from nominal values within the network. The optimization model integrates a time-of-use pricing scheme, encouraging EV charging during low-demand periods and discharging during peak hours. This approach enhances economic efficiency while contributing to demand curve flattening. The EV charging model considers constraints such as state-of-charge (SoC) limits, user-defined charging windows, and randomized user preferences. Daily mobility patterns are generated through Monte Carlo sampling to reflect realistic user behavior. A bi-objective optimization problem is solved using a genetic algorithm with elite preservation. The algorithm dynamically adjusts capacitor bank outputs to maintain voltage stability while managing EV charging and discharging schedules. Penalty terms are applied to ensure SoC remains within safe operating limits and to correct voltage violations.

Simulations conducted on the IEEE 33-bus test system demonstrate the effectiveness of the approach. Coordinated optimization of EV dispatch, distributed generation, and capacitor banks led to a 13.4% reduction in peak load, a 47.3% decrease in voltage deviations, and a 40.4% drop in active power losses. This paper distinguishes itself by integrating EV charging coordination with capacitor control through a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm. It incorporates realistic EV usage patterns, reactive power compensation, and user participation as a controllable parameter. The methodology is validated using the full IEEE 33-node distribution system, including realistic models of distributed generation and capacitor banks.

Source: Optimization Challenges in Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) Systems and Artificial Intelligence Solving Methods

[211] addresses critical challenges in Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) role optimization, including dynamic electricity pricing, variable user behavior, grid operational constraints, battery degradation, and the decentralized nature of electric vehicle (EV) availability. The core objectives are to minimize grid operating costs, improve user satisfaction, reduce emissions, and enable real-time system responsiveness. To meet these goals, the study introduces advanced artificial intelligence-based techniques. Simheuristics combine simulation with metaheuristics to manage uncertainty in energy flows and EV behavior. Learnheuristics apply machine learning to predict the quality of solutions, thereby reducing reliance on computationally intensive simulations. *Agile Optimization* introduces controlled randomness to enable fast and adaptive decision-making under dynamic conditions.

A practical case study demonstrates that these AI-driven methods significantly outperform traditional exact solvers such as Gurobi in terms of computational speed, successfully managing the scheduling of up to one million EVs in 4.5 seconds. The paper contributes a comprehensive taxonomy of V2G optimization challenges, addressing factors such as uncertainty, dynamic pricing,

and real-time decision-making requirements. It introduces three distinct AI-based frameworks—simheuristics, learnheuristics, and agile optimization—tailored to the specific needs of V2G coordination. The results show that these approaches can reduce costs by approximately 50% while offering substantial improvements in computational efficiency over conventional methods. Strategically, the paper shifts the paradigm from centralized, static models to decentralized, adaptive, and real-time AI-enabled systems. Additionally, it considers broader implications related to scalability, data privacy, and regulatory frameworks.

Source: Optimal management of vehicle-to-grid and grid-to-vehicle strategies for load profile improvement in distribution system

[212] establishes defined functional roles within the Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) ecosystem, modeling electric vehicles (EVs) as mobile distributed energy storage units capable of charging and discharging in response to grid requirements and dynamic pricing signals. EV behavior is represented stochastically, incorporating variables such as arrival and departure times, battery capacities, and travel distances. The plug-in patterns and mobility demands of EV owners serve as constraints within the optimization framework, ensuring realistic operational boundaries. Coordination is managed by a distribution system operator (DSO) or centralized control entity, which schedules EV charging and discharging across residential and administrative parking zones, each characterized by distinct load profiles and usage patterns. While the roles of aggregators and transmission system operators are not explicitly included, the DSO-like control mechanism implicitly fulfills the aggregator function. To optimize role allocation within this structure, the study proposes a hybrid stochastic-heuristic optimization framework. Monte Carlo Simulation is employed to model real-world uncertainty in EV behavior, producing probabilistic input distributions. Optimization is conducted using the Opposition-based Competitive Swarm Optimizer, selected for its enhanced convergence speed and solution quality compared to conventional swarm intelligence methods. This approach requires minimal memory and limited parameter tuning.

The optimization goal is to minimize daily load variance, subject to constraints related to power balance, state of charge (SoC), voltage stability, and thermal line limits. Operational constraints prevent simultaneous charging and discharging and require that EVs begin and end their schedules with identical SoC levels. Simulation results demonstrate a 32.67% reduction in load variance relative to uncontrolled charging scenarios. Additionally, the system shows improved voltage regulation and reduced power losses during peak demand periods. The proposed optimization method outperforms several well-known metaheuristics, including Genetic Algorithm, Particle Swarm Optimization, Artificial Bee Colony, Firefly Algorithm, and standard Competitive Swarm Optimization, across key performance indicators such as convergence speed, robustness, and solution accuracy.

The framework is applied to a realistic IEEE 69-bus distribution system and introduces a penalty factor-based objective function to effectively manage voltage and thermal violations. A parametric sensitivity analysis is included to calibrate the optimizer by adjusting variables like population size and social influence factors. For practical implementation, the model closely mirrors actual EV travel behavior by associating arrival and departure times with residential and workplace zones. SoC profiles are validated against mobility requirements, and the scheduling mechanism shifts energy usage from peak to off-peak hours. This leads to notable improvements in load leveling and voltage

control across the network.

Source: **Energy Cost Optimization of Hybrid Renewables Based V2G Microgrid Considering Multi Objective Function by Using Artificial Bee Colony Optimization**

[213] presents a comprehensive framework defining functional roles within a microgrid-integrated Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) system. Electric vehicles (EVs) are modeled as both dynamic electrical loads and distributed energy storage units. They operate either autonomously in a charging-only mode or in a coordinated charging and discharging mode, guided by real-time electricity prices and system load conditions. User influence on the load model is captured through probabilistic distributions reflecting spatial and temporal behavior, including arrival times and state of charge, with preferences modeled statistically. The microgrid operator is responsible for dispatch coordination, energy balance management, and the integration of EVs with distributed energy resources (DERs). Charging and discharging strategies are selected to optimize both economic performance and environmental impact. Distributed generators—including wind turbines, photovoltaic panels, diesel generators, and fuel cells—are scheduled based on cost, availability, and emission profiles. Battery storage systems enhance flexibility, particularly during islanded operation, while the external grid functions as an energy source or sink in grid-connected scenarios.

The study introduces a multi-objective economic dispatch model that incorporates operating cost, carbon emissions, and pollutant treatment cost. These objectives are weighted through a judgment matrix to facilitate trade-off analysis. Four operational strategies are evaluated under both grid-connected and islanded conditions. Coordinated V2G participation consistently yields superior results compared to autonomous charging, leading to notable reductions in both total cost and emissions. Optimization is carried out using the Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithm. Compared to Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), ABC demonstrates faster convergence, improved cost-effectiveness, and greater emission reduction capabilities. The algorithm employs a hierarchical role structure—comprising scout, onlooker, and employed bees—to navigate the solution space and avoid local minima. Simulations involving up to 700 EVs under various load-shedding scenarios show that the ABC algorithm achieves cost savings of up to 35.4% relative to PSO and provides greater resilience during peak demand periods.

This paper introduces a robust microgrid model that incorporates both autonomous and coordinated EV scheduling. It applies Artificial Bee Colony optimization in conjunction with a weighted judgment matrix to balance operational costs, environmental emissions, and pollutant treatment expenses. Realistic EV user behavior is statistically modeled to ensure practical applicability. Key results include up to 35% cost savings, a 52% reduction in emissions, and substantial decreases in pollutant treatment costs. The proposed approach enhances load leveling, peak shaving, and overall system flexibility in both grid-connected and islanded operating modes.

Source: **Optimal bidding and coordinating strategy for maximal marginal revenue due to V2G operation: Distribution system operator as a key player in China's uncertain electricity markets**

[214] examines the distribution of roles between Electric Vehicle Aggregators (EVAs) and Distribution System Operators (DSOs) within China's electricity markets. In this framework, electric vehicle (EV) owners serve as flexible energy storage providers, entering into contracts that grant DSOs con-

trol over their charging and discharging behavior. DSOs act as central coordinators with access to real-time grid data, enabling them to perform forecasting, bidding, dispatch, and revenue optimization. EVAs function as intermediaries but lack access to grid constraint information, often resulting in suboptimal coordination. Electricity market operations are managed by the Guangdong Power Exchange Center (GPEC), which oversees trading, and the Guangdong Power Dispatching and Control Center (GPDC), which ensures grid security and data dissemination. The study identifies DSOs as the more capable market participant due to their comprehensive access, operational authority, and system stability.

To optimize role allocation, the paper introduces a stochastic optimization model aimed at enabling DSOs to maximize marginal revenue while adhering to grid limitations and contractual terms. The model incorporates forecasted electricity prices, contract conditions, and EV behavioral data, including state of charge, arrival and departure times, and geographic location. The optimization problem is initially framed as a Mixed-Integer Nonlinear Program and is subsequently reformulated as a Second-Order Cone Program for computational efficiency. EV behavior is clustered into 12 representative types using the K-Means algorithm, while electricity pricing is modeled through scenario-based stochastic simulations. Two contractual frameworks are analyzed. The Discount Price Contract grants DSOs full control over scheduling in exchange for reduced charging costs and compensation for battery degradation. The Revenue Sharing Contract allocates profits and associated risks between DSOs and EV owners, serving as a buffer against pricing uncertainty and forecast errors.

The study shifts the central coordination role in V2G operations from EVAs to DSOs, demonstrating that DSOs are better positioned to manage grid constraints and market volatility. A contract-based management structure is proposed to formally delegate control of EV operations to DSOs. The paper validates this approach using empirical data from a 31-node campus grid in Guangdong. Results indicate that DSOs can achieve significantly higher marginal revenue—up to 13,477 yuan per day with 1,400 EVs—compared to EVA-led models. Additionally, the analysis of contractual risk reveals that revenue-sharing agreements reduce volatility in returns for DSOs by approximately 25% relative to discount-based contracts. The study also includes a spatial optimization component, showing that EV location within the grid has a direct impact on both energy losses and economic returns. Positioning smart chargers in close proximity to substations is shown to enhance profitability for DSOs.

6.1.6 Benchmarking Against Market and Regulatory Parameters

- **Market Frameworks**

- SGAM Architecture (ENTSO-E): Harmonized market role models ensure interoperability and efficiency in EU-wide grid services [193].
- Energy Arbitrage & FCR Participation: Aggregators and TSOs collaborate for dynamic market operations, using EVs to balance supply/demand [193], [195], [196].
- Local Flexibility Markets: Emerging platforms allow DSOs to directly procure flexibility [187], [197].

- **Business Models**

- Aggregator-Centric Revenue Sharing: Commission-based, SaaS, and shared revenue models promote alignment among EVAs, users, and infrastructure providers [196].

- Battery Leasing and Co-Ownership: Innovative ownership structures improve scalability and second-life applications [193].
- Smart Charging Service Providers (SCSPs): Act as intermediaries managing technical and business layers, integrating ISO/OICP protocols [189], [209].
- **Technical and Regulatory Readiness**
 - EU Data Act & RED III: Standardize data access and charging interoperability [189].
 - Bidirectional Readiness: OEM and charger compliance to ISO 15118 and IEC standards is critical [149], [209].
 - Cybersecurity & Privacy: User trust hinges on data protection mechanisms and transparent consent management [192].

Comparative Analysis and Best Practices The following table provides an overview of the comparative analysis in terms of roles and distributions as well as the previous mentioned criterion relevant for project NEVERFLAT.

Table 6.2: Comparative analysis and best practices for role distribution across market frameworks, business models, and the regulatory-technological landscape.

Criteria	High Benchmark (Best Practice)	Low Benchmark (Gaps Identified)
Role Clarity	ENTSO-E role harmonization; VPPO integration (Ref [210])	Fragmented ownership, unclear control pathways (Ref [187])
Market Access	Multilateral contracts, aggregator models (Ref [193], [196])	Lack of DR mechanisms and user engagement (Ref [190], [197])
Revenue Transparency	Distributed profits and open-market trading (Ref [198])	Uncoordinated incentive models (Ref [192])
Interoperability	Standards-based integration: ISO 15118, IEC 61850 (Ref [209])	Proprietary platforms, lack of SoC sharing (Ref [189])
User Inclusion	Demand Response Contracts, behaviour-centric models (Ref [198])	Minimal involvement beyond passive charging (Ref [210])

6.2 Regulatory Landscape

6.2.1 Key Criteria

To assess the readiness, effectiveness, and scalability of V2G and smart charging solutions across different regulatory environments, this analysis will be structured around five key criteria. These categories are selected based on their critical role in enabling or hindering the deployment of interoperable, flexible, and consumer-centric V2G charging solutions.

Regulatory and Market structure: A well-defined and adaptable regulatory framework is essential to enabling market access, incentivizing participation, and ensuring system reliability. This criterion examines whether the current market structure allows new actors-such as an independent aggregator-to offer flexibility services, and how supportive the existing regulations are in integrating emerging technologies like V2G.

Interoperability, Standardization and Communication: Communication standards and protocols are essential for enabling reliable data exchange between various actors in the V2G ecosystem—including EVs, charging stations, OEMs grid operators and energy providers. Interoperability depends on the alignment of these standards to ensure seamless coordination, efficient operation, and broad compatibility across different systems.

Data Management: Data is a fundamental enabler of the V2G ecosystem, driving efficient system coordination, enabling market participation, and fostering service innovation. Effective data governance is critical to maintaining trust, ensuring transparency, and safeguarding security. This criterion evaluates the strength of regulatory and policy frameworks to support secure, reliable and efficient data exchange.

Consumer Protection and Rights: For end-users to actively participate in V2G and smart charging, their rights must be protected. Transparent contracts, accessible information, clear liability rules, data privacy protection, user-friendly interfaces, and effective customer support all contribute to building trust and encouraging sustained engagement.

Environmental Considerations: The deployment of V2G must align with boarder climate and sustainability goals. This criterion ensures that the solutions being promoted are not only technically and economically viable but also environmentally responsible, contributing to decarbonization, resource efficiency, and long-term sustainability.

6.2.2 Europe

Vehicle-to-Grid and smart charging technologies are central to Europe's energy transition, offering pathways to decarbonize transport, enhance grid flexibility, and improve system resilience. Therefore, these innovations are receiving growing attention at the European policy level. The current landscape is marked by emerging technologies, varying levels of maturity, and ongoing pilot projects. In this context, the European legislative framework is designed to remove barriers and accelerate the rapid deployment of V2G and smart charging technologies.

Key legislative building blocks on the grid side include the Electricity Market Design reform that enables flexible and active participation by new actors such as EVs and aggregators. Additionally, clear grid codes are essential to integrate EV Charging into the broader electricity system safely and efficiently.

On the charging infrastructure side, three key legislative instruments play a central role: the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR), the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), and the Renewable Energy Directive (RED III). A critical element of the regulatory framework involves distinguishing between public and private charging infrastructure. AFIR establishes binding targets for the roll-out of public charging infrastructure and mandates interoperability standards to ensure seamless user experience and cross-border compatibility. The revised EPBD introduces provisions to integrate charging infrastructure into buildings, particularly in residential and commercial contexts, which is crucial for enabling V2G for private charging. Meanwhile, RED III strengthens the role of renewable energy in the transport sector and supports system integration, promoting the deployment of V2G as a flexibility resource.

Standardization and communication protocols play a crucial role in the deployment of V2G and smart charging across Europe. To support a truly open and competitive market, it is vital to avoid proprietary solutions that lead to fragmentation and limit the development of a level-playing field. In this regard, the AFIR Delegated Acts play a key role in mandating ISO15118-2 and –20 on the charging infrastructure side. However, legislation addressing charging infrastructure must work in parallel with mandates for OEMs to align the automotive and energy sectors under a coherent regulatory framework.

Access to data also plays a crucial role, with important groundwork from a regulatory standpoint. The Data Act provides a horizontal legal framework for data access and sharing, while sector-specific legislation, such as RED III (Art 20), mandates the availability of data necessary for smart charging and demand-side flexibility. In addition, the Sub-group on Governance & Standards, and Data of the Sustainable Transport Forum (STF)—an Expert Group of the European Commission—and the Data 4 Energy (D4E) working group within the Smart Energy Expert Group (SEEG) of the European Commission, together with the Coalition of the Willing (CoW) on Bidirectional Charging initiated by the German Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy, are jointly collaborating to identify practical steps to enable seamless and efficient data exchange across the EU for demand-side flexibility and smart, bidirectional charging. This collaborative effort is expected to lead to concrete recommendations for the European Commission.

In summary, while the full potential of V2G and smart charging is still being unlocked, the European regulatory framework is evolving to support this transition. Despite the progress made, several critical barriers continue to hinder the large-scale deployment of these technologies, particularly those related to interoperability and data management. One of the most pressing issues is the lack of a coherent, functional data ecosystem that enables the seamless and secure sharing of data between different stakeholders—OEMs, charging infrastructure, energy suppliers, grid operators, and aggregators.

6.2.3 Germany

Germany is one of the frontrunners in advancing bidirectional charging technologies, with a strong political mandate and coordinated policy frameworks. Germany has committed to a nationwide roll-out of bidirectional charging, as outlined in the Charging Infrastructure II Masterplan. The government expects vehicle-to-home (V2H) applications to be market-ready by 2025, followed by vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technologies. A significant expansion is planned from 2028, contingent upon the finalization of technical standards and regulatory frameworks. In addition, initiatives like the Coalition of the Willing on Bidirectional Charging, coordinated by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy, which brings together industry and policymakers across Europe, demonstrates the commitment in advancing V2G technologies.

However, despite a supportive legal framework, practical implementation is hindered by limited digital infrastructure, particularly the slow rollout of smart meters and the underdeveloped digitalization of the grid, which restricts the scalability of vehicle aggregation and demand-side services. Regulatory mechanisms to integrate controllable devices into the grid have also been proposed, offering tariff reductions in exchange for flexible consumption. Nevertheless, large-scale demand response programs remain underutilized, and dynamic pricing models that could motivate real-time

behavioral adjustments among EV users are not yet widely accessible.

It becomes clear that integrating bidirectional charging at scale requires ongoing adaptation to emerging technologies and market conditions. Communication between key actors—such as vehicle manufacturers, charge point operators, grid operators, and energy suppliers—remains insufficient to support complex services like bidirectional charging. Interoperability and communication protocols are supported by a robust standardization framework—but inconsistent implementation can lead to partial interoperability. Germany’s approach to embed control functions within Smart Meter Gateways (SMGW) offers a secure, standardized communication path, but this diverges from other EU member states and may complicate cross-border harmonization.

Consumer protection is receiving increasing attention. However, bidirectional energy discharged back to the grid still faces double taxation and grid fees, making it economically unattractive for many EV owners. While progress is being made, more work is needed to align tax structures and liability frameworks with the evolving use cases of mobile energy storage.

Ultimately, Germany’s commitment to bidirectional charging contributes directly to its climate goals by enabling deeper integration of renewable energy and improving grid resilience. The country has laid a strong regulatory and strategic foundation, but unlocking the full potential of bidirectional charging will require accelerated infrastructure deployment, targeted consumer incentives, streamlined market access, and harmonized data and communication systems.

6.2.4 Romania

While Romania has established foundational policies to promote electric vehicle adoption and charging infrastructure, specific regulations for bi-directional charging and V2G technologies are still in development. Romania’s Emergency Ordinance no.40 of 20 April 2011 (the “Ordinance”) transposed Directive 2009/33/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the promotion of clean and energy-efficient road transport vehicles. The Ordinance regulates the general obligation to promote clean energy by also promoting the market of non-polluting and energy-efficient vehicles. Another legislative measure to encourage EVs is Law no. 34/2017 (the “Law”) on the deployment of alternative fuels infrastructure (it transposes Directive 2014/94/EU). The Law establishes a common framework of measures for deploying an alternative fuels infrastructure. The aim is to minimise dependence on oil and to mitigate the environmental impact of transport. It sets out minimum requirements for developing the alternative fuels infrastructure, including recharging points for electric vehicles.

The principal provisions that came into force through Law 101/2020, which amends the provisions of Law 372/2005 on the energy performance of buildings, are:

- In the case of new non-residential buildings or those undergoing major renovation works that have more than 10 parking spaces, investors / their owners, as the case may be, are obliged to install at least one recharging point for electric vehicles, as well as recessed piping for electrical cables for at least 20% of the planned parking spaces.
- They must allow the recharging points for electric vehicles to be installed later. The rule applies when the parking lot is located inside or adjacent to the building or if the renovation measures include the parking lot or the electrical infrastructure of the building/parking lot.

- In the case of existing non-residential buildings with more than 20 parking spaces, the owners must install by January 1, 2025, several recharging points for electric vehicles at least equal to 10% of the total number of parking spaces, but not less than two recharging points for electric cars. Exceptions to these obligations are buildings owned and occupied by small and medium-sized enterprises.
- In the case of new or significant renovated residential buildings that have more than 10 parking spaces, investors / their owners, are obliged to ensure the installation of recessed electrical cable piping for each parking space to allow installation in a subsequent stage of recharging points for electric vehicles.
- The above provisions do not apply to new residential and non-residential buildings or those undergoing major renovations for which building permit applications were submitted before March 10, 2021. They also do not apply to existing residential and non-residential buildings undergoing major renovations. for which the estimated cost of recharging installations for electric and built-in vehicles, provided for in the general estimate and specified in the specialty memorandum, exceeds 7% of the total cost of the major renovation of the building.

According to Law No. 50/1991, obtaining a building permit is necessary for the construction or installation of EV charging stations. This process involves compliance with local building codes and may require environmental assessments and grid connection agreements from the municipality.

6.2.5 Spain

Spain has developed a comprehensive regulatory framework to support electric vehicle (EV) adoption and the deployment of charging infrastructure. However, specific regulations directly addressing bi-directional charging and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) or Vehicle-to-Home (V2H) technologies remain limited and under development. Nonetheless, several legislative instruments indirectly enable their deployment.

The Law 7/2021 on Climate Change and Energy Transition establishes targets for the decarbonization of transport and mandates the deployment of public charging infrastructure. It encourages innovation and the adoption of new technologies, such as smart charging, but does not yet specifically regulate V2G functionalities. Spain transposed Directive 2014/94/EU through Royal Decree 647/2011, which regulates the activity of energy recharging services for electric vehicles. The decree introduced the figure of the “charging manager” (gestor de carga) and laid the groundwork for commercial EV charging services. However, it does not mention bi-directional charging capabilities. Further developments came through Royal Decree 1053/2014, which approved the ITC-BT 52 technical instruction. This made it mandatory to include EV pre-installation (conduits, ducts) in new or renovated residential and non-residential buildings with private parking. The regulation does not yet cover V2G or storage functionalities, but it facilitates future installation of smart and potentially bi-directional chargers.

Under Royal Decree 184/2022, the Spanish government reformed the charging point installation process by streamlining administrative procedures, especially for large-scale deployment. It eliminated the requirement to register charging infrastructure as an energy activity, thus reducing barriers to market entry for operators. Again, V2G is not explicitly addressed, but this eases deployment of advanced charging technologies. On the energy side, Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector, as well

as subsequent regulations including Royal Decree 1183/2020, allow self-consumption and the participation of distributed energy resources in the electricity market. These frameworks may enable future integration of V2G systems, especially as the concept of aggregators (entities that group and manage distributed energy resources) gains traction in Spain. Aggregators are officially recognized and regulated by Royal Decree 244/2019 on self-consumption.

In terms of building regulations, the Technical Building Code (CTE), particularly Basic Document HE (Energy Saving), includes provisions for the installation of EV infrastructure in new buildings or those undergoing major renovations. It requires pre-installation for one charging point per 40 parking spaces in non-residential buildings and one per residence in residential buildings, but again does not refer specifically to bi-directional capabilities.

6.3 Identified Gaps and Barriers

6.3.1 EU perspectives

As the EU advances toward a decarbonized and resilient energy system, the integration of V2G and smart charging technologies emerges as a critical enabler of system flexibility and consumer empowerment. While the full potential of V2G technologies is still being unlocked, the European regulatory framework is evolving to support this transition. By addressing technical, market, and consumer-related challenges, the EU aims to ensure that these technologies can deliver benefits for the grid, the environment, and the end-users alike.

Despite the progress in regulatory frameworks, several barriers continue to hinder the large-scale deployment of V2G technologies, particularly those related to interoperability and data management. One of the most pressing issues is the lack of a unified and functional data ecosystem, that enables seamless and secure sharing of relevant data between different stakeholders-vehicle manufacturers, charge point operators, energy suppliers, grid operators, and aggregators. Currently, data sharing remains complex, both from a technical and legal perspective. There is limited clarity on data ownership, privacy requirements, access rights, and responsibilities. Moreover, the value of data-driven services, such as dynamic prices, real-time flexibility aggregation, or participation in ancillary service markets, is not fully realized due to fragmented and complex market rules. Another major gap is unclear definition of use cases, roles and responsibilities related to the types of flexibility services V2G can provide-whether to the transmission system, distribution networks, or energy suppliers-and under which regulatory frameworks they can be enabled. Without regulatory clarity on the market framework under which V2G services can operate, it remains difficult to design viable business models that attract investment or incentivize end-user participation.

To unlock the potential of these business models, there is a growing need to identify the specific data types required for different use cases-such as real-time charging data, grid status signal, or user preferences- and to develop standardized APIs that facilitate access to this data in a secure and interoperable way. From a regulatory standpoint, the EU has laid important groundwork with the Data Act and the RED III, but further work is needed to align and operationalize these frameworks and ensure level playing field data access and sharing. Standardization plays a key role in the deployment of V2G and smart charging across Europe and a particular focus should be placed on communication protocols that support a truly open and competitive market, avoiding proprietary

solutions that increase complexity, limit compatibility and risk market fragmentation.

Furthermore, the EU should foster end-user engagement through market design, simplify participation in demand response and flexibility programs, and introduce incentives for consumers who provide grid services via V2G technologies, and ensure transparency in pricing and remuneration schemes.

6.3.2 Germany perspectives

Germany possesses a strong regulatory foundation and technical expertise in V2G standardization, placing it in a favorable position to lead in this transformative technology. However, significant barriers continue to impede the widespread deployment of V2G technologies. Although Germany has established the technical and legal framework permitting the control of distributed assets via smart meter gateways (SMGWs), the slow and fragmented deployment of smart meters constrains practical V2G implementation. Without widespread deployment, the foundational infrastructure for secure, standardized communication essential for V2G is lacking, preventing scalable use cases such as redispatch, frequency containment reserve (FCR), or local congestion management involving flexible small-scale assets like electric vehicles.

Germany's smart meter penetration remains below 1%, and the legal requirement for re-certification of metering equipment under the Eichrecht creates additional obstacles to data accessibility and optimization. In addition to the slow roll-out of smart meters, Germany's highly decentralized municipal utility structure complicates unified V2G market development. The number of market players, especially DSOs in Germany, underlines the importance of standards and at the same time means that the national implementation is more difficult than in other countries. The absence of a functioning market for aggregated EV flexibility services, even though pooling of EVs is possible according to the current legislative framework, reflects broader digitalization deficits in the electricity system. Although a variety of dynamic and asset-specific tariffs exist already, practical consumer access remains limited. The disconnect between market design and practical accessibility undermines the scalability of demand-side flexibility.

While Germany has invested heavily in communication standards (IEC 61851, ISO15118, VDE-AR-E 2829-6-1, OCPP, EEBUS) the multitude of standard and freedom of interpretation among manufacturers create interoperability issues. This complexity raises the technical and operational barriers for seamless integration of diverse V2G technologies. Targeted policy action to accelerate smart meter deployment, work with EU partners to standardize interfaces for V2G applications, encourage harmonization of communication protocols, and foster market and consumer engagement will be crucial. By addressing these challenges, Germany can unlock scalable demand-side flexibility, support renewable integration, and pave the way for a more resilient, sustainable energy future.

6.3.3 Romanian perspectives

Regulatory and standardization barriers remain a significant hurdle for the successful implementation of the NEVERFLAT solution in Romania, particularly concerning the deployment of bi-directional charging and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technologies. At present, Romania does not have a unified or comprehensive regulatory framework that explicitly governs bi-directional energy flow between electric vehicles and the grid. This regulatory gap creates uncertainty for both developers and grid

operators, as key issues such as compliance with grid codes, energy trading, and system balancing responsibilities remain undefined for V2G scenarios.

Moreover, the absence of nationally recognized technical standards and certification procedures for bi-directional charging infrastructure exacerbates the challenge. Without clear specifications aligned with international standards such as ISO 15118 (which supports Plug & Charge and V2G communications), there is a heightened risk of interoperability failures between EVs, chargers, and distribution system operators (DSOs). This lack of harmonization may lead to delays in testing, validation, and eventual integration of BEIA's pilot solution with bi-directional charging components into the Romanian energy network. Additionally, regulatory ambiguity complicates the monetization of grid services provided by EVs, such as frequency regulation or load balancing, which are key incentives for V2G adoption. In the absence of mechanisms for grid remuneration or energy market participation, potential business models for V2G in Romania remain underdeveloped.

Since Romania's energy regulations are largely focused on traditional unidirectional grid infrastructure, introducing a disruptive, two-way energy flow model requires updates not only to legislation but also to operational practices and grid management protocols. Without these updates, there is a risk that the innovative functionalities of NEVERFLAT, particularly those demonstrated through the BEIA pilot, will face significant administrative and technical delays in scaling up to national or cross-border levels.

6.3.4 Spanish perspectives

Spain has not yet promulgated a legal article that explicitly authorises an electric vehicle to export stored energy through a public grid connection. There is still no specific regulation for bidirectional charging and that current rules prevent individual EV owners from feeding energy upstream of the meter. Because the Law 24/2013–184/2022 framework recognises CPOs and EMSPs but does not create an independent aggregator licence, small or mobile storage units cannot pool capacity, bid into balancing markets or receive firm remuneration for fast-response services. Flexibility products remain limited to large-scale assets, and the transmission-system operator has not opened its ancillary-services platform to distributed resources, leaving V2G value chains structurally undeveloped.

Economic signals are weak, the simplified compensation scheme under RD 244/2019 caps earnings for chargers below 100 kW at monthly netting value, while larger installations face producer registration, wholesale settlement and tax obligations—costly hurdles for low-power public V2G points. No dedicated tariff discounts, dynamic network charges or capacity payments exist for bidirectional EV batteries, so the investment premium over a standard charger is unrecovered. From a technical perspective, there is still no Spanish certification path for bidirectional EVSE. ITC-BT-52 lacks reverse-power test clauses; ISO 15118-20 conformance tests are not referenced in national regulations; and neither UL 9741 nor other safety standards have been transposed. As a result, manufacturers cannot obtain a clear conformity label for V2G devices, and installers face uncertain inspection criteria.

Data exchange is another bottleneck. Royal Decree 1183/2020 obliges network operators to digitalise access procedures, but Spain does not yet run a common flexibility data hub. Real-time metering, battery state-of-charge and price signals must be negotiated case-by-case between CPOs, retailers

and DSOs, delaying aggregation at scale and complicating settlement. Consumer protection lags behind, RD 184/2022 secures transparent billing for energy taken from the grid, but it is silent on contractual rights when the same battery becomes an energy supplier. There is no standard clause on battery-degradation compensation, metering accuracy for discharge, or liability if the vehicle fails to deliver scheduled energy. Until such annexes are drafted, retail V2G propositions expose drivers and CPOs to legal uncertainty.

Finally, distribution operators possess limited operational guidelines on high-penetration bidirectional flows. Hosting-capacity studies, voltage-control protocols and coordination tools for thousands of mobile storage units are still under development, so DSOs remain cautious about granting permits. Without technical codes that integrate aggregated V2G into network planning and ancillary-service dispatch, large-scale rollout will remain pilot-bound. In short, Spain has laid substantial groundwork—clear charging-service roles, streamlined grid access, ambitious climate targets and an active sandbox—but key enabling pieces are missing. Specific statutory language for bidirectional export, an aggregator market design, V2G-focused financial incentives, certified interoperability standards, standardised data channels and dedicated consumer safeguards must all be finalised before V2G can evolve from isolated trials to a bankable, system-wide flexibility resource.

6.4 Conclusion and Recommendations for Action

6.4.1 EU perspectives

To unlock the full potential of Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) and smart charging technologies, the EU must take a set of coordinated actions that address current regulatory, technical, and market-related challenges. First and foremost, the development of a robust and functional data ecosystem is essential. This involves defining who owns what data, under what conditions it can be shared, and how privacy and access rights are protected. Creating legal clarity around these issues will help build trust among stakeholders and ensure that valuable data can flow securely and efficiently between vehicle manufacturers, charge point operators, energy providers, grid operators, and aggregators.

Alongside this, the EU should prioritize the development of standardized and interoperable digital infrastructure. Defining the specific data needs for various use cases—such as real-time charging information, grid conditions, or user preferences—is a necessary step. Building secure, standardized APIs will support seamless data exchange and enable innovative services, from dynamic pricing to aggregated flexibility offerings. Another key priority is the harmonization of communication protocols. Adopting open, non-proprietary standards will prevent market fragmentation and reduce technical complexity. This will ensure that smart charging systems and V2G solutions can operate across different platforms and national markets, enabling a more competitive and integrated European energy landscape.

The regulatory framework should also clearly define the roles and responsibilities of different actors involved in V2G services. Clarifying which entities can benefit from V2G flexibility, and under which conditions, is critical. This clarity will support the development of robust business models, attract investment, and encourage the rollout of V2G infrastructure. Consumer engagement must not be overlooked. The EU should make it easier for individuals to participate in energy flexibility schemes by reducing complexity and making incentives more transparent and attractive. Financial

incentives, transparent pricing mechanisms, and accessible information will be essential in encouraging consumers to contribute to grid services through their electric vehicles. Finally, aligning policies across EU member states is crucial for scale and coherence. National regulations should be coordinated to ensure that V2G and smart charging technologies can be deployed consistently across borders, facilitating a truly integrated European market.

By addressing these areas—data ecosystem, standardization, regulatory clarity, and end user engagement—the EU can create the enabling environment needed for V2G and smart charging technologies.

6.4.2 Germany perspectives

To unlock the potential of Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technologies, Germany must address several structural and operational hurdles through targeted policy and regulatory action. A primary step is to significantly speed up the rollout of smart metering infrastructure. Although the legal framework enables control of distributed assets via smart meter gateways, the slow and uneven deployment has created a bottleneck. Without a reliable and widespread digital metering network, secure communication and coordination with electric vehicles remain limited.

While Germany has championed numerous relevant communication standards, the inconsistent adoption and interpretation of these protocols across manufacturers and system operators create interoperability barriers. To resolve this, regulatory bodies should facilitate the development of a unified implementation framework, including precise technical guidelines, compliance benchmarks, and testing procedures. Ensuring consistency in the application of standards will lower integration costs and support the development of a cohesive V2G ecosystem. To build a viable market for flexible EV-based services, Germany should also focus on enabling aggregated participation in grid support mechanisms. While the legal basis for pooling exists, practical access remains limited due to gaps in digital infrastructure and market interfaces. Improving consumer access to dynamic electricity pricing is another priority. Although tariff options exist, they often remain difficult to understand or access. Making these products more visible, easier to adopt, and linked with meaningful incentives can encourage EV owners to actively participate in grid balancing and unlock additional value from their vehicles.

Finally, Germany should strengthen collaboration with European partners to align its technical and regulatory approaches with broader EU initiatives. Germany should actively contribute to the development of unified EU-wide V2G interfaces and regulatory approaches. Engaging in European standardization bodies, sharing best practices, and coordinating policy with neighboring countries will support cross-border operability and ensure that Germany's efforts integrate seamlessly into a broader European flexibility market. By addressing these areas—digital infrastructure, standardization, market accessibility, consumer engagement, and EU coordination—Germany can create the right conditions for V2G to thrive and play a central role in its energy transition.

6.4.3 Romanian perspectives

To support the successful implementation of bi-directional charging and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technologies in Romania, policymakers should prioritize the development of a unified and forward-looking regulatory framework. Currently, bi-directional charging is not clearly recognized or differentiated within national legislation, which creates legal uncertainty for investors and technology

providers. Establishing a dedicated regulatory status for V2G as an energy service—complementary to existing provisions for distributed generation—would provide a foundational legal basis for pilot projects and future market integration.

In tandem with regulatory clarity, Romania must adopt and enforce internationally recognized technical standards for V2G communication and charger interoperability. Standards such as ISO 15118 and IEC 61851 are critical for enabling seamless interaction between electric vehicles, charging stations, and grid operators. Their inclusion in national regulation would ensure that new infrastructure deployments are future-proof and compatible with European best practices, facilitating scalability and cross-border functionality. Equally important is the creation of national certification and testing procedures for bi-directional chargers. At present, the absence of such processes poses risks in terms of safety, performance assurance, and administrative delays. National standardization bodies, such as ASRO (Romanian Standardization Association), should be mandated to develop and oversee certification schemes, supported by accredited testing laboratories. This would build confidence among grid operators and local authorities when integrating V2G infrastructure into public and commercial settings.

To drive market adoption, policymakers should introduce mechanisms that allow EVs and their aggregated fleets to participate in energy and ancillary services markets. This includes enabling remuneration for grid-stabilizing services such as frequency regulation, voltage support, and demand response. Creating financial incentives and removing entry barriers for V2G actors would unlock new business models, transforming EVs from passive energy consumers into active contributors to grid flexibility. The permitting and connection processes for charging infrastructure also require modernization. Simplifying and streamlining the administrative pathway for grid connection—particularly for bi-directional public chargers—will reduce deployment delays. A centralized, digital application process could be introduced to fast-track approvals, especially when integrated into smart city or sustainable transport initiatives.

Support from public authorities at the local level is essential. Financial support mechanisms—such as those available under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) or the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)—should prioritize V2G-compatible charging infrastructure, enabling hands-on testing and stakeholder engagement. Additionally, the government should take a strategic approach by developing a National Smart Charging Strategy, embedded within Romania's National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) and Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP). This strategy should outline a roadmap for scaling smart and bi-directional charging infrastructure in alignment with renewable energy and grid decarbonization targets.

Lastly, Romania should actively participate in EU-level working groups and policy forums focused on electric mobility and energy systems integration. Coordinating with initiatives and regulations such as the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR), Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), and other European platforms will ensure alignment with emerging EU standards, foster knowledge exchange, and enhance access to funding opportunities. Together, these actions will enable Romania to build a supportive environment for innovative charging solutions as NEVERFLAT, positioning the country as a proactive contributor to Europe's clean mobility transition.

6.4.4 Spanish perspective

Spain has already created the basic pillars for Vehicle-to-Grid: a modern electricity-sector law, streamlined grid-access rules, a dedicated decree for EV charging services, pilot authorisations and an energy-storage strategy that recognises mobile batteries. Yet bidirectional operation still lacks a formal legal status, independent aggregation remains only a draft proposal, and up-front incentives ignore the extra cost of V2G hardware. The resulting uncertainty keeps most projects in sandbox mode and prevents fleets from offering fast-response flexibility at national scale. Recent moves—the public consultation on a royal decree that defines independent aggregators and assigns Red Eléctrica to manage a central measurement platform, the CNMC resolution that shortens wholesale trading to fifteen-minute intervals, and the five MITECO flexibility pilots approved in March 2025—show Spain is prepared to close the gap, but decisive follow-through is now required.

The first legislative priority is to give explicit legal recognition to bidirectional export from electric vehicles. A short amendment to Law 24/2013 or its secondary decrees should state that electricity discharged from an EV battery is an authorised form of generation or storage behind the connection point, provided that certified bidirectional equipment is used and that energy is traded through an authorised supplier or aggregator. This single clarification would unlock producer registration for public chargers above 100 kW and allow smaller V2G points to operate under the simplified compensation scheme until more sophisticated remuneration is available. In parallel, the draft royal decree on electricity supply and contracting must be finalised and enacted without dilution. Clear licensing, balancing responsibility and settlement rules for independent aggregators will let fleets of EVs combine their capacity and bid into balancing, capacity and local flexibility markets. Deadlines for CNMC implementation should be fixed and short (for example six months) to avoid the present slide toward 2026 commercial entry.

Technical regulation must catch up. The low-voltage code ITC-BT-52 should be revised to include reverse-power protection tests, battery degradation criteria and cybersecurity assessments, and it should reference ISO 15118-20 and IEC 61851-24 explicitly. The Ministry could mandate ENAC-accredited laboratories to certify V2G chargers, creating a recognised conformity mark that installers and distributors can trust. Once the standard exists, MOVES-style grants should carry a bonus percentage for chargers bearing that mark, steering subsidies toward future-proof infrastructure. Market signals also need adjustment, dynamic network tariffs—already possible under the CNMC’s tariff methodology—should be published for small prosumers so that the price difference between export at peak hours and import at trough hours is wide enough to reward daily cycling. Introducing a storage-neutral capacity market or a flexibility tender, as envisaged in the Energy Storage Strategy, would provide longer-term revenue certainty and align V2G with planned large-scale BESS deployment. Any capacity contract should accept aggregated resources down to a few kilowatts, placing EVs on an equal footing with stationary batteries.

A central data hub run by Red Eléctrica, as outlined in the aggregator decree, must expose real-time meter data, validated baselines and settlement results through open APIs so that EMSPs can automate bidding and invoicing. Privacy safeguards from the data-protection law should be transposed into specific consent and revocation procedures for EV users, while consumer-protection clauses in RD 184/2022 should be extended to cover discharge transactions, battery health guarantees and dispute resolution. Finally, pilots must be scaled methodically. The five flexibility sandboxes approved

in March 2025 should publish open technical reports, and MITECO should launch a second call that focuses specifically on V2G aggregation in urban distribution grids. Lessons from these projects should feed directly into the update of the National Energy and Climate Plan.

If Spain enacts these measures swiftly and coherently, the country can turn its growing EV fleet into a distributed storage asset that supports renewable integration, offers new revenue to consumers and strengthens grid resilience—transforming today’s experimental V2G pilots into a bankable main-stream service within the decade.

7

Socio-Economic and Business Model Analysis

The successful deployment of Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technologies depends not only on technical maturity and regulatory frameworks but also on the socio-economic conditions and viable business models across the regions where these systems are implemented [215]. As part of the NEVERFLAT project, which aims to develop low-cost, low-power, and publicly accessible V2G charging infrastructure in both urban and rural environments, it is essential to assess the diversity of user profiles, economic barriers, and regional dynamics that may influence system acceptance and market success.

V2G technologies enable bidirectional energy flows between electric vehicles (EVs) and the power grid, transforming vehicles into distributed energy resources that can support grid stability, enable renewable integration, and create new value streams. According to recent market studies [216], the global bi-directional EV charger market was valued at approximately USD 1.4 billion in 2023 and is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of over 22.8% from 2024 to 2032. This surge is primarily driven by increasing EV adoption, government incentives, and a growing demand for advanced grid services.

In 2023 alone, nearly 14 million electric cars were registered worldwide, bringing the global EV fleet to over 40 million units. This marks a 35% year-over-year increase, demonstrating strong consumer demand and the accelerated transition to sustainable mobility. As more users and institutions adopt EVs for environmental, financial, and regulatory reasons, the demand for bi-directional charging infrastructure becomes increasingly relevant [217].

7.1 Methodology

The socio-economic and business model analysis presented in this section was developed through a multi-step, qualitative methodology designed to identify key factors, barriers, and opportunities for the large-scale deployment of public-access V2G infrastructure across diverse European regions. The methodology followed the sequential logic outlined below:

State-of-the-Art Review A comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify the main socio-economic variables influencing the adoption of V2G technologies. This included factors such as affordability, infrastructure availability, user demographics, and public perception. The review also examined existing challenges to business development in this domain and the types of value-added benefits V2G can provide to users, communities, and energy systems. Special attention was given to the typology of existing business models associated with V2G, covering actors involved, revenue streams, and context-specific applicability.

Regional Contextual Analysis Based on the insights from the literature, a contextual assessment was conducted for the three pilot regions of the NEVERFLAT project (Germany, Romania, and Spain). This analysis aimed to identify region-specific socio-economic conditions, infrastructure readiness, user profiles, and regulatory environments that influence V2G viability. The goal was to pinpoint localized barriers and enablers for inclusive and sustainable business models.

Benchmarking of Real-World Pilots A targeted benchmark analysis was carried out by selecting a set of representative V2G pilot projects—mainly within the European Union and the countries involved in NEVERFLAT. Each case study was analysed across multiple dimensions, including business logic, actors involved, user engagement, revenue mechanisms, and social impact. Lessons learned and key enabling factors were extracted for the design of the NEVERFLAT business models.

Gap Identification and Opportunity Mapping By synthesizing findings from the literature, regional context, and benchmark cases, the analysis identified systemic gaps, unmet user needs, and strategic opportunities for intervention. This step aimed to align the business logic of the project with both market realities and socio-environmental goals.

Recommendations for Action Finally, the methodology culminated in a set of strategic recommendations for the development of equitable, scalable, and context-aware business models for NEVERFLAT. These recommendations are designed to guide upcoming pilot activities, stakeholder engagement strategies, and the overall refinement of the V2G deployment framework.

This structured approach ensured that the analysis remains grounded in both theoretical understanding and real-world practice, providing a robust foundation for advancing the project's vision of inclusive, low-cost, and low-power V2G infrastructure across Europe.

7.2 State of the Art Analysis

7.2.1 Socioeconomic Factors Influencing V2G Adoption

The deployment and acceptance of V2G technologies are shaped by a diverse set of socioeconomic factors that influence user behaviour, investment decisions, and regional adoption rates. Understanding these variables is essential for tailoring infrastructure and service models that align with real-world usage patterns and societal needs.

Affordability, Investment Barriers and Revenues One of the main challenges to widespread V2G adoption is the high initial investment required, which includes both the cost of V2G-compatible

EVs and the associated charging infrastructure. These financial barriers are often amplified by user concerns about battery degradation and uncertainty regarding return on investment (ROI). Studies show that such perceived risks may discourage adoption, particularly among risk-averse or lower-income users [218]. However, recent evidence suggests that a large portion of EV drivers are willing to participate in V2G, primarily driven by financial incentives. In a stated intention study with over 1,000 participants in Germany, Bakhuis et al. (2025) found that 42% of users expressed a positive willingness to engage in V2G schemes, with nearly half identifying economic compensation as the main motivator—well ahead of grid stability or environmental concerns [219].

User Demographics and Geographic Distribution Electric vehicle ownership across Europe is unevenly distributed, with higher penetration in urban and peri-urban areas—especially in Northern and Western countries of Europe where purchasing power is higher. Middle- to high-income households dominate EV adoption, while rural areas—despite offering ideal dwell times for V2G services—exhibit lower adoption rates and infrastructure availability [220]. In general terms, the uptake of EVs is subject to demographic factors such as elder users (55+) tend to adopt EVs at higher rates in several EU countries, possibly due to greater financial stability and reduced sensitivity to range limitations [221]. However, disparities in EV adoption are also gender related. These disparities are not exclusive to EV or V2G technologies but rather reflect broader patterns in car usage. According to Sovacool et al. (2019), women tend to be more environmentally conscious and show stronger preferences for sustainable mobility solutions, which contributes to their greater acceptance of innovations such as V2G [222].

Social Equity, Energy Poverty and Inclusive Access The deployment of V2G infrastructure presents an opportunity to address structural inequalities in energy access and mobility. In regions affected by energy poverty or limited public transport, V2G-enabled EVs—especially when deployed in shared or community-based schemes—can provide dual benefits: access to affordable mobility and the ability to store and use energy flexibly. Community-owned EV pools or cooperatives may widen access to bidirectional charging benefits for groups traditionally excluded from the EV transition, including carless households or low-income families. A notable example is the UK-based VECTORS project, which explores how V2G and V2X technologies can be leveraged at the community level—including in rural areas—to enhance energy resilience, flexibility, and local ownership of energy systems [223]. Embedding equity considerations into V2G deployment strategies can help bridge the urban–rural divide and support a just energy transition. Nevertheless, recent research from the Nordic context highlights that without careful policy design, V2G and electric mobility systems may inadvertently reinforce social and spatial inequalities. As Sovacool et al. (2019) argue, such systems may erode distributive and procedural justice if they remain accessible only to wealthier users or ignore rural and marginalized communities. These findings underscore the importance of embedding equity safeguards and inclusive participation frameworks in all phases of V2G deployment [224].

Access to Charging Infrastructure The viability of V2G is closely linked to the availability and accessibility of charging stations. Inadequate spatial distribution, limited charger availability, and restrictions on access times contribute to user dissatisfaction and “range anxiety.” For V2G systems—where vehicles need to remain connected for extended periods—these challenges become even more pronounced. Studies show that user preferences lean toward flexible, conveniently located, and

user-friendly charging options, and any deficiency in these areas diminishes the attractiveness of V2G participation [225].

Mobility Patterns and Daily Routines Daily travel behaviour significantly influences the potential for vehicles to provide grid services. Research from Denmark and Norway indicates that vehicles parked during working hours or in residential settings with long dwell times present higher potential for effective V2G integration. Conversely, irregular or long-distance commuting limits V2G participation opportunities [226]. These insights underscore the importance of aligning infrastructure planning with real-world mobility profiles.

Awareness and Acceptance of V2G Public awareness of Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology in Germany has increased in recent years. According to the EAFO Consumer Monitor (2023), 41% of German EV drivers are familiar with V2G, and 66% expressed interest in owning a V2G-compatible vehicle [227]. While lack of awareness is no longer the primary barrier, knowledge gaps remain, particularly regarding the technical and economic implications. More prominently, concerns about battery degradation continue to affect user acceptance. Even among informed users, uncertainty about battery wear due to bidirectional charging remains a key factor influencing adoption decisions [228]. This perception is not unfounded. A cost-benefit analysis by Ahmadian et al. (2017) shows that battery degradation significantly reduces the net economic benefits of V2G participation, especially when no financial compensation mechanisms are in place. Their findings highlight that without proper incentives or warranties, the economic burden of battery aging may outweigh the expected gains from grid services [229]. Targeted information campaigns, user-friendly interfaces, and compensation schemes addressing battery longevity concerns are therefore essential to build trust and support wider acceptance of V2G systems.

7.2.2 Business Barriers to Public V2G Infrastructure Deployment

Despite the technical potential and policy interest surrounding V2G systems, several economic and business-related challenges limit their viability in public-access contexts. These barriers must be carefully addressed to ensure scalable, sustainable, and profitable deployment.

Low Throughput vs. V2G Dwell Time In the context of public charging infrastructure, throughput refers to the amount of energy delivered and the number of users served over a given time. High throughput—meaning frequent user turnover and fast charging sessions—is typically necessary for operators to maximize revenue and justify investment costs. However, V2G services require vehicles to remain connected for longer durations to provide grid services such as frequency regulation, voltage control, or peak shaving. This extended dwell time reduces user turnover and leads to lower energy throughput, challenging the profitability of conventional public charging business models. The resulting tension between the need for long connection times (essential for V2G) and the economics of high-turnover charging stations creates operational inefficiencies that hinder the commercial scalability of public V2G infrastructure [218].

High Installation and Operational Costs V2G-enabled chargers demand more advanced hardware—such as bidirectional inverters and communication modules—as well as potential grid reinforcements. These systems also face more complex certification and compliance requirements compared

to standard unidirectional charging. As a result, capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operational expenditures (OPEX) are currently higher.

Uncertain and Fragmented Revenue Streams A major economic barrier to the deployment of public-access V2G infrastructure is the lack of stable and predictable revenue models. Access to ancillary service markets, tariff structures for energy resale, and compensation mechanisms for flexibility services vary widely across EU member states. In many cases, participation is restricted to large-scale actors, excluding small aggregators and early-stage pilots. This regulatory fragmentation and limited monetization framework introduce uncertainty, making it difficult for investors and operators to build solid business cases around V2G services. Until transparent and accessible remuneration schemes are implemented, revenue uncertainty will continue to constrain broader adoption [230].

Early Adopter Disadvantage Like other network-dependent innovations, V2G technology exhibits characteristics of a network good—its overall value increases as more users participate. According to Grajek and Kretschmer (2008), once a critical mass of early adopters is reached, adoption tends to follow an exponential curve, accelerating rapidly toward market saturation. However, V2G has not yet crossed this threshold. Early adopters today often face higher relative costs, greater technological uncertainty, and limited access to services or compatible vehicles. These disadvantages reduce short-term returns and can dampen enthusiasm, slowing broader market uptake. Additionally, the current vehicle market remains constrained: many of the most popular EV models still do not support bidirectional charging, further limiting participation and delaying network effects [218].

Standardization and Interoperability Gaps V2G deployment is also challenged by the fragmented landscape of technical standards. Although ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1 offer a foundation for interoperability, implementation across EU countries remains inconsistent. Varying grid codes, certification procedures, and data exchange protocols increase integration costs and inhibit cross-border scalability. Harmonizing technical and regulatory standards is thus a critical enabler for future business viability [231].

Battery Warranty and Residual Value Risk Battery degradation remains a critical barrier to V2G adoption, especially from the perspective of private users and fleet operators. Many original equipment manufacturer (OEM) warranties do not currently cover degradation linked to V2G cycling, which creates uncertainty around residual vehicle value and long-term costs. While battery aging is primarily driven by calendar effects, studies show that participation in V2G can increase cyclic degradation by up to 10 percentage points over a 10-year period, raising total degradation from 10–15% to 20–25% under typical usage scenarios. This performance decline—albeit moderate—has direct economic implications. Modelling efforts estimate that financial compensation of €132/MWh (2030 scenario) or €70/MWh (2050 scenario) would be required to offset degradation-related costs for users. In the absence of such mechanisms, the risk of voided warranties and reduced resale value may discourage participation, particularly among cost-sensitive users [232]. To overcome this barrier, emerging solutions such as cycle-based insurance schemes or OEM-backed V2G warranties are gaining relevance. These mechanisms could help de-risk participation and create the confidence needed to attract early adopters and scale viable business models.

Regulatory Constraints and Market Access Although regulatory aspects are addressed in detail elsewhere in this document, it is important to emphasize that market access rules remain a critical bottleneck for many V2G business models. Current frameworks in several EU countries require a minimum capacity of 1 MW or more to participate, a threshold rarely reached by public-access V2G charging sites in early deployment stages.

7.2.3 Advantages and Benefits of V2G Implementation

Beyond the technical and regulatory challenges, the successful deployment of V2G infrastructure offers a range of economic, social, and environmental benefits. These advantages serve as key incentives for stakeholders—governments, grid operators, users, and communities—to invest in and support the integration of V2G systems.

Enhanced Grid Flexibility and Stability V2G technology enables electric vehicles (EVs) to act as distributed energy storage units, discharging electricity back to the grid during peak demand and storing it during periods of surplus. This bidirectional capability supports grid balancing, frequency regulation, and voltage control. It reduces the need for additional generation capacity and improves overall system efficiency. Pilot projects such as the Parker Project in Denmark have demonstrated that aggregated EV fleets can reliably deliver ancillary services and reduce grid strain, especially in regions with high renewable penetration [154]. Recent prospective life cycle assessments highlight that V2G charging can accelerate the integration of renewables and improve system efficiency in the medium term (2030–2035). In Germany, modelling shows that aggregated BEVs operating under V2G schemes could replace up to 117 GWh of stationary battery storage while lowering grid emission peaks and supporting faster decarbonization [233]. These benefits are particularly relevant in cost-optimized electricity systems aiming for high shares of solar and wind generation.

Facilitation of Renewable Energy Integration One of the major challenges in integrating intermittent renewable sources like wind and solar is managing variability in supply. V2G systems provide an effective solution by storing excess renewable generation and discharging it when production drops. In the Netherlands, Renault’s V2G partnership with the Utrecht car-sharing fleet is expected to provide up to 10% of the city’s flexibility needs, directly enhancing the stability of the local energy system and supporting higher shares of renewables [234].

Potential Revenue Streams for Users and Communities Once adequate frameworks are in place, V2G can offer additional income sources to EV owners and local aggregators. Users can earn compensation by participating in flexibility markets or through dynamic tariffs that reward energy discharge during high-demand periods. In France, for example, Renault and The Mobility House launched a program allowing users to sell stored energy back to the grid, helping offset charging costs and providing modest economic returns [235]. These financial incentives could play a significant role in improving affordability and encouraging participation, especially in low-income or rural areas.

Social and Environmental Equity If deployed with equity-oriented policies, V2G infrastructure has the potential to address longstanding disparities in energy access and mobility. The decentralized nature of V2G provides an opportunity to rethink energy access and equity. By enabling

households and small communities to participate actively in energy markets, V2G can contribute to reducing energy poverty and democratizing access to clean energy services. If deployed with inclusive policies, V2G infrastructure can prioritize underserved areas and ensure benefits are distributed equitably across regions, regardless of income or geographic location.

Support for Energy Security and Emergency Resilience V2G-capable EVs can serve as mobile energy reserves in emergency situations, providing backup power to critical facilities such as hospitals, shelters, or communication infrastructure. In Spain, the V2G Balearic Islands pilot led by ACCIONA Energía connected 16 bidirectional charging points and 8 EVs across various commercial partners. The system enabled energy dispatch back to the grid or directly to buildings during peak periods or outages, enhancing resilience and reducing dependency on fossil-fuel backup systems [236].

Contribution to Decarbonization Goals In addition to user-level gains, system-wide modelling suggests that BEVs with V2G can substantially reduce operational emissions—by as much as 200% in net terms—through strategic discharge into the grid during high-emission periods. These savings not only improve the life-cycle GHG profile of EVs but also shorten their environmental break-even point compared to internal combustion vehicles [233].

7.2.4 Typology of V2G Business Models

Table 7.1: *Types of V2G business model*

Model Type	Description	Key Actors	Revenue Sources	Applicability
Peer-to-Peer [237], [238]	EV users interact directly or via platforms with the grid to sell stored energy.	EV owners, DSOs, energy retailers	Time-of-use tariffs, local grid services, energy trading	Residential, semi-public chargers
Aggregator-Based [138], [239]	Aggregators pool EVs and offer services to the grid or energy markets	Aggregators, fleets, TSOs, market operators	Ancillary services, flexibility markets	Scalable, commercial/residential fleets
Fleet Operator [236], [240], [241]	Fleet managers monetize energy flexibility and manage charging cycles	Fleet operators, service providers	Ancillary services, peak shaving, operational cost savings	Public, logistics, company and industrial site fleets
Community-Based [223], [242]	Local communities share energy using V2G with equity and resilience goals.	Cooperatives, municipalities, prosumers	Shared tariffs, local flexibility markets, collective savings	Energy communities, rural/urban settings

Model Type	Description	Key Actors	Revenue Sources	Applicability
Subscription/ Energy-as-a- Service [243], [244]	Customers pay a fixed (usually monthly or annual) fee for bundled V2G-enabled charging, grid participation services, smart energy management, and software.	OEMs, energy retailers, smart-charging aggregators	Subscription fees, charging optimization, grid service credits	Private homeowners with V2G-capable EVs and home chargers
Battery-Leasing & Co-Ownership [245]–[247]	The EV battery is leased separately or co-owned by the user and a third party. This allows decoupling the vehicle's traction value from its grid-service potential, enabling tailored V2G participation.	OEMs, leasing companies, utilities, aggregators	Battery lease payments, grid services, lifecycle management revenue	V2G-focused EV models, fleets, lower-income user segments
Car-sharing V2G [234], [248]	Shared EV fleets maximise plug-in dwell time and optimise bidirectional charging for grid services.	Car share operators	Grid services, energy cost savings, shared asset value	Car sharing, municipal shared fleets
Micro-mobility & Heavy-duty V2X [249], [250]	Electric school buses, delivery trucks, and medium-/heavy-duty fleets provide high-capacity, depot-based V2X services. Their predictable schedules and long idle periods make them ideal for grid balancing, peak shaving, and emergency backup.	Fleet operators, city councils, OEMs, utilities, V2G aggregators	Ancillary services, peak shaving, infrastructure cost deferral	Bus depots, delivery/logistics hubs, city fleets

7.3 Regional Context Analysis

This section provides a contextual overview of the current state of EV adoption, charging infrastructure, and socioeconomic conditions in the three NEVERFLAT pilot countries: Germany, Romania, and Spain. The analysis focuses on the key enablers and barriers for V2G deployment in each region, highlighting both structural conditions and public perception factors.

7.3.1 Germany

Germany remains a European leader in electric vehicle (EV) adoption, driven by industrial capacity, proactive climate policies, and an expanding charging infrastructure. However, the deployment of advanced charging technologies such as Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) is still limited by regulatory uncertainty, regional inequalities, and low public awareness.

Infrastructure and Deployment Landscape As of February 2025, Germany has over 161,000 public charging points, marking a significant increase over recent years. The federal government aims to reach one million chargers by 2030. Deployment is highly concentrated in southern states like Bavaria and Baden-Württemberg, while eastern and rural areas lag behind. This regional disparity creates imbalances in EV accessibility and V2G readiness [251].

Policy and Regulatory Environment As discussed in Section 6.3.2, Germany lacks a fully operational regulatory framework for bidirectional charging and small-scale aggregator participation, which limits the scalability of low-power V2G business models. The absence of defined tariff structures and fiscal incentives, along with fragmented certification procedures, creates uncertainty for both users and market actors [252]. This regulatory immaturity discourages public adoption and prevents operators from capturing value through grid services—particularly in residential or small commercial settings [253]. Recent studies further highlight the unviable economics of V2G under current conditions, such as asymmetric pricing and high levies on re-injected energy [254].

Socioeconomic and Regional Factors Adoption patterns vary across states. Wealthier regions with stronger policy support show higher EV penetration, while less affluent or rural areas face barriers due to cost, access to infrastructure, and limited public transport alternatives. This deepens the mobility and energy divide between urban and rural communities.

Public Awareness and Acceptance Germany demonstrates a comparatively high level of public awareness and interest in V2G technology among Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV) drivers. According to the 2023 EAFO Consumer Monitor, 41% of German BEV drivers are familiar with V2G, and 66% express interest in purchasing a V2G-capable vehicle. The primary motivations for considering a V2G-capable vehicle include the ability to use the vehicle's battery to power their home (e.g., for heating, appliances) and the expectation of a purchase price comparable to their current BEV. However, concerns persist regarding battery degradation and system complexity, particularly among less technologically engaged or older user segments [227]. These findings suggest a solid foundation for public engagement with V2G technology in Germany. To capitalize on this interest, it is essential to implement educational initiatives and establish transparent remuneration schemes that address consumer concerns and highlight the benefits of V2G integration. Complementary qualitative research reinforces the importance of user-centric design and communication. A review by Fraunhofer ISI underlines the relevance of environmental attitudes, trust in technology, and clarity about user benefits as key factors in social acceptance. Similarly, recent studies on V2G-enabled carsharing indicate that when V2G services are bundled with visible advantages—such as energy compensation or enhanced convenience—they become more attractive to potential users. These insights point to the value of targeted outreach strategies and business models that emphasize simplicity, sustainability, and economic co-benefits [255], [248].

Opportunities for Deployment Despite the challenges, Germany presents strong foundations for V2G integration:

Renewable balancing: V2G offers grid flexibility as Germany increases its share of intermittent renewable energy.

Urban fleet aggregation: Public and commercial fleets with predictable schedules are ideal testbeds for V2G business models.

Industrial partnerships: OEMs and energy providers are already launching pilots. For example, Honda's V2G integration into a virtual power plant demonstrates V2G's role in grid stability.

Standardization leadership: Germany's role in defining EU-wide standards places it in a strong position to shape future V2G protocols.

To realize this potential, Germany will need to accelerate regulatory adaptation, promote public communication around V2G benefits, and ensure regional equity in infrastructure deployment.

7.3.2 Romania

Romania's electric vehicle (EV) market is gradually expanding, supported by public incentives and EU policy alignment. However, its full potential remains constrained by infrastructure gaps, socioeconomic limitations, regulatory uncertainty, and low public awareness. These challenges are particularly pronounced outside major urban areas, affecting both the pace and equity of EV adoption and the future viability of Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technologies [256].

Infrastructure and Deployment Landscape Romania's public charging infrastructure expanded by 50% in 2023, reaching a vehicle-to-charger ratio of 14.2—slightly better than the EU average. Growth was driven by government initiatives such as the Electric Up programme and private sector investment, with a notable increase in fast chargers (150 kW+), now twice as common as the EU average. However, charging points remain highly concentrated in urban areas, with rural and highway coverage still underdeveloped. Although 87% of EV users report improved access, over half cite insufficient infrastructure as a barrier. To meet its national target of 30,000 chargers by 2026, Romania must accelerate deployments and ensure more balanced geographic distribution [257].

Policy and Regulatory Environment While Romania has implemented foundational EV policies—including the transposition of EU directives on alternative fuels and the obligation to pre-install EV charging infrastructure in buildings—no dedicated legal framework exists yet for bidirectional charging or aggregator market access. As outlined in Section 7.2.4, this regulatory gap hinders V2G business models, particularly those relying on pooled flexibility or participation in balancing markets. Without legal recognition or tariff structures for small-scale grid injection, V2G-based services remain economically and operationally constrained.

Socioeconomic and Regional Factors Affordability remains a major hurdle for EV adoption in Romania. A 2023 PLS-SEM study of 413 Romanian drivers found that economic barriers—particularly high purchase costs and limited disposable income—significantly reduce both the intention to use and the actual usage of EVs [258]. Another 2023 survey of 545 Romanian consumers confirms that

educated, middle-aged males with higher incomes are the primary adopters, driven by environmental concerns and economic incentives [259]. This uneven demographic uptake has a spatial dimension: rural areas exhibit much lower EV penetration, correlated with weaker infrastructure and lower purchasing power—factors that reinforce existing inequalities [258]. The disparity in income levels further exacerbates this divide, making EV adoption, and by extension V2G access, less viable in less affluent regions.

Public Awareness and Acceptance Consumer awareness and acceptance of EV and V2G technologies in Romania remains limited, especially outside urban centres. Research by Türkeş & Acatrinei (2024) identifies low familiarity with government incentives and lack of knowledge about EV benefits as significant barriers, and energy saving awareness campaigns are suggested as effective interventions. On the other hand, the environmental effects of EVs are shown as a favourable factor [258]. According to a sociological survey, only 16% of Romanians consider buying an EV within one year, and 58% explicitly reject the idea, citing high initial costs, low availability of public charging and concerns about battery life [260].

Opportunities for Deployment Despite the current limitations, Romania presents important long-term opportunities for V2G development:

Urban public charging: Growing EV adoption in major cities offers an entry point for low-power V2G integration in municipal fleets and public access points.

Upcoming regulatory frameworks: Romania's evolving EV policies and EU alignment provide an opportunity to incorporate legal recognition for small-scale flexibility services and aggregator participation.

Equity-oriented use cases: In rural or underserved regions, public V2G infrastructure can support resilience, especially if linked to energy communities or shared mobility services.

Rising user interest: Environmental motivations and gradual increases in EV literacy suggest that targeted awareness campaigns could foster early V2G acceptance among key user groups.

With policy adaptation and inclusive planning, Romania could lay the groundwork for scalable, publicly accessible V2G solutions.

7.3.3 Spain

Spain has made notable strides in the electrification of transport over the past five years, driven by EU recovery funds, targeted subsidies, and an updated national climate and energy strategy. Despite this progress, structural and socioeconomic asymmetries continue to hinder the widespread deployment of advanced charging technologies such as V2G, particularly in rural and low-income areas [227].

Infrastructure and Deployment Asymmetries As of June 1, 2025, Spain boasts approximately 46,700 active public charging points, marking a 2.9% increase since the end of 2024; this growth trend is driven primarily by utilities and startups expanding high- and ultrahighpower stations (50–250 kW up by 61%, and >250 kW up by 39%) to support long-distance travel along major corridors

[208]. Despite this surge, infrastructure remains unevenly distributed: densely populated urban centres such as Madrid, Barcelona, and coastal regions host the majority, while inland and rural areas lag significantly in charger density (2 chargers per 9 km²) [261]. Additionally, while legal reforms (Royal Decrees 29/2021 and 5/2023) aim to simplify installation and ensure interoperability, persistent delays in municipal permitting and constraints in grid capacity continue to hamper deployment, particularly in low-density regions [262]. Lastly, Spain is home to its first industrial-scale V2G pilot—the “V2G Balearic Islands” project, featuring 16 bidirectional chargers and 8 EVs across eight businesses, backed by NextGenerationEU funding [263].

Policy Environment and Regulatory Gaps As explored in Section 6.2.5, current Spanish regulation imposes clear constraints on V2G business models: no legal recognition for aggregators or low-power V2G systems (<100 kW), excluding them from markets for flexibility or energy resale [264]. Consequently, business models relying on aggregated flexibility or revenue from energy trading are currently unfeasible. While draft regulations (e.g. the National Energy and Climate Plan and the Energy Storage Strategy plan to integrate V2G into grid stability services) signal upcoming integration of flexibility services—including V2G participation—Spanish policy remains in a transitional phase pending full market access implementation [265]. Similarly, this lack of V2G promotion policies limits the uptake and equitable deployment in Spanish territories.

Socioeconomic and Regional Disparities Two recent studies shed light on the diversity among Spanish EV users. Esteves et al. (2021) found that while men generally show stronger EV preference, low-income older women are the most EV-aware demographic, driven by sustainability concerns and driving experience [266]. The 2025 study also confirms younger users are more receptive to EV use, though cost and infrastructural barriers persist, but importantly higher income levels are a significant predictor of adoption, emphasizing that EV uptake remains skewed toward wealthier households [267]. Energy poverty disproportionately affects rural and lower-income communities in Spain, with approximately 9% of the population unable to adequately heat their homes, a rate higher than in urban areas [268]. This creates a double barrier: limited EV ownership and minimal access to charging—let alone V2G infrastructure—in these regions. However, there is growing evidence that community energy systems integrating V2G can enhance both energy equity and rural resilience. A 2024 Spain-specific study illustrates how nation-wide V2G-supported renewables can stabilize the grid, reduce costs, and bolster underserved regions [269].

Awareness and Public Acceptance Public awareness of V2G remains limited. A 2023 EAFO study revealed that only 11% of Spanish battery-electric vehicle (BEV) drivers were familiar with V2G, even though 68% expressed interest in acquiring a V2G-compatible vehicle [227]. These findings are based on a small sample size (37 respondents) and should be interpreted with caution. Nonetheless, concerns about battery degradation and lack of economic clarity remain common deterrents to adoption.

Opportunities for Deployment Despite the current limitations, Spain presents several promising pathways for V2G integration:

Urban fleet electrification: Public transport operators and municipal fleets in major cities—such as Madrid or Barcelona—can act as early adopters, leveraging high dwell times and political backing

for clean mobility. **Energy communities:** The regulatory framework enabling energy communities offers a foundation for V2G deployment in collective ownership models, particularly in rural or underserved regions.

Grid flexibility and storage goals: National plans envision increasing storage capacity and integrating distributed flexibility—making Spain a strong candidate for V2G-linked balancing services in the medium term.

Renewable energy integration: With Spain’s growing solar capacity and V2G’s ability to absorb excess generation, the country is well-positioned to pilot models coupling bidirectional charging with local renewable systems.

7.4 Benchmark of V2G Business Models

7.4.1 Introduction and Methodological Approach

This section provides a benchmark analysis of selected real-world Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) business models implemented across Europe and beyond. The objective is to identify patterns, critical success factors, and transferable elements that may guide the design of a value-added, scalable, and socially inclusive business model for NEVERFLAT.

The benchmark prioritizes initiatives developed in the project’s pilot countries—Germany, Romania, and Spain—where national contexts directly influence deployment feasibility. Additional case studies from comparable EU countries or international markets are included where they demonstrate innovative or contextually relevant approaches. All cases were selected based on their operational maturity, data availability, and potential alignment with NEVERFLAT’s scope: **public-access, low-cost, slow-charging V2G infrastructure** in both urban and rural settings.

Each case study is analysed through the following dimensions:

- i Project context and objectives
- ii Business model and actors involved
- iii Revenue mechanisms
- iv Regulatory and technical framework
- v User engagement and social impact
- vi Barriers faced and lessons learned

The comparative analysis aims to extract replicable components and highlight elements that can differentiate NEVERFLAT’s model in terms of accessibility, equity, and regional adaptability.

7.4.2 Case Study Analysis

The following section presents a structured overview of seven real-world V2G pilot projects selected based on their contextual relevance, technical maturity, and potential transferability to the NEVERFLAT framework. Each case is analysed across common dimensions to extract comparable insights and support the design of an inclusive, scalable business model for public-access V2G infrastructure.

Table 7.2: Nissan-TenneT V2G Pilot

Project Name	1. Nissan–TenneT V2G Pilot
Location	Germany – North-South power corridor
Main actors	Nissan (OEM), TenneT (TSO), The Mobility House (aggregator), German Ministry - SINTEG
Market status	Pre-commercial pilot (regulatory sandbox)
Context / Environment	Fleet-based, industrial/urban
Technical basis	CHAdeMO bidirectional chargers, EMS ChargePilot®

This pilot, part of Germany’s programme, aimed to demonstrate how bidirectional EVs could balance regional renewable surpluses by transferring wind energy from northern to southern Germany. **The business model** involved aggregating fleet vehicles into a virtual power plant controlled by a ChargePilot®(Energy Management System), with simulated system-level benefits such as redispatch cost reduction. While no **direct revenues** have yet been generated for users, the model highlighted future flexibility income potential. **From a regulatory perspective**, the pilot operated in a sandbox but revealed gaps, including the lack of recognition of EVs as grid assets and the limited availability of bidirectional functionality in CCS (Combined Charging System)-based charging systems, which remains a barrier to wider standardisation. **User interaction was minimal**, as it targeted commercial fleets, proved to work without technical failures and with no impact on driver behaviour. The main **barriers** were regulatory immaturity and limited market mechanisms, yet the project offered clear lessons about the feasibility of system-wide V2G aggregation and the importance of OEM – TSO collaboration [270].

Table 7.3: Iasi V2G Pilot

Project Name	Iasi V2G Pilot
Location	Romania – City of Iași (urban context)
Main actors	Iași City Council (promoter), Honojuli (charger supplier), local grid operator
Market status	Early-stage pilot (announced in 2023, deployment underway)
Context / Environment	Public-access charging, residential/urban
Technical basis	50 bidirectional chargers, V2G-enabled EVs (model unspecified)

The Iasi pilot is Romania’s first publicly promoted V2G project and involves installing 50 bidirectional charging stations to allow EVs to feed electricity back into the grid during peak demand. **The business model** anticipates user compensation for flexibility services, with early reports suggesting drivers could earn up to €120/month by participating. While real-world revenue streams remain unverified, the project’s vision aligns with emerging aggregator-based schemes. **On the regulatory and technical side**, Romania lacks a formal V2G framework, and the pilot thus operates in an exploratory phase, potentially helping to shape future policy. **User engagement** is a central component, targeting private EV owners and promoting V2G participation as a way to reduce energy costs. Among the **main challenges** are regulatory uncertainty, low EV penetration, and limited public awareness of V2G, yet the project represents a key step in testing scalable, citizen-facing V2G integration in Eastern Europe [271].

Table 7.4: V2G Balearic Islands - Acciona Energy Pilot

Project Name	V2G Balearic Islands - Acciona Energy Pilot
Location	Spain – Mallorca, Menorca, Ibiza (semi-rural, island context)
Main actors	Acciona Energía, 8 local businesses and entities, IDAE (support/funding)
Market status	Operational pilot (launched 2022) with active field testing
Context / Environment	Distributed public/private charging, industrial, tourism, rural mix
Technical basis	16 V2G smart chargers, 8 bidirectional EVs (model unspecified), solar PV integration

This pilot, launched by Acciona Energy, deployed 16 smart V2G charging points across several Balearic locations, pairing them with 8 bidirectional EVs provided to diverse participants such as SMEs (Small and Medium-size Enterprises), cooperatives, and a rural hotel. One of the aims is to obtain mobility patterns for each of the vehicles associated with companies in different sectors. **The business model** explores self-consumption optimisation and grid services, with energy being stored from solar PV and re-injected during peak demand or local outages. Revenues are expected through reduced energy bills and potential participation in flexibility markets. **From a regulatory and technical standpoint**, the project operates within current Spanish norms but contributes data for the emerging national framework on V2G. **User involvement** is high, with various real-world actors participating (from farms to social businesses), enabling a socially diverse testbed. The main **barriers** identified include limited interoperability across vehicles, user familiarity with V2G technologies, and the need for clear economic incentives—but the pilot demonstrates a modular, scalable model with strong applicability to rural and semi-urban areas [263].

Table 7.5: Scale-Up GridPilot – Avesa & City of Madrid

Project Name	Scale-Up GridPilot – Avesa & City of Madrid
Location	Spain – Madrid (urban mobility hub)
Main actors	Avesa (tech integrator), City of Madrid, EU Scale-Up consortium
Market status	Pilot phase under H2020 Scale-Up (2021–2024)
Context / Environment	Public-access charging in park-and-ride facility
Technical basis	Bidirectional chargers + AI-based energy management system (<i>GridPilot</i>)

GridPilot is a public-access V2G demonstrator integrated into a long-stay park-and-ride facility in Madrid as part of the EU-funded Scale-Up project. **The goal** is to optimise charging and discharging based on grid needs, energy prices, and vehicle availability using artificial intelligence. **The business model** combines dynamic pricing, shared user benefits, and energy resale to the grid or building, though monetisation mechanisms are still being tested. **Technically**, the system is interoperable and designed for scalability in urban infrastructure. **User participation** is indirect—EV drivers park and plug in, while AI manages V2G activity invisibly. The main **barriers** identified relate to user trust, regulatory restrictions for selling energy from public assets, and the still-maturing national rules for grid services via EVs. However, the pilot highlights the potential for integrating V2G into municipal infrastructure and creating shared economic value through AI-driven optimisation [272].

Table 7.6: *We Drive Solar – Bidirectional City Utrecht*

Project Name	We Drive Solar – Bidirectional City Utrecht
Location	Netherlands – Utrecht (urban neighbourhoods)
Main actors	We Drive Solar (mobility operator), City of Utrecht, Hyundai, <i>Cartesius</i> urban developers
Market status	Operational, ongoing expansion (since 2022)
Context / Environment	Shared mobility and residential solar-powered neighbourhoods
Technical basis	Hyundai IONIQ 5 with V2G, bidirectional public chargers, local PV integration

This project positions Utrecht as the world’s first “bidirectional city,” integrating V2G into its car-sharing system and urban planning. **The objective** is to use shared EVs as mobile energy buffers that absorb and release solar power from the neighbourhood grid. Nowadays, the project continues to grow by increasing the fleet, which is expected to be able to provide 10% of the flexibility needed to balance solar and wind energy at peak-hours. **The business model** is cooperative: vehicles are shared among residents, and energy transactions are managed via the local system operator, with economic and environmental benefits distributed collectively. **Revenue streams** include savings from self-consumption, potential remuneration for grid services, and long-term real estate value enhancement. **Technically**, the project uses CCS-compatible V2G infrastructure and integrates with the city’s renewable energy system. **User** engagement is central—citizens are both drivers and energy participants in this smart city model. Among the **main lessons**, the project demonstrates how V2G can be embedded into urban development and citizen co-ownership schemes, though it still faces challenges around upscaling, tariff regulation, and standardisation across car brands [273].

Table 7.7: *PowerLoop – Domestic V2G Trial (OVO Energy)*

Project Name	PowerLoop – Domestic V2G Trial (OVO Energy)
Location	United Kingdom – residential households (South of England)
Main actors	OVO Energy, Cenex, Indra, Nissan, Kaluza
Market status	Completed pilot (2018–2021), >300 households
Context / Environment	Residential homes with off-street parking
Technical basis	Nissan LEAF + Indra V2G chargers + Kaluza EMS platform

PowerLoop was the UK’s first large-scale domestic and private V2G trial focused on individual EV owners using their vehicles to support the grid from home. The project **aimed** to test user behaviour, technical performance, and revenue potential for homeowners using V2G-capable vehicles. **The business model** provided a financial incentive, which could save up to £725 per year for flexibility services, while electricity bills were optimised using dynamic time-of-use tariffs. **Regulatory constraints** included limited market access for domestic aggregators and a lack of established grid remuneration pathways, although the project benefited from Ofgem’s (the energy regulator for Great Britain) regulatory sandbox. **Users** played an active role—plugging in nightly and monitoring their contributions via a mobile interface. The pilot confirmed strong interest and acceptability among participants, though some technical issues were noted. **Key lessons** learned include the importance of user education (acceptance of charging time schedules and balancing convenience and benefit), reliable software interfaces, and the need for clearer grid service monetisation for private users in future deployments, all in a mass roll-out [274].

Table 7.8: Parker Project – Technical Validation of V2G

Project Name	Parker Project – Technical Validation of V2G
Location	Denmark – Copenhagen region
Main actors	DTU (Technical University of Denmark), Nuvve, Nissan, Mitsubishi, PSA, Enel X, Insero, Frederiksberg Forsyning
Market status	Completed (2016–2020); pre-commercial pilot with real FCR provision and detailed performance validation
Context / Environment	Utility and municipal fleet testbed providing Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) services; lab testing at DTU for controlled technical benchmarks
Technical basis	CHAdeMO-based DC V2G chargers (Enel X), Nissan e-NV200, Evalia, Mitsubishi Outlander PHEV, PSA iOn; Nuvve aggregation and control platform

The Parker Project aimed to determine whether EVs could technically support the power grid by delivering reliable Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) services without compromising vehicle availability. The business model was built around the aggregation of utility and municipal fleet vehicles via Nuvve’s V2G platform, enabling real-time grid interaction and service provision. Revenues were not directly distributed to drivers but were instead used to calculate the theoretical economic value of FCR, estimated at up to €1,860 per vehicle per year under optimal market participation scenarios. From a regulatory standpoint, the project operated within Denmark’s supportive energy framework, but market integration was limited to test settings without full commercial deployment. User involvement was minimal, as vehicles were operated by institutional fleet managers with low-touch interaction from individual users. Key contribution: Parker stands as one of the earliest and most comprehensive validations of V2G technical feasibility, setting performance benchmarks for future standardisation efforts and demonstrating multi-brand compatibility, operational stability, and the economic potential of fleet-based V2G aggregation [154].

7.4.3 Key Lessons and Strategic Opportunities for NEVERFLAT

The following summary provides a comparative overview of the seven benchmarked V2G pilot projects. Although each case differs in its technological setup, stakeholder ecosystem, and regulatory context, several recurring patterns emerge:

Most projects rely on **multi-actor collaborations**, including OEMs, energy providers, and aggregators.

Revenue models remain in early stages, ranging from simulated grid services to user incentives.

User involvement varies widely—from passive fleet use to active citizen participation.

Common challenges include **regulatory gaps**, **limited standardisation**, and **cost barriers**.

Table 7.9: Summary table of the business model benchmark

PROJECT	MAIN ACTORS	USER INVOLVEMENT	REVENUE MODEL	KEY INSIGHT
NISSAN-TENNET - Germany & Industrial / Fleet	Nissan, TenneT, The Mobility House	Low (fleet-based)	Simulated redispatch cost reduction	Strong TSO integration, proven grid balancing feasibility
IASI PILOT - Romania & Urban / Residential	Iași Council, Honojuli, local DSO	Medium (public targeting)	Projected user compensation (€120/month)	First Romanian V2G pilot, testing compensation and legal adaptations
V2G ISLAS BALEARES - Spain & Rural / SME / Tourism	Acciona Energía, local businesses	High (multi-sector)	Self-consumption & future grid services	Flexible, distributed, rural-friendly V2G with real-world actors
GRIDPILOT (MADRID) - Spain & Urban / Park&Ride	Avesa, City of Madrid, EU Scale-Up	Indirect (parking users)	Dynamic tariffs, building integration	Municipal V2G use case with AI-based optimisation
WE DRIVE SOLAR - Netherlands & Urban / Cooperative	We Drive Solar, Utrecht, Hyundai	High (shared ownership)	Solar storage, energy sharing, grid tie-in	Community-driven V2G tied to urban planning and housing
POWERLOOP (OVO) - United Kingdom & Residential / Homeowners	OVO, Indra, Kaluza, Nissan	High (domestic users)	Monthly incentive + tariff optimisation	Residential V2G with financial reward and behaviour tracking in mass deployment
PARKER PROJECT - Denmark & Utility / Municipal fleet	DTU, Nuove, Nissan, local utilities	Low (technical focus)	Simulated value from grid services	Technically validated V2G for FCR with real-world operation and multi-brand setup

7.5 Identified Challenges and Opportunities

The NEVERFLAT project aims to deploy an innovative, accessible, and scalable V2G charging infrastructure, enabling bidirectional, low-power, low-cost, and public-access solutions in both urban and rural environments. This model must respond not only to technological and economic conditions but also to social, territorial, and regulatory diversity across Europe. This section outlines the core challenges, success factors, and strategic opportunities that should guide the development of the NEVERFLAT business model.

7.5.1 Core Challenges

The analysis reveals a set of interconnected challenges that affect the technical feasibility, market acceptance, and scalability of the envisioned system:

Technological maturity and interoperability: V2G-compatible CCS hardware remains limited in the European market, with CHAdeMO dominating early deployments. The lack of widespread bidirectional vehicle compatibility and standardised communication protocols hampers large-scale interoperability. Integration of advanced features such as Plug&Charge or ISO 15118-20 is still emerging.

Economic uncertainty and viability: Public-access V2G infrastructure faces unclear and often fragmented revenue channels. Monetisation of grid services through aggregators is not uniformly regulated or accessible across countries. CAPEX and OPEX remain relatively high, especially when paired with grid upgrade needs in rural or underdeveloped areas.

Regulatory fragmentation and legal gaps: Several pilot regions, such as Spain and Romania, lack comprehensive regulation that recognises EVs as grid assets or permits energy reselling from private vehicles. Harmonising these frameworks at EU and national levels remains a pending challenge.

User acceptance and behavioural barriers: Many potential users are unfamiliar with V2G functionality or remain concerned about battery degradation and perceived system complexity. Accessibility also depends on clear communication, intuitive interfaces, and inclusive design for all demographics, including users with special needs.

Battery degradation and residual value concerns remain a key adoption barrier, especially in the absence of user-level control or warranty coverage. Operational models must be designed to minimise impact on battery health, particularly in public-access and shared-use contexts.

Misalignment between real-world mobility patterns and V2G operational requirements (e.g. dwell time, availability during grid peak hours) can limit the technical and economic viability of public V2G solutions.

Data security and privacy: As digital platforms and predictive models become central to managing bidirectional charging, the system must comply with GDPR and ensure robust protection of user data and energy usage patterns.

7.5.2 Critical Success Factors

NEVERFLAT's business model can overcome these challenges by leveraging key enablers observed in successful initiatives and aligned with project values:

Plug-and-charge simplicity: V2G operations must be seamless for users, with energy exchanges automated through interoperable systems and intuitive human-machine interfaces (HMI). Avoiding behavioural friction is essential for mainstream adoption.

Inclusive user experience: SSH-informed design is key. The interface, service logic, and economic incentives must be accessible and equitable. Digital tools should support a wide range of users, from individual car owners to cooperative members or municipal operators.

Designing services that engage users with diverse and complementary routines: (e.g. commuters, fleet vehicles, community users) can maximise infrastructure usage across time windows and enhance value delivery.

Tangible and fair incentive schemes: Compensation mechanisms for energy returned to the grid—whether fixed payments, dynamic tariffs, or aggregated service rewards—must offer real motivation while maintaining system viability. These models should be co-designed and tested in pilots with diverse stakeholders.

Stakeholder coordination: Local authorities, OEMs, grid operators, aggregators, and social actors must work in tandem. Multi-actor governance improves legitimacy, implementation efficiency, and alignment with local needs.

Digital intelligence and operational optimisation: The use of machine learning, digital twins, and predictive analytics will be essential to optimise charger deployment, match energy supply with user patterns, and minimise operational costs.

7.5.3 Strategic Opportunities for NEVERFLAT

NEVERFLAT holds a unique position to deliver a value-added and scalable V2G model across European Union, building on several distinctive strategic assets:

Low-power, low-cost infrastructure as a competitive advantage: Instead of focusing on high-speed commercial corridors, the project targets long-parking scenarios such as office areas, rural centres, or peri-urban zones—where dwell time favours V2G participation and deployment costs are more manageable.

Public-access as a vector of equity and visibility: Unlike private charging schemes, public-access V2G can extend benefits to wider user groups (e.g. users of shared mobility or cooperative fleets), reinforcing social inclusion and public value.

Cross-border interoperability and EU integration: By adopting open protocols and leveraging standards such as ISO 15118-20, NEVERFLAT contributes to a coherent European charging ecosystem, simplifying user experience across countries.

Integration with renewable energy and local energy systems: V2G deployment can be paired with PV self-consumption, microgrids, and smart community energy schemes, increasing local resilience and environmental performance.

Replicability and scalability: The modularity of the proposed infrastructure allows for phased, adaptive deployment in diverse contexts—urban, rural, semi-public—enabling customised business model variants.

7.5.4 Alignment with the Project's Vision

The proposed business model framework directly supports the overarching mission and objectives of NEVERFLAT, as defined in the Grant Agreement:

It enhances **grid resilience** and energy efficiency by turning EVs into decentralised energy assets.

It promotes **affordability and inclusion** by targeting underserved areas and public spaces with smart, intuitive, low-cost solutions.

It strengthens **social acceptance** and system legitimacy through the integration of SSH methodologies, participatory design, and ethical considerations.

It enables **long-term sustainability** by aligning the business model with environmental goals and scalable operational efficiency.

It contributes to the **cohesion of the European charging landscape** through interoperability, standardisation, and cross-border accessibility.

By integrating socio-technical innovation with a user-centred business approach, NEVERFLAT is well positioned to accelerate the deployment of V2G infrastructure that is inclusive, sustainable, and market-ready.

7.6 Conclusion and Recommendations for Action

The deployment of public-access, low-cost, low-power V2G infrastructure is not merely a technical or regulatory challenge—it represents a systemic transformation with deep implications for equity, sustainability, and socio-economic viability. The findings from the NEVERFLAT pilot countries—Germany, Romania, and Spain—reveal marked disparities in the maturity of the V2G ecosystem, shaped by infrastructure availability, user awareness, socio-demographic conditions, and business model readiness.

7.6.1 Key Conclusions

Socioeconomic conditions are decisive for V2G adoption. Income levels, territorial disparities in charging infrastructure, access to incentives, and the presence of energy communities are all key factors that shape the feasibility and fairness of implementation.

Public-access, slow, and affordable V2G infrastructure remains underdeveloped, yet offers strong potential for complementing fast-charging networks and enabling socially inclusive access to flexibility markets.

Public acceptance depends on clear, tangible incentives as well as simple, intuitive service models. Concerns about battery degradation and a general lack of familiarity with V2G remain significant barriers, especially among non-technical user groups.

Business models must be tailored to local contexts. Solutions suited for dense urban areas are not directly transferable to rural or low-income regions. Community-based, cooperative, or shared fleet models may provide viable and inclusive alternatives in these cases.

NEVERFLAT can play a pioneering role by demonstrating that low-power, bidirectional public charging is both technically viable and economically sustainable—when supported by smart design, regulatory support, and user-centred innovation.

7.6.2 Strategic Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are proposed for the next phases of the NEVERFLAT project:

Pilot real-life incentive schemes across diverse user profiles to test willingness to participate in V2G and assess fairness, motivation, and scalability of compensation models.

Leverage SSH methodologies to co-design interfaces, business logic, and outreach strategies with local stakeholders, ensuring inclusive access and contextual relevance.

Implement clear and progressive compensation mechanisms, tailored to the risk sensitivity and cost burden of different user profiles. Demonstrating tangible economic value to users will be essential to foster participation and trust in V2G schemes.

Emphasise low-cost V2G infrastructure and service models as a foundation for equitable access, not only by reducing energy charging costs, but by lowering the overall barriers to participate in V2G systems. Affordability is essential to ensure that low-income users, rural communities, and other underserved groups can engage meaningfully in the energy transition.

Incorporate battery health considerations into V2G operational models, by developing charging and discharging strategies that minimise battery degradation and preserve long-term performance, especially in public and shared use contexts.

Define territorial equity criteria for charger deployment, prioritizing areas with low infrastructure density, higher energy poverty, or poor public transport access.

Incorporate user mobility patterns into the design and localisation of V2G infrastructure, ensuring alignment between charging opportunities, dwell times, and energy service provision. Engaging a diversity of user profiles—with complementary routines and usage times—can improve system utilisation, technical viability, and value generation.

Position NEVERFLAT as a model for inclusive energy transition, using public-access V2G as a platform not just for charging, but for social innovation, sustainability, and regional resilience.

The roadmap ahead will involve testing these hypotheses in real-world pilots, evaluating user behaviour, system performance, and business viability. The findings will serve as the basis for refining the business model and ensuring its long-term sustainability and scalability. By aligning technical innovation with social equity, NEVERFLAT can redefine what a just and inclusive EV charging infrastructure looks like across Europe.

8

Key Insights

The comprehensive analysis conducted in the scope of the NEVERFLAT project has brought to light several converging insights across technological, regulatory, market, and socio-economic domains. Drawing from the State-of-the-Art (SotA) assessment, regulatory and market analysis, and socio-economic and business model perspectives, it becomes evident that the landscape for bidirectional charging and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) integration is characterised by promising technological progress juxtaposed with systemic challenges that hinder large-scale deployment. The following key insights synthesize the collective findings of all analytical dimensions:

1. Technical Readiness is Emerging but Fragmented Bidirectional charging technologies have transitioned from pilot-phase to early commercialisation, supported by maturing standards such as ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.0.1. Multiple commercial AC/DC and DC/DC charging solutions are now available with integrated V2G capabilities. Nevertheless, interoperability remains a critical challenge. Variability in the implementation of communication protocols across manufacturers, combined with the limited pace of infrastructure upgrades and delayed implementation of the latest communication and cybersecurity standards in public charging stations, limits plug-and-play compatibility in real-world deployments. Additionally, wide output voltage ranges and safety certification requirements impose further complexity and cost on manufacturers.

2. Regulatory Frameworks are Structurally Diverse and Rich in Insights The regulatory and market analysis conducted in the context of NEVERFLAT reveals a diverse landscape shaped by varying interpretations of roles, processes, and responsibilities. Across the Member States analysed—Germany, Spain, and Romania—clear divergences emerge in how bidirectional charging is treated within the broader energy framework. For instance, grid codes and balancing mechanisms are not uniformly structured to account for behind-the-meter flexibility from electric vehicles. In several cases, limitations in data transparency, lack of harmonised grid access criteria for flexible resources, and the absence of robust metering and remuneration mechanisms for energy exported to the grid significantly impede the integration of bidirectional assets. Moreover, the role of actors such as Balancing Responsible Parties (BRPs), Aggregators, and Virtual Power Plant Operators (VPPOs) is either not explicitly regulated or treated inconsistently across Member States, leading to challenges in implementation and cooperation.

3. Market and Regulatory Conditions Impede Activation of System Flexibility The analysis identifies a misalignment between the system value of EV flexibility and the mechanisms currently available to activate this flexibility in energy markets. Although mechanisms such as Virtual Power Plants (VPPs) and aggregators are explicitly designed to enable the participation of distributed energy resources, their practical deployment remains limited due to complex prequalification procedures, limited visibility in balancing markets, and regulatory uncertainty concerning their interaction with distribution system operators (DSOs). Moreover, EV fleets are not yet systematically integrated as dispatchable resources in flexibility registers. Energy tariff structures in many jurisdictions do not yet incentivise dynamic charging and discharging, and key parameters such as double taxation, grid fees, or balancing responsibility for exported energy are inconsistently addressed. These limitations restrict the scalability of V2G services despite their demonstrated technical feasibility.

4. Socio-Economic Benefits are Recognised but Underleveraged V2G offers demonstrable socio-economic benefits, including energy cost reduction, increased integration of renewable energy sources, emission reductions, and enhanced grid stability—particularly in supporting local flexibility and peak load balancing. However, these advantages are not yet fully perceived or accessible to the end-user. Bidirectional charging is often seen as complex, costly, or incompatible with existing usage patterns. A lack of awareness and guidance on its benefits, coupled with the limited market availability of compatible vehicles and infrastructure, has contributed to a low adoption rate. Social acceptance and perceived reliability play a crucial role and must be addressed through user-centric design, education, and trust-building initiatives.

5. Interoperability, Data Governance, and Cybersecurity Are Critical Enablers The fragmented implementation of technical standards, including differing interpretations of ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.0.1, combined with a lack of clear frameworks for data ownership, access, and usage rights, presents significant challenges for the interoperability and trustworthiness of V2G systems. Moreover, as energy and mobility systems become increasingly digitalised and interconnected, cybersecurity is becoming a core prerequisite for secure V2G operations. Ensuring end-to-end protection of communication channels, protecting charging and user data from unauthorised access, and defining responsibilities for incident management and resilience will be central to fostering long-term user confidence and regulatory compliance. In summary, the analyses conducted within the framework of this deliverable point toward a clear convergence: while the building blocks for bidirectional charging and V2G integration are in place, realising their potential will require coordinated action across technical, regulatory, market, and societal domains.

6. Energy Tokenisation should be implemented based on the following recommendations. A custom implementation on **Polygon**, supported by MKI, provides the best combination of technical performance, regulatory alignment, user experience, and strategic flexibility. It positions the NEVERFLAT project to deliver secure, scalable, and user-centric tokenised energy services both now and in the future.

9

Conclusion and Recommendations

The analysis undertaken in Deliverable D1.1 of the NEVERFLAT project highlights a multifaceted opportunity space for Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) integration within the evolving eMobility and energy system landscape. Across all analytical strands—technical, regulatory, economic, and socio behavioural — there is strong evidence that the fundamental capabilities required for bidirectional charging are advancing rapidly. However, persistent structural and systemic barriers continue to inhibit full realisation of these capabilities in the European context.

To support the uptake and scalability of bidirectional charging and smart charging solutions, the following cross-cutting recommendations are derived from the collected evidence and are addressed to stakeholders across the mobility and energy value chains, including policymakers, regulatory authorities, energy system operators, and eMobility actors:

1. Harmonise Regulatory Roles and Framework Conditions A clear and harmonised regulatory framework across Member States is critical to enable consistent implementation of V2G functionality. Definitions of roles and responsibilities—particularly those of aggregators, Virtual Power Plant Operators (VPPOs), or other Balancing Responsible Parties (BRPs)—should be aligned with current and future market needs. Moreover, regulatory pathways should ensure that behind-the-meter flexibility from EVs can be fairly remunerated and integrated into system planning, including via transparent metering and settlement mechanisms for energy exported to the grid.

2. Enable Market Access for Distributed Flexibility Electric vehicles should be recognised as active contributors to system stability and flexibility. Regulatory and market entry barriers for distributed flexibility actors—such as aggregators and fleet operators—should be reduced by streamlining prequalification procedures, creating proportional participation thresholds, and clarifying interactions with DSOs and TSOs. Flexibility registers and coordination mechanisms should explicitly support the registration and dispatch of aggregated EV fleets.

3. Ensure Interoperability through Standard Conformance and Clarity Interoperability is a fundamental enabler of scale. Stakeholders should work toward the consistent interpretation and implementation of standards such as ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1. This includes promoting transparent

certification procedures, test procedures, and compliance monitoring to ensure system-level compatibility and integration across diverse hardware and software solutions.

4. Address Socio-Economic Adoption Barriers through User-Centric Approaches Incentive structures and service models must be designed around the expectations, constraints, and preferences of end-users. Transparent communication of potential cost savings, environmental impact, and system benefits of V2G—especially in terms of supporting grid reliability and the energy transition—will be essential to building societal acceptance. Simplified interfaces and service offers, combined with educational efforts, can help overcome complexity and trust barriers.

5. Prioritise Cybersecurity and Data Governance Frameworks As digitalization, especially within the energy markets, deepens, ensuring robust cybersecurity and data governance is not optional but essential. Technical specifications should mandate secure communication channels, data minimisation, and role-based access control. Moreover, clear accountability for cybersecurity incident response and continuous risk assessment must be institutionalised across the V2G value chain. Data sharing protocols and privacy-compliant governance frameworks must be clarified to unlock value while protecting users. Taken together, these recommendations form the basis of a systemic response to the challenges identified throughout this deliverable. The coordinated implementation of these measures will support the emergence of a future-proof, user-oriented, and grid-integrated charging infrastructure in Europe.

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Appendices

Regulatory Analysis

A.1 Europe

Table A.1: Regulatory and Market Structure – Evaluation and Maturity Level

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Regulatory and Market Structure			
Regulatory Bodies	European Commission, European Council, European Parliament, ENTSO-E, ACER, CEER		
Energy market participation (e.g., Market access and potential aggregated services)	<p>Energy market participation for bidirectional charging is steadily advancing at the EU level, driven by regulatory developments that aim to integrate flexible energy assets into wholesale and balancing markets.</p> <p>The Clean Energy Package, adopted in 2019, paved the way for a new electricity market design, introducing among other things, a new Electricity Directive and Regulation. The EU’s Internal Electricity Market Directive (2019/944) and Regulation (EU 2019/943), which establish common rules for the energy market, cover areas such as energy generation, transmission, distribution, and storage, with a focus on fostering demand-side flexibility.</p> <p>According to the Internal Electricity Market Directive 2019/944 (Article 17) demand response from final customers-either directly or through aggregation-must be granted non-discriminatory access to all electricity markets, including energy, capacity, and ancillary service markets. These legislative provisions acknowledge independent aggregators as valid market participants. They mandate that all Member States establish a regulatory framework to allow these actors to enter the market, however many of the details of the implementation are left at the national level.</p> <p>In addition, on June 13, 2024, Regulation 2024/1747 and Directive 2024/1711 were officially adopted, with the main purpose to amend the Electricity Market Directive (2019/944) and Regulation (EU 2019/943) in order to improve the EU’ electricity market design (EMD). These legislative revisions introduce a more robust and inclusive framework for independent aggregators and demand-side response with the electricity market. They explicitly recognize independent aggregators as key market participants and require Member States to ensure that they can access the market on equal and non-discriminatory terms. One of the most significant changes is the removal of the requirement for prior consent from energy suppliers, which has previously limited the ability of aggregators to offer services directly to consumers. On the demand-side response side, the provisions stipulate that DSR can participate in all segments of the electricity market-wholesale, balancing, and capacity mechanisms-on an equal footing with generation. Additionally, customers should be allowed multiple metering and billing points under a single connection to enable separate supply and pricing for high-consumption, flexible appliances such as electric vehicles and heat pumps.</p>	<p>From a regulatory perspective, the EU’s Electricity Market Design establishes a strong legislative foundation aimed at removing existing barriers to demand side-flexibility.</p> <p>In particular, demand-side flexibility in ancillary services has made significant progress and is increasingly recognized as a crucial component for enhancing the stability and efficiency of Europe’s electricity systems, although its implementation varies across Member States. However, progress at the national level remains limited. The transposition of key provisions into national legislation has been slow and inconsistent, leading to significant disparities across Member States. This lack of timely and effective regulatory adaptation has resulted in fragmented markets and underutilized</p>	Mid

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Grid management and control (Demand Response programs and Grid Frequency Regulation)	<p>The integration of EVs into the energy grid is influenced by the network codes that regulate grid connections. These codes, which establish the requirements for connecting new consumers and generators, are crucial in maintaining the stability and safety of the grid by preventing overloading. As such, they can either promote or restrict the expansion of V2G technology. The European network codes and guidelines provide the foundation for the technical integration of EVs. Relevant codes, such as the connection codes (Network code on Requirement for Grid Connection of Generators and Network code on Demand Connection) and the draft Network Code on Demand Response (NCDR), are key in this context. The EU Network Codes explicitly include electric vehicles, bidirectional chargers, and storage systems, marking a clear step toward integrating V2G into electricity markets.</p> <p>The European network codes facilitate the participation of decentralized systems, such as EVs with bidirectional charging capabilities, in flexibility markets. At the national level, any modifications to the implementation of these grid codes should be avoided, unless they are technically required. The proposed EU Network Code on Demand Response (NC DR), submitted by ACER in March 2025, introduces key enablers for market access, enabling demand response resources—including consumers, storage providers, and distributed generation—to fully participate in wholesale electricity markets. This network code and related amendments to existing regulations (covering balancing, system operation, and demand connection) focus on four key areas:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. New EU-wide rules will simplify market participation for smaller energy players. A standardized European registry will ensure fair and consistent measurement of demand response. 2. Simplified prequalification, streamlined product verification, and a national system for managing participation will facilitate all resources in providing services to system operators. 3. Transparent and efficient procurement of system operator services—such as congestion management and voltage control—will be ensured. Any exceptions to market-based procurement will require clear justification, with guidelines to prevent market distortions. 4. Enhanced collaboration between distribution and transmission system operators will better integrate renewables, manage congestion and voltage control, and prevent system disruptions. Clear rules will ensure that interventions in one part of the system do not cause problems elsewhere. <p>According to the Automotive Action Plan, the European Commission should deliver a new Network Code on Demand Response in Q1 2026. The Commission will afterwards begin the process of establishing the Demand Response (DR) Regulation, along with amending the three related regulations. Once adopted by Member States, these regulations will become legally binding throughout the EU.</p>	<p>While the regulatory direction is positive, the new Demand Response Regulation has not yet been adopted by the European Commission, and its implementation by Member States will take additional time. Until then, the legal and technical frameworks required for consistent market participation across the EU remain incomplete. Furthermore, OEM certification processes, grid prequalification requirements, and aggregator access mechanisms are still being standardized, and not all national systems are fully prepared to accommodate V2G. To unlock the full potential of demand-side flexibility across Europe, it is critical that the Network Code for Demand Response is finalized and implemented without delay. This code represents a foundational step toward the harmonization of DSO-level flexibility markets, addressing regulatory gaps that currently limit the participation of aggregators and small-scale distributed assets. By providing clear rules on settlement, baseline methodologies, and compensation, the code will reduce entry barriers and administrative burdens that discourage market participation. Furthermore, by defining standardized Terms & Conditions for flexibility services at the local level, the code will support the creation of transparent, interoperable and technology-neutral flexibility markets.</p> <p>Despite the Electricity Market Design Directive, which already gives Member States the tools to promote smart and bidirectional charging and the strategic direction of the Automotive Action Plan, there is currently an uneven implementation of frameworks across Member States. This hinders the harmonized development of V2G integration and limits the potential of demand-side flexibility. Member States should develop and implement comprehensive national frameworks that promote smart and bidirectional charging, leveraging EU tools and guidance. Additionally, they should actively participate in the European Commission’s action to share best practices.</p>	Mid
Charging infrastructure regulations (Smart and bidirectional provisions)	<p>The Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (including the proposed AFIR Delegated and Implementing Acts), the Renewable Energy Directive III, and the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) include provisions on smart and bidirectional charging. AFIR Article 5 (8) stipulates that all publicly accessible recharging points built after 13 April 2024 or renovated after 14 October 2024 must be capable of smart recharging. In addition, AFIR Art 15 requires Member States to assess how charging infrastructure can support electric vehicles in contributing to energy system flexibility, including participation in balancing markets and integration if renewable energy-including specific attention to smart and bidirectional charging. In addition, national regulatory authorities must also evaluate the potential of bidirectional charging to reduce user costs and increase renewable energy integration.</p> <p>While the AFIR Delegated Acts mandate ISO15118-20 for publicly accessible and private charging points (mode 3 and 4), they do not mandate the activation or deployment of bidirectional charging- only that charging infrastructure be capable of it.</p> <p>According to EPBD Article 14, Member States must ensure that newly installed recharging points support smart charging, and where appropriate, bidirectional charging should be operated based on non-proprietary and non-discriminatory communication protocols and standards, in an interoperable manner in compliance with any European standards and Delegated Acts adopted according to AFIR.</p> <p>Under RED III (Art 20) Member States are required to ensure that all new and replaced non-publicly accessible charging points support smart charging functionalities, and where appropriate, capable of interfacing with smart metering systems and support bidirectional charging.</p>	<p>While bidirectional charging is explicitly acknowledged in AFIR, RED III, and the EPBD, it is currently treated as an optional or enabling feature, not a mandatory deployment requirement. To fully enable bidirectional charging across the EU, legislative frameworks such as AFIR, RED III, and the EPBD must be reinforced through coordinated implementation. The EU should ensure consistent enforcement, support certification and interoperability testing, and support activation of bidirectional functionality. RED III should explicitly integrate bidirectional EVs into definitions of storage and flexibility, allowing their participation in self-consumption and grid services. The EPBD must go further by requiring bidirectional readiness in new and renovated buildings, particularly those equipped with solar PV.</p>	Mid

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Financial and non-financial incentives (Energy contracts and tariffs, participation in demand-side flexibility programs, grid tariffs, taxes and levies)	To accelerate the adoption of V2G technologies and maximize their contribution to grid flexibility, both financial and non-financial incentives play a crucial role. Financial incentives include tailored energy contracts and dynamic tariffs that reward flexible charging and discharging behaviors, enabling EV owners to benefit economically by participating in demand-side flexibility programs. Gris tariffs and taxes also influence the business case for V2G. Fair and transparent network fees that avoid penalizing stored energy use—such as double charging for energy input and output—are essential to ensure cost-effectiveness. The proposal to revise the Energy Taxation Directive (2003/96/EC) (ETD) is relevant to V2X, as it includes measures aimed at preventing double taxation. However, this revision is currently stalled in the Council.	According to the Automotive Action Plan, Member States should make sure that distribution system operators apply fair network fees and avoid charging twice for stored energy, such as in electric vehicles batteries. It is recommended that Member States use electricity taxation policies to help create a viable business case for bidirectional charging. These measures should be supported by aligned national strategies and financial incentives—such as grants, tax relief, and dynamic pricing—to unlock the full flexibility potential of V2G technologies. Non-financial incentives should complement monetary measures by fostering awareness, providing clear regulatory guidance, and enabling easier market access for aggregators and consumers. These may include streamlined procedures for participation in flexibility markets, and access to technical support.	Mid-Low
Regulatory flexibility (i.e., adaptability to emerging technologies)	The EU's regulatory framework is gradually evolving to accommodate emerging technologies like V2G. The European Commission's Energy Union Strategy and its digital transition initiatives show adaptability in terms of future-proofing regulations. However, these regulations still face implementation challenges in terms of integrating new technologies and ensuring regulatory harmonization.	Despite the EU's forward looking regulatory approach, a key challenge lies in the slow pace of regulatory adaptation compared to the rapid evolution of emerging like V2G. While EU-level policies show intent to be future-proof, national-level implementation often lags, leading to inconsistent or incomplete regulatory environments. Key barriers include fragmented implementation across Member States, slow regulatory response times, and inconsistent national frameworks, which hinder harmonized integration. These gaps between policy ambition and on the ground execution make it difficult for new solutions to enter the market efficiently, limiting innovation and slowing the large-scale deployment of V2G technologies.	Mid
Standards for V2G charging infrastructure	Standardized communication protocols are essential for ensuring real-time coordination, system efficiency, and the successful integration of electric mobility into the broader energy infrastructure. By enabling seamless communication between all key stakeholders –including electric vehicles, Distribution System Operators, Charge Point Operators, and aggregators—these protocols form the backbone of a smart charging ecosystem. The proposed AFIR Delegated Acts mandate the implementation ISO15118-20 starting with 1 January 2027. According to the Automotive Action Plan, the European Commission will evaluate the requirements for ensuring that electric vehicles are ready for smart and bi-directional charging, as part of the Type Approval Regulation. In addition, the Commission plans to initiate a regulatory sandbox for V2G pilot projects to tackle regulatory, technical, and market-related challenges ahead of broader deployment.	To accelerate the transition to a smart, flexible, and resilient energy system, the EU legislative framework must prioritize the development and enforcement of open, harmonized standards for smart charging. Without a clear regulatory push for standardized interfaces and protocols, Europe risks continued fragmentation, limited scalability and inefficiencies in integrating EVs into the energy system. The European Commission should ensure that electric vehicles are equipped for smart and bidirectional charging, by incorporating a ISO15118-20 mandate for OEMs in the Type Approval Regulation. This would facilitate the integration of EVs into the energy system and support grid flexibility.	Mid
Communicative connection between key actors (Interaction between vehicles, charging infrastructure, grid operators, and other key stakeholders)	To support smart charging and effective bidirectional energy flows, there is a need for standardized, secure, and interoperable communication across the entire EV ecosystem. This includes clear connections between grid and charger, vehicle and charger (in both directions), CPO and charger, aggregator to grid, aggregator to charger, and customer to third-party service provider. These connections enable real-time coordination, load balancing, and system optimization.	Swift development and implementation of the technical specifications outlined in Annex II of AFIR is essential to enable smart and bidirectional charging across the EU. This includes standardized communication between the electric vehicle and charging point (V2G), between the charging point and its management system, and between the Charging Point Operators and distribution System Operators. Establishing harmonized, secure, and interoperable communication protocols across these interfaces will allow for real-time coordination, dynamic load management, and system optimization—critical for unlocking demand-side flexibility and integrating EVs into the electricity grid.	Mid
Grid compatibility and standards (Interconnection standards, Power Quality Regulations, etc.)	Grid compatibility is a critical enabler for scaling V2G technologies, ensuring that vehicles can not only charge but also discharge power without disrupting grid stability and adhering to local power quality standards. The EU Electricity Regulation (EU 943/2019) establishes a strong framework to ensure grid compatibility, outlines grid standards, and support the integration of innovative technologies, such as V2G. In addition, the Network Code on System Operation contains rules on managing interconnectors, contingencies, and security standards.	Grid compatibility and interconnection standards for V2G are progressing, but practical implementation gaps, local grid variability and technical standards fragmentation remain significant barriers.	Mid
System integration and pilot programs	System integration is essential for unlocking the full potential of V2G and smart charging in the energy transition. Without seamless coordination between electric vehicles, charging infrastructure, grid operators, V2G technologies can not reliably provide flexibility services. As part of the Automotive Action Plan published on 5 March, the European Commission is launching a regulatory sandbox initiative to support pilot projects for vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technologies. The aim is to tackle key regulatory, technical, and market challenges before V2G can be deployed at scale. The initiative aims to explore how Member States can set up regulatory sandboxes to test innovative V2G solutions under a controlled environment. These pilots will help identify practical short-term fixes and inform the development of a long-term regulatory framework. Participating Member States would voluntarily establish a special regulatory regime, limited in scope and duration (4–5 years), to support V2G pilot activities. The European Union's Innovation Fund supported several pilot projects and system integration efforts.		Mid

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Data Management			
Data privacy and security (Data protection and cybersecurity regulations)	V2G systems collect and exchange a large amount of data, and ensuring data privacy is essential. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies to any data processing involved in V2G. As the EU moves toward digital grids, cybersecurity is a high priority, with efforts being made to align V2G systems with the NIS2 Directive (Network and Information Systems Directive) for cybersecurity in critical infrastructure. In addition, the EU's Cyber Resilience Act significantly strengthens this foundation by requiring that all products with digital elements meet essential cybersecurity requirements throughout their lifecycle. This includes embedding security by design, providing clear information to end users, and committing to ongoing security updates.	A major challenge in the development of V2G technologies is ensuring robust data privacy and security while enabling increasingly innovative and interconnected solutions that rely on extensive access to data. In light of the rapid pace of innovation evolving regulatory frameworks and coordinated cybersecurity strategies are needed that can help adapt to new threats and address the risks of data breaches. While cybersecurity is increasingly recognized as critical to protecting digital infrastructure-including smart charging systems, EVs and grid interfaces-the existing regulatory framework is still evolving and lacks specific, enforceable standards tailored to the complexities of V2G. While the Cyber Resilience Act marks a major step forward, the complexities of V2G ecosystem demands further sector-specific cybersecurity provisions and close alignment with existing frameworks like NIS2.	Mid
Data exchange and accessibility (Europe-wide framework for non-discriminatory access to EV data, the EU Data Act, and RED III)	We have currently a very complex ecosystem, with a lot of players that need to share data. To fully realize the benefits of smart and bidirectional charging, various stakeholders-charge points operators, OEMs, grid operators, energy suppliers, and service providers-must exchange real-time data related to charging sessions, grid conditions, user preferences, pricing signals, and flexibility offers. From a regulatory standpoint, the EU legislative framework provides a solid basis, with a horizontal legislation for data access and sharing, provided by the EU Data Act and sector-specific legislation, such as RED III (Renewable Energy Directive), aiming to ensure access to relevant EV data (Art 20).	According to the Automotive Action Plan the European Commission will take measures on access to vehicle data, functions and resources including guidance on Data Act, and if needed a legislative proposal on vehicle data. It remains to be seen if a dedicated legislative proposal will be put forward by the European Commission (In-Vehicle-Data Act).	Mid
Consumer protection and rights (contractual transparency, access to information, and liability framework)			
Consumer protection and rights (contractual transparency, access to information, and liability framework)	Consumer protection in V2G transactions is an emerging area. Clear contractual terms regarding vehicle use, charging protocols, and the rights and responsibilities of users are necessary. The EU Consumer Protection Framework will likely evolve to include specific provisions for V2G to protect consumers from unfair terms, data misuse, and unsafe practices.	Current regulatory frameworks do not adequately address consumer protection and rights specific to V2G, particularly in areas such as contractual transparency, access to information, and liability. Additionally, access to essential information about charging costs, data usage, and potential impacts on vehicle performance is frequently limited or insufficiently communicated. The absence of a clear liability framework further complicates matters, leaving consumers uncertain about who is responsible in cases of equipment failure, service interruptions, or damage during bidirectional energy transactions. These gaps undermine consumer trust and highlight the need for tailored regulations that ensure transparency, informed consent, and robust liability protections in V2G services.	Mid-Low
Environmental considerations (emission reduction goals)	The European Green Deal sets ambitious goals for emission reductions, and V2G can play a key role by enabling greater integration of renewable energy and facilitating decarbonization of the transport and energy sectors. V2G is seen as a way to enable grid flexibility and enhance the integration of renewable energy sources, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and supporting EU-wide decarbonization goals.	Although V2G is recognized as a promising tool to enhance grid flexibility and facilitate greater integration of renewable energy sources, it is not yet explicitly embedded in binding EU-wide emission reduction frameworks or policies. This lack of explicit inclusion in environmental legislation limits the technology's potential to contribute effectively to the EU's ambitious environmental goals.	Mid-High

A.2 Germany

Table A.2: Regulatory and Market Structure – Evaluation and Maturity Level for Germany

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Regulatory and Market Structure			
Regulatory Bodies	BMWK, Bundesnetzagentur, dena, DIN, PTB		
Energy market participation (e.g., Market access and potential aggregated services)	German legislation enables demand-side response programs, where EVs and aggregators can participate. The German Bundestag passed in January 2025 an amendment to the Energy Industry Act (EnWG), marking a significant contribution to enable bidirectionally used electric vehicles and charging points to participate in the electricity markets. In addition, Germany has announced plans to introduce a Capacity Market starting in 2028, with Demand Side flexibility expected to be actively incentivised. A decentralised element of the mechanism is being considered to enable broader participation by flexible and distributed resources.	In Germany, grid-serving flexibility is theoretically enabled by regulation, as control of distributed assets via smart meter gateways is both technically and legally permitted. Although pooling of EVs is legally allowed, it is currently not yet implementable on a larger scale, due to lack of digitalization and lack of smart meter roll-out. V2G participation is currently limited by the lack of a legal structure for wholesale market integration and the absence of dedicated local flexibility markets, which are critical for grid service monetization.	Mid

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Grid management and control (Demand Response programs and Grid Frequency Regulation)	<p>The Federal Network Agency (Bundesnetzagentur) launched consultations to integrate controllable consumer devices such as electric vehicle charge points into the electricity grid, aimed at allowing grid operators to manage consumption during peak times. The new Section 14a of the Energy Industry Act (EnWG) has been in force since January 1, 2024. In case of overload, the network operator is allowed to reduce the power consumption of private controllable devices to up to 4.2 kW for the duration of the specific overload. In exchange, consumers benefit from financial incentives through reduced grid fees, offered via three distinct discount modules based on metering arrangements and consumer flexibility.</p> <p>Devices installed prior to 2024 are grandfathered unless already subject to control agreements, with a compliance deadline of January 1, 2029, for transitioning to the new requirements. For network operators, Section 14a provides a valuable tool to enhance grid stability and prevent overloads without incurring substantial infrastructure costs. Such interventions are expected to be exceptional and temporary, with provisions to incorporate anticipated throttling into grid expansion planning. Section 14c of the Energy Industry Act (EnWG) mandates that network operators implement flexibility services in a transparent, non-discriminatory, and market-based manner.</p> <p>The Federal Network Agency (BNetzA) is empowered to establish specific procedural guidelines and determine any applicable exceptions. While the legal framework is established, the detailed operationalization of this section, including the design of incentives to promote its application, remains under development.</p>	Germany lacks large-scale, dedicated demand response programs that actively engage consumers or aggregators. There are few incentives tied to real-time grid conditions, such as dynamic pricing or time-of-use tariffs tailored for EV charging behavior. As a result, EV owners and fleet operators have limited motivation to align their charging with grid needs, and the commercial case for demand-side flexibility remains weak.	Mid
Charging infrastructure regulations (Smart and bidirectional provisions)	<p>The German Federal Government has set a clear goal to introduce bidirectional charging nationwide in a non-discriminatory manner, as highlighted in the coalition agreement and Measure 47 of the Charging Infrastructure II Masterplan. Building on thorough analyses of the current situation and potential use cases such as vehicle-to-home (V2H) and vehicle-to-grid (V2G), the government has developed a detailed roadmap with concrete recommendations and rollout timelines. Market-ready V2H applications are expected to become available by 2025, with V2G solutions anticipated to follow shortly thereafter.</p> <p>A significant expansion of interoperable and standardized V2H and V2G technologies is projected from 2028 onwards, provided that relevant standards are finalized and the necessary regulatory and technical frameworks are established. In addition, Germany has revising its Charging Point Ordinance (Ladesäulenverordnung), to comply with the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation, which is the overarching legislative framework at the EU level, touching upon smart and bidirectional charging. In addition, the draft includes provisions regarding the task and responsibilities of the Federal Network Agency (Bundesnetzagentur) for monitoring the compliance and enforcing the implementation of the AFIR's legal provisions. A consultation process with federal states and associations on the amendment of the Charging Station Ordinance (LSV) is currently underway, following the previous legislative period in which the amendment could not be completed (deadline for submissions is 4 July).</p>	The nationwide rollout of bidirectional charging in Germany faces several regulatory challenges that must be addressed to ensure a smooth and effective implementation. In this context, the legal, technical, tax, and economic frameworks need to be enhanced to better enable and support the deployment and operation of bidirectional charging technologies.	Mid
Financial and non-financial incentives (Energy contracts and tariffs, participation in demand-side flexibility programs, grid tariffs, taxes and levies)	Dynamic tariffs are mandated for larger suppliers starting and will apply to smaller suppliers in 2025. Nevertheless, most residential consumers still use static tariffs. Germany has introduced the pass-through model with regard to tenders for truck charging, meant to create transparency in electricity prices and create planning security, especially given the challenges with regard to grid connection of e-HDVs. In addition, non-financial incentives also have significant potential to promote the adoption of bidirectional charging services. Bidirectional charging empowers individuals to contribute to carbon emissions reduction and the integration of renewable energy sources. By allowing electric vehicles to both consume and supply electricity when beneficial, users can support grid stability and reduce reliance on fossil fuels, thereby advancing the energy transition.	In Germany, although a wide range of dynamic tariff structures exist, practical consumer access remains limited. The slow and fragmented roll-out of smart meters, coupled with highly decentralized municipal utility landscape, creates significant barriers to implementation. As a result, many consumers are unable to benefit from these dynamic or asset-specific offers. This disconnect between market design and real-world accessibility undermines the scalability of demand-side flexibility.	Mid
Regulatory flexibility (i.e., adaptability to emerging technologies)	Germany is one of the frontrunner countries regarding the topic of bidirectional charging, which is reflected in the Masterplan Charging Infrastructure II and, in the recommendations , put forward by the Advisory Board of the National Center for Charging Infrastructure. In addition, the Coalition of the Willing was established under the coordination of the BMWK (German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action), involving industry and policy stakeholders from across Europe. The working group reports of the "Coalition of the willing on bidirectional Charging" can be found here .	The complexity of integrating smart and bidirectional charging technologies into existing grids, ensuring consumer acceptance, and maintaining competitive market access requires continued efforts. These challenges highlight that, while Germany leads in policy and coordination, practical implementation and scaling remain critical obstacles to fully realize the potential of bidirectional charging.	Mid
Interoperability, Standardization, and Communication			

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Standards for V2G charging infrastructure	Germany supports a wide range of international and national standards- including ISO 15118, IEC 61851, OCPP, VDE-AR-E 22829- 6-1 and EEBUS-to ensure interoperability between electric vehicles, charging infrastructure, and energy systems. These standards are widely adopted by manufacturers, promoting cross-compatibility. However, inconsistencies in implementation continue to introduce complexity and risk partial interoperability. To streamline integration, Germany is looking to embed control functions directly into the Smart Meter Gateway (SMGW). This would eliminate the need for additional hardware (HEMS) and allow secure, standardized communication between EVs and the energy system via SMGW and EEBUS protocols.	A key advantage is that the SMGW in Germany already provides a standardized and secure interface. However, this model does not exist in all Member States, which would mean that Germany is following a distinct path, complicating European harmonization efforts and creating additional integration challenges for cross-border solutions.	High-Mid
Communicative connection between key actors (Interaction between vehicles, charging infrastructure, grid operators, and other key stakeholders)	Although significant progress has been made in the implementation of communication connections between key actors, further efforts are needed. The communication between key players in the energy system, such as charging point operators (CPOs) and energy suppliers, is currently insufficient to effectively manage bidirectional charging services. This gap can be addressed by advancing smart grid technologies, including harmonized sub-metering as well as improved measurement and settlement systems.	Although protocols like ISO 15118-20 and OCPP 2.1 provide many of the necessary data points when a bidirectional EV connects to a compatible charger, they do not cover data exchanges between the IT/backend systems of car manufacturers and third-party service providers when the vehicle is in use. To ensure a level playing field and non-discriminatory services—while respecting customer consent—it is recommended to accelerate the provision of open API access to the backend systems of original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) and energy suppliers, employing standardized data formats. This recommendation aligns with the European Commission’s guidance on implementing Article 20a of RED III, including references to the Data Act and Regulation 2023/2854, promoting interoperable, transparent, and consumer-centric data sharing.	Mid
Grid compatibility and standards (Interconnection standards, Power Quality Regulations, etc.)	Germany applies a comprehensive framework of technical regulations -notably Technische Anschlussregeln (TAR) and the Technischen Anschlussbedingungen (TAB) -which govern the connection, quality and controllability of energy fed into the public grid. These rules, enforced by Distribution System Operators, define the conditions under which systems such as bidirectional electric vehicles and energy storage must operate. This includes compliance with voltage limits, grid stability requirements, and the ability to respond to external control signals, ensuring safe and reliable system integration at all voltage levels. The following standards apply: Low Voltage: For a facility with a maximum active power up to 135 kW, the Low Voltage Connection Rules (TAR Niederspannung) apply (VDE-AR-N 4100 for consumers and VDE-AR-N 4105 for producers). Medium Voltage: For a facility with a maximum active power from 135 kW up to 36 MW, the Medium Voltage Connection Rules (TAR Mittelspannung) apply (VDE-AR-N 4110 for consumers and producers). High Voltage: VDE-AR-N 4120:2018-11	Germany applies detailed, technically advanced and future-ready standards for grid connection and compatibility, supporting both current and emerging technologies such as V2G. The system addresses power quality, grid safety, and control responsiveness comprehensively across voltage levels and is well-integrated into operational enforcement.	High

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
System integration and pilot programs	<p>Germany is taking major steps toward integrating bidirectional electric vehicle (EV) charging through several pilot projects.</p> <p>Since 2022, E.ON has been running its Bi-clEVer pilot project to test the practical application of bidirectional electric vehicle (EV) charging. The goal: to explore how EVs can contribute to greater sustainability, lower energy costs, and reduce dependence on traditional energy sources. The headline insight: households using both vehicle-to-home (V2H) and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) functionalities could save up to €920 per year on energy costs. The Bi-clEVer project offers valuable real-world data showing how smart charging can turn EVs into active components of the energy system—supporting grid stability, improving energy efficiency, and delivering tangible savings for users.</p> <p>In addition a pilot project was launched in March 2025, under the patronage of the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK), involving a coalition of leading companies—including BMW, TenneT, Octopus Energy, The Mobility House, and TransnetBW—to demonstrate how smart, bidirectional EV charging can support the electricity grid at all network levels. The project, fully funded by industry partners and coordinated by UnternehmerTUM, aims to show the first grid- and market-supportive charging and discharging operations within just six months. It brings together stakeholders from the automotive, energy, and digital sectors and is supported by the European Coalition of the Willing for Bidirectional Charging. The focus is on practical, customer-centered use cases tested both in the lab and in the field.</p> <p>Furthermore, InterBDL is a research-driven project launched in 2023 and funded by the BMWK. Led by academic and technical institutions such as Technische Hochschule Ulm, the German Aerospace Center (DLR), and EEBus, it is focused on building the technical and regulatory groundwork for large-scale V2G integration. Over the course of 3.5 years, the project explores critical aspects such as interoperability, energy and mobility forecasting, open data standards, and innovative business models. It includes comprehensive lab simulations, interface testing, and long-term field studies.</p>	Germany's pilot projects for system integration of bidirectional charging are well-funded, cross-sectoral, and strategically focused on real-world applications. These initiatives provide a strong foundation for future scaling but are still transitioning from testing and demonstration to widespread deployment.	High-Mid
Data Management			
Data privacy and security (Data protection and cybersecurity regulations)	Germany is in the process of transposing the NIS2 Directive into national legislation. The deadline for implementation is 17 October 2024, but Germany has not met this deadline (the draft bill has been submitted and will result into the revision of the Act of the Federal Office for Information Security (BSIG))	Key areas to focus on include maintaining data integrity and protection, managing user consent, ensuring high data quality, and adopting standardized data formats and content.	Mid
Data exchange and accessibility (Europe-wide framework for non-discriminatory access to EV data, the EU Data Act, and RED III)	Germany's effort to enable V2G is slowed due to low digitalization of the grids—as of 2022 smart meter penetration was below 1%. In addition, the German Calibration Law (Eichrecht) mandates the re-certification of smart meters used for bidirectional charging, which represents an additional hurdle. A nation-wide rollout is already planned through 2032, but this slow pace is hindering the deployment of dynamic tariffs and data-driven energy optimization.	To enable effective bidirectional charging, collaboration among all data providers—electricity providers, grid operators, charger manufacturers, and car manufacturers—is essential. Beyond simply collecting data, it is crucial to ensure a performant, consistent, and compliant data flow that allows for easy and non-discriminatory exchange with customers' preferred third-party service providers. Additionally, the system must be scalable, with clearly defined data points that directly link to existing protocols and clearly state the purpose of each data element to support seamless integration and interoperability.	Mid
Consumer protection and rights (contractual transparency, access to information, and liability framework)			
Consumer protection and rights (contractual transparency, access to information, and liability framework)	Consumer protection is being addressed under several initiatives, such as the simplification of the tax regime introduced in 2024, ensuring that electricity in the vehicle to home or vehicle to business use case is not accounted for as a 'electricity supplier', and therefore electricity tax does not have to be accounted for anymore. From a regulatory perspective, there are no obstacles to implementing bidirectional use cases behind the meter (i.e. after the power meter). According to §3 paragraph 46 of the German Income Tax Act (EStG), electricity used for charging electric vehicles at the workplace or at a company-provided charging point at home is tax-exempt. So far, there are no explicit legal consequences for potential misuse, such as feeding electricity back into a private household.	When feeding electricity back into the grid, a user becomes a producer. Producers do not pay taxes, fees, or surcharges, as these costs are borne by end consumers. Conversely, when drawing electricity from the grid, the user acts as an end consumer and must pay full taxes, fees, and surcharges. This creates a double burden because consumption is charged both when electricity is stored and again when it is drawn back after feeding into the grid. Only in certain cases can exemptions be applied for storage systems. Regarding electricity tax (§5 paragraph 4 of the Electricity Tax Act - StromStG), electricity taken for feeding into the grid is generally subject to electricity tax. Stationary battery storage systems are considered part of the supply network and are thus exempt from this tax, giving them an advantage over mobile storage. Mobile storage users (EV Owners) currently still face double taxation, when discharging energy back into the grid. In this regard electricity taxes and grid fees mean that bidirectional charging is not represented as a financially attractive model for EV owners until now.	Mid-Low
Environmental considerations (emission reduction goals)			
Environmental considerations (emission reduction goals)	Germany's initiatives, such as the integration of the EVs into the energy grid and the promotion of bidirectional charging, contribute to the country's environmental goals by enhancing grid stability and supporting the use of renewable energy sources.		Mid-High

A.3 Romania

Table A.3: Regulatory and Market Structure – Evaluation and Maturity Level for Romania

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Regulatory and Market Structure			
Regulatory Bodies	Romanian National Energy Regulatory Authority - ANRE		
Energy market participation (e.g., Market access and potential aggregated services)	<p>Participation in the Romanian energy market has become an increasingly relevant topic, especially in the context of energy transition and digitalization. Market access and the development of aggregated services are two essential components for the valorisation of decentralized energy resources and the active involvement of consumers – prosumers.</p> <p>In Romania, participants can access several types of energy markets: (1) Day-Ahead Market (DAM) – the main mechanism for setting energy prices; (2) Intraday Market (IDM) – provides additional flexibility to participants; (3) Balancing Market (BM) – managed by Transelectrica, to ensure system balance; (4) System Services Market – for the provision of services such as power reserves.</p> <p>The key players having access into the market are the following: Energy suppliers, Prosumers, Grid operators (DSOs and the Romanian TSO), and Aggregators – an emerging role that will become increasingly important.</p> <p>Types of services offered through aggregation: (1) Providing flexibility to system operators, (2) Participation in the balancing market or capacity markets, (3) Optimization of consumption and storage for customers, and (4) Aggregated trading for renewable or stored energy.</p>	<p>Among the challenges of participating in the energy market in Romania, there are the following: the lack of clear regulations for independent aggregators (currently under development), limitations related to technological infrastructure (smart meters, communication platforms), and the lack of financial incentives and scalable business models. On the other hand, there is a number of opportunities for further advancements regarding the integration of renewable energy and emission reduction, increasing the participation of prosumers and active users, access to new sources of income for flexible consumers, as well as contributing to energy security and grid stability.</p> <p>From the perspective of aggregation and the opportunities given by the regulator's concerns, we can foresee a series of potential aggregated services in Romania, with a medium and short-term projection: aggregation of flexible household consumption (e.g. consumption control from smart appliances), aggregation of stationary batteries (including those of electric vehicles), aggregation of photovoltaic systems from households or commercial buildings, as well as aggregators that provide balancing services for Transelectrica.</p> <p>Participation in the energy market through aggregation services is an inevitable future, especially for the integration of prosumers and distributed resources. Although Romania is in an early stage in this area, the European framework and the growing interest in the energy transition create a favorable context for the development of this segment.</p> <p>Romania's energy market participation framework has evolved significantly, particularly with the enactment of Government Emergency Ordinance No. 143/2021, which amended the Electricity and Natural Gas Law No. 123/2012. This amendment aligns Romania's legislation with EU Directive 2019/944 and Regulation 2019/943, fostering a more integrated and flexible energy market.</p>	Mid-Low
Grid management and control (Demand Response programs and Grid Frequency Regulation)	<p>For Grid management and control, both from the perspective of Demand Response and Grid Frequency Regulation, the following regulatory provisions are in force:</p> <p>ANRE Order No. 124/2022: Approves the rules for congestion management by using the flexibility of resources in the distribution and transmission networks, promoting the market-based use of this flexibility. It also includes rules for the purchase of reactive energy for steady-state voltage regulation by transmission and distribution operators. The order was amended by ANRE Order No. 9/2024 to update and complete the existing regulations.</p> <p>Technical Norm 30/05/2019: Establishes technical requirements for consumption points and distribution systems that can provide controllable consumption services, including active and reactive power regulation, as well as network congestion management.</p> <p>Procedure 11/12/2019: Sets out the requirements for testing and validating the participation of consumption and generation units in frequency regulation, including parameters such as response time and insensitivity. This applies to units that can continuously modify active power to contribute to frequency stabilization.</p> <p>ANRE Order No. 127/2021: Approves the Regulation on the terms and conditions for balancing service providers and frequency stabilization reserve providers, establishing the contractual and technical framework for their participation in maintaining the balance of the energy system. Additionally, from the perspective of data exchange between the transmission system operator (TSO), distribution operators and significant network users, to facilitate coordination and transparency in the grid operation, there are in force the provisions of ANRE Order no. 233/2019. ANRE's regulatory program for the period 2024–2025 includes plans to update and develop regulations in the field of electricity, providing a vision of future regulatory directions.</p>	<p>In Romania, the regulatory provisions addressing the grid management and control has been significantly developed in recent years, especially in the context of alignment with European legislation and standards. However, there are still several gaps and challenges that affect the efficiency and security of the energy system: Lack of a clear framework for the digitalization of energy. Although there are strategies at national and European level (e.g. the European Green Deal), concrete regulations regarding the digitalization of electricity networks (smart grid, IoT, big data, AI) are either vague or delayed. The lack of unified technical standards for smart equipment installed in the network is another impactful fact from this perspective.</p> <p>Weaknesses in the regulation of prosumers and distributed sources: legislation for prosumers was introduced relatively recently, but there are delays in the implementation of methodological norms; regulations are sometimes unclear or rigid regarding the connection and compensation of energy delivered to the grid, and adequate incentives for the installation of storage systems are lacking.</p> <p>Institutional fragmentation and lack of a coherent vision: Multiple institutions (ANRE – Romanian Regulatory Authority in Energy, Transelectrica – Romanian Transmission System Operator, Ministry of Energy, OPCOM - Electricity and Natural Gas Market Operator) involved, but coordination between them is sometimes insufficient or ineffective; Lack of a coherent national strategy for the development of smart grids and for managing the energy transition. Outdated infrastructure and lack of coordinated investments: Many distribution networks are outdated and do not allow for the effective integration of renewable sources or smart metering; There is no effective mechanism for prioritizing investments based on energy efficiency and network security criteria.</p> <p>Insufficient regulations on cybersecurity - In a context where the digitalization of electricity networks increases exposure to cyberattacks, Romania does not yet have a solid and specific framework for protecting critical energy infrastructure from these risks.</p> <p>Gaps in energy market integration at European level - Although Romania is part of the single European energy market, market integration mechanisms (e.g. market coupling) are still under development and encounter technical and administrative implementation difficulties</p>	Mid-Low

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Charging infrastructure regulations (Smart and bidirectional provisions)	<p>In Romania, EV charging infrastructure is regulated by a combination of national legislation and European regulations, which mainly establish obligations for new construction, major renovations and the location of charging stations.</p> <p>These references to buildings and constructions that can integrate charging stations are found in Law 101/2020, which amends Law 372/2005 on the energy performance of buildings and imposes a series of specific obligations regarding the installation of a minimum number of charging stations in relation to a certain number of parking spaces belonging to a building, depending on the type of building, residential or non-residential.</p> <p>Rules are also provided regarding the location of charging stations, more specifically location restrictions depending on the context and characteristics of the buildings, as well as the necessary documentation. [275], [276]</p>	<p>Currently, there are no specific regulations in Romania that directly address bidirectional charging of electric vehicles (V2G), however, current regulations regarding bidirectional charging infrastructure for electric vehicles are in the development and implementation phase, in accordance with European Union directives. The main challenges we have identified regarding the implementation of V2G on the Romanian market are the following: There are no clear regulations on how electric vehicles can interact with the power grid or other consumers. Most existing charging stations are not equipped to support V2G functionalities. Implementing V2G requires significant investments in equipment and technology, and the economic benefits for users and operators are not yet fully clear. Romania is in the process of developing a legislative framework to support electric vehicle charging infrastructure. According to a draft law, by June 30, 2026, Romanian authorities must establish an intelligent transport system that uses digital technologies, including for monitoring and managing electric vehicle charging infrastructure. There are also initiatives such as the ElectricUP 2024 program, which aims to install charging stations for electric and plug-in electric vehicles, accompanied by energy storage systems. These projects can be an important step in developing the infrastructure needed for the implementation of V2G technologies. Although Romania does not yet have specific regulations for bidirectional charging of electric vehicles, there are measures being implemented that can support the development of this field. It is expected that, as V2G technology becomes more accessible and widely used, Romanian authorities will adopt regulations that facilitate its integration into the national electricity grid.</p>	Low
Financial and non-financial incentives (Energy contracts and tariffs, participation in demand-side flexibility programs, grid tariffs, taxes and levies)	<p>In Romania, electric vehicle charging infrastructure benefits from financial and non-financial incentives, directly or indirectly aimed at supporting its development and promoting flexibility in energy demand:</p> <p>“Rabla Plus” and “Rabla” programs - These programs provide subsidies for the purchase of electric and hybrid vehicles. For example, “Rabla Plus” can provide up to EUR 8,500 for a BEV in 2025, with the aim of stimulating the transition to electric mobility. Support for the installation of charging stations - Through the programs managed by the Environmental Fund Administration (AFM), funding of up to EUR 30,000 is provided for high-capacity charging stations (>22 kW), covering up to 80% of the eligible costs.</p> <p>“ElectricUp” program - This program provides funding of up to EUR 150,000 for SMEs, including for the installation of charging stations and alternative heating systems, thus supporting the transition to electric mobility. [277]</p>	<p>The topic of incentives for the development of electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure is essential for the transition to sustainable mobility. In Romania, both financial and non-financial incentives have developed in recent years but face several limitations and challenges: Considering financial incentives, high bureaucracy, lack of co-financing, approval and settlement delays, geographical inequality and lack of incentives for household consumers are some of the constraints that limit the smooth integration of EVs. With reference to the second category, non-financial incentives, we have several limiting perspectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - inconsistent application at local level - EV facilities vary greatly between cities. - lack of a coherent and stable legislative framework - regulations change frequently and lack clear implementation rules. - poor collaboration between authorities and the private sector - many projects are not coordinated, leading to inefficiency. - education and mentality - low level of awareness regarding the advantages of EVs and distrust in the charging network. - interoperability issues - lack of a unified payment and charging station location system. 	Mid-Low
Regulatory flexibility (i.e., adaptability to emerging technologies)	<p>The perspective of regulatory flexibility in Romania, in the context of electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure, is influenced by several factors: the national legislative framework, European initiatives, the speed of adoption of emerging technologies, as well as the administration’s capacity to respond quickly and coherently to changes in the field of electric mobility.</p> <p>The current regulatory framework is in an area between compliance and the need for adaptation, based on a series of support programs (Rabla Plus, PNRR for public charging infrastructure, etc.), rules on pre-equipping with infrastructure for charging stations as well as the transposition of minimum technical regulations for charging stations (connectors, accessibility, interoperability).</p>	<p>All the existing regulations within their framework tend to be reactive, not proactive. There is a lag between the emergence of emerging technologies (e.g. ultra-fast charging, wireless charging, smart charging, V2G - vehicle to grid) and the adaptation of legislation. Regulatory flexibility in Romania is often constrained by bureaucracy, fragmentation, and limited capacity for anticipation; for example, technologies such as mobile charging stations or roaming between network operators are poorly regulated or insufficiently supported.</p> <p>From the perspective of adaptability to emerging technologies, Romania has an obvious openness and has started to integrate some modern concepts: fast and ultra-fast charging stations, some pilot projects for integration with smart grids, and private initiatives (e.g. Hsubject, EVconnect), but regulations regarding roaming or real-time data are poorly developed. Another challenge in this context of regulatory flexibility is related to the fact that autonomous vehicles, wireless charging stations or peer-to-peer energy systems are not provided for in the legislation, which slows down implementation.</p> <p>Romania has moderate regulatory flexibility, with a positive but slow trend. Compared to the rapid pace of innovation in the field of electric vehicles, regulatory adaptation is still suboptimal.</p>	Low
Regulatory Bodies	Interoperability, Standardization, and Communication		

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Standards for V2G charging infrastructure	<p>With reference to the charging infrastructure for electric vehicles (EV) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) systems, in Romania we refer to a series of national and international technical standards, which ensure interoperability, safety and energy efficiency:</p> <p>ISO 15118-20:2022 - This standard defines the requirements for the network layer and the second-generation application layer in bidirectional vehicle-to-grid (V2G) communication. It includes specifications for application messages, wireless communication, and the interface between the vehicle communication controller (EVCC) and the charging station communication controller (SECC).</p> <p>SR EN ISO 15118-20:2022 - The equivalent Romanian standard, adopted by ASRO, regulates the same technical aspects, ensuring compliance with international requirements. SR EN IEC 61851-1:2019/AC:2023 - This establishes the general requirements for conductive charging systems for electric vehicles, including safety and electromagnetic protection requirements. The updated version includes relevant technical changes for the implementation of charging infrastructure.</p> <p>SR EN 62196-2 and SR EN 62196-3 - These standards define the types of connectors for alternating current (Type 2) and direct current (Combo 2) charging, essential for the interoperability of charging stations. According to official guidelines, charging stations must be equipped with at least these types of sockets and connectors.</p> <p>OCPP 1.6 - The Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) version 1.6 is required for charging stations, ensuring interoperability and integration into smart energy management networks. Stations must have interfaces in Romanian and English and allow real-time monitoring.</p>	<p>Although technical standards for V2G are in place, effective implementation in Romania depends on the development of smart grid infrastructure and collaboration between local authorities, grid operators and equipment suppliers. The adoption of ISO 15118 and associated protocols will facilitate the integration of electric vehicles into smart energy grids, contributing to the stability and efficiency of the national energy system.</p>	Mid
Communicative connection between key actors (Interaction between vehicles, charging infrastructure, grid operators, and other key stakeholders)	<p>To achieve an effective communicative connection between the key actors involved in the Romanian electric mobility ecosystem — electric vehicles, charging infrastructure, network operators and other stakeholders — a well-defined cooperation and interoperability framework is required, supported by technology, regulations and public-private collaboration.</p> <p>The interaction between key actors can be very well represented through a matrix, in which we have the types of actors between which the interaction exists, the type of interaction and the protocols and technologies used.</p> <p>For example, in Romania, between the EV and the charging station, we have the authentication-charging interaction type using OCPP, ISO 15118 communication protocol.</p> <p>Currently, the communication levels between infrastructure and network operators, between infrastructure and authorities, between users, digital platforms and infrastructure are partially defined and properly operating. From this perspective, direct collaboration and coordination between the Energy Regulatory Authority (ANRE) and the National Authority for Administration and Regulation in Communications (ANCOM) is critical.</p>	<p>The main challenges of the Romanian context on this subject can be summarized as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fragmentation of charging networks and lack of interoperability - Poor communication between authorities and the private sector - Lack of a unified technical regulatory and monitoring framework - Electricity grid capacity issues in certain areas - Limited standardization in terms of communication protocols 	Mid-Low
Grid compatibility and standards (Interconnection standards, Power Quality Regulations, etc.)	<p>The grid compatibility and standards in Romania are regulated by a complex legislative and technical framework, aligned with European Union directives and partially implemented by national authorities and operators. They aim at the interconnection of electricity grids, the power quality and ensuring the safe and efficient operation of the National Power System (SEN).</p> <p>Regarding interconnection standards in Romania, both the technical norms for grid connection, developed by ANRE, and the European Grid Code established by ENTSO-E, Regulation (EU) 2019/943 on the internal electricity market and finally, the SR EN 50160 Standard - on the characteristics of the voltage supplied by public distribution networks - are considered. Relevant Power Quality Regulations are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ANRE Order No. 31/2018 – regarding the approval of the Technical Norm for power quality; - Technical Code of the Electric Transmission Network – issued by Transelectrica (Romanian TSO – Transmission System Operator) and approved by ANRE; - Standard SR EN 50160 – defines the permissible deviations for parameters such as voltage, frequency, voltage unbalance, etc. 	<p>In the context of integrating renewable energy sources and modernizing the energy infrastructure, Romania faces a series of challenges and limitations regarding grid compatibility and standards. With reference to Interconnection standards, there is a fragmentation of regulations, a limited absorption capacity of the network, lack of a clear technical framework for prosumers, a long approval time for obtaining the technical connection permit, and weak standardization for smart equipment. With reference to Power Quality Regulations, there are also several challenges and limitations:</p> <p>The increase in the number of intermittent renewable sources (photovoltaics, wind) has led to greater variations in voltage, frequency and harmonics. The current grid was not designed for a bidirectional flow of energy, which complicates maintaining power quality.</p> <p>Insufficient monitoring of quality parameters – the measurement equipment installed in distribution networks does not cover parameters such as THD (Total Harmonic Distortion), flicker or phase imbalances well enough. Lack of clear penalties framework for non-compliance – although the legislation provides for minimum quality requirements (in accordance with SR EN 50160), sanctioning mechanisms are rarely applied or ineffective.</p>	Mid-Low

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
System integration and pilot programs	<p>In Romania, V2G technology is still in its infancy, but there are several relevant directions, favorable conditions and initiatives for its development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Romanian Energy Strategy 2020-2030 mentions the digitalization of the grid and the integration of distributed sources. - The PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan) allocates funds for the development of charging infrastructure, but does not directly specify V2G, but provides the innovation framework for such pilot projects. - The AFM (Environmental Fund Administration) supports the acquisition of electric vehicles and the development of charging infrastructure, without explicitly mentioning V2G. <p>With reference to initiatives and pilot programs, able to provide support in raising awareness of V2G technologies and creating a favorable context for adoption through regulations, we can mention the following:</p> <p>smart grid and microgrid research projects, where V2G can be tested in controlled environments; private initiatives through the involvement of energy companies (e.g. Enel X, E.ON Romania), which are exploring smart charging solutions and could test V2G in the future in partnership with car manufacturers; Tesla, Nissan (Leaf) and other manufacturers already offer V2G-compatible technology, but integration into Romanian networks requires local regulations and testing; by involving Romanian entities in international research projects, such as the NEVERFLAT project.</p>	Romania is in a favorable position to experiment with bidirectional V2G charging, but legislative reforms, concrete pilot projects, public-private partnerships, and adaptation of the national grid to the new realities of electric mobility are needed.	Low
Regulatory Bodies	Data Management		
Data privacy and security (Data protection and cybersecurity regulations)	<p>The topic of data privacy and security in the context of the energy and electric vehicle (EV) market in Romania is increasingly relevant, given the accelerated pace of digitalization, energy transition and the increased interconnectivity between energy, transport and technology systems.</p> <p>An overview of the regulations applicable on the data privacy and security topic, with reference to the situation in Romania and the EVs context, discloses the following: GDPR (EU Regulation 2016/679)</p> <p>National Supervisory Authority for Personal Data Processing (ANSPDCP) - It is the regulatory body in Romania that oversees the application of the GDPR. It can issue guidelines and sanctions in case of violation of the rights of data subjects. Law No. 362/2018 on ensuring a high common level of security of networks and information systems; refers to regulations on cybersecurity in energy, a transposition of the NIS Directive (EU Directive 2016/1148) for Romania. The law provides a series of obligations for energy actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification as Operators of Essential Services (OSE) – e.g. energy distributors/suppliers, smart grid operators, EV infrastructure companies. - Implementation of technical and organizational measures to prevent cyber incidents. - Notification of security incidents to the National Cybersecurity Incident Response Center (CERT-RO) - Authority responsible for the national coordination of cyber incidents, including in the energy field. <p>Electricity and Natural Gas Law No. 123/2012 – amended in 2022 to include aspects regarding digitalization and smart grids. PNRR – Component 10 (Energy) and Component 5 (Renovation Wave) – support investments in smart infrastructure, also involving IT security requirements.</p> <p>National Cyber Security Plan – updated strategy for the period 2022–2027, in which energy infrastructure is considered a critical area.</p> <p>Specific aspects related to electric vehicles and charging infrastructure include the following:</p> <p>Data collected from users through smart charging stations: identity, payment method, vehicle type, consumption, usage schedule, etc.</p> <p>Applications that allow station location, reservation, payment, and consumption monitoring must respect the principles of privacy by design and privacy by default.</p> <p>Managing possible attacks on the electrical grid through charging points or vehicle software interfaces (IoT).</p> <p>Implementation of international security standards (e.g. ISO/IEC 27001, ISO 15118 – for communication between EVs and charging stations).</p>	<p>The existing regulatory gaps in the field of data privacy and security in the energy sector in Romania, with a focus on Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology, reflect a combination of factors related to the rapid evolution of energy technologies and the slower pace of adaptation of the legislative framework. V2G technology is not explicitly regulated in Romanian legislation, and this creates uncertainties regarding the status of the mobile prosumer (the user who supplies energy from the vehicle), the rules regarding network access, pricing and compensation, but also liability in case of cyber incidents or data leaks.</p> <p>Although Romania applies the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), transposition in the energy field, especially for new V2G technologies, is insufficient. The data potentially collected through V2G infrastructure is extremely detailed (e.g. real-time location, usage patterns, charging preferences), which allows for user profiling and there is no clear framework regarding explicit consent for the collection and use of this data by suppliers, system operators or third parties (aggregators, IoT platforms).</p> <p>There are currently no national standards or clear ANRE/ANCOM regulations that impose cybersecurity requirements for encryption of transmitted data, device authentication, and secure firmware/software updates.</p> <p>There is also an inadequacy of the ANRE regulatory framework for digitalization and IoT in energy; ANRE regulations are largely oriented towards classic infrastructure and only recently integrate digitalization aspects, so there are no ANRE guidelines or regulations for certifying the security of these devices or for digital interoperability. There is also a sharp fragmentation of institutional responsibilities, such that ANRE, ANCOM, CERT-RO, the Ministry of Energy and ANSPDCP (data protection) have overlapping or uncorrelated responsibilities.</p>	Mid-Low

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Data exchange and accessibility (Europe-wide framework for non-discriminatory access to EV data, the EU Data Act, and RED III)	The regulation of data exchange and accessibility in the context of V2G (Vehicle-to-Grid) in Romania is still in its early stages, but the topic is becoming increasingly relevant in the context of the energy transition and the digitalization of energy networks.	Standardization of data and communication protocols, data exchange and accessibility – Romania does not yet have specific regulations regarding interoperability in the V2G context. Therefore, there are no clear rules regarding who has access to the data generated by an EV in V2G mode (operators, suppliers, aggregators). The main challenges can be summarized as follows: Lack of a market framework for aggregators – there is no regulation on how aggregators can operate in Romania (a key player for V2G). Absence of an incentive framework for V2G users – there is no clear reward for participating with EV energy. Low interoperability – lack of clear technical regulations regarding OCPP, ISO 15118, Standards.	Low
Consumer protection and rights (contractual transparency, access to information, and liability framework)			
Consumer protection and rights (contractual transparency, access to information, and liability framework)	No regulatory provisions in force.	Consumer protection and rights in the context of V2G (Vehicle-to-Grid) in Romania is an emerging topic, as V2G technology is in an early stage of implementation, but it obviously involves important challenges from a consumer rights perspective, especially regarding contractual transparency, access to information and the liability framework.	Low
Environmental considerations (emission reduction goals)			
Environmental considerations (emission reduction goals)	With reference to environmental considerations, there are general legislative provisions in Romania, not aspects specifically and exclusively addressed to V2G, and the most relevant are the following: Law No. 293/2018 transposing EU Directive 2016/2284 (NEC) on national targets for the reduction of emissions of atmospheric pollutants (SO ₂ , NO ₂ , NH ₃ , VOC _{nm} , PM _{2.5}), with objectives for the period 2020–2029 and post-2030; GD no. 119/2023 – National Air Pollution Control Program (PNCPA) - Approves reduction measures in all relevant sectors, with periodic update of policy options and estimated impact; GD no. 643/2024 - Amends the annexes to Law 293/2018 in accordance with current progress and targets” [278]	Environmental considerations and emission reduction objectives related to Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology in Romania are relevant in the context of the energy transition, the European Green Deal and Romania’s decarbonization commitments.	low

A.4 Spain

Table A.4: Regulatory and Market Structure – Evaluation and Maturity Level

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Regulatory and Market Structure			
Regulatory Bodies	Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO), National Commission on Markets and Competition (CNMC), Red Eléctrica de España (REE), IDAE – Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving, OMIE – Iberian Electricity Market Operator, Ministry of Transport and Sustainable Mobility (formerly MITMA), Spanish Tax Agency (AEAT), Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD), Ministry of Industry and Tourism (MINTUR)		
Energy market participation (e.g., Market access and potential aggregated services)	Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector, Royal Decree (RD) 1183/2020, and RD 244/2019 regulate self-consumption and aggregation of distributed energy resources. CNMC (National Commission on Markets and Competition), IDAE, and the Ministry for the Ecological Transition. - Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector: establishes the legal framework for electricity market participants, including producers and (potentially) aggregators, and guarantees access and connection rights to the grid. - Royal Decree 244/2019: regulates self-consumption schemes. For installations ≤100 kW, it allows simplified compensation of surplus energy, while for >100 kW or non-compensated setups, it enables direct participation in the electricity market through energy sales, subject to registration as a producer. Applies to V2G when the charging point operator (CPO) is the owner of the installation. - Royal Decree 1183/2020: governs grid access and connection procedures for generation and storage facilities, including small, low-voltage installations such as public, low-power V2G chargers.	- There is no specific regulatory framework for V2G participation in electricity markets. Current mechanisms only allow market participation for registered producers, which is impractical for individual EV owners or small-scale public chargers. - Independent aggregators are not yet enabled under Spanish regulation, limiting the ability of low-power V2G infrastructure to access flexibility or wholesale markets in an aggregated manner. - No dedicated mechanisms exist for the participation of public, slow charging points in the electricity or capacity markets.	Low

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Grid management and control (Demand Response programs and Grid Frequency Regulation)	<p>Demand response is legally recognized. Flexibility services allowed via aggregators.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector: defines demand-side management as a component of the electricity system and allows the implementation of mechanisms to enable new actors. - Royal Decree 216/2014: establishes the voluntary price for the small consumer (PVPC), including time-of-use signals that could be leveraged for demand-side management, but does not address dynamic flexibility services. - National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) and the Energy Storage Strategy: promote the integration of distributed resources and flexible systems, including vehicle-to-grid (V2G), in future grid stability services. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are no operational programs or market mechanisms in Spain enabling low-power, public V2G chargers to participate in demand response or frequency regulation services (ref. Law 24/2013 and RD 216/2014). - Spain lacks an operational balancing market open to distributed energy resources (DERs), in contrast to countries like Germany, where V2G systems can monetize fast-response services (gap in market design by the system operator). - There is no technical or regulatory framework for integrating V2G into TSO platforms for ancillary services. - No remuneration or certification mechanisms exist for small-scale actors such as CPOs offering real-time flexibility. 	Low
Charging infrastructure regulations (Smart and bidirectional provisions)	<p>ITC-BT-52, RD 1053/2014, and the Spanish Building Code (CTE) require EV pre-installation in new/renovated buildings. RD 184/2022 streamlines installation procedures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Royal Decree 1053/2014: establishes the ITC-BT-52 technical instruction, setting requirements for EV charging installations in buildings. It does not address bidirectional charging. - Spanish Building Technical Code (CTE): mandates the pre-installation of charging infrastructure in new buildings and car parks, without differentiation between unidirectional and bidirectional charging systems. - MOVES III Programme: provides financial support for the installation of EV chargers, without specifically incentivizing V2G-capable or smart technologies. - Royal Decree 184/2022: regulates the provision of public EV charging services, setting obligations for CPOs in terms of information transparency, user access, pricing, and interoperability. It applies to public V2G chargers, although it does not explicitly address bidirectional functionality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is no specific technical regulation for bidirectional chargers (ref. RD 1053/2014 and CTE), creating uncertainty in terms of certification, grid connection, and safety requirements. - The lack of tailored standards for V2G interoperability, communication protocols, and cybersecurity limits large-scale deployment (ref. RD 184/2022, although it sets general interoperability obligations). - No administrative or technical guidelines exist for deploying V2G chargers in public spaces, particularly those with low-power and slow-charging profiles (relevant for the project context). - The current national incentives framework (ref. MOVES III) does not differentiate or promote smart or bidirectional technologies over conventional unidirectional chargers. 	Low
Financial and non-financial incentives (Energy contracts and tariffs, participation in demand-side flexibility programs, grid tariffs, taxes and levies)	<p>MOVES III program provides subsidies for EVs and charging infrastructure. Time-of-use electricity tariffs available.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Royal Decree 244/2019: regulates self-consumption with excess energy. For installations ≤ 100 kW, it allows simplified compensation, where surplus energy injected into the grid is credited against consumption on the monthly bill (but does not generate direct income). For installations > 100 kW (or those not under compensation), it allows the direct sale of electricity to the wholesale market, subject to producer registration. - Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector: sets out the fiscal and administrative obligations for electricity producers, applicable to V2G operators aiming to sell energy. - MOVES III Programme: provides subsidies for EV charging infrastructure but does not offer specific support or incentives for V2G or bidirectional charging solutions. - General taxation and tariff framework: there are no specific exemptions, incentives or reduced grid fees for V2G-enabled systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The simplified compensation scheme (RD 244/2019) limits the economic viability of V2G installations ≤ 100 kW, as it does not allow net revenue generation beyond offsetting consumption. - For systems > 100 kW, the registration process and fiscal obligations (Law 24/2013) represent a significant barrier for CPOs operating low-power, public charging points. - There are no grid tariff structures or dynamic pricing models that specifically incentivize the bidirectional use of EV batteries. - The MOVES III Programme does not prioritize advanced technologies like V2G, putting them at a disadvantage compared to conventional unidirectional chargers. 	Low
Regulatory flexibility (i.e., adaptability to emerging technologies)	<p>The legal framework allows for innovation (e.g., energy regulatory sandbox by the Ministry).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector: provides a general framework that is relatively open to innovation, acknowledging new actors such as storage and aggregators, though their detailed regulation is pending. - The National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC 2023–2030) and the National Energy Storage Strategy explicitly identify V2G as a promising solution for distributed flexibility, and encourage its integration in future grid services. - Existing secondary regulations (RD 244/2019, RD 184/2022) do not include specific measures or fast-track procedures for emerging technologies such as V2G, nor do they provide legal certainty for pilot projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Although strategic documents (PNIEC, Storage Strategy) recognize V2G, there is no specific legal framework or secondary regulation to enable its deployment. - There is no regulatory sandbox or controlled pilot scheme to test emerging technologies like V2G under real-world conditions. - The regulatory environment lacks agile tools and adaptive mechanisms to incorporate innovation with legal certainty. - Existing laws and decrees do not offer exemptions, simplified procedures, or tailored pathways for disruptive or experimental technologies. 	Mid
Interoperability, Standardization, and Communication			
Standards for V2G charging infrastructure	<p>Spain follows EU/ISO standards for EV-grid communication. The ISO 15118-20 (bidirectional charging communication) was ratified in EU in 2022. RD 184/2022 encourages interoperability: it allows charge point operators and mobility service providers to make non discriminatory interoperability agreements (e.g. roaming), and requires an open payment mode.</p>	<p>The regulatory framework is adapting, but many measures are still proposals. As of 2024, there is legal uncertainty (e.g. pending new Supply Reg).</p>	Medium

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Communicative connection between key actors (Interaction between vehicles, charging infrastructure, grid operators, and other key stakeholders)	Charging stations must support digital connectivity. RD 184/2022 requires publicly accessible chargers to allow pay-as-you-go (no contract) via an interface. CNMC and grid operators are enhancing data transparency (e.g., TSOs must publish network capacity data). Consumers have smart meters with two-way data exchange.	Data exchange for V2G (e.g. real-time price signals from grid to EVs, or state-of-charge data to TSOs) is not standardized. Market roles like aggregators need new data channels that current regulations have not established.	Low
Grid compatibility and standards (Interconnection standards, Power Quality Regulations, etc.)	Spanish network codes (RD 1699/2011 for generation, and distribution regulations) apply to storage broadly. CNMC Circular 1/2024 explicitly includes storage in grid access criteria. EV chargers connect to the grid under normal distribution rules (typically low/medium voltage). European grid codes (e.g. NC ER, NC HVDC) permit storage services but do not mention EVs explicitly.	No separate grid code provisions exist for EVs for V2G; they are treated like batteries/loads. DSOs have not issued EV-specific voltage or loading profiles. This gap means system compatibility is assumed under general rules, with limited grid management insight on large EV fleets.	Low
System integration and pilot programs	Several V2G pilots and demonstrations are underway. The ACCIONA “V2G Islas Baleares” project (2022–) installed 16 bidirectional chargers and vehicles to test grid services. Other local pilots (e.g. bus depots, fleet trials) exist. The regulatory sandbox has open calls for flexibility pilots (Order TED/567/2023). Spain participates in European R&D projects on EV grid integration.	These projects prove technical feasibility but are limited in scope and duration. There is no national plan to scale V2G. Integration into the mainstream grid will require regulatory and business-model development.	Low-Medium
Data Management			
Data privacy and security (Data protection and cybersecurity regulations)	Charging networks and services must comply with EU GDPR and Spain’s LOPDGDD for user data. The metrology Order highlights anti-tampering and cybersecurity (e.g. ensuring authenticated payment) in charger design.	No EV-specific privacy/cyber rules exist beyond general IT and utility obligations. Issues like driver consent for data sharing or EV-to-grid hacking risks are not yet regulated. Operators must self-manage these under normal security standards.	Low
Data exchange and accessibility (Europe-wide framework for non-discriminatory access to EV data, the EU Data Act, and RED III)	Spain’s electricity system uses registries (CUPS) and smart-meter data portals (DSO databases) for consumption data. CNMC and REE require transparency. A draft supply reg contemplates data exchange obligations among TSOs, suppliers and aggregators. However, no dedicated platform exists for EV-grid data (e.g. EV state-of-charge, real-time pricing).	Lacking a national data hub or standard API for EV/V2G data. Aggregators and network operators must negotiate bespoke interfaces. This slows large-scale deployment of smart charging or V2G services.	Low
Consumer protection and rights (contractual transparency, access to information, and liability framework)			
Consumer protection	General electricity consumer rights apply (fair billing, switching, complaint processes). The draft Reglamento introduces new rights: to resell one’s energy to EV charging services and to dynamic pricing contracts. EV charging service providers must bill transparently (RD 184/2022). Charging-station operators have obligations (safety signage, outages info).	Specific V2G consumer safeguards (e.g. guarantees on battery health, metering accuracy for discharge) are absent. Consumers may face uncertainty on reimbursement or liability for feeding the grid. Regulatory clarity on V2G user contracts is still needed.	Medium
Environmental considerations (emission reduction goals)			
Environmental Considerations	Climate law (Ley 7/2021) and PNIEC set ambitious decarbonization goals. Spain achieved 59% renewable power by 2022 and targets 81% by 2030. EV uptake and renewable integration are intertwined: the PNIEC explicitly promotes bidirectional charging in demand-side management training and projects. Public EV fleet mandates and low-emission zones also support clean mobility.	V2G is recognized as beneficial for renewables (e.g. storing solar surplus), but no additional climate subsidies or emissions credits are given for using V2G. Environmental targets push adoption, but policy instruments don’t specifically reward V2G beyond general clean-tech support.	Medium
Technical Aspects			
Royal Decrees	The installation of EV charging infrastructure in Spain was first regulated by the Royal Decree 1053/2014, complemented by the technical guide ITC-BT 52. The Royal Decree mandates the inclusion of a minimum of one EV charging station for every forty parking spaces, when designing and constructing new public parking facilities or private parking areas owned by companies operating vehicle fleets. Additionally, the grid operator must ensure energy supply to these charging stations. A more recent decree is the Real Decreto 184/2022, that regulates the activities related to EV charging. This decree clearly defines the roles and responsibilities of charging point operators, mobility service providers and other actors working in the EV ecosystem.	The degree is specific for EV charging, but without details regarding V2G.	Low

Category	State-of-the-Art (SoA)	Evaluation	Maturity Level
Technical Guides	<p>The guide ITC-BT 52 recommends various specifications for the design of the infrastructure, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The lighting in the area of the charging station must guarantee a minimum level of 20 lux outside and 50 lux inside during the start and the end of the charging session. - The maximum voltage deviation of the circuit from the beginning to the charging station will not be larger than 5%. - The cables' cross-section should not be lower than 2.5 mm² (copper), or 4 mm² (aluminium). - For installations with more than five charging stations, specific for electric vehicles, the potential requirement of installing filters to correct harmonics should be evaluated. - The circuit supplying the charging stations must be dedicated solely to this purpose, with the exception of auxiliary equipment directly related to the charging infrastructure. - Further design specifications include the design of the neutral and the protection systems. 	The technical guide does not provide details regarding V2G.	Mid

